

Optimization Strategy for Architecture and Packaging for High Power PEBB based on Wide-Band-Gap Semiconductor Devices

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—Final Report—

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Executive Summary

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This final report summarizes all the work conducted at the Center for Power Electronics Systems (CPES) under the ONR contract N00014-7-0777, entitled “Optimization Strategy for Architecture and Packaging for High Power PEBB based on Wide-Band-Gap Semiconductor Devices”. The objectives of this work have been to develop and validate feasible and reliable packaging approaches for constructing a high-voltage and high-current switch based on state-of-the-art and emerging wide-band-gap semiconductor devices; and to verify, develop and validate an architecture design and optimization procedure for the building of a High-Power, High-Voltage, High-Frequency, and High-Density (H^4) power electronics building block (PEBB), using silicon carbide (SiC) devices of relatively limited ratings. These objectives have been achieved through the hierarchical analysis, design and optimization of a dual-active-bridge (DAB) DC-DC converter based on CPES-built PEBBs with SiC power switches. Due to the rating limits of the available devices, the converter has been scaled down to 5 kW and 300 ~ 600 V in the total power and the voltage level, but scaled up to 500 kHz in the switching frequency, in order to keep the device switching speed (i.e. dv/dt) and design challenges relatively unchanged.

Four major tasks have been identified and undertaken in the process of the project. The research first started with the complete characterization and testing of SiC JFETs and MOSFETs, two kinds of most mature wide-band-gap semiconductor devices, to study the device static and switching performances and generate the datasheets for the future converter design. The utilization of SiC devices has brought the opportunity to apply unipolar devices in the > 600 V applications to replace the conventional, relatively slow Si IGBT, achieving higher switching frequency and hence higher power density of the converters. With the advancement in the device switching speed, however, the circuit parasitic impedances, especially the parasitic

inductances, have become the main limiting factor in the converter by causing device over-stresses and EMI problems through excessive ringing in the switching transients. To solve these issues, great efforts have been made on identifying the most critical parasitics in the circuit, and optimizing the circuit layout through compact packaging strategies. From the material side of the packaging technology, two basic components, namely the direct-bonded-copper (DBC) substrate and the encapsulant materials, have been studied and characterized in their material properties and reliability in high-voltage, high-temperature environments. All of these basic studies finally lead to the analysis and design of the 5 kW, 500 kHz DAB with self-built phase-leg PEBB based on both Si and SiC technologies. Related technical issues such as the single-phase and three-phase transformer comparison, high-speed miniature nano-controller design, etc, have all been extensively studied.

Along with the above story, modeling and simulation have been carried out at all hierarchical levels as an useful and effective tool aiding the analysis and the design. Device models for SiC switches have been built based on the characterization data, and have been combined with circuit parasitics models to study the detailed switching performance of the power modules. Terminal modeling of the phase-leg PEBB has also been explored for the simulation of the converter constructed by these PEBBs. Each type of model serves each sub-level in the hierarchical design process, and constitutes one stage of the well-known ISO/OSI seven layer reference model in the field of power electronics.

Based on the above objectives and tasks, this report is accordingly organized in four parts. Part I (Chapter 1 to 2) documents the characterization and modeling of the two wide-band-gap devices - SiC JFET and MOSFET. Part II (Chapter 3 to 7) mainly discusses the effects of the package parasitics and the corresponding modeling process, as well as the optimization strategy through packaging technology. Part III (Chapter 8 to 11) is mainly about the study of planar packaging technologies and the related packaging material issues. Finally, in Part IV (Chapter 12 to 17) the DAB-related studies, i.e. converter design and analysis, phase-leg PEBB design and modeling, transformer and controller designs, etc. are all presented.

In conclusion, the results of this project have successfully verified the concept and feasibility of H⁴ PEBB with the state-of-the-art SiC power devices, and explored further in this direction the hierarchical and modularized design and optimization strategies. Many ideas proposed but not yet realized in this project are still worth studying in the future projects.

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Part I

Characterization and Modeling of Silicon Carbide Active Devices

Chapter 1 CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING OF 1.2 kV, 5 A SiC JFETs

I. Introduction

The development of power semiconductor devices is always a propelling force to the development of power electronics. Conventional power semiconductors are all silicon (Si) based. However, recently silicon carbide (SiC) power devices have begun to emerge with superior performance to that of Si power devices. Being a wide-band-gap solid material, SiC, especially 4H-SiC, has an order of magnitude higher breakdown electric field than Si, thus leading to the design of SiC power devices with thinner (1/10 of Si devices) and more highly-doped (10 times higher) voltage-blocking layers [1]. For majority carrier devices such as JFETs and MOSFETs, this means a factor of 100 reduction in specific on-resistance compared to Si-based devices with the same ratings [2]. Furthermore, good thermal performance of SiC devices also makes them more stable under elevated temperatures. All these advantages make SiC high power devices a promising substitute for their Si counterparts in the near future.

Table 1-1 shows a comparison of material properties between Si and SiC.

Table 1-1 Comparison of Si and SiC material properties

Parameter	Si	4H-SiC	Unit
Bandgap energy	1.1	3.3	eV
Relative permittivity	11.8	10	-
Critical electric field	0.3	2.0	MV/cm
Electron saturated drift velocity	1.0	2.0	$\times 10^7$ cm/s
Thermal conductivity	1.5	4.9	W/cm·K

Although being normally-on is generally not a desirable feature for a power switch, the development and application of SiC JFETs are still very hot topics today due to its reliability and more mature manufacturing techniques compared to other categories of SiC devices (e.g. SiC MOSFET). At the time of this work, the only available 1.2 kV level SiC devices that have been demonstrated to operate reliably at temperatures beyond 150 °C are - besides the already commercialized SiC Schottky diodes - SiC JFETs, which are also expected to be the first commercialized SiC active switch [3]-[7].

I.1. Technical Objectives

So far there have been many efforts on the characterization and modeling of SiC JFETs. To name a few, [3] and [8] measured the SiC JFET static and capacitance characteristics under different temperatures, and tried to fit the characterization data to a subcircuit model based on the SPICE Version 2 (SPICE 2) JFET model. [4] and [9], on the other hand, established more physics-based equations to describe the static and dynamic behaviors of the device. The characterization and modeling work in this case, however, requires the easy availability of device characteristics, fast and convenient extraction process of model parameters, as well as

the complete inclusion of all the electrical characteristics particular to the SiC JFETs, so that the developed device model can be incorporated in system-level simulation for the purpose of converter design. The first and second conditions require that the characterization be achieved with the use of basic instruments such as the curve tracer and the impedance analyzer, and the model parameters can be extracted directly based on the characterization results. This usually eliminates the use of the physics-based device model because many parameters in such a model are not accessible to device users, such as the doping density, electron mobility, etc. Plus, the development of a physics-based model requires professional knowledge in solid-state physics and semiconductor devices, and the model itself is generally too complicated to be suitable for system-level simulation. In this sense, a subcircuit model is more preferable in our case. The mostly used subcircuit model in the papers, however, is based on the SPICE 2 JFET model which is originally developed for a lateral structure JFET. Therefore, certain features are not included in this model for high-voltage, vertical structure SiC JFETs. This makes the direct use of the SPICE 2 model insufficient for SiC JFETs, and the model needs to be modified accordingly to include the particular features of vertical JFET such as the body diode. Unfortunately none of the previous work fulfilled all these requirements, and thus a characterization and modeling procedure becomes necessary in this work.

I.2. Technical Approach

This chapter will present the development of a SPICE 2-based SiC JFET model and its corresponding characterization process. The device under study is a 1.2 kV, 5 A SiC JFET prototype manufactured by SiCED [10], with a 2.4 mm × 2.4 mm die packaged in a TO-220 case. The static characteristics of the device are measured with the use of the curve tracer and the impedance analyzer. Based on the characterization data, the SPICE 2 JFET model is then modified to fit the SiC JFET characteristics by curve-fitting method. Issues in the device characterizations and the limitations of the model will be discussed in this chapter.

II. SPICE 2-Based SiC JFET Model

The proposed SiC JFET model is illustrated in Fig. 1-1 (a). The core of this model is a SPICE-2 JFET model, which describes the basic JFET static (current-voltage, I-V) and dynamic (capacitance-voltage, C-V) characteristics, as seen in Fig. 1-1 (b). This level-1 SPICE-2 model contains less than 20 parameters, which can be easily extracted from conventional characterization data, such as the output and transfer characteristics. The detailed descriptions of the SPICE 2 JFET model can be found in [10].

Fig. 1-1 SiC JFET model structures. (a) Proposed model, (b) SPICE 2 JFET model

As said previously, the SPICE 2 JFET model is originally developed for lateral structure device, therefore it is insufficient to model the vertical structure SiC JFET. Fig. 1-2 exhibits a typical cross-sectional structure of SiC JFET. As seen, instead of all three terminals being on the same side, the drain terminal in vertical structure is on the bottom while the source and gate sit on the top of the device. The P⁺ layer buried under the source terminal and the N layers below constitute a PN junction between the drain and source terminals. This equivalently adds a body diode as well as a drain-source junction capacitance C_{DS} to the JFET, which is not modeled for lateral structure in the SPICE 2 model. This body diode is included in the proposed model by adding an anti-paralleled power diode model to the SPICE 2 model, and the drain-source capacitance is then interpreted as the diode junction capacitance, as seen in Fig. 1-1 (a).

Fig. 1-2 Typical cross-sectional structure of SiC JFET [1]

Besides the body diode, an extra SPICE diode model is also added across the gate-source terminals in order to model the gate breakdown characteristics of the device. This is necessary for the case when the gate of the SiC JFET is intentionally driven in breakdown mode [12]. Also seen in Fig. 1-1 (a) is a resistor connected in series with the gate terminal representing the internal gate resistance of the device, while the package stray inductances are lumped into series inductances shown. All these components together describe the SiC JFET static and switching behavior under normal operating conditions.

III. Characterizations of SiC JFET and Model Parameter Extractions

III.1. Static I-V Characteristics

The static I-V characteristics are measured with a Tektronix 371B curve tracer. Fig. 1-3 shows the measured output and transfer characteristics of the SiC JFET. It can be told from the figures that device under test (DUT) has an on-state resistance $R_{DS(ON)}$ of around 0.3Ω at $V_{GS} = 0 \text{ V}$ and $I_{DS} = 5 \text{ A}$, and the device is pinched off at $V_{GS} \approx -22 \text{ V}$.

Fig. 1-3 SiC JFET output (a) and transfer (b) characteristics

In SPICE 2, the JFET model uses the following piecewise equations to describe the output characteristics:

$$I_D = \begin{cases} 0, & V_{GS} - V_{T0} \leq 0 \quad (\text{Pinch-off}) \\ \beta(V_{GS} - V_{T0})^2(1 + \lambda V_{DS}), & 0 < V_{GS} - V_{T0} \leq V_{DS} \quad (\text{Saturation}) \\ \beta V_{DS}[2(V_{GS} - V_{T0}) - V_{DS}](1 + \lambda V_{DS}), & 0 < V_{DS} < V_{GS} - V_{T0} \quad (\text{Linear}) \end{cases} \quad (1-1)$$

where model parameter β is the transconductance, λ is the channel-length modulation parameter, and V_{T0} is the threshold voltage.

A curve-fitting method is carried out in Matlab to extract these parameters. Basically V_{T0} can be extracted from the interception point of V_{GS} for the square root value of I_{DS} - V_{GS} graph. The square root of β can be approximated by the slope of the square root value of the same graph [3][8][13]. The optimized V_{T0} , β and λ can be determined by running a least-mean-square (LMS) Matlab program to curve fit the measurement data.

Considering the nominal current rating of the DUT, the curve fitting is done within a current range of 0 to 3 A. The result is shown in Fig. 1-4 as the set of red dashed curves, where as seen a good agreement is achieved between the measured and simulated curves.

Fig. 1-4 Curve-fitting results of SiC JFET output characteristics.
Solid: measurement; dashed: simulation

III.2. Gate Junction Diode Characteristics

The JFET gate-drain and gate-source junctions behave like two diodes when forward-biased, due to the PN junctions formed between the terminals as seen in Fig. 1-2. The static characteristics of the two gate diodes are displayed in Fig. 1-5.

Fig. 1-5 Gate junction diodes forward static characteristics

Note in the figure that due to the asymmetrical structure of the G-D junction and G-S junction, the static characteristics of the two diodes are slightly different. However, the SPICE 2 model uses exactly the same equations to describe these two diodes because in lateral structure JFET the positions of the drain and source terminals are essentially symmetrical. In SPICE the equation for G-D junction is given as follows:

$$I_{GD} = \begin{cases} -I_S + V_{GD}GMIN, & V_{GD} \leq -5\frac{kT}{q} \\ I_S \left(e^{qV_{GD}/kT} - 1 \right) + V_{GD}GMIN, & V_{GD} > -5\frac{kT}{q} \end{cases} \quad (1-2)$$

where I_S is the saturation current, q is the electron charge, T is the temperature in Kelvin and k is the Boltzmann constant. $GMIN$ is a parameter for the sake of convergence in the SPICE simulation. Replacing I_{GD} , V_{GD} with I_{GS} and V_{GS} in (1-2) gives the equation for G-S junction.

In order to extract the model parameters the G-D and G-S diode characteristics are averaged to get one curve for curve-fitting, which is shown as the cyan curve in Fig. 1-5. This is based on the facts that (1) the two characteristics are only slightly different, and (2) the two gate diodes are never forward biased in normal JFET switching operation. Therefore the forward characteristics of these two diodes will not affect the model behavior a lot in our application. The LMS curve fitting is still carried out in Matlab and the result is shown in Fig. 1-6.

Fig. 1-6 Curve-fitting result of gate diode forward characteristics

III.3. Junction Capacitance Characteristics

Two gate junction capacitances, namely gate-source capacitance C_{GS} and gate-drain capacitance C_{GD} are included in the SPICE 2 model. The C_{GS} capacitance is described by

$$C_{GS} = \frac{C_{GS}(0)}{\sqrt{1 - V_{GS}/\phi_0}} \quad (1-3)$$

where the model parameter $C_{GS}(0)$ is the G-S capacitance at zero bias voltage, and ϕ_0 is the gate junction potential parameter. Substituting C_{GS} , V_{GS} with C_{GD} and V_{GD} in (1-3) gives the equation for the C_{GD} capacitance.

The C-V curves can be measured with an Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer [3][4][14]. From the parameter extraction point of view, it is necessary to obtain the C-V characteristics of these two capacitances from zero bias voltage. However, being a normally-on device, the SiC JFET has a shorted channel when it is not pinched off, which means C_{GS} and C_{GD} are effectively paralleled without pinching off the channel. Consequently, the only measurable capacitance from device terminals is the input capacitance C_{ISS} ($= C_{GS} + C_{GD}$). Fig. 1-7 shows three configurations trying to measure C_{GS} and C_{GD} directly, where Hp, Hc and Lp, Lc represent the High Potential / High Current and Low Potential / Low Current terminals of the impedance analyzer. The measurement results shown in Fig. 1-8, however, indicate clearly that the C-V curves measured from the first two setups in Fig. 1-7 overlap from zero bias to around -22 V, the pinch-off voltage. And Fig. 1-7 (c) measurement proves that this overlap range is the C-V characteristic of the input capacitance C_{ISS} .

Fig. 1-7 Direct measurement configurations of junction capacitances.
(a) Measuring G-S terminals, (b) measuring G-D terminals, (c) measuring G-D with D-S shorted

Fig. 1-8 C-V characteristics measured from configurations in Fig. 1-7.
Red: Fig. 1-7 (a); magenta: Fig. 1-7 (b)

In order to measure C_{GS} and C_{GD} separately, it is first necessary to pinch off the JFET channel, and a three-terminal measurement should be implemented with the Agilent 16047E test fixture [15]. Fig. 1-9 shows the 4294A setup for C_{GD} measurement. The black circuits are instrument internal functions to generate the magnitude-phase vs. frequency characteristic of the impedance to be measured; the red part is the equivalent circuit of the JFET, while the blue components are auxiliary circuits. As seen, a voltage source V_G of 25 V is connected across G-S terminals to pinch off the JFET, and C_D is an isolating capacitor to block the ampere meter within the instrument. This configuration, at first sight, seems to be able to measure the correct C_{GD} . However, the external V_G already imposes a negative bias of -25 V across the gate-drain capacitor, and this negative bias cannot be offset by using external DC bias voltage across drain-source terminals because this voltage will be clamped by the JFET body diode. As a result, the C_{GD} - V_{GD} characteristic can only be measured using this method for voltages lower than pinch-off, and C_{GS} - V_{GS} measurement has the same situation [16]. This fact is not discussed in [14].

Fig. 1-9 Impedance analyzer measurement of C_{GD}

Although C_{GS} and C_{GD} cannot be measured independently from zero to pinch-off voltage, the sum of the two can be measured as shown in Fig. 1-8. One way to determine $C_{GS}(0)$ and $C_{GD}(0)$ is to estimate them from $C_{ISS}(0)$ by matching the simulation switching waveforms with the experimental results. Another more reasonable way than “guessing” is to look at the gate charge characteristics of the DUT. However this method is more complicated and requires specially-designed test circuits, thus is not adopted in this work just for simplicity.

The measurement of the drain-source capacitance C_{DS} is similar to that of C_{GS} and C_{GD} , but in this case C_{DS} does not suffer from the pinch-off problem. Fig. 1-10 shows the measurement setup, and the result is displayed in Fig. 1-11. This capacitance does not exist in lateral structure JFET and it will be modeled as the junction capacitance of the body diode, which will be discussed in the next section.

Fig. 1-10 Impedance analyzer measurement of C_{DS}

Fig. 1-11 C_{DS} measurement result

III.4. Body Diode Characteristics

Unlike conventional PiN or Schottky diodes, the I-V characteristic of the SiC JFET body diode is gate-voltage dependent. Fig. 1-12 shows an example of this characteristic. For this SiC JFET (not the same DUT as used above), the channel is completed pinched off below -19 V, whereas the body diode I-V curve is seen to shift to the right with decreasing gate-source voltage, i.e. the turn-on voltage becomes bigger. The slopes of these curves remain constant, which means there is no change in the diode series resistance.

Fig. 1-12 Gate-voltage-dependent body diode I-V curves

This gate-voltage dependence cannot be modeled by any existing model. Therefore in this work, the body diode is still treated as being independent of the gate voltage, where a specific I-V curve is picked according to the final gate voltage used in the circuit. The diode model is built with the *Power Diode Tool* in Synopsys Saber, where the model characteristic curves (i.e. I_{SD} - V_{SD} and C_{DS} - V_{DS} curves) are tuned visually to fit the characterization data [17]. The curve-fitting results are shown in Fig. 1-13, where a good agreement can be seen between the simulation and the measurement. The resultant power diode model is then connected in anti-parallel with the SPICE 2 JFET model working as the body diode as shown in Fig. 1-1 (a).

Fig. 1-13 Body diode curve-fitting results. (a) Forward I-V, (b) junction capacitance

III.5. Other Parameters

In some applications the gate of the SiC JFET is intentionally driven in breakdown mode to adapt to the non-uniformity in the JFET gate characteristics [12]. To include that feature into the device model, an additional SPICE diode model is paralleled to the G-S of the SPICE 2 JFET

model to simulate the gate breakdown effect since it is not modeled in SPICE 2. The only parameters modified in the diode model are BV and VJ. BV is the reverse breakdown voltage and is set as the actual gate breakdown voltage of the SiC JFET. VJ is the junction potential or forward turn-on voltage. This parameter should be set bigger than that of the JFET intrinsic gate-source diode such that it will never be conducting in the simulation.

The internal gate resistance R_{GI} as seen in Fig. 1-1 (a) is also important and necessary for the device model as it determines the ultimate switching speed of the SiC JFET. In this work R_{GI} is finely adjusted to match the experimental waveforms. The package parasitic inductances L_G and L_S , on the other hand, are simply taken as 1 nH each, which are typical values for the TO-220 package.

The finalized parameters for the proposed SiC JFET model are listed in Table 1-2.

Table 1-2 SiC JFET model parameters

Parameter	Value	Unit	Parameter	Value	Unit
SPICE 2 JFET model			ISL	17.673	nA
VT0	-22.02	V	NL	3.037	-
BETA	0.096	AV^{-2}	ISH	97.667	nA
LAMBDA	0.002	V^{-1}	NH	3.887	-
RD	0	Ω	CJO	806.4	pF
RS	0	Ω	VJ	5.8	V
IS	1×10^{-58}	A	M	0.9	-
CGS0	1000	pF	FC	0.5	-
CGD0	190	pF	Other Parameters		
PB	7.7	V	G-S SPICE diode BV	-28	V
FC	0	-	Internal gate RGI	5	Ω
Power diode model (body diode)			Stray LG, LS	1	nH
RS	0.48	Ω			

IV. SiCED SiC JFET Model

The manufacturer SiCED also provides its own SiC JFET model based on the measured data of a typical 1.2 kV SiC JFET, different from the DUT in this work [18]. This is a non-SPICE 2 sub-circuit model, originally given in SPICE codes and then re-coded in Saber MAST language to be used in Saber. The manufacturer didn't provide the information about parameter extraction for this model, therefore it's hard to use this model to fit the device in this work. However, this model still provides an alternative way to model the SiC JFET, and is briefly discussed in this section.

The equivalent circuit of the SiCED model is illustrated in Fig. 1-14. Some model facts are listed as follows:

- 1) Pinch-off voltage: -19 V,

- 2) Gate breakdown voltages: -35.7 V and 2.14 V,
- 3) Zero-biased C_{GD} : 431 pF,
- 4) Zero-biased C_{GS} : 1481 pF,
- 5) Internal gate resistance: 14 Ω ,
- 6) Gate parasitic inductance: 5 nH,
- 7) Source parasitic inductance: 1 nH.

Fig. 1-14 Equivalent circuit of SiCED SiC JFET model. (a) Electrical circuit, (b) thermal circuit

The model uses voltage controlled current sources to describe the channel current and the non-linear capacitance currents, found as GIDK, GCGD, GCGS, and GCDS in Fig. 1-14 (a). A very large resistance RGS is connected between gate and source to model the gate leakage current, while two face-to-face connected diodes are used to model the forward and reverse gate breakdown. The body diode model used is also a self-built model whose equivalent circuit is not displayed here due to complexity. Thermal dynamic characteristics of the device are also modeled through the thermal circuits for both the JFET and the body diode. Fig. 1-14 (b) just shows the thermal circuit of the JFET.

The output characteristics predicted by the SiCED model are shown in Fig. 1-15 (solid curves). The curves predicted by the SPICE 2 model (for DUT in this work) are superimposed in the same figure just for comparison.

Fig. 1-15 Output characteristics. (Solid) SiCED model, (dashed) SPICE 2 model

V. Model Verifications

The SiC JFET model is simulated in an inductive-load double-pulse tester circuit in Saber for verification purposes. A real double-pulse tester as shown in Fig. 1-16 has been built to study the switching characteristics and the design of an ultra-fast gate driver for the SiC JFET. The device is driven by a high-speed, high-current gate driver IC IXYS IXDD414, with gate bias voltage from -30 V to 0 V. An R-C-D network is used between the gate driver and the JFET to adapt to the non-uniformity in the gate characteristics of different devices [12]. With this network, the JFET is working in the gate breakdown mode, and the capacitor in the R-C-D network takes the difference between the breakdown voltage and the gate drive turn-off voltage. A 1.2 kV, 10 A prototype SiC Schottky diode by Infineon is used as the free-wheeling diode, and a shunt resistor SSDN-10 manufactured by T&M Research [19] is used for drain current measurement.

Fig. 1-16 JFET double-pulse tester schematic

The same circuit is simulated in Saber to verify the JFET model previously built. Due to the lack of Infineon diode model, a similar model for the Cree 1.2 kV, 10 A SiC Schottky diode is

used instead. A comparison between experimental switching waveforms and the simulated results is displayed in Fig. 1-17.

Fig. 1-17 Model verification: experiment vs. simulation. Time: 5 ns/div. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off

The waveforms are obtained under 600 V and 5.5 A load conditions. To do the comparison the experimental and simulated gate voltage V_{GS} waveforms are aligned in timing. As seen, for the turn-on transients the JFET drain-source voltage V_{DS} and drain current I_D have around 4 ns advance in time compared to the experiments, which means the model predicts less turn-on delay than the real condition. Nonetheless 4 ns is small enough and tolerable in this work. The slew rates of V_{DS} and I_D are predicted quite well by the model during both turn-on and turn-off processes, indicating that the model is good enough overall in predicting the correct waveforms and switching loss of the SiC JFET. Also note that the additional SPICE diode model is working well because during turn-off V_{GS} stops at around -28 V, the gate breakdown voltage, instead of -30 V, the gate drive turn-off voltage. The only intolerable difference is the turn-on current spike which in the simulation is about 4 A higher than the experiment. This current spike is mainly

related to the characteristics of the freewheeling diode. If the Infineon diode model is available, the simulation would match the experiment even better.

As stated previously, in the SPICE 2 model the ratio of the Miller (gate-drain) capacitance C_{GD} and the gate-source capacitance C_{GS} should be adjusted by trial and error in order to match the experimental waveforms, since only C_{ISS} could be directly measured. Some interesting observations can thus be made from this matching process. With a fixed input capacitance C_{ISS} , the ratio of C_{GD} and C_{GS} is of vital importance to the slew rate of the switching waveforms. Generally C_{GD} is smaller than C_{GS} due to the fact that the gate-drain junction is thicker than that of gate-source in a vertical structure device, and that the junction capacitance is inversely proportional to the junction width (See Fig. 1-2). Moreover, smaller C_{GD}/C_{GS} ratio leads to faster slew rate. This conclusion can be supported by the switching behavior analysis of either MOSFETs or JFETs [20], which will be further discussed in the following chapters.

Another fact worth noting is the fast switching speed of this SiC JFET. As seen from Fig. 1-17, the DUT switches 600 A and 5.5 A within 20 to 30 ns, achieving a maximum dv/dt rate of around 60 kV/ μ s and a maximum di/dt rate of 3 kA/ μ s, much faster than the commercially available silicon unipolar technology (e.g. MOSFET) of similar nominal voltage and current ratings. It is thus foreseeable that with the use of SiC devices, the high-frequency, high-temperature and high-power-density applications will become achievable more easily.

VI. Conclusions and Discussions

This chapter has proposed a SPICE 2-based SiC JFET model which is suitable for system-level simulation, and has presented the modeling process of a 1.2 kV, 5 A SiC JFET prototype from SiCED. To extract the model parameters, device characterizations have been conducted on this JFET. Issues during the characterization process have been explained and solutions been provided. By comparing simulation with experiment the effectiveness of the device model has also been verified.

The SPICE 2 JFET model is chosen as the base of the proposed SiC JFET model in the first place because (1) it is a compact model which does not contain too many parameters. This is a preferable feature considering that the model will finally be used in system-level simulation. And (2) the model parameters do not contain physical ones that are inaccessible to the device users, thus are easy to be extracted from conventional characterization process. Nevertheless, the use of the SPICE 2 model also poses some limitations to the final SiC JFET model.

First of all, since the SPICE 2 model is originally developed for lateral structure JFETs, the equation (1-1) is not able to describe the complete static behavior of the SiC JFET very well. Fig. 1-18 (a) is the curve fitting result of (1-1) in 0 to 3 A current range, which looks quite good, whereas Fig. 1-18 (b) shows the same curve fitting but on a 0 to 20 A scale. It can be seen clearly that the SPICE model fails to match the measurement as current increases, although in our case this won't bother because the SiC JFET to be modeled will never operate in that high current range.

Fig. 1-18 SPICE 2 model unable to predict static characteristics in large scale. (a) 0-3 A curve fitting, (b) same curve fitting in 0-20 A scale

The second problem is with the gate diode description. Under the assumption of symmetrical lateral structure the SPICE model uses the same equation for both G-D and G-S diodes, which is not true for the vertical structure of the SiC JFET. Besides, there is no emission coefficient n existent in (1-2) which would usually appear in the exponential term $\exp(qV/nkT)$. This leads to the unreasonable small saturation current I_S (1×10^{-58} A) from curve fitting.

Thirdly, though the SPICE model requires junction capacitance parameters CGS0 and CGD0, it has been explained above that it is not easy to directly measure these two capacitances from zero bias. Although in this chapter the two parameters are adjusted to match the experiments, using the gate charge characteristic is still a better way to more precisely determine their values.

Some other work that has not been conducted but is worth doing includes the temperature-dependent device characterization and modeling. This is important since the SiC JFET would not be working in room temperature in the converter eventually. The same characterization process introduced in this chapter can still be applied, except that the junction temperature of the device needs to be controlled during measurement. Besides that, future efforts are also worthwhile in studying and understanding the nature of the SiC JFET body diode.

VII. References

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Chapter 2 CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING OF 1.2 kV, 20 A SiC MOSFETs

I. Introduction

Silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFET has become another competitor among new wide bandgap devices which is promising to substitute silicon (Si) devices in high-voltage, high-frequency applications, due to its higher breakdown voltage, lower on-state resistance, and better high-temperature operation capability [1]-[3]. Compared to SiC JFET, it also possesses the advantage of being a normally-off device, providing more benefits to the converters in terms of safe operation and failure protection. Currently, laboratory prototypes of this new device are still under improvement and have not been commercialized yet, which means manufacturer datasheets are still unavailable. Therefore, it is necessary to fully characterize these SiC MOSFETs in order to evaluate their potential performance in converter systems and to compare them with their Si counterparts. The work described in this chapter investigates a TO-247 packaged, 1.2 kV, 20 A SiC MOSFET manufactured by CREE [4] (See Fig. 2-1). The most important static characteristics, namely I-V curves, body diode, junction capacitances, etc, have all been measured and their respective measurement methods have been described as well. The static characterizations have also been carried out under different temperatures from 25 °C to 200 °C, the results of which show the superiorities of the SiC device under much higher junction temperature than Si.

Fig. 2-1 CREE 1.2 kV, 20 A prototype SiC MOSFET in TO-247 package

The switching characterization of the device has been conducted under room temperature as well. A carefully designed double-pulse tester (DPT) with minimized circuit parasitics is used to reveal the intrinsic switching behavior of the SiC MOSFET. Important quantities such as switching times and losses are also recorded and investigated in this chapter.

For the design and analysis of converters utilizing the new device, a compact device model is also a necessity. In this chapter, the Synopsys Saber *Power MOSFET Tool* – a mature Si MOSFET modeling tool – has been used to model the SiC MOSFET successfully. This chapter presents its use as well as some modeling issues and measures about predicting more accurate switching waveforms of the SiC MOSFET.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The SiC MOSFET prototype will be fully characterized such that its static and switching performance can be evaluated in the absence of manufacturer datasheet. The device model will then be built based on the characterization data with the use of mature Si MOSFET modeling tool. The use of the device model through circuit simulation can finally replace the time-consuming hardware iterations, greatly easing the design and analysis process of high-power PEBB utilizing the new device.

I.2. Technical Approaches

For static characterizations, the DC characteristics (i.e. I-V curves) are measured with a Tektronix 371B curve tracer, while the AC characteristics (i.e. impedances) are measured using an Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer. Because neither instrument provides elevated temperature, a hotplate is used to heat the device such that temperature-dependent characteristics can be measured. Fig. 2-2 shows an example of such characterization setup where the curve tracer is used to measure the I-V curves of the MOSFET.

Fig. 2-2 Static characterization setup

The switching characteristics, on the other hand, are measured using a carefully designed double-pulse tester, as shown in Fig. 2-3. With the use of this tester, the SiC MOSFET can be switched under any desired voltage, current, as well as junction temperature. Meanwhile, the PCB layout of the tester is also optimized such that the impact of the circuit parasitics on the device switching waveforms is reduced to the minimum.

Fig. 2-3 Double-pulse tester for switching characterization. (a) Tester schematic, (b) tester

The characterization data are then imported into Saber's *Power MOSFET Tool* to build the device model for the SiC MOSFET. In this tool, the model parameters are extracted by visually fitting the model curves against the measured curves. The detailed characterization and modeling process will be described in the following sections.

II. Static Characterizations

The static characterizations of SiC MOSFET include DC characteristics measured with a Tektronix 371B curve tracer, and AC characteristics measured using an Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer. The DC characteristics are represented by the leakage current I_{DSS} , output and transfer characteristics, on-state resistance $R_{DS(ON)}$, and body diode I-V curves. The AC characteristics include the internal gate resistance R_{GI} , nonlinear junction capacitances, as well as package parasitic inductances. All these parameters are directly related to the performance evaluation and modeling of the device. For the temperature-dependent characterization, a hotplate is used to heat the MOSFET since neither of the above mentioned instruments can deal with elevated temperatures.

II.1. Drain Leakage Current I_{DSS}

Same as the drain-source breakdown voltage BV_{DSS} , the drain leakage current is also an evaluation of the device blocking capability. However, I_{DSS} is adopted in this work instead of BV_{DSS} because it is measured under the rated voltage with the gate-source terminals shorted, hence avoiding the risk of destroying the device. Fig. 2-4 shows the measurement results, where a positive temperature coefficient for I_{DSS} can be inferred. As seen from the figure, the leakage current is well below $10 \mu\text{A}$ for the entire temperature range, which indicates a good blocking capability of the device at the rated voltage.

Fig. 2-4 Leakage current vs. temperature

II.2. Output and Transfer Characteristics

The output characteristics are measured under different gate voltage V_{GS} up to 15 V – the suggested drive voltage by the manufacturer. The transfer characteristic, on the other hand, is obtained under 15 V V_{DS} bias while varying V_{GS} . Fig. 2-5 plots these characteristics under 25, 100, 125 and 200 °C respectively. As seen from Fig. 2-5 (a), the trend of the output I-V curves of this 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET under varying temperature is quite different from what would be expected for Si MOSFETs. For $V_{GS} < 9$ V, the channel conductivity improves with the increasing temperature, while for $V_{GS} = 15$ V the slope of the I-V curve first becomes steeper but then decreases again as the temperature increases. For the transfer characteristics shown in Fig. 2-5 (b), the threshold voltage $V_{GS(TH)}$ decreases with increasing temperature as expected, whereas the transconductance g_{fs} increases. This is again against the general knowledge about Si MOSFETs that g_{fs} should drop under higher temperature. These phenomena, however, can be explained from the variation trend of the on-state resistance about temperature in the next section.

(a)

Fig. 2-5 Temperature-dependent output (a) and transfer (b) characteristics

II.3. On-State Resistance $R_{DS(ON)}$

The on-state resistance can be read directly from the output characteristic curves. In this work $R_{DS(ON)}$ is measured under $V_{GS} = 15$ V and $I_D = 10$ A. Fig. 2-6 shows the variation of $R_{DS(ON)}$ with regard to the temperature.

Fig. 2-6 On-state resistance vs. temperature

Different from Si, the SiC MOSFET takes on an initial decrease in $R_{DS(ON)}$ with increasing temperature at low temperatures, then followed by an increase at higher temperatures. This is because of the different temperature dependence of three primary resistances within the device: channel resistance R_{CH} , JFET resistance R_{JFET} , and drift layer resistance R_{DRIFT} . R_{CH} decreases with increasing temperature due to the threshold voltage reduction and simultaneous increase in the channel mobility. R_{JFET} and R_{DRIFT} , on the other hand, increase as temperature rises due to the more active lattice vibrations. At low temperatures, R_{CH} decreases faster than the combined effect of R_{JFET} and R_{DRIFT} , causing the initial decrease in $R_{DS(ON)}$. At higher temperatures, the increasing effect of R_{JFET} and R_{DRIFT} dominates the overall resistance, resulting in the

consequent increase in $R_{DS(ON)}$. The non-intuitive temperature-dependence of the output and transfer characteristics is thus explained.

It needs to be noted that the above phenomenon is only observed for 1.2 kV level devices, since their channel resistance is comparable to the JFET and drift layer resistances. For higher voltage rating SiC MOSFET (e.g. 10 kV), the much thicker drift layer makes R_{CH} negligible compared to R_{DRIFT} and thus gives a positive temperature coefficient for $R_{DS(ON)}$ at all temperatures [3].

When comparing with state-of-the-art Si technology, a 5-8 times reduction in $R_{DS(ON)}$ can be found for SiC MOSFET at this voltage level. Fig. 2-7 (a) illustrates the on-state resistance comparison between the SiC MOSFET under study and a 600 V, 20 A Si CoolMOS (APT20N60BCF by MicroSemi), while Fig. 2-7 (b) sketches the $R_{DS(ON)}$ breakdown for SiC and Si MOSFETs respectively. As seen from the figures, the higher breakdown field of the SiC material allows big shrink in drift layer thickness to block the same voltage, resulting in much smaller on-state resistance. Moreover, the junction temperature of SiC MOSFET can go up to as high as 200 °C, while 150 °C is almost the limit for normal Si MOSFET operation. Over the entire temperature range, the resistance of SiC MOSFET is also seen to be less sensitive to the temperature change compared to Si MOSFET.

Fig. 2-7 $R_{DS(ON)}$ comparison: Si vs. SiC

II.4. Gate Threshold Voltage $V_{GS(TH)}$

In some application notes, the gate threshold voltage $V_{GS(TH)}$ is defined as the gate-source voltage which produces 250 μA drain current when drain and gate are shorted (e.g. $V_{DS} = V_{GS}$) [5], but this criterion differs. Some datasheets use bigger drain current such as 1 mA, 2.5 mA, etc, which leads to bigger $V_{GS(TH)}$. This work follows the criterion of 250 μA .

The curve tracer is still used for this measurement because it can sense very small current (μA to mA level) in the High Voltage Mode. However, under this mode the minimum voltage resolution of the instrument is 50 V/div, too coarse for $V_{GS(TH)}$ measurement. Thus an oscilloscope is used to measure the accurate gate-source peak voltage, whose results are shown in Fig. 2-8. As one can see, $V_{GS(TH)}$ basically decreases with the increasing temperature, with its lowest value found to be 1.5 V at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Note that if a higher drain current criterion were used, the measured $V_{GS(TH)}$ would be higher. However the lower $V_{GS(TH)}$ at higher temperatures still indicates potential false trigger problem of the SiC MOSFET when operating in full power.

Fig. 2-8 Gate threshold voltage vs. temperature

II.5. Body Diode I-V Characteristics

The body diode I-V curves are shown in Fig. 2-9. Less steep slants are observed as expected due to the increasing series resistance of the diode as the temperature goes up. However, the forward turn-on voltage does not always decrease as expected, and an increase is observed for the 200 °C condition. This phenomenon is different from conventional Si MOSFETs. The cause, according to the manufacturer, is that the body diode conduction involves certain interaction with the MOSFET channel, thus this diode is not a pure PiN diode and its I-V curves are also affected by the channel I-V characteristics. However the essential mechanism behind this phenomenon is still under study now and publications about this issue have not been found so far.

Fig. 2-9 Temperature-dependent body diode I-V curves

II.6. Internal Gate Resistance R_{GI}

The internal gate resistance is modeled as a lumped resistance in series with the MOSFET gate terminal, representing the distributed resistor network connecting the individual cells within

the device [6]. Its value is important as it affects the time constant of the gate voltage and ultimately determines the switching speed limit of the SiC MOSFET. However, this parameter is usually not provided in the datasheet. The measurement of R_{GI} is identical to the measurement of a capacitor equivalent series resistance (ESR), and is carried out with an impedance analyzer measuring the gate-source terminals with the drain and source of the device shorted, as shown in Fig. 2-10 (a). This setup equivalently measures the impedance of R_{GI} in series with the input capacitance $C_{ISS} (= C_{GS} + C_{GD})$, seen as Fig. 2-10 (b).

Fig. 2-10 Internal gate resistance measurement setup.
(a) Measurement setup, (b) equivalent circuit

The measurement results are displayed in Fig. 2-11. Fig. 2-11 (a) exhibits the originally measured impedance vs. frequency curves. As one can see, the distributed parameter nature of the internal gate resistance causes several resonant peaks beyond 30 MHz, whereas only one value should be selected for the lumped R_{GI} model. If choosing the resistance at the first resonant peak (at around 38 MHz), then R_{GI} vs. temperature graph can be plotted in Fig. 2-11 (b), which depicts an linearly increasing resistance of 0.4Ω to 0.55Ω with the increasing temperature.

(b)

Fig. 2-11 Internal gate resistance. (a) Measured impedance at 25 °C, (b) R_{GI} vs. temperature

II.7. Nonlinear Junction Capacitances C_{ISS}, C_{RSS} and C_{OSS}

The junction capacitances, namely input capacitance C_{ISS} (= C_{GS} + C_{GD}), reverse transfer capacitance (or Miller capacitance) C_{RSS} (= C_{GD}), and output capacitance C_{OSS} (= C_{DS} + C_{GD}), are formed by the gate oxide layer and PN junctions within the MOSFET. From the device structure, the gate oxide layer capacitance C_{GS} is essentially a linear capacitance, while the PN junction capacitances C_{GD} and C_{DS} are strongly nonlinear functions of drain-source voltage V_{DS} [7]. These parameters are of vital importance to the MOSFET as they determine the dynamic behavior of the device during switching transients. As for their measurements, the impedance analyzer alone is not sufficient as it cannot provide high enough voltage to bias the device (only 40 V maximum for Agilent 4294A). In this case, auxiliary circuits are adopted together with the impedance analyzer to extend the voltage bias to a much wider range. The circuits used in this work are modified from [5] and [8], and are illustrated in Fig. 2-12 through Fig. 2-14.

Fig. 2-12 C_{ISS} measurement setups. (a) Real circuit, (b) equivalent AC circuit

Fig. 2-13 C_{OSS} measurement setups. (a) Real circuit, (b) equivalent AC circuit

Fig. 2-14 C_{RSS} measurement setups. (a) Real circuit, (b) equivalent AC circuit

In the above figures, the 1 μF capacitor directly connected to the “H” terminal is used to isolate the instrument from the high voltage DC source V_{DS} . The oscillation level of the impedance analyzer is chosen to be only 50 mV because the junction capacitances are very sensitive to the amplitude of the small signal. The capacitance values are read at 1 MHz for all measurements, which is also the frequency used in most datasheets. With the above configurations, the measured capacitance is effectively the junction capacitance in series with the isolation capacitance, and the capacitance of interest can be simply compensated by

$$C_u = \frac{C_k C_m}{C_k - C_m} \quad (2-1)$$

where C_u is the junction capacitance to be measured, C_k is the isolation capacitance, and C_m is the measured capacitance. In this case, however, considering that junction capacitances are usually in the range of tens of pF to several nF, these measurements will still produce very small error even without compensating off C_k , namely $C_u \approx C_m$.

The measurements are taken under three different temperatures 25, 125, and 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ respectively, and the results are shown in Fig. 2-15. As seen, the junction capacitances drop drastically in the first 30 V and then decrease very slowly as the bias voltage continues increasing. The bias voltage stops at 250 V since the trend of each C-V curve can be seen clearly and extrapolation is quite easy. One can also tell from the overlapped curves that the C-V characteristics are insensitive to the change of temperature.

Fig. 2-15 Temperature-dependent capacitance-voltage characteristics

It also needs to be noted that, although the measurement circuits look very simple, they cannot be implemented using breadboards, because the breadboards themselves carry tens of pF intrinsic parasitic capacitance which will cause great relative error to the measurement results at high V_{DS} bias. For this reason, three small printed circuit boards (PCB) are made to provide interconnection for each measurement. Besides eliminating parasitic capacitances, these small PCBs are also suitable for temperature-dependent measurements, as seen in Fig. 2-16 (a) and (b).

Fig. 2-16 Junction capacitance measurement PCBs.
(a) DUT and PCBs, (b) setup for elevated temperature measurements

II.8. Package Stray Inductances L_G , L_D and L_S

The device under study is in a TO-247 package. The stray impedances of the package can be lumped by three inductances L_G , L_D and L_S , which are in series with the gate, drain, and source terminals respectively [9]. Basically three measurements are necessary to extract the stray inductances. As shown in Fig. 2-17, measuring the inductance between gate and source terminals with the drain floating gives the value of $L_G + L_S$. Likewise, measuring drain and source inductance gives $L_D + L_S$, and measuring gate and drain gives $L_G + L_D$. The respective stray inductances can then be simply calculated from these measurements. In this case, the inductances are measured to be $L_G = 4.5$ nH, $L_D = 0.04$ nH, and $L_S = 3.2$ nH respectively, which are typical values for the package. Note that L_D is much smaller than the other two inductances because the drain of the MOSFET is attached to the package case, forming smaller loop and thus smaller inductance.

Fig. 2-17 Measurements of package stray inductances

The measured stray inductances, however, are strongly affected by the lead lengths in the measurements. The above results are measured at the roots of the package leads (See Fig. 2-18 (a)), but when measured at the tips of the leads, the inductances would be almost five times bigger (Fig. 2-18 (b)). Therefore, when including package parasitics in the MOSFET model, it is important to relate the actual stray inductances to how the device is mounted on the PCB, otherwise the stray inductance values would be meaningless.

Fig. 2-18 Different measurements of package stray inductances. (a) At roots, (b) at tips

III. Switching Characterizations

The switching characteristics of the SiC MOSFET are also measured under room temperature with the use of the double-pulse tester as shown in Fig. 2-3 (a). The circuit layout of the tester is designed carefully to minimize the parasitics, so that the switching waveforms can reflect the device behavior as faithfully as possible. The gate drive chip used is IXYS IXDD414 which can achieve rise and fall times of 10 ns when driving 2 nF capacitive load. The drive voltage applied is 0-15 V. The freewheeling diode is a 1.2 kV, 20 A SiC Schottky barrier diode (SBD) prototype from Infineon. The use of the SBD eliminates the reverse recovery effect, and thus limits the current spike of the MOSFET during turn-on. The tests are done up to 600 V DC bus voltage, while varying the load current from 4 A to 10 A (considering margin for the current spike). The switching speed is adjusted by using different gate resistances of 10 Ω , 5 Ω and 2 Ω respectively.

The characterization setup is illustrated in Fig. 2-19. As seen, the double-pulse signals with adjustable pulse widths are sent to the tester through an arbitrary waveform generator, controlled by a PC controller through the USB or RS-232 interface. The switching waveforms of

the SiC MOSFET are then measured by an oscilloscope and the data are transferred back to the controller through the GPIB or LAN interface. The PC controller is responsible for editing the double-pulse signals, collecting switching waveforms, and after that calculating switching times and losses automatically in MATLAB. With this configuration, the post-measurement data processing can be done as soon as the waveforms are collected.

Fig. 2-19 Switching characterization setup

III.1. Typical Switching Waveforms of SiC MOSFET

Fig. 2-20 shows the typical turn-on and turn-off transients of the gate voltage V_{GS} and current I_G , the drain-source voltage V_{DS} , as well as the drain current I_D , under 600 V, 8 A switching condition with a gate resistance of 10 Ω . As seen from the figure, the rise and fall slew rates of I_D are quite fast compared to V_{DS} , achieving 6.5 ns during turn-on and 24.4 ns during turn-off, while it takes 63.1 ns and 41.2 ns for V_{DS} to achieve full swing during turn-on and turn-off respectively. Also, compared with typical Si MOSFET gate voltage waveform, the SiC MOSFET does not have a very obvious “plateau” region in V_{GS} . This is because the SiC MOSFET has a bigger channel-length modulation coefficient than the conventional Si device. Or, in another word, the I-V curves of the SiC MOSFET are not as flat as those of Si MOSFET in the saturation region, which can be inferred from Fig. 2-5 (a).

Similar switching characteristics can also be observed in other switching conditions with reduced gate resistance. Fig. 2-21 shows the typical switching waveforms under 600 V, 8 A with $R_G = 5 \Omega$, while Fig. 2-22 exhibits the 600 V, 4 A, $R_G = 2 \Omega$ case. As seen, using smaller gate resistance makes the switching speed faster. However, this also causes more severe parasitic ringing during the switching transients, which is apparent from these figures.

**Fig. 2-20 Typical turn-on (a) and turn-off (b) waveforms under 600 V, 8 A with $R_G = 10 \Omega$.
Time: 40 ns/div**

**Fig. 2-21 Typical turn-on (a) and turn-off (b) waveforms under 600 V, 8 A with $R_G = 5 \Omega$.
Time: 20 ns/div**

Fig. 2-22 Typical turn-on (a) and turn-off (b) waveforms under 600 V, 4 A with $R_G = 2 \Omega$.
Time: 20 ns/div

III.2. Body Diode Reverse Recovery Characteristic

The reverse recovery characteristic of the SiC MOSFET body diode has also been tested using a similar tester except that the body diode now is working as the freewheeling diode. Fig. 2-23 shows the comparison of the body diode reverse recovery characteristic between the SiC MOSFET, a 1.2 kV SiC SBD from CREE, and a 600 V Si CoolMOS from MicroSemi. At present, the inferior performance of the Si MOSFET body diode is the main bottleneck for high-frequency applications with ZVS operation. From the figure, however, it can be seen that the body diode of SiC MOSFET has a significant improvement in the reverse recovery performance, with only about 40 ns reverse recovery time (t_{rr}) at the room temperature. This performance is even comparable to that of the SiC Schottky diode. The low t_{rr} is mainly a result of the very small minority carrier lifetime as well as the thin drift layer. Moreover, unlike Si devices, t_{rr} of the SiC MOSFET is relatively insensitive to the temperature change [10].

Fig. 2-23 Body diode reverse recovery characteristic comparison between 1.2 kV SiC SBD, 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET, and 600 V Si CoolMOS. Measured at room temperature

III.3. Major Switching Characteristics

Fig. 2-24 exhibits the device total turn-on and turn-off times at 600 V as a function of the load current for different gate resistances. As seen, both the turn-on and turn-off times are approximately in linear proportion to the load current. The turn-on time increases with the load current, which is in accord with the common intuition, whereas the turn-off time decreases with the load current. This reduction is because higher drain current leads to higher “plateau” voltage in V_{GS} during turn-off, increasing the gate discharge current and thus speeding up the turn-off process.

Also note in the figure that only one load current (4 A) is tested for $R_G = 2 \Omega$ case. This is to leave enough margins for the very high current spike (almost three times the steady-state value as seen in Fig. 2-22 (a)) during MOSFET turn-on process that would possibly degrade the device’s static characteristics. The next section will discuss more about the device degradation.

Fig. 2-24 Switching times vs. load current at 600 V, for different switching speeds.
(left) Turn-on times, (right) turn-off times

Fig. 2-25 Switching energies vs. load current at 600 V, for different switching speeds.
(left) Turn-on energies, (right) turn-off energies

Fig. 2-25 shows the switching energies versus drain current for different switching speeds. Both the turn-on and turn-off energies increase almost linearly with the load. However, E_{off} does not increase as fast as E_{on} because of the reduction in the turn-off time. Also seen from the figure is the remarkable reduction in the switching energies as the gate resistance is cut by half from 10Ω to 5Ω , while only minor improvement can be observed when R_G is further reduced by

half to 2 Ω . Fig. 2-26, on the other hand, exhibits the device stresses under the increasing switching speed, which implies that the benefits obtained from faster switching speed are accompanied by the penalties of worse device stresses and electromagnetic noises due to the high-frequency parasitic ringing.

Fig. 2-26 Device stresses vs. load current for different switching speeds. (left) I_D overshoot during turn-on, (right) V_{DS} overshoot during turn-off

III.4. Summary of Device Characteristics

To summarize the SiC MOSFET static and switching characterization results, the following “datasheet” can be tabulated.

Table 2-1 CREE 1.2 kV, 20 A SiC MOSFET datasheet

Parameter	Symbol	Test Conditions	Value	Unit
Drain leakage current	I_{DSS}	$V_{GS} = 0 \text{ V}$, $V_{DS} = 1200 \text{ V}$	3.5 / 9.2 ⁽¹⁾	μA
Gate threshold voltage	$V_{GS(TH)}$	$V_{GS} = V_{DS}$, $I_D = 250 \mu\text{A}$	2.1 / 1.7 ⁽¹⁾	V
On-state resistance	$R_{DS(ON)}$	$V_{GS} = 15 \text{ V}$, $I_D = 10 \text{ A}$	0.124 / 0.137 ⁽¹⁾	Ω
Input capacitance	C_{ISS}	$f = 1 \text{ MHz}$, osc. level = 50 mV	1955 / 1864 ⁽²⁾	pF
Output capacitance	C_{OSS}		617 / 170 ⁽²⁾	
Reverse transfer capacitance	C_{RSS}		185 / 37 ⁽²⁾	
Gate stray inductance	L_G	Osc. level = 500 mV	4.5	nH
Drain stray inductance	L_D		0.04	
Source stray inductance	L_S		3.2	
Turn-on time	t_{on}	$V_{DS} = 600 \text{ V}$, $V_{GS} = 0/15 \text{ V}$, $I_D = 10 \text{ A}$	83.7 / 50.5 ⁽³⁾	ns
Turn-on energy	E_{on}		268.5 / 161.0 ⁽³⁾	μJ
Turn-off time	t_{off}		49.1 / 31.4 ⁽³⁾	ns
Turn-off energy	E_{off}		134.0 / 97.7 ⁽³⁾	μJ

If not specified, all data are in room temperature ($\sim 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

(1) Before slash – $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; after slash – $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

(2) Before slash – $V_{DS} = 25 \text{ V}$; after slash – $V_{DS} = 200 \text{ V}$.

(3) Before slash – $R_G = 10 \Omega$; after slash – $R_G = 5 \Omega$.

IV. Device Degradation

Device degradation has also been observed after the switching characterization. Fig. 2-27 exhibits the static I-V curves of one SiC MOSFET before (red curves) and after (blue curves) the double-pulse tests. This specific DUT has been switched up to 800 V and 20 A with 15 V gate voltage. As seen, the threshold voltage $V_{GS(TH)}$ increases by more than 1 V, and the on-state resistance $R_{DS(ON)}$ doubles from 124 m Ω to 249 m Ω after the switching tests. The body diode I-V characteristic has degraded as well. The same kind of degradation has also been confirmed by the manufacturer. The cause of the degradation, however, has many possible explanations.

Fig. 2-27 SiC MOSFET degradation after switching tests. (a) Output characteristics, (b) transfer characteristic, (c) body diode I-V characteristic. Red – before test; blue – after test

There have been several papers discussing the reliability issues of the SiC MOSFET [11]-[13]. According to [11], one possibility of degradation is due to the gate oxide defects which tend to increase the threshold voltage $V_{GS(TH)}$, and resultantly increase $R_{DS(ON)}$ under the same gate voltage. The oxide defects are caused by the so-called Fowler-Nordheim tunneling current, which is higher for SiC than Si under the same oxide layer electric field due to the inherent property of the SiC-dielectric interface. Besides, to achieve a very low $R_{DS(ON)}$ a 15 V gate voltage is used to switch the SiC MOSFET, which is higher than the normal gate voltage (usually 10 V) for Si MOSFET. In this sense, SiC MOSFETs would face more serious long-term reliability issue than Si MOSFETs. According to [11]-[12], the gate oxide reliability issue is the most likely cause of the degradation for this 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET.

Another degradation mechanism is the stacking faults. It is reported in [13] that the phenomenon of recombination-induced stacking faults (SFs) will occur in 10 kV-level SiC MOSFETs when the body diode is conducting. The SFs are claimed to be caused by the basal plane dislocations formed in the epi-layer during the recombination process, and are positively related to the thickness of this layer. Device degradations, such as higher $R_{DS(ON)}$, larger leakage current and greater body diode on-voltage, etc, will occur due to the SFs. Therefore, it is recommended in [13] that the body diode of the 10 kV-level SiC MOSFET be bypassed by an external anti-parallel diode. However, as the epi-layer thickness reduces for lower voltage structures, such as the 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET in this work, the SFs, although still existent, are not expected to show significant impact on the device degradations.

To verify this statement, a SF test is conducted on the 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET by conducting a continuous DC current of 5 A in its body diode. The case temperature is kept at 50 °C during the test, and the conduction continues for 0.5, 1, and 1.5 hours sequentially, adding up to a total of 3 hours, similar to the test conditions used in [13]. The MOSFET output and transfer characteristics, as well as the body diode I-V curve are measured after each period, and the results are shown in Fig. 2-28. As seen, no obvious degradation can be observed after the SF test, implying that SFs are not very likely to be the cause of degradation in this work.

Fig. 2-28 Stacking faults test results.

(a) Output characteristics, (b) transfer characteristic, (c) body diode I-V characteristic

However, the above short-term test still cannot guarantee the long-term reliability of the device. It has also been noticed that the degradation occurs only after the device switching high current. For instance, when the switching current of the MOSFET is limited within 10 A, the device is safe and its static characteristics almost do not change. Nonetheless, when the current is close to 20 A, the degradation becomes apparent right away. From this angle, the degradation may also be related to the high-current conduction in the MOSFET channel, or the combined effect of both high current and the resultant high junction temperature. Future efforts are necessary to identify the ultimate cause of the degradation.

If necessary, the following process (Fig. 2-29) can be adopted to identify the real cause of the degradation, although the physics behind it still needs further study.

Fig. 2-29 Testing process to identify the cause of device degradation

V. Modeling of SiC MOSFET

V.1. General Structure of a Power MOSFET Subcircuit Model

There have been several preceding papers on the modeling of SiC MOSFET. Some papers developed physical models for SiC MOSFET which focused more on the fundamental physical characteristics of the device, such as [14]-[16]. This type of MOSFET model is not suitable for circuit simulation and system analysis, so is not preferred in this work. More papers used subcircuit model instead to describe the SiC MOSFET [17]-[19]. [20]-[22] discussed subcircuit models of Si power MOSFET but many concepts and ideas introduced in these references are still valuable for SiC MOSFET modeling. Although the developed model differs in each work, the structures of these models, however, are more or less similar, and can be simplified as the circuit shown in Fig. 2-30.

Fig. 2-30 General subcircuit model structure of power MOSFETs

The major components of the MOSFET model include:

(A) MOS: Ideal MOSFET

The MOS part in the model structure looks like a MOSFET. Indeed this part represents an ideal MOSFET and describes the static I-V characteristics of the device, namely output and transfer characteristics and their temperature dependence. This is the most common subject in most MOSFET modeling papers, and different papers have different ways to describe this part. For example, [17] and [19] reuse the built-in lateral MOSFET model in SPICE to describe the characteristics of SiC MOSFET; [18], on the other hand, established its own channel current expressions that considered the different channel regions and enhanced linear region transconductance of SiC MOSFETs. No matter what method is used, the goal is always to capture the device static characteristics accurately.

(B) Body diode

The body diode is a parasitic component formed by the PN junction between the drain-source terminals of the vertical structure power MOSFET. This diode is necessary for the MOSFET if used, and can usually be modeled as a power diode connected in anti-parallel with the MOSFET. The major characteristics include the forward conduction characteristic, junction capacitance, as well as reverse recovery characteristic. The junction capacitance can usually be lumped into the MOSFET drain-source capacitance C_{DS} . [23] and [24] discussed general PiN diode modeling and SiC PiN diode modeling.

(C) C_{GS} , C_{GD} and C_{DS} : MOSFET parasitic capacitances

The capacitances surrounding the MOSFET in Fig. 2-30 are the device parasitic capacitances, where C_{GS} is mainly the gate oxide capacitance and C_{GD} , C_{DS} represent the PN junction capacitances between gate-drain and drain-source terminals. These parameters are significant to the MOSFET model because they determine the switching behavior of the device.

Most models treat C_{GS} as a linear capacitance due to the fact that it is mainly formed by a linear dielectric – the gate oxide layer. However, as some papers pointed out, this capacitance increases when V_{GS} becomes negative [21]-[22]. This nonlinearity is important for the model when a negative gate voltage is used.

C_{GD} is also called the Miller capacitance and is the most important nonlinear capacitance for the MOSFET model especially in the inductive load, hard-switching condition, due to the Miller effect [21]. The reason for this will be explained mathematically later. Different papers use different nonlinear equations to describe the voltage dependence of this capacitance, and the independent variable (i.e. the voltage) also differs. Some papers model C_{GD} to be dependent on V_{GD} [17][18][20], while some other works and most datasheets express C_{GD} as a function of V_{DS} .

C_{DS} is also a nonlinear function of V_{DS} . [21] pointed out that this capacitance is important in damping V_{DS} overshoot in unclamped inductive load and ZVS operation, but not significant in determining PWM clamped inductive load switching waveforms. Perhaps for this reason most papers do not talk about the modeling of this capacitance and its effect on the MOSFET switching waveforms. However, in the later chapter of this report, C_{DS} effects as well as those of the other two capacitances will all be studied and discussed in detail.

(D) R_{GI} : Internal gate resistance

The internal gate resistance becomes important in high-speed switching conditions. As the external gate resistance is reduced to speed up the switching transients, this resistance will finally become the major damping factor within the gate drive loop. Considering the distributed nature of the gate contact mesh, the modeling of a lumped resistance R_{GI} is only an approximation of the overall contact resistances.

(E) L_G, L_D, L_S : Package stray inductances

These inductances are necessary only if the MOSFET is packaged. They can be removed or set to zero when the device comes in die form.

The purpose of this work is to build a SiC MOSFET model so that its switching behavior and performance can be studied through simulation. To achieve this goal all of the above components should be included to make a complete MOSFET model. This effectively eliminates the papers which only talk about part of (A) to (E), such as [19], [20]. Moreover, the model should be simple in terms of parameter extraction and should not contain any inaccessible parameters to the device users. This also makes some other approaches not suitable for this work, such as [17] and [18]. Based on these reasons, this work explores the possibility of building a SiC MOSFET model based on the conventional static and switching characterization data previously obtained, by the use of a mature Si MOSFET modeling tool. To this end, the Synopsys Saber *Power MOSFET Tool* is used to build the model for this 1.2 kV SiC MOSFET [25].

V.2. Modeling Processes and Issues

The Saber *Power MOSFET Tool* generates the level-1 model which is well suited for examining the switching transients and losses of the power MOSFET. The graphic user interface of the program is displayed in Fig. 2-31, which also shows the model structure. It can be seen that this model basically follows the general model structure shown in Fig. 2-30.

This modeling tool requires the device information of output and transfer characteristics, body diode characteristic, parasitic capacitances, internal gate resistance, as well as package stray inductances, all of which can be obtained from the characterization process presented in Section II and III. These characteristic curves and parameters can be imported into the program, and the model parameters can be adjusted visually to curve-fit the imported data. A built-in optimization function of the program can also be used to achieve an optimal curve-fit of the imported data. Detailed modeling procedures can be found in Chapter 4 and Chapter 8 of [26].

Fig. 2-31 Saber *Power MOSFET Tool* graphic user interface

The temperature-dependent characteristics of the device will be modeled in this program as different sets of model parameters for several discrete temperatures, and Saber will automatically calculate the linear interpolations of these parameters to determine the model behavior at any given temperature. In this sense, modeling at 25 °C has the same process as modeling at 200 °C. Therefore in this section the SiC MOSFET is only modeled at the room temperature.

Fig. 2-32 shows the curve fitting results of the SiC MOSFET output and junction capacitance characteristics, which are apparently good predictions from the figure. However, in order to simulate the switching behavior of the device more accurately, measures should be taken beyond simply fitting the characteristic curves.

Fig. 2-32 Curve fitting results of (a) output characteristics, and (b) junction capacitances

One problem lies in the curve-fitting of the output characteristics. Different from Si MOSFET, the I-V characteristics of SiC MOSFET transit gradually from the linear region to the saturation region [18]. Therefore, the device has not fully entered the saturation region even if the curve tracer has reached its maximum output voltage of 30 V, which can be inferred from Fig. 2-5 (a). Conducting the curve-fitting only in the linear and transition regions may lead to incorrect saturation region characteristics for the model. In Fig. 2-32 (a) the mathematically optimal curve-fitting result gives the channel-length modulation parameter LAMBDA (i.e. the slope of the I-V curves in the saturation region) of about 0.15, which is far too big for a reasonable LAMBDA value.

The parameter of LAMBDA is critical as it determines the shape of the saturation region. Simulation shows that the model with better fitted saturation region can predict the switching waveforms more accurately. This result is also intuitive as most part of the device switching trajectory lies in the saturation region under the clamped inductive load. The major slew rates of both the voltage and current waveforms are consequently affected by the shape of this region. Therefore, it is necessary to get a picture about how the saturation region looks like, when it is not available from the curve tracer measurement.

The information needed for reconstructing the saturation region is the transfer characteristic under high V_{DS} bias, which can be extracted by plotting I_D vs. V_{GS} from the switching waveforms. This follows from the MOSFET switching theory that when I_D rises and falls in a clamped inductive load, V_{DS} keeps almost constant, and the switching trajectory is well within the saturation region where the I_D vs. V_{GS} graph represents the transfer characteristic at the corresponding V_{DS} bias [7]. To get this graph, the MOSFET should be switched very slowly at the desired V_{DS} by using a big gate resistance to minimize the circuit parasitic ringing and the currents flowing through the MOSFET junction capacitors. In this work, a 200 Ω gate resistance is used and the MOSFET is still switched using the aforementioned double-pulse tester.

The I_D - V_{GS} curves obtained in this way, however, are different for turn-on and turn-off processes, seen as the blue and yellow curves in Fig. 2-33 (a). This is due to the voltage measurement aberrance in the V_{GS} waveform caused by the common source inductance L_{SS} , as illustrated in Fig. 2-33 (b). To compensate off the L_{SS} effect, the real I_D - V_{GS} relationship can be derived as follows.

Fig. 2-33 Verification of transfer characteristic prediction in simulation. (a) I_D - V_{GS} curves, (b) V_{GS} measurement includes L_{SS} voltage drop

During turn-on:

$$v_{GS_on} = v_{GI} + L_{SS} \frac{\Delta I_D}{\Delta t_r} \quad (2-2)$$

During turn-off:

$$v_{GS_off} = v_{GI} - L_{SS} \frac{\Delta I_D}{\Delta t_f} \quad (2-3)$$

where v_{GS_on} and v_{GS_off} are the measured gate voltages, v_{GI} is the real MOSFET gate voltage, Δt_r and Δt_f are the drain current rise and fall times, and ΔI_D is the switching current. It is assumed here that the drain current changes linearly during the switching transients, and that the gate current slew rate is much smaller than that of the drain current, so that the voltage drop across L_{SS} is solely determined by I_D .

The real gate voltage is hence the weighted average of

$$v_{GI} = \frac{v_{GS_on} \Delta t_r + v_{GS_off} \Delta t_f}{\Delta t_r + \Delta t_f} \quad (2-4)$$

Plotting I_D vs. v_{GI} will then give the “real” transfer characteristic.

This method has been verified through Saber simulation. As shown in Fig. 2-33 (a), the blue and yellow curves are got from the slow switching waveforms of the preliminary version of the SiC MOSFET model built in this work. The green curve is an averaged curve based on the blue and yellow curves. The red dotted curve in the figure is the “static” transfer characteristic of the MOSFET model at the same V_{DS} voltage, which is obtained from a DC sweep of the model. The close match of the green and red curves proves the effectiveness of this method.

Using the proposed method, the “predicted” transfer characteristics of the SiC MOSFET are obtained experimentally and plotted in Fig. 2-34. As seen, the characteristic curves shift to the left as the V_{DS} bias increases, indicating a bigger transconductance under higher drain-source voltage, which is reasonable for power MOSFET in general. In this work, the additional transfer characteristic at 300 V is imported into the *Power MOSFET Tool* to adjust LAMBDA, which turns out to be 0.009 after adjustment (See Fig. 2-35). Note that by doing this certain accuracy is sacrificed in the linear and transition region curve fittings. However, as it will be shown later, better fitting in the saturation region of the model will still produce more accurate results in matching the experimental switching waveforms.

Fig. 2-34 Predicted transfer characteristics from slow switching test

Fig. 2-35 Model revision using predicted transfer characteristics. (left) Original model transfer characteristic at $V_{DS} = 300$ V, (right) revised transfer characteristic at $V_{DS} = 300$ V

Another important parameter in MOSFET modeling is the Miller capacitance C_{RSS} . It is found from simulation that the MOSFET switching waveforms are extremely sensitive to the

characteristic of C_{RSS} , especially in the inductive load, hard switching condition, whereas small changes in C_{ISS} or C_{OSS} do not affect the switching behavior too much. This has also been stated elsewhere but the reason has not been explained explicitly [21]. In principle, C_{RSS} is a capacitor connecting the input (gate) and the output (drain) of the MOSFET if one regards the device as a two-port network. According to the Miller Effect theory, this capacitor can be decoupled by putting two equivalent capacitors at the input and output ports separately, as shown in Fig. 2-36. From the input side, the decoupling capacitance is given by

$$C_{GD_input} = C_{RSS}(1 - A_v) \quad (2-5)$$

where A_v is the AC amplification coefficient, given by

$$A_v = \frac{dV_{DS}}{dV_{GS}} = \frac{dV_{DS}}{dt} \bigg/ \frac{dV_{GS}}{dt} \quad (2-6)$$

Fig. 2-36 Decoupling of the Miller capacitance (Only input capacitances are displayed)

Because V_{GS} and V_{DS} always change in the opposite direction, therefore $A_v < 0$. During the switching transients, when V_{DS} does not change, $A_v = 0$ and the input capacitance is simply C_{ISS} . However, during V_{DS} rising or falling period, V_{GS} is effectively in its “plateau” stage while V_{DS} swings drastically between full bus voltage and nearly zero. This results in an extremely large A_v which significantly magnifies C_{RSS} and makes C_{GD_input} dominate the input capacitance. Any small discrepancy in C_{RSS} will then be exaggerated by A_v , leading to switching waveform mismatch, especially in V_{DS} . As a result, the seemingly perfect C_{RSS} curve fitting does not guarantee an accurate prediction of the switching waveforms, as even several pF changes in C_{RSS} can make a big difference in C_{GD_input} . In this case, experimental waveforms must be obtained so that the C-V curve of C_{RSS} can be finely adjusted in the model to match the real switching waveforms.

V.3. Model Verifications

Fig. 2-37 shows the comparisons of experimental and simulation waveforms under 600 V, 8 A inductive load, hard-switching condition with $R_G = 10 \Omega$. This is also the case used to finely adjust C_{RSS} . Both simulation results with and without adopting the transfer characteristic prediction are superimposed to show the difference. As seen from the figure, the model considering the saturation region characteristics simulates the voltage and current slew rates much better than the one only fitting the linear and transition regions.

The model is then used to predict another switching condition where the gate resistance is reduced to 5Ω , as shown in Fig. 2-38. The device model simulates correctly the major

characteristics of the switching waveforms, such as V_{DS} and I_D slew rates, I_D and V_{GS} spikes during turn-on, as well as V_{GS} notch during turn-off. However, the simulation is not able to capture the high-frequency ringing in the waveforms because the parasitic components in the tester circuit are not considered in the simulation. These parasitics need to be involved in order to predict more precisely the high-speed switching behavior of SiC MOSFET under the influence of these parasitics. This will be taken care of in the later chapter.

Fig. 2-37 Comparisons of experimental (colored) and simulation (black and grey) waveforms under $R_G = 10 \Omega$. (left) Turn-on, (right) turn-off. Time: 40 ns/div. Black – with transfer characteristic prediction; grey dashed – without transfer characteristic prediction

Fig. 2-38 Comparisons of experimental (colored) and simulation (black) waveforms under $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (left) Turn-on, (right) turn-off. Time: 40 ns/div

The only discrepancies observed in the above figures are the V_{GS} and V_{DS} waveform mismatches during the turn-on process. As seen, the simulated V_{GS} seems to have a shorter “plateau” period, thus leading to a faster V_{DS} falling rate. Looking back at the MOSFET modeling process, one can find that only one transfer characteristic curve is allowed to be imported and fitted in the MOSFET modeling tool, limited by the program function, which means the saturation region can only be partially fitted. Besides, the Si MOSFET model still has difficulties in fitting perfectly both the linear and saturation regions, and both the low-current and high-current regions of the SiC MOSFET I-V characteristics at the same time.

Another possible cause for the discrepancies is that the gate structure of the MOSFET is simplified as a single internal gate resistance in the model, whereas a more accurate circuit for the fast switching condition would be an R-C ladder, as multiple resonant peaks can be observed beyond 50 MHz in Fig. 2-11. This is another limitation of this SiC MOSFET model.

VI. Conclusions

This chapter has presented the complete static and switching characterizations of a 1.2 kV, 20 A prototype SiC MOSFET. The static characterization results show the SiC device's superiority in blocking higher voltage while still keeping a very low $R_{DS(ON)}$ even under much higher junction temperature compared to Si technology. The characterization process is also generic so that it can be applied to studying any new MOSFET. Several explanations have been introduced for the possible cause of the device degradation observed after the switching tests.

The characterization data are then used to build a SiC MOSFET model using the Si power MOSFET modeling tool. Discussions have been made on the most critical factors in the modeling process – the saturation region characteristics and the Miller capacitance – in order to accurately predict the MOSFET switching behavior. A technique has also been proposed to obtain saturation region characteristics from switching waveforms. The developed model successfully simulates the real switching behavior of the device, although some discrepancies are also observed and explained. The discussions presented in this chapter are applicable to the general MOSFET modeling procedures, and are helpful for developing and building future models for SiC MOSFETs.

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Part II

Evaluation and Analysis of Influence of Circuit Parasitics on Power Electronic Converters

Chapter 3 MODELING AND SIMULATION OF SiC MOSFET FAST SWITCHING BEHAVIOR UNDER CIRCUIT PARASITICS

I. Introduction

The demands of the power electronics building block (PEBB) for high density and high efficiency require that the power semiconductor devices have minimized conduction loss and switching loss, which means they should have very small on-state voltage and resistance, and can be switched as fast as possible. However, the problem accompanying the faster switching speed is the more severe high-frequency ringing during the switching transients, due to the existence of the circuit parasitic impedances. The parasitic ringing deteriorates the electromagnetic interference (EMI) and device stress, which ultimately offsets the benefits of reduced switching loss from faster switching speed.

Designers usually need to be very careful in designing the layouts for these high-speed switching circuits, trying to minimize the circuit parasitics and the side effects brought by these parasitics, even though it is impossible to make them totally zero. The problem of the current practice is that the effects of the circuit parasitics can be observed only after the circuit (say a printed circuit board (PCB) or a power electronics module) is manufactured and tested, because it is very hard to estimate their values and impacts on the device switching waveforms beforehand. If the circuit performance does not meet the requirement, the entire design process has to be repeated to get a refined circuit, which is usually quite costly and time-consuming.

For this reason, it is preferable to simulate the device switching behavior under the influence of circuit parasitics before realizing the circuit physically. This is especially helpful in the design of high-speed switching circuits, where designers can adjust their circuit layouts or compare different layout options based on the simulation results. Another advantage with the simulation method is that, as long as the simulation is accurate enough in predicting the real waveforms, measurement components and test points can be saved in the hardware to make the design even more compact. Moreover, quantities that are hard to measure physically in the circuit can also be observed in simulation without any difficulty, such as the current distributions between multiple dice in a power module.

To this end, this chapter explores a modeling methodology to predict the silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFET fast switching behavior under the influence of circuit parasitics. The MOSFET double-pulse tester presented in previous chapters has been used again as the case study in this work. The major components of the tester, including the passive components (inductor and capacitors), SiC Schottky diode, gate drive integrated circuit (IC), as well as the PCB parasitics, have all been modeled. These models are then combined with the SiC MOSFET model in a circuit simulator to predict the device switching waveforms. Finally, simulation results are compared with the experiments to verify the effectiveness of this modeling methodology.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The major objective of this chapter is to develop a modeling methodology to accurately predict the device (esp. SiC MOSFET to be used in the future PEBB) switching waveforms under the influence of circuit parasitics.

I.2. Technical Approach

The MOSFET double-pulse tester has been used for the development of the methodology. The major circuit components in the tester have all been modeled, including the SiC devices, gate drive IC, passive components (inductors and capacitors), as well as the device package and the PCB parasitics. All these models are then combined in a circuit simulator to simulate the device switching waveforms. The simulation results are also compared with the experiments presented in Chapter 2 for verification purposes.

II. Modeling of Surrounding Circuit Components

The surrounding circuit components in the double-pulse tester include the freewheeling diode, load inductor, gate drive IC, PCB package, as well as other passive components like the DC bus capacitors and gate drive power supply capacitors. These components also play very important roles in determining the fast switching behavior of the main switch, so it is necessary to consider all of them in the simulation in order to predict the real switching waveforms with detailed spikes and ringing. The following sections discuss the modeling of these components.

II.1. The Load Inductor

The load inductor used in the double-pulse tester is composed of four small inductors connected in series, achieving a total inductance of 672 μH . The considerations of the inductor design are (1) to have a very low equivalent parallel capacitance (EPC) so that the MOSFET turn-on current spike can be minimized, and (2) to have a high enough saturation current level so that the device can be tested up to the desired current without saturating the inductor.

Fig. 3-1 shows the measured impedance of the final inductor versus frequency, from which an EPC of only 1 pF can be observed.

The inductor is modeled by including an ESR, an EPC, as well as an EPR together with the main inductance, as shown in Fig. 3-2. By curve fitting the measured impedance, the parameters of the inductor model are extracted to be $L = 672 \mu\text{H}$, $\text{ESR} = 0.11 \Omega$, $\text{EPC} = 1 \text{ pF}$, and $\text{EPR} = 69 \text{ k}\Omega$. The Bode plot of the model is also shown in Fig. 3-1 as the red dashed curves, where a good agreement is achieved up to 2 MHz for this model. Above that frequency, the parasitic components from interconnections of the inductor become effective, and modeling of that part is not necessary in this work.

Fig. 3-1 Load inductor measurement vs. model

Fig. 3-2 Inductor equivalent circuit

II.2. The Freewheeling Diode

The freewheeling diode is a 1.2 kV, 20 A SiC Schottky barrier diode (SBD) prototype from Infineon. The forward I-V curve of the diode is measured using the Tektronix 371B curve tracer, and the junction capacitance-voltage characteristic is obtained from the Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer using a similar method as introduced in Chapter 2. The diode model is then built using Saber *Power Diode Tool* [1]. Similar to Saber *Power MOSFET Tool*, the static and capacitance characteristics of the diode model are tuned visually to match the imported measurement data [2]. Fig. 3-3 shows the graphic user interface of the diode modeling tool and the model structure. The ideal diode and series resistance R_S represent the forward I-V characteristic of the device, C_J represents the junction capacitance, and Q_{rr} represents the reverse recovery characteristic. The curve fitting results are shown in Fig. 3-4, from which a good agreement can be seen between the measurement and the model. It needs to be noted that the diode used is of Schottky type, whereas the program generates models for PiN diodes. Therefore to adapt the model for the SBD, the reverse recovery effect of the diode model is set to minimum, as seen in Fig. 3-4 (c).

The stray inductance from the device's TO-220 package has also been measured and modeled as a 7 nH inductance in series with the diode model.

Fig. 3-3 Saber *Power Diode Tool* graphic user interface

Fig. 3-4 Diode model curve fitting results.

(a) Forward I-V curve, (b) junction capacitance-voltage curve, (c) reverse recovery characteristic

II.3. The Gate Drive IC

The gate drive IC used in the tester is IXYS IXDD414. The SPICE model of this chip can be downloaded from the manufacturer’s website. Fig. 3-5 shows the equivalent circuit of the SPICE model. This model, however, is quite complicated and cannot be translated into Saber template directly, so a simplified Saber model is built based on the SPICE model, as shown in Fig. 3-6. Fortunately, the output totem-pole structure of the original model uses only conventional SPICE MOSFET models with all the parameters given, and therefore can be easily rebuilt in the Saber model. The digital logic portion of the SPICE model is just simplified as a NAND gate with certain propagation delay, as seen in Fig. 3-6.

Fig. 3-5 Equivalent circuit of original IXDD414 SPICE model

Fig. 3-6 Simplified Saber model of the gate drive IC

The Saber model with the original parameters, however, does not match the IC datasheet, as this model switches 2 nF capacitive load within 1 ns, while in the datasheet the rise time and fall time are around 10 ns. To adjust the rise and fall times of the model, two small capacitances (red in Fig. 3-6) are added to the top PMOS and bottom NMOS respectively, both of which are smaller than 1 pF. The output resistance of the model is also adjusted to be 1 Ω according to the datasheet to get the correct the rise and fall times.

II.4. The Capacitors

The capacitors used in the double-pulse tester, namely the DC bus bulk and decoupling capacitors, as well as the gate drive power supply capacitors, are also measured and modeled. The parasitic ESRs and ESLs are taken into consideration in the capacitor modeling, as shown in Fig. 3-7. These parameters are important as they, especially ESLs, affect the high-frequency ringing during the fast switching transients.

The ESRs and ESLs can be extracted using the curve fitting method, and two examples of the capacitor models are displayed in Fig. 3-8. A full list of the capacitor models is also given in Table 3-1.

Fig. 3-7 Capacitor model equivalent circuit

Fig. 3-8 Capacitor model examples.

(a) 820 μF DC bus bulk cap, (b) 100 nF gate drive power supply cap

Table 3-1 Capacitor model parameters

Capacitor	Capacitance (F)	ESL (nH)	ESR (Ω)
DC bus bulk and decoupling capacitances			
820 μF	750 μ	30	0.04

300 nF	300n	15	0.019
120 nF	120n	9	0.027
100 nF	100n	4.5	0.08
Gate drive power supply capacitances			
470 μF	450μ	4	0.15
10 μF	10μ	4	1
100 nF	110n	2	0.05

II.5. The Coaxial Shunt Resistor

In the double-pulse tester the coaxial shunt resistor is selected over other current sensors to measure the MOSFET drain current because of its significantly higher bandwidth [3]. This work uses a 0.1 Ω shunt resistor (SSDN-10) manufactured by T&M Research, whose appearance and equivalent circuit are illustrated in Fig. 3-9. This shunt resistor claims an equivalent bandwidth over 1 GHz [3]-[5]. However, when measuring the impedance of the resistor from A port (See Fig. 3-9), a 2.2 nH series inductance can be observed from the Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer. Based on the following equation

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{R}{L} \quad (3-1)$$

this corresponds to a corner frequency of only 7.2 MHz, which is obviously too low for the shunt resistor. On the other hand, when measuring from B port, a 5 nH series inductance can still be observed. Including 2 nH in series with the shunt resistance would greatly increase the aberration in the measurement of fast changing current, which seems to contradict the manufacturer's specification on the bandwidth. This seeming contradiction can be explained by looking at the internal structure of the shunt resistor.

Fig. 3-9 Coaxial shunt resistor (left) and equivalent circuit (right)

Shown in Fig. 3-10 (left) is the internal structure of the coaxial shunt resistor. The principle of this device is that the current flowing through the inner and outer resistance tubes creates a zero magnetic field region within the shunt resistor. Therefore, wires can be extended in this region for measurement (B port) without any induced voltage due to the fast changing current, which guarantees the accuracy in the measurement [5]. However, the main current, seen as the

red arrows in the figure, still forms a big loop within the resistor which causes the 2.2 nH measured from the impedance analyzer. But notice that the real resistance for measurement is made up of the inner and outer resistance tubes which are only a small part of the current loop. This part thus produces a parasitic inductance much smaller than 2.2 nH. Furthermore, although the twisted pair to B-port is not inducing any voltage from the main current loop, it still causes around 5 nH parasitic inductance itself. It is just that this inductance is in series with the measurement probe with much higher impedance, and thus will not cause big aberration in the measurement.

Based on the above analyses, the equivalent circuit of the coaxial shunt resistor is shown on the right hand side of Fig. 3-10. In a word, the 2.2 nH is indeed in series with the resistance, however its voltage drop will not be included by the measurement port.

Fig. 3-10 Coaxial shunt resistor internal structure (left) and model (right)

II.6. The PCB Parasitics

Many preceding works have conducted the evaluations and analyses of circuit parasitics in converters and their impacts on the device switching characteristics. Basically these works can be divided into two major categories in terms of study method. One is the measurement-based method, which evaluates the parasitic impedances of the existent PCB or power module through physical measurement, such as [6]-[8]. These works used either time domain reflectometry (TDR) method or the impedance analyzer to evaluate the circuit parasitics. This method, however, is complicated and time consuming, and only applies to some simple circuits where the parasitic inductances and capacitances can be clearly defined and identified. For more complex power modules or printed circuit boards, measuring the parasitics becomes unpractical because for so many erratically separated interconnects it is even hard to identify the parasitic impedances, not to mention measuring them and applying the measurement results in future simulation to investigate their effects. Furthermore, some quantities are very difficult to measure even in simple circuits, such as tiny small inductances and mutual inductances. All of these factors confine the use of this measurement-based method to a very narrow scope.

Another method adopted by many works is the simulation-based method, which extracts the package parasitics using finite element analysis (FEA) or partial element equivalent circuit (PEEC) methods. Electromagnetic (EM) analysis software such as INCA and Ansoft Q3D have been used in these work for the parasitics extraction [9]-[12]. Using the FEA method, any

arbitrary interconnect geometry can be analyzed numerically as long as they can be modeled in the software. The separated interconnects without physically measurable inductance can also be evaluated based on the well-established concept of partial inductance, and the mutual terms can be taken care of automatically as well [13]-[15]. Furthermore, some EM analysis software also provides interfaces for commonly-used circuit simulators such that the evaluation results can be directly used in circuit simulations to see the impacts of the parasitics.

For the reasons stated above, this work adopts the simulation-based method to evaluate the PCB parasitics of the double-pulse tester. The software used in this work is Ansoft Quick 3D Extractor, which is used not only because of its availability in the lab, but also because of its modeling capability of arbitrary 3-dimensional geometries and accurate calculations of RLC parasitic parameters [16][17]. The modeling process of the PCB is illustrated in Fig. 3-11. The main steps are:

(A) Designing the PCB layout

The original PCB layout is designed in Altium Designer – commonly-used PCB design software.

(B) Exporting the geometry model

Altium Designer supports exporting the PCB layout in different 3D geometry model formats, such as AutoCAD drawing format and STEP (Standard for the Exchange of Product model data) format. In this work, AutoCAD is selected just for simplicity.

(C) Building Q3D model

The geometry model obtained in (B) is then imported into Q3D. In this work four layers of copper traces are obtained after import, as seen in Fig. 3-11 (C). Material properties are then assigned to different structures (copper for traces and FR4 epoxy for insulators) in Q3D because the original geometry model does not carry any material information. Also for simplicity some geometric details are removed, such as vias, through-holes and round corners. Interconnects for the digital circuits are also removed. Only the gate drive and power stage interconnects are modeled finally.

(D) Interpreting structures into impedances

After assigning electrical excitations to different copper traces, Q3D analyzes the structural parasitics and calculates the corresponding self and mutual impedances. The detailed calculation method and process can be found in [15].

(E) Calculation of impedance matrices

Q3D presents the results in forms of resistance, inductance, and capacitance matrices after the analysis.

(F) Converting to Saber equivalent circuit

The impedance matrices are then exported in netlist form and converted to Saber template for the subsequent circuit simulation.

Fig. 3-11 PCB modeling procedure

III. Device-Package Combined Simulation

III.1. Simulation vs. Experiment

All of the above models are then combined together in Saber to simulate the switching waveforms of the SiC MOSFET under circuit parasitics. Fig. 3-12 shows the device-package combined simulation circuit in Saber. The circuit includes the SiC MOSFET and SiC Schottky diode models with their respective package parasitics, gate drive IC model, PCB model, as well as passive component models with the corresponding ESR/EPC or ESR/ESL. The operation condition of the simulation circuit, namely the DC bus voltage and the pulse widths of the double-pulse signal, are exactly the same as what are used in the experiments.

Fig. 3-12 Saber circuit of device-package combined simulation

Fig. 3-13 shows the waveform comparison between experiment and simulation under 600 V, 8 A switching condition with 5 Ω gate resistance. As seen from the figure, the simulation waveforms resemble the experimental ones very well, with the correct prediction of the parasitic ringing in the drain current I_D waveform, and the overshoot in the drain-source voltage V_{DS} waveform. What does not match the experiment most is the gate drive output voltage V_{DRIVE} due to the model problem. However, the currently used gate drive model is still kept in the simulation since it is essentially manufacturer's model. On the other hand, the I_D spike in the simulation is slightly higher than the experiment and the settling time is longer, as seen in Fig. 3-13 (a). This is probably due to the modeling of the parasitic resistance and the freewheeling diode, which will be discussed in detail later.

Fig. 3-13 Comparison of experimental (left) and simulation (right) waveforms: 600 V, 8 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on transients, (b) turn-off transients

The above analyses also apply to Fig. 3-14, where the SiC MOSFET is switched under 600 V, 4 A with 2 Ω gate resistance. As one can see, in this case the simulation again captures correctly the more severe parasitic ringing with increased switching speed, especially in I_D waveform.

Fig. 3-14 Comparison of experimental (left) and simulation (right) waveforms: 600 V, 4 A, $R_G = 2 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on transients, (b) turn-off transients

To verify the simulation, two other conditions with different load current and bus voltage have also been simulated and compared to the experiments. Fig. 3-15 shows the switching waveforms under 600 V, 6 A with $R_G = 5 \Omega$, while Fig. 3-16 displays the condition of 200 V, 8 A with $R_G = 5 \Omega$. As seen, in both cases the simulation predicts the MOSFET switching behavior very well, validating the effectiveness of this modeling methodology.

As a comparison, now look back at Fig. 2-37 and 2-38, where the simulation does not consider any parasitics coming from the circuit. It is very clear in these figures that all the details about the parasitic ringing are lost in the fast switching transients. This again emphasizes the importance of the circuit parasitics in the modeling process so as to study their impacts on the SiC MOSFET switching behavior from simulation.

Fig. 3-15 Comparison of experimental (left) and simulation (right) waveforms: 600 V, 6 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on transients, (b) turn-off transients

Fig. 3-16 Comparison of experimental (left) and simulation (right) waveforms: 200 V, 8 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on transients, (b) turn-off transients

III.2. Quantification of Simulation Results

To evaluate the accuracy of the simulation, the simulated waveforms have also been quantified and compared to the experiments in terms of the switching energy, voltage and current overshoots, as well as parasitic ringing frequency. Shown in Fig. 3-17 is the switching energy comparison where the energies during turn-on and turn-off are plotted against different load current for $V_{DS} = 600$ V and $R_G = 5 \Omega$ condition. As seen, the simulated turn-off energy predicts the real E_{off} quite well, whereas the turn-on energy is smaller in the simulation compared to the experiment. This discrepancy is due to the faster turn-on V_{DS} slew rate in the simulation because of the MOSFET model problem, which has already been discussed in Chapter 2. In another word, the accuracy of the switching energy is to a great extent related to the accuracy of the device models instead of the circuit parasitics. As long as a better SiC MOSFET is available, the prediction of the switching energy can be improved.

Fig. 3-17 Switching energy comparison between experiment and simulation.
Test condition: 600 V, $R_G = 5 \Omega$

Fig. 3-18 compares the drain current I_D and drain-source voltage V_{DS} overshoots between simulation and experiment. The current overshoot is predicted very well by the simulation, except that a positive systematic error can be inferred from the figure due to the accuracy of the freewheeling diode model. As discussed in the previous section, the SBD used in the tester is modeled by a PiN diode model, whose intrinsic reverse recovery characteristic, though has already been set to a very small value, cannot be totally set to zero. This results in a relatively higher reverse recovery current under fast switching transients (i.e. high di/dt), and accounts for the consequent systematic error observed in the figure. Moreover, the I_D overshoot is mainly contributed by the charging current of the SBD junction capacitance, and is almost the same for different load current because V_{DS} keeps unchanged, and so does its dv/dt . The descending trend of the overshoot percentage is simply because the load current is increasing.

The prediction of V_{DS} overshoot is still good, though it is not as precise as that of I_D . The simulation predicts less V_{DS} peak voltage by 5 to 8 percent compared to the experiment. It can thus be inferred that the models previously obtained underestimate the parasitic inductance from either the device packages or the PCB within the main switching loop.

Fig. 3-18 Turn-on current overshoot (left) and turn-off voltage overshoot (right) comparisons.
Test condition: 600 V, $R_G = 5 \Omega$

Fig. 3-19 Ringing frequency comparisons between experiment and simulation.
Test condition: 600 V, $R_G = 5 \Omega$

Fig. 3-19, on the other hand, compares the experimental and simulated ringing frequency of I_D during both turn-on and turn-off processes, where a good agreement can be seen between the two. Note that here the “ringing frequency” is measured from the first ringing period of I_D waveforms, since the device junction capacitances change during the switching transients and hence the ringing frequency. Also notice that the ringing is faster during turn-on than turn-off because the switching loop parasitic inductance resonates with different capacitances during the two transients. This will be discussed in detail in Chapter 4.

IV. Conclusions and Discussions

This chapter presents the modeling of the surrounding components in the double-pulse tester and the simulation combining both device and package models. The modeling methodology has been proven effective in predicting the fast switching behavior of the SiC MOSFET under the influence of circuit parasitics. This methodology would be a very useful tool for the engineers to design and verify high-speed switching circuit layout before manufacturing and testing the hardware, saving great amount of time and effort in the development of this kind of circuits.

Nevertheless, there are still quite a few drawbacks with this modeling and simulation method. First of all, in order to capture the high-frequency switching characteristics, the circuit needs to be modeled in as much detail as possible. The parasitic impedances coming from both

the components and the PCB need to be considered during the modeling process. It can be imagined that when the circuit complexity increases, the modeling itself would be quite a burden, and so would be the subsequent simulation. This practically constrains the applicability of this modeling method to relatively simple circuits.

Secondly, some simplifications in the modeling process prevent the simulation from precisely predicting the experimental waveforms. For example, the parasitic resistances extracted from Q3D are frequency-independent, and in this case are simply modeled as DC resistances. For the high-frequency ringing current, the effective resistances actually become bigger due to the skin effect, and thus would damp the ringing faster. Besides resistances, the parasitic inductances are also affected by the frequency. However, it is commonly known that the frequency-dependent impedance is hard to be modeled and implemented in time-domain simulation. Even if this is feasible, taking this effect into account would further increase the complexity of the modeling and simulation.

Lastly, the PCB modeling treats the parasitics as a network which contains hundreds and thousands of small self and mutual impedances representing each trace on the board. Therefore, it is hard to tell from so many impedances the most important ones that would shape the switching behavior of the MOSFET. It is also difficult to conclude a rule of thumb about how to optimize the circuit layout by just looking at this huge impedance network. For this reason, it is necessary to identify several impedances to be “the most critical” ones and study their effects individually. The identification and study of these impedances will be the topic of the next chapter.

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Chapter 4 PARAMETRIC STUDY OF THE PARASITIC IMPEDANCE INFLUENCE ON MOSFET SWITCHING BEHAVIOR

I. Introduction

It has been shown in the previous chapters that in high-speed switching circuits, the parasitic inductances become a significant factor that can cause severe ringing in the switching waveforms. Due to the existence of these parasitics, faster switching speed always comes with the penalties of worsened device stresses and electromagnetic interference (EMI), which can easily overwhelm the benefits of the lower switching loss. Therefore, great care needs to be taken when designing the layout for this kind of high-speed circuits. Chapter 3 has exhibited the detailed modeling of the double-pulse tester which successfully reproduces the real switching waveforms. However the modeling tool is still unable to provide the designers with a general guideline about what should be optimized in the circuit to reduce the parasitic ringing and maximize the benefits of higher switching speed. To achieve this goal, it is very important to understand the influence of different parasitic impedances on the MOSFET switching behavior.

There have been a lot of preceding efforts on the study of circuit parasitic inductances. Some of them have focused on the extraction and modeling of these parasitic parameters so as to capture their effect from circuit simulations [1]-[6]. In these, the parasitic inductances have been directly measured on existent circuits or power modules, or calculated using theoretical or finite element analysis. However, the above pieces of work usually treated the parasitic components as an inductive network and did not study their effects individually.

Some other contributions have investigated the effects of individual stray inductances analytically, where differential equations were established to solve the switching waveforms under different parasitic inductances [7]-[9]. Due to the nonlinear nature of the switching device, however, the solutions were usually very complicated and thus the stray inductance effects could not be intuitively seen from the expressions. Furthermore, the analytical solutions were only approximate because of the many assumptions made to make the equations solvable. This would also limit the conclusions obtained from the analytical study in question.

This chapter, from another angle, systematically studies the effects of the two aspects of the switching ringing – the parasitic inductances coming from the device packages and circuit interconnections, and the parasitic capacitances originating from the device junctions. Instead of analytical analysis, the parametric study has been conducted mainly through experiments. Several most critical parasitic parameters have been identified and investigated on their individual effect through the MOSFET switching test. Corresponding circuit simulations have been used to verify the conclusions obtained from the experiments. The influence of the parasitics on the MOSFET switching characteristics has also been studied and summarized.

II. Parametric Study of the Parasitic Inductances

The MOSFET switching test is still conducted with the use of the double-pulse tester introduced in the previous chapters. To save the costly SiC MOSFET, a 600 V, 20 A Si CoolMOS (APT20N60BCF from MicroSemi) is used instead for the study, and the gate drive voltage from IXDD414 is accordingly adjusted to 0 ~ 10 V. The other circuit components remain the same.

From the derivation of Faraday's Law, it is clear that inductance is only defined for a closed contour. This means that it is the closed current loop formed by a wire that has inductance, not the wire itself [10]. Based on this concept, three primary stray inductances can be identified based on the structure of the double-pulse tester, namely (1) the gate loop inductance L_{GS} formed by the gate current path; (2) the main switching loop inductance L_{DS} formed by the drain current path, and (3) the common source inductance L_{SS} shared by both loops. The switching loop inductance is essentially a lumped one which includes the partial inductances from the MOSFET and diode packages, and the PCB interconnections. The common source inductance can be treated as a mutual inductance between the gate loop and the switching loop.

To study the influence of these parasitic parameters, the current paths in the tester have been broken at the points shown in Fig. 4-1 (a), so that small inductances can be inserted into the loop to mimic the parasitic ones coming from the structure. The small inductances are made of several air-core coils with 2 turns, 4 turns and 5 turns respectively (Fig. 4-1 (b)), which produce the corresponding inductances of 22 nH, 47 nH and 65 nH. In the experiment, each type of stray inductance is controlled with the rest breakpoints simply shorted, such that its effect can be studied independently.

Fig. 4-1 Double-pulse tester with external parasitic inductances.
(a) Schematic, (b) inductor coil

In the experiment, the MOSFET is switched up to 400 V, 10 A, with different gate resistances to adjust the switching speed. A similar simulation circuit is also built in Synopsys Saber, where 5 nH gate loop inductance and 20 nH switching loop inductance are assumed for the intrinsic parasitics of the PCB. The MOSFET model is provided by the manufacturer and available on their website.

II.1. Gate Loop Stray Inductance L_{GS}

Fig. 4-2 shows the MOSFET 400 V, 10 A switching waveforms with 5 Ω gate resistance, under the influence of the gate loop stray inductance L_{GS} . In the experiment, L_{GS} is increased gradually from 0 nH to 65 nH. This inductance, as stated in many publications, tends to resonate with the MOSFET input capacitance and thus causes oscillation in the gate-source voltage waveform, which is quite apparent in the turn-off transients. However, the oscillation in

V_{GS} only leads to limited ringing in drain-source voltage and drain current waveforms. For the turn-on transients, V_{DS} and I_D almost do not change; while for turn-off the ringing starts to deteriorate in these waveforms as L_{GS} increases. For instance, the turn-off V_{DS} spike increases from about 460 V when $L_{GS} = 0$, to 480 V when $L_{GS} = 65$ nH. Even so, the influence of L_{GS} is still quite limited within the gate loop, and the MOSFET switching waveforms are only slightly affected if compared to the effect of the main switching loop inductance L_{DS} .

Accordingly, the simulation results are shown in Fig. 4-3. Observed again in the figure is the limited ringing in V_{DS} and I_D caused by V_{GS} , which is consistent with the experimental results. From this it can be concluded that the gate loop oscillation can be coupled to the main switching loop, however its effect on the switching waveforms is very limited.

Fig. 4-2 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of gate loop stray inductance L_{GS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-3 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of gate loop stray inductance L_{GS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

II.2. Main Switching Loop Stray Inductance L_{DS}

Fig. 4-4 shows the effect of the main switching loop stray inductance L_{DS} under the same switching condition as that of Fig. 4-2. As seen from the figure, the increase in L_{DS} introduces oscillations in all V_{GS} , V_{DS} and I_D waveforms, and during both turn-on and turn-off transients. Compared with the effect of L_{GS} shown in Fig. 4-2, in this case the ringing amplitude, frequency, as well as settling time all become worse with the increasing L_{DS} . Still examining the turn-off V_{DS} waveform, one may find that the voltage spike increases from about 460 V when $L_{DS} = 0$ nH, to almost 530 V when $L_{DS} = 65$ nH. By comparison, it can be clearly seen that the switching loop inductance affects the MOSFET switching characteristics much more than the gate loop inductance, causing even worse oscillation and stress on the device.

The simulated waveforms shown in Fig. 4-5 again verify the results seen in the experiment. Furthermore, the simulation also shows that, as long as the parasitic inductance is serially connected within the main switching loop, it produces exactly the same waveforms no matter it is connected in direct series with the MOSFET, the diode, or the DC source. This again proves the effectiveness of lumping partial inductances along the loop to represent the total stray inductance.

Fig. 4-4 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of main switching loop inductance L_{DS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-5 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of main switching loop inductance L_{DS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

II.3. Common Source Stray Inductance L_{SS}

Fig. 4-6, on the other hand, exhibits the effect of the common source inductance L_{SS} on the switching waveforms. In this case the MOSFET is tested under the same voltage and current stresses but with 15Ω gate resistance. Basically, L_{SS} serves as a negative feedback from the main switching loop to the gate loop, as the voltage drop across L_{SS} counteracts the change of the gate voltage during I_D rise and fall periods, thus slowing down the drain current [11]-[12]. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 4-6. The consequence of a bigger L_{SS} is not to worsen the voltage stress and current ringing of the device – due to its slowing-down effect, but to significantly increase the switching energy at turn-on and turn-off. The simulation result shown in Fig. 4-7 leads to the same conclusion.

Due to the negative feedback effect of L_{SS} , when L_{DS} and L_{SS} are both in the circuit, the ringing caused by L_{DS} tends to be suppressed by L_{SS} . This can be seen from Fig. 4-8, where the switching loop inductance is fixed at 65 nH, while the common source inductance varies from 0 to 47 nH. As seen, both V_{DS} and I_D spikes are reduced as L_{SS} increases, which is consistent with the analytical solutions in [8]. However the price paid is still much higher switching loss due to the slower drain current slew rate.

Fig. 4-6 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of common source inductance L_{SS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-7 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of common source stray inductance L_{SS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-8 Co-effect of L_{DS} and L_{SS} .
 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

II.4. Magnetic Coupling between the Gate and the Main Switching Loops

Based on the loop concept, the only reasonable origin of the common source inductance L_{SS} is the magnetic coupling of the gate loop and the main switching loops. Through simulations it was observed that the switching waveforms (V_{GS} , V_{DS} and I_D) under decoupled L_{GS} and L_{DS} , with L_{SS} being the common source inductance, are exactly the same as those under coupled ($L_{GS} +$

L_{SS}) gate loop self-inductance and $(L_{DS} + L_{SS})$ switching loop self-inductance, with L_{SS} being the mutual part and no additional independent inductance on the common source path.

The above results were also verified through experiments by inserting $L_{GS} = 47$ nH and $L_{DS} = 65$ nH into the breakpoints shown in Fig. 4-1. These coils were placed on the tester board in such a way that they produced either decoupled (very weakly coupled) or coupled inductances, as illustrated in Fig. 4-9. As seen, positioning the two coils perpendicular to each other produced the decoupled condition, while putting them side-by-side coaxially produced the coupled condition; the latter with a positive or negative coupling. The former generated a positive feedback with a negative common source inductance, and the latter a negative feedback with a positive common source inductance. Fig. 4-10 shows the corresponding experimental waveforms, evincing how the negatively coupled condition produced slower slew rates and less ringing compared to the decoupled case, while the positively coupled condition exhibited just the opposite—faster switching speed but more severe ringing.

Fig. 4-9 Magnetic coupling between gate loop and main switching loop.
(a) Decoupled condition, (b) coupled condition with different polarities, (c) equivalent circuit

Fig. 4-10 Influence of different magnetic coupling conditions between gate loop and main switching loop. 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. Time: 20 ns/div. (left) Turn-on, (right) turn-off

These results can be explained using the coupled inductor model used in Fig. 4-9 (c). Specifically, when the two loops are negatively coupled, the equivalent self-inductances become smaller ($L_{GS} - M$ and $L_{DS} - M$), and a positive inductance M appears on the common source path. Both effects tend to reduce the switching speed and hence the switching ringing. On the other hand, for the case of positive coupling, not only do the self-inductances become larger in both loops ($L_{GS} + M$ and $L_{DS} + M$), but a negative common source inductance $-M$ also forms a

positive feedback that further deteriorates the situation. This is the reason why much more severe ringing is observed in all the waveforms in the positive coupling condition.

II.5. Summary of Parasitic Inductance Effects

Based on the experimental and simulated results, the following conclusions can be reached from the parametric study:

(1) Generally speaking, the parasitic ringing due to fast switching speed is more sensitive to the main switching loop inductance L_{DS} than the gate loop inductance L_{GS} , although both of them increase the severity of ringing. There are three reasons for this:

First of all, the gate drive circuit layout can be localized more easily than the main power loop, which means L_{GS} is usually smaller than L_{DS} ;

Secondly, more damping exists in the gate loop than the switching loop, such as the gate resistance, gate driver output impedance, and MOSFET internal gate resistance, while the only damping in the switching loop comes from the interconnect resistances, which is usually too small to decay the oscillation quickly;

Thirdly, the gate current slew rate is also much smaller than that of the drain current. The peak gate current is around 1 A in this work, ten times smaller than the drain current. The corresponding di/dt in the gate loop is thus much smaller than the switching loop.

(2) The common source inductance L_{SS} works as a negative feedback from the switching loop to the gate loop, making the drain current slower, and consequently increasing the switching loss significantly. However, it hardly affects the drain-source voltage slew rate, nor does it cause any parasitic ringing in the switching waveforms.

(3) When L_{DS} and L_{SS} are both in the circuit, L_{SS} can help suppress the parasitic ringing caused by L_{DS} by slowing down the drain current. However the penalty is the increased switching loss.

III. Parametric Study of the Parasitic Capacitances

III.1. Understanding the Parasitic Ringing

It has been concluded from the last section that the parasitic ringing is more sensitive to the main switching loop inductance L_{DS} than the gate loop inductance L_{GS} . Then the question is: what is resonating with L_{DS} during the switching transients? This can be answered by looking at the different current paths during turn-on and turn-off respectively.

Fig. 4-11 shows the current path during the turn-on process. During this period the current in the freewheeling diode is transferred to the MOSFET. After the MOSFET has taken all the load current, the drain-source voltage starts to fall and the freewheeling diode stops conducting. As V_{DS} decreases, the diode junction capacitance C_J gets charged and the MOSFET output capacitance C_{OSS} gets discharged. The ringing current then “sees” the impedance of C_J , L_{DS} and C_{OSS} in series, and the current ringing during this period should be caused by L_{DS} resonating with C_J and C_{OSS} in series.

Fig. 4-11 Current paths during turn-on process (a) and corresponding waveforms (b)

In this work, the junction capacitance C_J of the freewheeling Schottky barrier diode (SBD) is much smaller than the MOSFET output capacitance C_{OSS} . Therefore C_J in series with C_{OSS} results in a capacitance very close to C_J . In this sense, the turn-on ringing can be treated as solely determined by the diode junction capacitance C_J in this specific work.

On the other hand, the turn-off ringing current sees different impedance along its paths, as shown in Fig. 4-12. The current in the MOSFET is transferred back to the freewheeling diode during this period. As V_{DS} rises, C_J gets discharged and C_{OSS} gets charged. Once the MOSFET blocks the full bus voltage, the freewheeling diode starts to conduct, effectively bypassing its junction capacitance. The ringing current in this case sees only L_{DS} and C_{OSS} in series. Therefore, the turn-off ringing is caused by L_{DS} resonating with C_{OSS} alone.

Fig. 4-12 Current paths during turn-off process (a) and corresponding waveforms (b)

The different resonating capacitances during turn-on and turn-off also account for the different ringing frequencies observed for the SiC MOSFET in Chapter 2: Because C_J is smaller than C_{OSS} , the turn-on ringing always has a higher frequency than turn-off.

Based on the above analyses, it can be foreseen that devices with lower junction capacitances can be switched faster under the same condition of parasitic ringing. Actually if comparing the switching waveforms of SiC JFET in Chapter 1 and SiC MOSFET in Chapter 2, one can find that SiC JFET can be switched faster with even less parasitic ringing. The different response of the two devices to the same amount of parasitic inductance can be traced back to the difference in their junction capacitances – the SiC MOSFET has around 2.5 nF of C_{DS} at zero voltage, while the SiC JFET has only around 1.0 nF. The junction capacitances, especially the output capacitance C_{OSS} , make the difference in the switching transients.

To consolidate the above hypothesis, a parametric study has been conducted on the device parasitic capacitance as well. The same test circuit is used as in the last section. The MOSFET is switched under 400 V, 10 A with a fixed gate resistance of 15 Ω . External capacitances are added across different device terminals to mimic the bigger junction capacitances. Note that in the experiments the junction capacitances can only be made bigger by paralleling external capacitances. However, the trend is clear enough to infer what would happen in case of lower junction capacitances. For verification purposes, circuit simulation is also done under exactly the same operating condition.

III.2. MOSFET Drain-Source Capacitance C_{DS}

Fig. 4-13 shows the effect of paralleling capacitances to the drain-source terminals of the MOSFET to mimic a bigger C_{DS} . As seen from Fig. 4-13 (a), the turn-on waveforms almost do not change as the capacitance increases from 0 to 500 pF. Only V_{DS} slew rate is slowed down a little bit due to the longer charging time of C_{DS} . No excessive ringing is observed in V_{DS} or I_D waveform. This verifies the fact that during turn-on the ringing is mainly determined by the freewheeling diode junction capacitance C_J , which in this case is not changed. The simulation shown in Fig. 4-14 (a) exhibits the same results.

During the turn-off transients, however, the ringing in V_{DS} and I_D waveforms increase apparently as the capacitance becomes bigger. As stated above, C_{OSS} of the MOSFET is the major contributor to the parasitic ringing during this period, and C_{DS} is just the major part of C_{OSS} . One may question the severe ringing in I_D under such moderate switching speed ($R_G = 15 \Omega$). It is true that under normal speed the switching waveforms should not oscillate so severely, or even do not oscillate at all, but this happens for the original C_{DS} of MOSFET which is around 100 pF under $V_{DS} = 400$ V. In this test, however, the additional C_{DS} is over five times the original value, which causes the excessive ringing even under moderate switching speed. Or, in other word, if a device has such a big C_{DS} , even this moderate switching speed would become the speed limit for the device.

Fig. 4-13 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{DS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-14 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{DS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

III.3. Freewheeling Diode Junction Capacitance C_J

Fig. 4-15 shows the effect of C_J , the junction capacitance of the freewheeling diode. As analyzed previously, this capacitance increases the turn-on current spike and the parasitic ringing, which is clearly seen from Fig. 4-15 (a). During turn-off, C_J draws more current from the load to discharge itself, and faster I_D falling speed can be observed. However, C_J does not cause any excessive ringing during this period as seen in Fig. 4-15 (b). This again proves the correctness of the previous analyses.

The simulation waveforms in Fig. 4-16 do not predict the parasitic ringing. However C_J 's charging and discharging effect on the drain current is still very obvious.

III.4. MOSFET Gate-Drain (Miller) Capacitance C_{GD}

Fig. 4-17 and Fig. 4-18 show the effect of the Miller capacitance C_{GD} . As explained earlier, Miller capacitance can be decoupled into an equivalent input capacitance which is greatly amplified during V_{DS} rise and fall periods. Therefore, V_{DS} slew rates are very sensitive to and essentially determined by C_{GD} . As seen from both figures, V_{DS} becomes slower (and correspondingly V_{GS} plateau region expands) as the external Miller capacitance increases from

0 to 15 pF. The I_D slew rate is not affected at all, except that during turn-off I_D is delayed a little bit due to the slower V_{DS} . However, adding extra Miller capacitance does not cause extra ringing in the switching waveforms.

Fig. 4-15 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of freewheeling diode C_J . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-16 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of freewheeling diode C_J . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-17 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{GD} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-18 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{GD} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

III.5. MOSFET Gate-Source Capacitance C_{GS}

Fig. 4-19 and Fig. 4-20 show the effect of the gate-source capacitance C_{GS} . This capacitance mainly determines the time constant of the MOSFET gate circuit. Therefore, as the external C_{GS} increases from 0 to 1.5 nF, V_{GS} becomes slower, and accordingly the switching delay increases and I_D slew rate decreases. Still, this capacitance does not have a great influence on the high-frequency parasitic ringing.

Fig. 4-19 Experimental waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{GS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

Fig. 4-20 Simulation waveforms showing the influence of MOSFET C_{GS} . 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off. Time: 50 ns/div

III.6. MOSFET with Smaller Junction Capacitances

From the above parametric study it has been clearly exhibited which capacitance plays what role in the MOSFET switching characteristics. The limitation of the experiments is that the capacitances can only be made bigger. To strengthen the hypothesis, it is desirable to see how the same device behaves with less junction capacitances, and one can easily achieve this in the simulation by manipulating the MOSFET model. In the following simulation, the C_{DS} , C_{GD} and C_{GS} of the SiC MOSFET model are respectively reduced by about 50 % of their original values. The corresponding switching waveforms are then compared with the original model, which are shown from Fig. 4-21 to Fig. 4-23. As seen in Fig. 4-21, with half C_{DS} the turn-on current ringing is reduced and turn-off ringing is almost eliminated. Whereas for the other two cases, only voltage or current slew rates and delays are changed, while the parasitic ringing still remains in the switching waveforms.

Fig. 4-21 Switching waveforms of SiC MOSFET model: original vs. 50 % C_{DS}

Fig. 4-22 Switching waveforms of SiC MOSFET model: original vs. 50 % C_{GD}

Fig. 4-23 Switching waveforms of SiC MOSFET model: original vs. 50 % C_{GS}

III.7. Summary of Parasitic Capacitance Effects

The following can be concluded for the MOSFET parasitic capacitances:

(1) The MOSFET drain-source capacitance C_{DS} is the main contributor to the parasitic ringing. It is effective during both turn-on and turn-off transients. Smaller C_{DS} results in smaller ringing, which is most apparent in the turn-off transients.

(2) The freewheeling diode junction capacitance C_J is another major contributor to the current spike and the parasitic ringing during turn-on transients. It appears only during turn-on because during turn-off it is effectively shorted by the diode.

(3) The Miller capacitance C_{GD} mainly determines the V_{DS} slew rate. Smaller C_{GD} results in faster V_{DS} and thus lower switching loss. On the other hand, this capacitance, though part of the MOSFET output capacitance C_{OSS} , does not affect too much the parasitic ringing. Smaller C_{GD} even has a negative effect on the ringing because V_{DS} is faster.

(4) The gate-source capacitance C_{GS} mainly determines the switching delays and the drain current slew rate. It does not influence the parasitic ringing too much either.

IV. Quantification of the Parametric Study

To evaluate the effects of the parasitics, the parametric study has also been conducted in terms of device stress, switching energy, and EMI noise.

IV.1. Effects on Device Stresses

Fig. 4-24 summarizes the V_{DS} and I_D overshoots under different parasitic impedances, in 400 V, 10 A switching condition, with 15 Ω gate resistance.

Fig. 4-24 Parasitic effect on device stresses. 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$. (left) V_{DS} overshoot, (right) I_D overshoot

As seen from Fig. 4-24 (a) and (b), the gate loop inductance has only a minor effect on the MOSFET switching waveforms. Both voltage and current overshoots basically remain unchanged in this case. The switching loop inductance on the other hand increases both overshoots. Comparing the condition where both L_{DS} and L_{GS} are 65 nH, the V_{DS} overshoot for the former case is greater by about 8 % and I_D overshoot by 7 %. Note that in this comparison $R_G = 15 \Omega$. For even faster switching speed the difference would be further exacerbated. The common source inductance L_{SS} , as discussed, relieves the device stresses by slowing down the switching, which is also apparent from the figure.

The MOSFET C_{DS} and freewheeling diode C_J basically do not worsen the voltage stress, however they mainly cause drain current oscillations with C_{DS} being the major contributor to the turn-off ringing and C_J being the critical one to the turn-on overshoot, as seen from Fig. 4-24 (c) and (d). (e) and (f) show that bigger Miller capacitance C_{GD} relieves both voltage and current stresses by slowing down the V_{DS} waveform, which is consistent with the previous analysis. The gate-source capacitance C_{GS} , however, does not have direct impact on the device stresses, as it can be seen from (g) to (h).

IV.2. Switching Energy and Loss

Fig. 4-25 shows the parasitic effect on the switching energy E_{on} and E_{off} , and the total switching loss $E_{tot} = E_{on} + E_{off}$. As seen in Fig. 4-25 (a), the increase in L_{GS} and L_{DS} almost do not affect the switching energy, despite of the more severe ringing observed in the waveforms. This is verified by inspecting the instant power waveform of the MOSFET ($I_D \cdot V_{DS}$), which appears to be purely decaying reactive due to the almost 90° shifted V_{DS} and I_D ringing waveforms. A close scrutiny of (a) also tells that L_{DS} reduces the turn-on energy a little bit due to its snubber effect, and does the opposite to E_{off} because of higher V_{DS} overshoot. The overall loss, however, is almost unchanged. Fig. 4-25 (b) displays the influence of L_{SS} , which as stated above significantly increases the switching energy due to its negative feedback nature. In effect, the total switching loss when $L_{SS} = 65$ nH is over four times bigger than E_{tot} under the same value of L_{DS} .

Fig. 4-25 Parasitic effect on switching energy. 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 15 \Omega$

In Fig. 4-25 (c), it can be seen that bigger C_J increases the turn-on energy due to its discharging current that adds to the load current, and decreases the turn-off energy as it draws the load current to charge itself. The overall effect is to increase the total loss. On the other hand, adding more C_{DS} increases both switching energies and the total switching loss, which seemingly conflicts with the common knowledge that adding more drain-source capacitance can help reduce the switching loss. This will be discussed later.

Fig. 4-25 (d) and (e) clearly tell that both C_{GD} and C_{GS} tend to increase the switching energy and total loss as they become bigger. It is also obvious that the switching loss is much more sensitive to C_{GD} than C_{GS} .

IV.3. EMI Noise

Finally, to study the impact of the parasitic ringing on the EMI noise, the common-mode (CM) current on the DC bus of the double-pulse tester is also measured. Fig. 4-26 displays the spectrum of this current during MOSFET turn-off transients, under $L_{DS} = 0$ nH and $L_{DS} = 65$ nH conditions respectively. As seen, the high-frequency oscillation caused by this inductance is also coupled to the DC bus CM current, whose spectrum rises by around 5 to 10 dBmA at 60 to 90 MHz – the range of the ringing frequency, indicating potentially higher EMI radiation.

Fig. 4-26 Spectrum of DC bus CM current. 400 V, 10 A, $R_G = 7.5 \Omega$

V. Effect of MOSFET Drain-Source Capacitance C_{DS}

From Fig. 4-13 it can be seen that C_{DS} mainly modifies the drain-source voltage slew rate, but does not affect the di/dt of the drain current. This is intuitive because larger C_{DS} will need more time to be charged or discharged between zero and full bus voltage, thus causing both turn-on and turn-off energy to increase since they are calculated by $\int I_D V_{DS} dt$.

However, this seems to be conflicting with the common practice of paralleling external drain-source capacitances to reduce the turn-off loss. As a matter of fact, the seeming conflict originates from the way of current measurement and the definition of “switching loss”. The existence of MOSFET C_{DS} tends to make the drain current I_D measured outside the device deviate from the real channel current $I_{channel}$. Therefore, the real switching loss should be evaluated as $\int I_{channel} V_{DS} dt$ instead of $\int I_D V_{DS} dt$. During turn-off, C_{DS} draws part of the load current to charge itself, which makes $I_{channel} < I_D$, and correspondingly $\int I_{channel} V_{DS} dt < \int I_D V_{DS} dt$. As C_{DS} increases, more current from the load goes to charge the capacitance instead of flowing through the channel. Thus, $\int I_{channel} V_{DS} dt$ decreases although from the outside $\int I_D V_{DS} dt$ seems bigger. For the turn-on transients the process is just the opposite: the C_{DS} discharging current makes $\int I_{channel} V_{DS} dt > \int I_D V_{DS} dt$. In this sense, the expression of $\int I_D V_{DS} dt$ can only be called “switching energy” as it does not represent the real turn-on or turn-off loss.

The following simulation shown in Fig. 4-27 further reveals the current distribution between the MOSFET channel and C_{DS} . In the simulation a 5 nF external linear capacitance is paralleled

to the drain-source terminals of the MOSFET. It can be clearly seen from the figure how much difference C_{DS} has caused between the measured drain current and the lossy channel current.

Fig. 4-27 Simulation showing the effect of C_{DS}

The following conclusions can be reached based on the above simulation:

(1) Under the clamped inductive load, increasing C_{DS} increases both turn-on and turn-off energy, although the real turn-on loss is increased and the turn-off loss is reduced.

(2) If adding the measured switching energies together ($402.1 + 424.8 = 826.9 \mu\text{J}$) and comparing with the sum of the real loss ($815.5 + 16.9 = 832.4 \mu\text{J}$), one can find that they are almost equal. This means although E_{on} and E_{off} do not represent the real loss, the sum of them is still the overall switching loss in one switching cycle.

(3) The I_D and V_{DS} ringing results in purely reactive power which does not cause any extra loss for the MOSFET.

The conflict is thus resolved: the external C_{DS} does reduce the turn-off loss by converting the load current to the stored energy, as long as this energy is not dissipated in the MOSFET channel during turn-on. This is true for the commonly implemented R-C-D snubber circuit where the stored energy is dissipated through the external resistor; and for the zero-voltage-switching operation where the energy is used to charge / discharge the inductor. However, if C_{DS} is internal to the MOSFET, or in another word, if the MOSFET has very big junction capacitance, the overall switching loss always increases for hard-switching operation, because the energy stored in C_{DS} can only be dissipated in the channel. The bigger C_{DS} , the bigger loss.

VI. Conclusions

This chapter has systematically studied the impact of the parasitic impedances on the MOSFET switching behavior. From the parametric study results, the following conclusions can be reached:

(1) The parasitic ringing during the fast switching transients is mainly caused by the switching loop inductance L_{DS} resonating with the MOSFET drain-source capacitance C_{DS} .

(2) The parasitic ringing worsens the device stresses and EMI radiation, but does not significantly increase the switching loss.

(3) The common source inductance L_{SS} and the MOSFET Miller capacitance C_{GD} are the two critical factors that impact the switching speed and loss, and thus must be kept as small as possible.

(4) The measured switching energy E_{on} and E_{off} do not represent the real losses. However, the sum of E_{on} and E_{off} does represent the real switching loss in one switching cycle.

VII. References

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Chapter 5 MODELING AND SIMULATION OF 2 kV, 50 A SiC MOSFET/JBS POWER MODULES

I. Introduction

Power electronic modules constitute one of the driving forces towards modularization and integration of power electronic systems, improving the system performance by greatly reducing the package parasitic impedances without losing the total functionality of the systems [1]. Moreover, the compact integration of power electronic modules makes them more suitable and qualified for the concept of Power Electronics Building Block (PEBB), where a converter can be built quickly and reliably by just connecting several sub-converter-level systems (e.g. phase-legs) together, allowing for faster design and construction of a converter system for even non-power-electronics specialists.

On the other hand, power semiconductor devices are another dominant factor for power electronic technologies. The newly developed silicon carbide (SiC) power MOSFET, featuring its high blocking voltage, low on-resistance, fast switching speed, and good thermal characteristics, has promised to become a superior substitute for silicon (Si) high power devices in the future. Although no commercial SiC MOSFET is available yet, lab prototypes have been developed, and considerable efforts have been made on the characterization and modeling of these devices [2]-[7]. SiC MOSFET models can thus be built based on published data, and computer simulations with these models can be used as the first means of exploring these new devices in the absence of practical experience with them.

To study the high-power MOSFET modules where paralleled SiC dice are required, the package parasitic impedances should also be taken into consideration since the power MOSFETs can be easily switched within 50 to 100 nano-seconds, creating enormous stress on the circuit due to the consequent dv/dt and di/dt induced transients. The package model of the power module can be obtained from finite element electromagnetic analysis, following the same process as presented in the previous chapter, and also measured by different methods for model verification purposes.

This chapter presents the modeling in Synopsys Saber [7] of a 2 kV 5 A SiC MOSFET die, together with the physics-based model of an actual 10 kV SiC MOSFET/JBS power module based on measurement and computer-aided analysis. Both the device and package models are simulated in Saber in a double-pulse test circuit, pinpointing the parameters of interest within the power module and showing their different effects on the SiC devices during switching and conduction states. The simulation results show how the proposed models can be used as an effective design tool for the study of the device performance and the characterization of the module physical layout.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The objective of this chapter is to explore a method of modeling high-power SiC MOSFET module in Saber, and to study the effects of package parasitic impedances on the SiC MOSFETs in the module. The results obtained will illustrate how the proposed models can be used as an effective design tool for the study of device performance, the characterization of module physical layout, and ultimately the design of the gate driver and ancillary circuitry.

I.2. Technical Approach

The SiC MOSFET model is built in Saber based on the experimental data published in [4], by using the Saber *Power MOSFET Tool*. The module package model is obtained from the electromagnetic analysis by Maxwell *Quick 3D Extractor* (Q3D) [11], and then converted into Saber templates for the device-package combined simulation of an inductive-load, double-pulse tester in Saber. Data exchange is realized between MATLAB, Saber, and Q3D. The modeling processes of the device and package models are illustrated in Fig. 5-1 and Fig. 5-2 respectively. These approaches will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

Fig. 5-1 Modeling approach of SiC MOSFET model

Fig. 5-2 Modeling approach of the module package model

II. SiC Power MOSFET Model

This section presents a 2 kV, 5 A SiC power MOSFET model built in Saber based on the device characteristics predicted by Hefner's power MOSFET model and published experimental data in [4]. The modeling process is basically the same as that presented in Chapter 2, but will be discussed in more details in this chapter.

II.1. Hefner's Power MOSFET Model

Hefner's model is based on the latest version of the power MOSFET formulation utilized in Hefner's IGBT model [9]. Its main features are:

- 1) Unique channel current expressions that consider the channel regions at the corners of the square or hexagonal cells that turn on at lower gate voltages;
- 2) Enhanced linear region transconductance due to diffusion in the non-uniformly doped channel; and

3) Two-phase nonlinear gate-drain overlap capacitance and nonlinear body-drain depletion capacitance that are important to describe the dynamic performance of the device.

The model uses over 50 parameters and more than 20 equations to describe the static and dynamic behavior of the device. The important equations include:

1) On-state channel current, the high current component of which is given by

$$I_{mosh} = \begin{cases} \frac{(1 - K_{fl})K_f K_p \left[(V_{gs} - V_{Th})V_{ds} - \frac{P_{vf}^{y-1} V_{ds}^y (V_{gs} - V_{Th})^{2-y}}{y} \right]}{(1 + \theta(V_{gs} - V_{Th}))} & \text{for } V_{ds} \leq \frac{V_{gs} - V_{Th}}{P_{vf}} \\ \frac{(1 - K_{fl})K_p (V_{gs} - V_{Th})^2}{2(1 + \theta(V_{gs} - V_{Th}))} & \text{for } V_{ds} > \frac{V_{gs} - V_{Th}}{P_{vf}} \end{cases} \quad (5-1)$$

where

I_{mosh} – high current region component,

K_f – linear region transconductance factor,

K_{fl} – low current region transconductance factor,

K_p – saturation region transconductance,

P_{vf} – pinch-off voltage factor,

θ – transverse electric field parameter,

V_{ds} – MOSFET channel voltage,

V_{gs} – gate-source voltage,

V_{Th} – high current MOSFET channel threshold voltage,

y – a function of K_f and P_{vf} .

Low current component takes a similar expression to (5-1). The total channel current is the sum of the high current and low current.

2) Transient equations, which are given by

$$C_{dsj} = \frac{A_{ds} \mathcal{E}_{semi}}{W_{dsj}} \quad (5-2)$$

and

$$C_{gd} = \begin{cases} C_{oxd}, & V_{ds} \leq V_{gs} - V_{Td} \\ \frac{C_{oxd} C_{gdj}}{(C_{oxd} + C_{gdj})}, & V_{ds} > V_{gs} - V_{Td} \end{cases} \quad (5-3)$$

where

A_{ds} – drain-body junction area,

C_{dsj} – drain-source junction capacitance,

C_{gd} – gate-drain capacitance,

C_{oxd} – gate-drain overlap oxide capacitance,

C_{gdj} – gate-drain depletion capacitance,

ϵ_{semi} – semiconductor dielectric constant,

V_{Td} – gate-drain overlap depletion threshold,

W_{dsj} – drain-body depletion width.

The channel current equations determine the static characteristics of the MOSFET. The capacitance equations, on the other hand, determine the transients of the device during turn-on and turn-off processes, through the input capacitance C_{iss} , output capacitance C_{oss} , and reverse transfer capacitance C_{rss} , which are given by

$$C_{iss} = C_{gs} + C_{gd} \quad (5-4)$$

$$C_{oss} = C_{gd} + C_{dsj} \quad (5-5)$$

$$C_{rss} = C_{gd} \quad (5-6)$$

The gate-drain capacitance C_{gd} and drain-source capacitance C_{dsj} are P-N junction capacitances, and thus are nonlinear about the voltages across them—these two capacitances drop as the voltages rise. The gate-source capacitance C_{gs} is essentially a linear and fixed-value capacitance, which is determined by the physical structure of the oxide layer between the gate and source terminals.

Not all parameters need to be directly measured however, as in [4], only 18 of them were extracted from a prototype 2 kV 5 A SiC MOSFET, while the remaining 30 or so parameters were simply calculated from them. These parameters and respective equations can be coded in MATLAB to generate the characteristic curves of the device. Equation (5-1) is used to plot the output characteristic curves, and (5-4) to (5-6) are used to plot the capacitance curves, as shown in Fig. 5-3 (a) and (b) respectively. These characteristic curves will be imported into Saber later to build the Saber MOSFET model.

Fig. 5-3 Characteristic curves of the prototype 2 kV, 5 A SiC MOSFET.
(a) Output characteristics, (b) capacitance characteristics

II.2. Saber Power MOSFET Model

The *Power MOSFET Tool* is a built-in program of Saber which generates level-1 MOSFET models intended for power electronics simulation. These models are well suited for examining the switching transients and losses of power MOSFETs. A fairly low level of complexity ensures good convergence in simulation. A limited number of parameters – less than 30 in total – make parameter extraction more easily from datasheet information [10]. Fig. 5-4 shows the main user interface of this program, where an equivalent circuit of the MOSFET model is also illustrated.

Fig. 5-4 Saber *Power MOSFET Tool* user interface and MOSFET model equivalent circuit

This program requires three pieces of information to characterize a MOSFET model, namely:

- 1) Output characteristics, which are represented by the three resistances R_g , R_d , R_s , and the intrinsic MOSFET, according to Fig. 5-4;
- 2) Capacitance characteristics, which are represented by the three capacitances C_{gd} , C_{gs} , and C_{ds} from Fig. 5-4. The actual capacitances Saber accepts are C_{iss} , C_{oss} and C_{rss} (versus V_{ds}), which are simply linear combinations of C_{gd} , C_{gs} , and C_{ds} according to equations (5-4)–(5-6).
- 3) Body diode static and reverse recovery characteristics. The body diode is modeled as a power diode connected in anti-parallel with the MOSFET. The junction capacitance of the body diode is assumed to be lumped with the drain-source capacitance C_{ds} of the MOSFET.

Most of the above information can be found from the device datasheet, except for the internal gate resistance R_g , which should be measured by the user in order to accurately model the MOSFET. In our case however, since the paper [4] provides only the output and capacitance characteristics (Fig. 5-3), only these two parts are modeled accordingly in the *Power MOSFET Tool*, while the rest of the model parameters are left as default.

Output and capacitance characteristic curves can be imported into the program in form of images using *Scanned Data Utility*, which is a function coming with the program to digitalize the datasheet curves. Saber allows users to adjust the model parameters visually such that the

characteristic curves predicted by the model can fit the imported data. By running the *Optimizer Utility* (another built-in function of the program) after manual adjustment, the model parameters can be tuned achieving an optimal curve-fit of the original data. As seen in Fig. 5-5, good agreement has been achieved between experiments and model predictions. The body diode model can be extracted in the same way if its characteristics are available.

Fig. 5-5 Curve fitting results. (a) Output characteristics, (b) capacitance characteristics

Table 5-1 shows the extracted model parameters for this 2 kV, 5 A SiC MOSFET.

Table 5-1 Model parameters of the 2 kV, 5 A SiC MOSFET

Parameters	Description	Value	Unit
tempj	Temperature	25	°C
vt	Gate threshold voltage	5.77	V
vgs, vds, ids	Reference point on I_d surface	10, 5.177, 2.649	V, V, A
rds	Inverse of the initial slope of the I_d vs V_{ds} curve going through the (vds, vgs, ids) point	0.523	Ω
rs	Source series resistance	0.1	Ω
rd	Drain series resistance	0.03	Ω
rg	Gate series resistance	0.1	Ω
lamda	Slope in the saturation region	0.0001	-
crss0	Maximum crss value	2.180	nF
crss1	crss value for v1	0.823	nF
crss2	crss value for v2	0.128	nF

coss0	Maximum coss value	2.440	nF
coss1	coss value for v1	1.076	nF
coss2	coss value for v2	0.245	nF
ciss0	Maximum ciss value	4.860	nF
v1	First reference voltage	0.105	V
v2	Second reference voltage	10.0	V
profile	Doping profile parameter	0.45	-

To verify the model, the same resistive-load test circuit as described in [4] is simulated in Saber, as shown in Fig. 5-6. A comparison of the simulations and the experiments (Fig. 5-7) shows a good agreement between the two, verifying the accuracy of the model.

Note that the MOSFET model is limited by the device information available. The model predicts the correct device behavior at only 25 °C, because that's the only temperature provided by [4]. Furthermore, since there is no body diode data, the model behavior is trustable only when the body diode is not conducting, such as the case of an inductive-load, double-pulse circuit, which will be discussed later in the following sections.

Fig. 5-6 Resistive load test circuit

Fig. 5-7 Turn-on transient waveforms comparison between simulation and experiment [4].
 (a) Gate current, (b) drain current, (c) drain voltage

III. Modeling and Simulation of Power MOSFET Module

III.1. Power MOSFET Module

The power MOSFET module under study is an actual phase-leg module designed and manufactured by Powerex Inc., whose 3D layout is shown in Fig. 5-8. This module is 17.4 mm × 13.3 mm × 2.9 mm in size and rated at 10 kV, 110 A. In order to handle very high voltage and power, the module is designed to utilize totally twenty 10 kV, 10 A SiC MOSFET dice with ten in

parallel acting as one switch of the phase-leg. Another twenty 10 kV 10 A Junction-Barrier-Schottky (JBS) diodes are placed next to the MOSFETs acting as the anti-parallel diodes, while eight 100 V 60 A Si Schottky diodes are connected in series with the MOSFETs working as the blocking diodes to prevent the intrinsic body diodes from conducting.

Fig. 5-8 3D layout of the power MOSFET module

As seen from Fig. 5-8, four pieces of direct-bonded-copper (DBC) substrates are placed over a large copper baseplate. Five SiC MOSFETs, five SiC anti-parallel diodes and two Si blocking diodes sit on each substrate, where ten parallel devices (on the two substrates from either top side or bottom side of the module in Fig. 5-8) form one switch in the phase-leg. Several laminated buses, namely D1, S1D2, and S2 lie across the central line of the module, whereas the gate signal buses G1, S1P, and G2, S2P lie on the two sides of the module. All the dice and buses are interconnected using wire-bond technology, with four bonding wires per chip for each MOSFET/diode pair, which leads to a total of approximately 200 bonding wires in the module. Fig. 5-9 shows the internal view of the module with all wires-bonds connected, as well as its equivalent circuit.

Fig. 5-9 Internal view of the power MOSFET module and its equivalent circuit

III.2. Package Model

Ansoft *Quick 3D Extractor* [11], commercial 3D finite-element electromagnetic analysis software, is chosen for modeling the above power MOSFET module. Provided with the correct dimensions, material properties (resistivity of conductors and permittivity of insulators), and boundary conditions (the conductors and current paths), the software can extract the parasitic impedances of any arbitrary geometry [13]. Moreover, the analysis results, namely the R , L , and C matrices, can be exported in different formats, making data exchange more flexible between Q3D and other circuit simulation software.

The physical geometry of the module is imported into Q3D from the original computer-aided-design (CAD) file provided by the manufacturer. The CAD file contains only the geometrical information of the baseplate, DBC substrates, bus bars, etc, without the bonding wires. The material information is not included either. Therefore in Q3D, different materials are assigned to different module structures, and wire-bond interconnections are added to the module as well. A total of 200 or so bonding wires within the module would make the geometry quite complex. However, not all these wires are necessary for the package model. Because in a double-pulse tester only half of the phase-leg conducts, only the corresponding wires need to be modeled in order to simplify the structure and reduce the analysis time. The final model is shown in Fig. 5-10.

For future reference, both the MOSFETs and diodes are numbered 1 to 10 from left to right in the module shown in Fig. 5-10.

Fig. 5-10 Q3D package model: (left) model geometry, (right) modeled parts in the phase-leg (black)

Q3D can calculate the parasitic impedances for both DC and AC current excitations. For DC excitation, Q3D assumes that the current frequency is low such that there is no skin effect or proximity effect existent. While for the AC situation, Q3D calculates the impedances assuming that the high-frequency current has well established the skin effect and proximity effect. Thus, the resistances calculated in DC case are lower than those in AC case; while the inductances are higher (the capacitances however are not affected). In our case, a DC analysis is adopted since the larger inductances help to reveal the worst effect the parasitic impedances would have on the devices.

In quasi-static electromagnetic analysis, the parasitic inductances and resistances are calculated between structure terminals, which define the current paths. The capacitances are calculated between conductors, which also include the capacitances to a common ground – the baseplate in our case. Three matrices, namely R , L , and C , are generated after the analysis. These matrices represent the parasitic components of the module structure. The total analysis time for this configuration takes about 1.5 hours on a Pentium 4 PC with 3 GB memory.

The RLC matrices are then exported as an equivalent circuit in form of a netlist file. An interpretation of the matrices, the equivalent circuit is composed of R_s , L_s , and C_s representing the parasitic impedances. The simplest equivalent circuit Q3D adopts is a lumped T-shaped circuit model, as illustrated in Fig. 5-11. The external nodes (i.e. the nodes outside the shaded box) represent the terminals of the system. The resistance and inductance calculated for each current branch are then split equally into two (named as “XZhalf1” and “XZhalf2” respectively), and are connected in series using internal nodes (i.e. the nodes in the box). The parasitic capacitances, represented by the parallel sub-circuit “XY1”, are connected from the internal nodes to the ground or from one internal node to other internal nodes [13].

Q3D can use more complicated equivalent circuit to interpret the same RLC matrices by increasing the number of internal nodes, which is referred to as the “number of lumps”. For example, a π -shaped equivalent circuit can be obtained by using two internal nodes. As the internal nodes increase, the equivalent circuit for each current branch becomes more distributed and more like a transmission line, thus leading to higher bandwidth for the circuit model. However, doing this would increase the number of components in the equivalent circuit, resulting in higher system resource consumptions and longer simulation times for the circuit simulator. For simplicity, the T model is chosen in this work.

Fig. 5-11 T-shaped equivalent circuit model

The equivalent circuit can be exported in several different formats. A PSPICE netlist is used in our case. The netlist contains three sub-circuits, with one representing the top-level structure (the connections of XY1, XZhalf1 and XZhalf2), and the other two representing the inner connections of XZhalf and XY1. Before the PSPICE netlist can be used in Saber, it needs to be converted to Saber templates using the Saber conversion tool *Nspitos* [14]. The *.sin* file obtained after conversion also contains three sub-templates, corresponding to the original three sub-circuits in the netlist file. Saber has problem dealing with multiple templates in one *.sin* file, so these templates are saved separately, with their file names the same as their respective template names. Symbols are also created for each template. At this point, the package model of the power MOSFET module has been ready for further circuit simulation.

III.3. Q3D Model Verification

To verify the package model, the parasitic impedances are also measured in an actual module for comparison purposes. As shown in Fig. 5-12, the measurements are conducted on a module with all its interconnections in place, but where all the semiconductor devices have been removed. Different sections of interest are measured and compared with the Q3D results. For parasitic resistances and inductances, the measured sections are:

- 1) G1 terminal to S1P terminal,
- 2) G2 terminal to S2P terminal,
- 3) D1 terminal to S2 terminal,
- 4) D1 terminal to S1D2 terminal,
- 5) S1D2 terminal to S2 terminal,
- 6) D1 terminal to D1 bar end,
- 7) S2 terminal to S2 bar end,
- 8) A – D1 center to up-left MOSFET drain pad,
- 9) B – S1D2 terminal to up-left MOSFET drain pad,
- 10) C – D1 center to S1D2 terminal,
- 11) D – S2 center to down-left MOSFET drain pad,

- 12) E – S1D2 terminal to down-left MOSFET drain pad,
- 13) F – S2 center to S1D2 terminal.

For capacitance, the measurement is done between all the interconnection parts (which are shorted together) and the baseplate.

Fig. 5-12 Actual power MOSFET module with sections of interest indicated

The following methods are used to measure the parasitic impedances.

A. Impedance Analyzer

An Agilent 4294A Precision Impedance Analyzer is used to measure the parasitic inductances and capacitance of the aforementioned sections. Because of the long distance between module terminals (e.g. D1 to S1D2), the probe kit 42941A with clip leads (Fig. 5-13 and Fig. 5-14) have to be used to connect the module terminals. The measurement is straightforward. However, the clip leads form different current loops for calibration and measurement. Although these loops can be reduced by twisting the two leads, the configuration difference between calibration and measurement still causes big relative errors in the inductance measurements, considering the very small value of parasitic inductances. Therefore, the measured inductances can only serve as a reference for other measurement methods. On the other hand, the capacitance measurement is not affected by the clip lead loop and can be measured with trustable results.

Fig. 5-13 42941A impedance probe kit

Fig. 5-14 Clip leads of 42941A probe kit.
(a) SHORT compensation configuration, (b) measurement configuration

B. V-I Method

To avoid the high relative error in the previous measurements, a V-I method is also adopted to measure the parasitic impedances. The measurement setup is illustrated in Fig. 5-15. For this method, a 300 kHz sinusoidal wave is applied to the different section terminals. The voltage across the section and the current flowing through it are then captured with oscilloscope. At this frequency, the reactive component would dominate the total parasitic impedance. For inductance, the voltage leads the current by almost 90 degrees, resulting in the measured inductance of

$$L = \frac{V_m}{\omega I_m} \quad (5-7)$$

where V_m and I_m are the measured voltage and current magnitudes, and ω is the angular frequency of the excitation. Similarly, the measured capacitance is given by

$$C = \frac{I_m}{\omega V_m} \quad (5-8)$$

Fig. 5-15 V-I method setup

The V-I method is not affected by the experimental setup as the impedance analyzer is, so it provides more repeatable and trustable measurement results for the module parasitics.

C. Kelvin Sensing (Four-Terminal Method)

Although the impedance analyzer is able to measure small resistances, yet the contact resistances caused by the clips can still result in great error. Considering this, Kelvin sensing, or the four-terminal method, is used to measure the small parasitic resistances. This method eliminates the contact resistances, and can accurately measure resistances down to several m Ω .

Table 5-2 summarizes the module parasitics obtained from different methods (simulation and measurement). It can be found through comparison that the Q3D model shows a good agreement with the measurements, verifying that the model correctly represents the package parasitics of the power module.

Table 5-2 Comparison of package parasitics of the power module

Sections	Inductance [nH]			Resistance [m Ω]		Capacitance [pF]		
	V-I method	Impedance analyzer	Q3D	Kelvin	Q3D	V-I method	Impedance analyzer	Q3D
G1 – S1P	33.1	25.8	21.4	2.96	3.55	---	---	---
G2 – S2P	27.1	28.0	21.4	3.04	3.56	---	---	---
D1 – S2	47.1	47.0	36.8	---	---	---	---	---
D1 – S1D2	71.2	78.8	83.0	0.95	1.15	---	---	---
S1D2 – S2	78.4	73.8	84.5	0.95	1.04	---	---	---
D1 – D1 end	53.2	44.0	72.8	---	---	---	---	---
S2 – S2 end	53.2	43.4	76.9	---	---	---	---	---
A	19.2	14.2	10.3	---	---	---	---	---
B	24.9	40.9	24.7	---	---	---	---	---
C	39.2	55.9	38.3	---	---	---	---	---
D	21.5	19.1	11.4	---	---	---	---	---
E	30.3	31.0	23.9	---	---	---	---	---
F	46.6	57.0	37.3	---	---	---	---	---
Interconnection to baseplate	---	---	---	---	---	635	584	542

III.4. Device-Package Combined Simulation

Although the Powerex module requires 10 kV SiC MOSFETs, the device model is not available at the time of the work, and there is not enough data from publications for us to build such a model. Therefore, the 2 kV 5 A SiC MOSFET model is used instead with the package model to simulate an inductive-load double-pulse tester circuit in Saber. To study the effect of the package parasitics, two simulation circuits are set up in Saber, with and without the package model, as shown in Fig. 5-16, where the rectangular block in (b) represents the parasitic impedance network. An ideal piecewise-linear voltage source is used as the gate driver. The Cree 1200 V, 10 A SiC Schottky diode is selected as the free-wheeling diode, whose SPICE model is downloaded from Cree's website and then converted to Saber model. The parameters of the simulation circuit are listed in Table 5-3.

Fig. 5-16 Double-pulse tester simulation circuit. (left) No parasitics, (right) with parasitics

Table 5-3 Parameters of the simulation circuit

Parameters	Values
DC Bus Voltage V_{DC}	600 V
Bus Series Resistance R_s	40 Ω
Load Inductance L	0.2 mH
Inductor Series Resistance R_L	0.1 Ω
Gate Voltage V_g	15 V
Gate Voltage Rise Time t_r	10 ns
Gate Voltage Fall Time t_f	10 ns
Gate Resistance R_g	1 Ω

Fig. 5-17 shows the MOSFET drain current—normally measured with a shunt resistor, the actual current flowing through the device channel, and the Miller and gate-source capacitance currents during turn-on and turn-off transients in the ideal case. It can be observed that the real channel current is greater than the measured drain current during turn-on and smaller during turn-off, due to the existence of capacitance currents. Considering that the channel current causes the real loss, these results unveiled by the device model can help evaluate the MOSFET switching loss more accurately.

Fig. 5-18 shows the MOSFET current sharing condition under the effect of module parasitics. For a clear view of the waveforms only MOSFET 5 and 6 are displayed. It is observed that MOSFET 5 conducts the minimum current and MOSFET 6 conducts the maximum among all ten chips, due to the difference in interconnection resistances. Under 1 A load condition, the maximum steady-state current difference between MOSFET 5 and 6 is about 50 mA, fairly small because of the symmetrical design of the power module. However this difference will increase as the load current increases.

Fig. 5-17 Comparison of drain current, channel current and junction capacitance currents. (left) Turn-on, (right) turn-off

Fig. 5-18 MOSFET current sharing

Fig. 5-19 illustrates the current sharing condition among free-wheeling diodes. It can be seen that these currents differ a lot during the switching transients but tend to merge as they come into the steady state. Also observed is the big ringing due to the resonance between device junction capacitances and module parasitics. Noticing that the free-wheeling diode is Schottky type with negligible reverse recovery, the negative currents observed in Fig. 5-19 are actually the charging currents of the junction capacitances, which is verified by directly observing the capacitance currents from the diode model.

Fig. 5-19 Current sharing of the free-wheeling diodes

Comparisons are also made between simulations with and without the package model. Fig. 5-20 shows the drain-source voltage and Fig. 5-21 shows the drain current of one switch during its turn-on and turn-off processes. It is clear that the waveforms are delayed by the presence of the parasitic impedances, and the effect of the characteristic ringing is also apparent from these figures.

Fig. 5-20 Drain-source voltages during (a) turn-on and (b) turn-off

Fig. 5-21 Drain currents during (a) turn-on and (b) turn-off

The device-package combined simulation can be used as a strong evaluation tool for the module layout and gate driver design. The current sharing and parasitic-induced oscillations can be investigated from simulation before any hardware is built, thus greatly reducing the development cycle of power modules for the manufactures.

IV. Conclusions

In this chapter, the modeling and simulation method has been applied again to the study of a high-voltage, high-power SiC MOSFET/JBS module in Saber, using parameter extraction methods based on MATLAB, Saber, and Q3D. The combined simulation of the SiC MOSFET and the package models reveals how the package parasitics affect the device switching transients and the current sharing conditions. Furthermore, the device model is used to unveil the internal current distributions of the MOSFET, providing critical information for the accurate evaluation of the switching loss, and the design of ultra-fast gate-drive circuits, since the latter is highly sensitive to the device and layout parasitics due to the very high dv/dt nature of SiC devices (could be $> 100 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$). It is also shown the possibility that the package model can be used to substitute the time-consuming hardware design with much faster software design and simulation iterations, greatly speeding up the development cycles of power modules.

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Chapter 6 CONSIDERATIONS ON SERIES AND PARALLEL DEVICES INTERCONNECTIONS FOR POWER MODULE DESIGN

I. Introduction

For ultra-high power converter design, power semiconductor switches are required to be paralleled in order to support the high current ratings, and to be connected in series to support the high voltage. SiC power devices have become a suitable candidate for high power applications, where currently the junction field effect transistor (JFET) is the most mature device up to date. However, the normally-on characteristic of the JFET limits its range of application. A good solution for this is to form a normally-off switch by connecting a Si MOSFET and SiC JFET in a cascode (series-connection) structure. Furthermore, the voltage rating of this normally-off cascode switch can be extended using a multi-fold structure, which is nonetheless limited by the breakdown during turn-off of the gate-side diodes used in this type of structure. Addressing this shortcoming, in this chapter a circuit is proposed to protect the gate diode from being destroyed. The paralleling of power semiconductor devices on the other hand requires good current sharing and temperature balance, where the current and temperature distribution within the power module are partially determined by the layout of its interconnections. In this chapter the layout of a paralleled power switch is designed to achieve similar loop inductances for each device. Thermal simulations are used to compare the temperatures of paralleled devices and optimize the dimensions of the layout.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The objective of this work is to design the circuit and layout for the connection of power semiconductor devices in series and parallel. The switch using this circuit and layout design should provide higher voltage and current than a single device. The requirements of voltage sharing and current sharing need to be fulfilled for the high power switch.

I.2. Technical Approach

For series devices, a multi-fold Si MOSFET/SiC JFET cascode structure is used to increase the voltage rating. A protection circuit is proposed to avoid the breakdown of the gate diodes of the new device. The simulation software Saber is used to study the circuit behavior using Cree's SiC diode model and SiCED's SiC JFET model. The gate current results of two cascode topologies are compared. For paralleled devices, the layout of the module is studied to optimize the loop inductance using Maxwell Q3D. The extracted loop inductances are incorporated into Saber to simulate the overall circuit performance. Thermal issues are considered at the same time using Maxwell ePhysics to simulate the heat conduction for the electrical-thermal co-design of the module layout.

II. Series Connection of Devices

Most conventional converter design procedures assume that the semiconductor switches used are normally-off. This not the case when using SiC JFETs, so in order to provide normally-off operation for the latter, an approach using series-connected JFETs based on the cascode structure was introduced in [1]. Specifically, the SiC JFET is packaged in a cascode connection

with a normally-off Si MOSFET, which is shown in Fig. 6-1. When the MOSFET is turned on, the gate-source voltage of the JFET is low, so the JFET is turned on; when the Si MOSFET is turned off, the D-to-S voltage is applied between the source and gate of the JFET. As the source voltage of the JFET increases, its gate-source voltage reaches the pinch-off value of the device turning off the JFET. Therefore, when the cascode switch is turned off, the voltage applied on the Si MOSFET is the pinch-off voltage of the SiC JFET.

Fig. 6-1 Si MOSFET/SiC JFET cascode

Several low voltage SiC JFETs can be used to fabricate a multi-fold stacked high voltage switch [2]. The circuit schematic is shown in Fig. 6-2. The high voltage switch includes four SiC JFETs, one Si MOSFET, and three Si diodes. Between the gate terminals of the SiC JFETs are Si diodes. The drain of the Si MOSFET is connected to the source of the bottom JFET, and the source of the MOSFET is connected to the gate of the bottom JFET. The function of this stacked cascode can be described as follows.

Fig. 6-2 Multi-fold Si MOSFET/SiC JFET cascode

In conduction mode, a positive voltage higher than the threshold voltage is applied between the gate and source of the power MOSFET. When M1 is turned on, between the gate and source of the JFET appears the on state drain-source voltage of M1, which is small, therefore J1 is turned on too. Due to the same reason, J2, J3 and J4 are turned one after another. In the on state, the power switch consists of series resistive elements. If M1 is turned off, the bias starts to increase between gate and source of J1 until the pinch off voltage of J1 is reached. Accordingly, the source and gate of J2 become negative biased, as its gate is connected via D1 to the gate-drive circuit ground. Thus if the bias at the source of J2 reaches the sum of the pinch-off voltage of J2 and the blocking voltage of D1, the gate-source voltage of J2 is less than the pinch-off voltage, and J2 is turned off. The same holds for J3 and J4.

II.1. Issues for the Cascode Topology

Though the multiple JFETs cascode can block high voltage, there is still a problem limiting the application of this circuit. When the JFETs are turned off at rising voltages, the Si gate diodes of the cascode can be destroyed because of the excessive avalanche energies [3].

The breakdown of Si diodes can be analyzed with Kirchhoff's current law. As shown in Fig. 6-3, when the lower JFET connected to the source is turned off, the source-to-gate voltage of the higher JFET is low and the source voltage starts to increase. Therefore the current goes through the channel of the JFET because the device is still on. However, the source current of the JFET is nearly 0 A because the current flow has been cut off by the bottom (already turned-off) device. According to the Kirchhoff's current law, $\sum I = 0$, the gate current of the top device

is hence equal to its drain current until the channel of this JFET is completely pinched off. Consequently, if the diode connected to the gate is not carefully selected, it will be destroyed immediately.

Fig. 6-3 JFET and gate diode during turn-off

II.2. Protection Circuit for the Cascode

To make the multi-fold SiC JFET/Si MOSFET cascode suitable for high voltage converter, a protection circuit should be connected to the gates of the JFETs to reduce the current stress of the diode. Fig. 6-4 shows a proposed protection circuit. A two-fold cascode circuit is used as the low side switch. Two SiC JFETs J1 and J2 are connected in series with the Si MOSFET M1. The high side switch is replaced by an ideal current source. The current bias is 10 A and the DC bus voltage is 1200 V. For Saber simulations, the SiCED 1400V JFET model is used. The IR irfr/u48z device is selected as the low voltage MOSFET in the cascode, and the Cree C2D10120 is selected as the gate diode. A simplified gate drive with a 5 Ω internal resistance is used to switch the bottom Si MOSFET. The cascode works in hard switching mode at the frequency of 500 kHz.

Fig. 6-4 Proposed protection circuit for the multi-fold SiC JFET/Si MOSFET cascode

The function of the circuit is described as follows. When M1 is turned off, it behaves like a capacitor. The capacitor is charged to the pinch-off voltage of J1 when J1 is turned off. After that, M1 is equal to a voltage source and J1 behaves like another capacitor C2. When C2 is charged to the pinch-off voltage of J2, the cascode switch is completely turned off.

During the turn-off transient of the cascode switch, the drain current of the top JFET will go through the gate, which destroys the gate diode without protection circuit. Because of the existence of the Zener diode D2, the current will partially go through the Zener diode. The breakdown voltage of the Zener diode is set to half of the DC bus in simulation. In real design, several Zener diodes can be connected in series to achieve the high breakdown voltage.

As the current in the Zener diode increases, the voltage drop on the resistor R1 increases. When the gate voltage of M2 is larger than the threshold voltage, the MOSFET is turned on and the gate current of the JFET will go through the MOSFET and the secondary side of the transformer. The transformer can return the extra energy to the source. With the protection, the current of the Si diode connected to the gate of JFET is much less than the original case.

The DC simulation shows that the drain-to-source voltage of the top JFET is 584 V, and the drain current is 1.74 μA . The bottom JFET is clamped by the Zener diode, so the drain-to-source voltage is 600 V. The voltage drop on the Si MOSFET is 17.4 V. Each JFET can block nearly half of the bus voltage. Fig. 6-5 shows the current spike in the gate diode of the JFET. In the new cascode circuit, the current of the gate diode is 40 mA when the switch is turned off. But in the conventional cascode circuit, the current of this Si diode is 9.58 A, which is nearly the output of the ideal current bias (notice that the oscillograms have different scales).

Fig. 6-5 Current spikes in the gate diodes of two cascode circuits

Because an extra Si MOSFET is added to the circuit, more energy loss is consumed and the efficiency is decreased to some extent. Fig. 6-6 shows the dynamic behavior of the Si MOSFET. The green line is the gate voltage, the blue line is the drain current, and the red line is the drain-source voltage. In the turn-on transient, the voltage falling time is 40 ns, and the current rising time is 45 ns. In the turn-off transient, the voltage rising time is 58 ns, and the current falling time is 47 ns.

Fig. 6-6 The waveforms of the Si MOSFET in the switching transients

(a) Waveforms of gate voltage (green), drain-source voltage (red), and drain current (blue) in the turn-on transient (b) Waveforms of gate voltage (green), drain-source voltage (red), and drain current (blue) in the turn-off transient

Fig. 6-7 shows the waveform of the power loss on the MOSFET M1 and the calculated results are listed in Table 7-1. The energy loss in the transient is 1.9 μJ . Since the switching frequency of the Si MOSFET is 500 kHz, the power loss is 0.95 W. The energy loss is 1.7 μJ , and the power loss is 0.85 W. The conduction loss of the Si MOSFET is 0.76 W.

(a) Waveforms of gate-source voltage, drain-source voltage, and drain current.

(b) Waveform of power loss on the MOSFET

Fig. 6-7 Switching loss of the Si MOSFET (a) Waveforms of gate voltage, drain current and drain-source voltage (b) Power loss in turn-on and turn-off transients

Table 6-1 Power loss of the bottom Si MOSFET in the cascode

MOSFET	Energy	Frequency	Loss
turn-on	1.9 μJ	500kHz	0.95W
turn-off	1.7 μJ	500kHz	0.85W
conduction			0.76W

(a) Turn-on time
Voltage fall time: 11ns
Current rise time: 17ns

(b) Turn-off time
Voltage rise time: 30ns
Current fall time: 26ns

Fig. 6-8 The waveforms of the cascode switch in the switching transients (a) Waveforms of the voltage (blue) and current (red) in the turn-on transient (b) Waveforms of the voltage (blue) and current (red) in the turn-off transient

Fig. 6-8 shows the dynamic behavior of the cascode switch. The red line is the current, and the blue line is the voltage. In the turn-on transient, the voltage falling time is 11 ns, and the current rising time is 17 ns. In the turn-off transient, the voltage rising time is 30 ns, and the current falling time is 26 ns.

Fig. 6-9 shows the waveform of the power loss on the top JFET J2 and the calculated results are listed in Table 6-2. The energy loss in the transient is 160 μJ . Since the switching frequency of the Si MOSFET is 500 kHz, the power loss is 80 W. The energy loss is 64 μJ , and the power loss is 32 W. The conduction loss of the Si MOSFET is 60 W.

(a) Waveforms of drain-to-source voltage and drain current.

(b) Waveform of power loss on the JFET-MOSFET Cascode

Fig. 6-9 Switching loss of the top SiC JFET (a) Waveforms of drain current and drain-source voltage (b) Power loss in turn-on and turn-off transients

Table 6-2 Power loss of the SiC JFETs in the cascode

Cascode	Energy	Frequency	Loss
turn-on	160 μJ	500kHz	80W
turn-off	64 μJ	500kHz	32W
conduction			60W

III. Paralleling of Devices

III.1. Issues for Paralleling of Devices

When power semiconductor devices are connected in parallel, a good current balance has to be achieved. This is because a current unbalance can cause current concentration in a single device and even its thermal runaway in the worst case. Fig. 6-10 illustrates the parasitic elements in a power circuit containing N parallel branches. The current unbalance of the paralleled devices is affected by many factors such as on-state resistance mismatch, threshold voltage mismatch, gain factor mismatch, capacitance mismatch, gate loop inductance mismatch, drain inductance mismatch, and source inductance mismatch [4]. With the exception of the

Fig. 6-11 The symmetrical layout with similar loop impedances

There are nine possible current paths from the “plus” terminal to the “minus” terminal. Considering the three paths in Fig. 6-11 (b), the current can flow from “plus” to “minus” via S1-output-S4, S2-output-S5, or S3-output-S6. The length of each path can be compared by simple calculation. For each selected path, the total length of the black lines on the path is nearly constant; therefore balanced loop inductances are achieved. Besides the power loop design, several other requirements are also taken into account: The “plus” and “minus” terminals are close, which is suitable for putting a bypass capacitor in between; wide copper tracks and short bond wires are used to reduce the inductance; all the pins are located at the edge of the layout to form easy connections.

The temperature distribution is simulated in Maxwell ePhysics. The same geometry is used in both Q3D and ePhysics. The devices are mounted on the DBC which is a copper-alumina-copper tri-layer structure. No heatsink is attached to the DBC substrate and only natural conduction is used as the thermal exchanging approach. The thermal simulation shows the temperatures of the central devices are slightly higher than the devices at the edge. This can be explained by the thermal coupling effect. Because inductances of interconnections are kept small, the distance between devices is short. Therefore the thermal coupling effect increases the temperatures of the central devices. However the temperatures difference of semiconductor devices are within 1 °C, and the maximum temperature is about 150 °C, which could be further decreased by applying a heat spreader.

Fig. 6-12 Temperature distribution of the symmetrical phase-leg layout

Fig. 6-13 shows two unbalanced layout in which the loop inductances are different. The maximum and minimum loop inductances are compared in Table 6-3 for the three layouts shown in Fig. 6-11 and Fig. 6-13.

Fig. 6-13 Layouts with unbalanced loop inductances

Table 6-3 The loop impedances of the balanced and unbalanced layouts

Minimum Loop Inductance (nH)	Maximum Loop Inductance (nH)
------------------------------	------------------------------

Balanced Layout	17.34	20.21
Unbalanced Layout 1	17.8	28.86
Unbalanced Layout 2	13.07	23.56

The parasitic circuit of the balanced layout is extracted at 500 kHz using Maxwell Q3D. A circuit net-list can be exported based on the extracted data from Q3D. By importing this net-list as a sub-circuit, the original phase-leg circuit can be simulated with the parasitic elements. Fig. 6-14 shows the schematic of the paralleled devices and their parasitic circuit in Saber. The DC bus voltage is 600 V. The SiC JFETs are paralleled to form high current switches. The high side switch and low side switch are driven by ideal square waves respectively. Half a period is set as the time delay between the two gate signals. The switching frequency is 500 kHz and the duty cycle is 50%.

Fig. 6-14 Schematic of the phase-leg and parasitic circuit in Saber

The drain current waveforms of the low side and high side JFETs are shown in Fig. 6-15. At $T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the devices near to the power terminals have higher overshoot current during turn-on. In the high side paralleled devices, the rightmost JFET S3 has the largest switching energy, as shown in Fig. 6-15 (a). While in the low side paralleled JFETs, the leftmost one S4 has the largest switching energy, as shown in Fig. 6-15 (b). The devices further away from the power terminals dissipate less energy in the switching transients.

The gate currents of the high side and low side paralleled JFETs are shown in Fig. 6-16. The gate currents have similar energy distribution as the drain current during turn-on. The devices with short source-to-terminal inductances need higher gate current to switch.

The current difference during turn-on can be attributed to the different source interconnect layouts. The layouts determine the source inductance difference of paralleled devices. Because the source inductance is the common element of the power loop and the gate drive loop, its difference can affect the interaction between the gate drive circuit and the power circuit. Thus further layout design has to decrease the difference of the common source inductances in the circuit loops to minimize the power-drive interaction.

(a) The drain current waveforms of the paralleled high side JFETs

(b) The drain current waveforms of the paralleled low side JFETs

Fig. 6-15 The drain current waveforms of the paralleled devices (a) high side JFETs (rightmost JFET sustains more overshoot current) (b) low side JFETs (leftmost JFET sustains more current)

(a) The gate current waveforms of the high side paralleled JFETs

(b) The gate current waveforms of the low side paralleled JFETs

Fig. 6-16 Gate current waveforms of the paralleled JFETs (a) high side JFETs (b) low side JFETs

IV. Conclusions

According to circuit simulation analysis presented, the current through the gate diode is 9.58 A in the original multi-fold MOSFET/JFET cascode structure device. When the protection circuit is added to the topology of the cascode, the gate diode current is effectively reduced to 40 mA, which eliminates the probability of destroying the gate diode and the complete high power switch. The extra switching loss of the Si MOSFET in the cascode is only 2.56 W based on the circuit simulations. Regarding the parallel operation of devices, a phase-leg was designed for a high-current converter, where each switch of the phase-leg consisted of three paralleled devices. A physical layout was successfully designed and optimized to achieve similar inductances for all the different current loops. Based on Maxwell Q3D, the loop inductances attained were within a range of 17.34–0.21 nH.

V. References

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Chapter 7 PLANAR PACKAGING TECHNOLOGY FOR HIGH-CURRENT MULTI-CHIP POWER MODULE

I. Introduction

The increasing power ratings of converters designed for electric ships necessitate power modules with higher ampacity. Thus, a power electronic module usually contains a number of transistors in parallel to provide higher currents. The current sharing is a significant issue for the paralleled devices [1]. In a power module using bonding wires as interconnects, the imbalance among the layout impedances associated with the layout results in high current spikes and long time lags among the paralleled devices. The imbalance of currents can cause quite different junction temperatures, degrading reliability of the power modules.

In this chapter, the full circuit models of two power modules carrying insulated-gate bipolar transistors (IGBT) are obtained using electro-magnetic simulation. Simulation of the full circuit models shows that the planar IGBT module excels the wire-bonded IGBT module in the current sharing capability. The gate inductances and resistances are found to be 60% less in the planar interconnect module than in the wire-bonded module. As a result, the power module with planar interconnects yields faster response, which decreases the switching energy imbalance caused by the time lags. The variation of the threshold voltages has a significant effect on the switching energy distribution among the devices. The IGBT with lower threshold voltage tends to be turned on earlier and turned off later than the IGBT with higher threshold voltage. Therefore, a substantial amount of current will travel through the IGBT with lower threshold voltage during switching transient. The continuous operation of the power modules leads to junction temperature imbalance on the IGBTs. The thermal imbalance can further cause imbalance of energy dissipation. Simulation shows that the planar module layout can decrease the impact of layout impedances, thermal imbalance, and process variations.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The current imbalance between semiconductor devices in a power module is not only caused by the process variation during device fabrication, but also caused by the package and interconnects design. The parasitic impedances in the package can cause current imbalance even for completely identical devices. The planar packaging technology is investigated as a means to improve the current-sharing capability. The bonding wires are eliminated from the planar package and therefore the power module achieves extremely low parasitic impedances. The current sharing among paralleled devices in wire-bonded and planar power modules is compared by simulating the switching characteristics of IGBTs.

I.2. Technical Approach

The approach is considering the impact of parasitic circuit caused by packages during analysis of current sharing. The packages and interconnects of power modules are converted to circuits and analyzed along with all the semiconductor devices. The circuit models of wire-bonded and planar IGBT power modules are extracted using Ansoft Q3D. Then the two circuit models are exported from Q3D and simulated in a chopper circuit using Saber, and the switching energies of the paralleled devices are compared. The switching energies are calculated by integrating the product of voltage and current across the collector and emitter of each IGBT in the two modules. The simulation results show that the planar packaging method

reduces the imbalance of switching energies of IGBTs by decreasing the layout impedances and the time lags.

II. Module Layouts and Equivalent Parasitic Circuits

The three-dimensional models of wire-bonded and planar power modules are constructed in Ansoft Q3D (Fig. 7-1). The sizes of the wire-bonded and planar modules are 35 mm × 35 mm and 23 mm × 34 mm, respectively. Four 10 mm × 10 mm IGBT dies and two 10 mm × 10 mm diode dies are attached to the alumina direct bond copper (DBC) substrates by a 2-mil solder layer. The thicknesses of the copper layers and the alumina layer are 8 mils and 25 mils, respectively. The IGBTs are connected in parallel and the diodes are anti-parallel. The IGBTs closer to the collector pad or the emitter pad are named the “near” IGBTs, and the others are named the “far” IGBTs. Since the layouts are not symmetrical, the corresponding layout impedances of the paralleled IGBTs do not match. The planar power module can reduce the layout impedances thanks to the short interconnects which also have large cross-section areas. One method to implement the planar module is to use another DBC to connect the emitter pads of IGBTs [2]. Between the patterned top DBC and the emitter pads there are copper shims which prevent the copper tracks on the top DBC from contacting the guard rings of the chips. The two sides of the copper shim are soldered to the DBC and the emitter pad, respectively.

Fig. 7-1 Schematic (a) and layouts of the wire-bonded (b) and planar (c) power modules carrying IGBTs

The layout impedances of the power modules are extracted in low-frequency region using the partial equivalent element circuit method [3], [4] (Fig. 7-2). The planar power module shows much less layout impedances than the wire-bonded power module. The extracted gate resistance and inductance of the wire-bonded module are 3.9 m Ω and 14 nH, whereas the extracted gate resistance and inductance of the planar module are 1.58 m Ω and 4.26 nH, a 60% reduction. In the power wire-bonded module, mutual inductances are found to be much smaller than the self inductances, and are thus neglected in circuit simulation [5]. The gate-to-ground capacitance is reduced from 11.8 pF in the wire-bonded module to 2.76 pF in the planar module. In the planar power module, the mutual inductances cannot be neglected because of the close proximity of the copper traces.

Fig. 7-2 Equivalent circuits of the IGBT modules using bond wires (a) and planar interconnects (b)

Table 7-1 summarizes the self-inductances and self-resistances of the gate, emitter, and collector interconnects in the wire-bonded and planar power modules. In the wire-bonded module, the gate and emitter self-impedances are high owing to the long aluminum bonding wires. In the planar module, shorter aluminum wires are attached to the gate pads vertically to conduct driving signals and the bonding wires on emitter pads are replaced by the copper shims for the interconnection to the DBC.

Table 7-1 Comparison of impedances of wire-bonded and planar modules.

Impedance	Wire-Bonded	Planar
Gate self-inductance (nH)	14.13	4.26
Gate self-resistance (mΩ)	3.9	1.58
Emitter self-inductance (nH)	1.83	0.005
Emitter self-resistance (mΩ)	0.214	0.0003
Collector self-inductance (nH)	0.254	0.221
Collector self-resistance (μΩ)	9.9	8.38
Gate-emitter capacitance (pF)	11.8	2.76

III. Double-Pulse Simulation

The equivalent layout circuit and IGBT model are simulated in a chopper circuit with inductive load (Fig. 7-3). The IGBT model IRGC25B120UB (1200 V, 25 A) and diode model CSD10120 (1200 V, 10 A) are used in this double-pulse simulation. In the simulation, two current pulses are applied to the power modules. One pulse lasting 25 μs comes first to set up

the current in the inductor. A second pulse lasting $5 \mu\text{s}$ then arrives to generate the turn-on and turn-off voltage and current waveforms. The switching energies are calculated by integrating the product of I_c and V_{ce} over the switching transient. The DC bus voltage is 400 V. The inductor is 0.5 mH. A 5Ω resistor is selected as the gate resistance. The amplitude of gate driving signal is 10 V. The total current of one near IGBT and one far IGBT is designed as 10 A.

Fig. 7-3 Schematic of the chopper circuit in Saber simulation.

III.1. Current Sharing at Low and High Junction Temperatures

The IGBTs are operated at 25°C and 125°C to compare the current sharing capability of the wire-bonded and planar power modules.

The near IGBTs have less layout impedances than the far IGBTs thanks to the shorter interconnects in the layout. During turn-on, more current travels through the near IGBT because it is switched before the far IGBT. Therefore, the turn-on energy of the near IGBT is higher than that of the far IGBT. During turn-off, the near IGBT is also switched faster than the far IGBT. The current travels through the far IGBT after the turn-off of the near IGBT. As a result, the turn-off energy of the far IGBT is higher than that of the near IGBT.

At 25°C , the far IGBT lags the near IGBT by 21 ns in wire-bonded module, and by 14 ns in the planar module (Fig. 7-4). The shorter time lag in the planar module stems from the lower impedances in the gate-to-emitter loop. During the switching transient, more than 60% of the current travels through the near IGBT while the collector-to-emitter voltage remains high. Therefore, a longer time lag will result in more switching power dissipation. The turn-on energy mismatches between the near and far devices are 0.078 mJ in wire-bonded module and 0.031 mJ in planar module. Both of the energy imbalances are less than 20% of the total turn-on energy. During turn-off, the switching time lag is almost zero and the mismatch of switching energies is less than 0.01 mJ.

Fig. 7-4 Switching time lag during turn-on at 25°C for wire-bonded (a) and planar (b) power modules.

At 125°C, the effects of the mismatch of layout impedances are not as prominent as the case at 25 °C thanks to the positive on-state voltage temperature coefficient of the IGBT IRGC25B120UB. The time lag and switching energy imbalance in the wire-bonded module are reduced to 17 ns and 0.063 mJ (Fig. 7-5). These two values decrease to 13 ns and 0.031 mJ in the planar module.

Fig. 7-5 Switching time lags during turn-on at 125°C in the wire-bonded (a) and planar (b) power modules.

Table 7-2 summarizes the switching energy imbalance in wire-bonded and planar modules at 25°C and 125°C, respectively.

Table 7-2 Comparison of switching energy of wire-bonded and planar modules.

Junction	Switching Energy (mJ)	
Temperature	Wire-Bonded	Planar
$T_j = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{off_near}} = 0.216$ $E_{\text{off_far}} = 0.222$ $E_{\text{on_near}} = 0.266$ $E_{\text{on_far}} = 0.188$	$E_{\text{off_near}} = 0.203$ $E_{\text{off_far}} = 0.205$ $E_{\text{on_near}} = 0.219$ $E_{\text{on_far}} = 0.188$
$T_j = 125\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$E_{\text{off_near}} = 0.288$ $E_{\text{off_far}} = 0.292$ $E_{\text{on_near}} = 0.226$ $E_{\text{on_far}} = 0.171$	$E_{\text{off_near}} = 0.260$ $E_{\text{off_far}} = 0.261$ $E_{\text{on_near}} = 0.197$ $E_{\text{on_far}} = 0.166$

III.2. Impact of Junction Temperature Imbalance between Devices

The reliability of a power module is eventually determined by the junction temperatures of the devices. The junction temperature of the near IGBT will rise in continuous operation due to the higher switching energy. The worst-case results can be simulated by setting a temperature of 125°C on the near IGBT and 25°C on the far IGBT. Due to the positive temperature coefficient of the IGBT, the on-state current in the far IGBT is higher than that in the near device (Fig. 7-6).

Fig. 7-6 Current sharing performance with $T = 125\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on the near IGBT and $T = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on the far IGBT in the wire-bonded (a) and planar (b) power modules.

The switching energy imbalances are 0.14 mJ and 0.2 mJ during the turn-off and turn-on of the wire-bonded module. In the planar module, the turn-off and turn-on energy imbalances are 0.13 mJ and 0.15 mJ, respectively. About 60% of the total switching energy is dissipated by the near IGBT.

The planar module has smaller impedances on the gate and emitter than the wire-bonded module, which results in shorter time lag in switching transient. Therefore, in the planar module, the current difference during the switching transient is reduced. The threshold voltage of IGBT has a negative temperature coefficient. As a result, the IGBT with the higher temperature turns on at a lower threshold voltage. The difference of threshold voltages determines that the near IGBT turns on earlier and turns off later than the far IGBT. More current tends to travel through the near IGBT during the switching transient, leading to higher turn-on and turn-off energies.

The plateau at the end of the switching transient is caused by the Miller effect. The paralleled gate-to-collector capacitors function as a current divider. The total current is split according to the ratio of the capacitances.

Table 7-3 summarizes the impact of junction temperature imbalance on the switching energy imbalance in wire-bonded and planar modules.

Table 7-3 Imbalance in switching energy versus imbalance in junction temperatures

Junction Temperature	Switching Energy (mJ)	
	Wire-Bonded	Planar
$T_{j_near} = 125\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$E_{off_near} = 0.34$ $E_{off_far} = 0.198$	$E_{off_near} = 0.315$ $E_{off_far} = 0.19$
$T_{j_far} = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$E_{on_near} = 0.306$ $E_{on_far} = 0.11$	$E_{on_near} = 0.292$ $E_{on_far} = 0.138$

III.3. Impact of Threshold Voltage Imbalances among Devices

According to the datasheet of IRGC25B120UB, the variation of the threshold voltage of the IGBT is from 4.4 V to 6 V. By setting the threshold voltages of the near and far IGBTs to the lower and upper limits, the worst-case results are obtained for the threshold mismatch (Fig. 7-7). The simulation is carried out based on the assumption that the junction temperatures are 25°C for all the IGBTs. The largest switching energy mismatch is 0.28 mJ during the turn-on of wire-bonded module. This value is reduced to 0.25 mJ in the planar module. More than 90% of the turn-on energy is dissipated in the near IGBT which has the lower limit of threshold voltage. In this operating condition, the difference in the threshold voltages dominates the switching behavior of the IGBTs.

Fig. 7-7 Current sharing performance of the power module with $V_{th} = 6\text{ V}$ on the near IGBT and $V_{th} = 4.4\text{ V}$ on the far IGBT in the wire-bonded (a) and planar (b) power modules.

At turn-on, the IGBT with lower V_{th} is switched earlier than the IGBT with higher V_{th} . The current goes entirely through the IGBT with lower V_{th} . At turn-off, the IGBT with higher V_{th} is switched earlier than the IGBT with lower V_{th} . Therefore the current goes entirely through the IGBT with lower V_{th} . The IGBT with lower threshold voltage dissipates most of the switching energy. When the near and far IGBTs are completely turned on, the currents travelling through the two IGBTs are quite close.

Table 7-4 summarizes the impact of threshold voltage imbalance on the switching energy imbalance in wire-bonded and planar modules.

Table 7-4 Imbalance in switching energy versus imbalance in threshold voltages

Junction	Switching Energy (mJ)	
	Wire-Bonded	Planar
$V_{th_near} = 4.4\text{ V}$ $V_{th_far} = 6\text{ V}$	$E_{off_near} = 0.28$ $E_{off_far} = 0.149$ $E_{on_near} = 0.29$ $E_{on_far} = 0.014$	$E_{off_near} = 0.295$ $E_{off_far} = 0.148$ $E_{on_near} = 0.263$ $E_{on_far} = 0.014$
$V_{th_near} = 6\text{ V}$ $V_{th_far} = 4.4\text{ V}$	$E_{off_near} = 0.152$ $E_{off_far} = 0.317$ $E_{on_near} = 0.074$ $E_{on_far} = 0.238$	$E_{off_near} = 0.148$ $E_{off_far} = 0.275$ $E_{on_near} = 0.077$ $E_{on_far} = 0.288$

IV. Conclusions

The circuit model of a planar power module and a wire-bonded power module are extracted using the partial equivalent element circuit method. The gate inductances and resistances are

found to be 60% less in the planar interconnect module than in the wire-bonded module. Thus, the module with planar interconnects yields faster response based on the current sharing simulation of the IGBTs.

The wire-bonded and planar power modules are simulated at both 25°C and 125°C. The turn-on energy imbalance in the planar module is 50% of that in the wire-bonded module. During turn-off, the switching energy imbalances of both modules are quite close. Simulating IGBT imbalances also shows that threshold voltage mismatch has a significant impact on the current sharing in the IGBT modules. The largest switching energy imbalance of IGBTs is decreased in the planar module. When there is junction temperature imbalance inside the module, the planar module tends to balance the switching energies of near and far devices. The hardware of modules and circuits is being constructed for the experimental verification.

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Part III

Study of Planar Packaging Technologies and Packaging Materials

Chapter 8 PLANAR PACKAGING PROCESS FOR HIGH-VOLTAGE DIE

I. Introduction

A planar packaging technology called Embedded Power (EP) technology has been developed in CPES [1][2][3]. This technology is used for fabricating planar interconnections for power semiconductor devices and integrating power electronic components in a low profile structure. By adding interlayering to the fabrication process, the embedded power package is designed for voltage ratings higher than 10 kV.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The objective of this chapter is to develop a fabrication process for the package of high voltage power semiconductor modules. The novel SiC power devices designed for high voltage applications require higher power ratings for the package. Though the Embedded Power technology has the advantages of a low parasitic inductance and high power density [1][2][3], it has not been explored using semiconductor devices with voltage ratings as high as 10 kV. The high voltage embedded power (HVEP) technique aims at the SiC power semiconductor devices whose power rating is higher than 10 kV. Higher switching frequency is always a trend of advanced power converter design. Therefore the packaging technology must have good performance from DC to high frequency (> 500 kHz). A methodology for modeling and simulating the broadband planar packaging design has to be explored.

I.2. Technical Approach

TCAD software MEDICI is used to simulate the electric field in the packaging materials and design the planar package of a 10 kV SiC diode. The thin film deposition technology (radio-frequency sputtering) and thick film deposition technology (screen printing) are the major approaches to fabricating the multi-layer structure of the embedded power module. The interconnections for semiconductor devices are formed by sputtering and electroplating, and the insulating interlayer is formed by screen printing and low temperature curing. The layout of a multi-chip power module is simulated in Maxwell Q3D and the parasitic elements of each branch of the conductors can be extracted. For each separated conducting branch, an R-L ladder equivalent circuit is implemented to mimic the skin effect.

II. High Voltage Planar Packaging

In the electronic package design, it is important to know the electric field distribution inside the packaging materials, which is affected by the internal structure of the device. MEDICI, an industry-standard TCAD simulator, can be used to simulate the behavior of semiconductor devices. It computes the two dimensional (2-D) distributions of electric potential in a device and can be used to predict electrical characteristics for arbitrary bias conditions. Thus, extensive 2D simulations using MEDICI are performed to study the high voltage planar package of a 10 kV SiC diode [4] based on the Embedded Power technology.

II.1. Issues for High Voltage Planar Packaging

The structure of the embedded power module is illustrated in Fig. 8-1. This technology is used for bonding and interconnecting power semiconductor devices and integrating power electronics modules. In the cross-sectional view of the module, the bare die of a semiconductor device is embedded in a ceramic carrier. The insulating material (polyimide) is deposited on the top of the die by screen printing, a kind of thick film technology, and the metallization is formed by RF sputtering, a kind of thin film technology. The gaps between the die and the ceramic carrier are filled with insulating material (epoxy). The structure has been demonstrated to have better thermal performance and lower parasitic characteristics than conventional wire-bonded structures [1][2][3]. Currently the embedded power technology has been applied to a 10 kW 1200 V converter system [5].

Fig. 8-1 Structure of device package using Embedded Power technology

Fig. 8-2 shows the simulation results in MEDICI of an existing device package using Embedded Power technology applied to the 10 kV SiC diode. Fig. 8-2 (a) is the cross section showing the low profile structure and dimensions of a half of the package. In the simulation, the SiC diode is reversely biased. The cathode is connected to 14 kV voltage source, and the anode is grounded. Fig. 8-2 (b) shows the simulated equipotential lines in the diode as well as in the package. Since the voltage is applied to the metallization on the top of the polyimide and the cathode of the diode, and the thickness of the polyimide is much less than the thickness of the ceramic, most of the equipotential lines bend down at the upper corner of the device, and some of them also bend at the lower corner of the device. Thus two of the electric field “hotspots” are located at the upper and lower edges of device inside the epoxy and the polyimide respectively, as shown in two circles in Fig. 8-2 (b). Fig. 8-2 (c) is the maximum electric field inside polyimide, which is measured along the x direction from the left of the polyimide layer to the right, as the dash-dot line shown in Fig. 8-2 (a). Fig. 8-2 (d) is the maximum electric field intensity inside the epoxy, which is measured along the y direction from the top of the epoxy layer to the bottom, as the dash line shown in Fig. 8-2 (a). The highest electric field intensity points in both polyimide and epoxy are located at the upper corner of the device; in the epoxy, the second highest electric field intensity is at the lower corner of the device.

Fig. 8-2 Simulation structure and results of device package using Embedded Power technology. (a) Dimensions and materials of the package. (b) Distribution of equipotential lines. (c) Maximum electric field in the polyimide. (d) Maximum electric field in the epoxy

The dielectric strength of each material in the Embedded Power planar structure is shown in Table 8-1. At the bias of 14 kV, the maximum electric field inside the epoxy and the polyimide has already exceeded the dielectric strength of the two materials, which means this package structure cannot survive at such high voltage.

Table 8-1 Dielectric strength of material in the Embedded Power package [6][7]

Material	Dielectric strength (kV/mm)
SiC (intrinsic)	250
Polyimide	50
Epoxy	25
Ceramic	15

II.2. Design for High Voltage Embedded Power

Principles and simulation

Fig. 8-3 (a) illustrates the novel high voltage package structure. In this structure, the metallization is formed at the cathode and backside of the substrate. A conducting interlayer

connected to the cathode is inserted into the polyimide to reshape the electric field distribution. Fig. 8-3 (b) – (d) is the simulation results. Because the epoxy is surrounded by metal layer, the electric field at the lower corner is nearly eliminated. There is no bending of equipotential lines at the upper corner of the device, thus the hotspot there is eliminated. The electric field in the polyimide, as shown in Fig. 8-3 (c), crowds at the locations of JTEs on the surface of the device. This high electric field intensity cannot be reduced because it is dependent on the internal structure of the device, which is determined by the device manufacturers. Although this phenomenon exists, it is not the main issue when the electric field intensity at the upper corner of the device is much higher than the electric field intensity at these locations. The maximum electric field at the upper corner of the device in epoxy is reduced to almost 1/6 of the value in the structure shown in Fig. 8-2 [8].

Fig. 8-3 Simulation structure and results in Medici. (a) Dimensions and materials of the package. (b) Distribution of equipotential lines. (c) Maximum electric field in the polyimide. (d) Maximum electric field in the epoxy

III. Fabrication Process

III.1. Low Voltage Embedded Power Module

Fig. 8-4 illustrates the process flow of the embedded power chips stage.

Step 1 The preparation of the ceramic frame (chips carrier). A ceramic frame with multiple openings is formed using a power laser machine. These openings are ready for the embedding

of the power chip dice. In order for accurate alignment of the following processes, tiny tips are formed around the edges of each opening to fix the chips tightly and the same fiducial is used in the following steps.

Step 2 The embedding of the dice. The gaps are filled completely with a dielectric paste. Then the package is cured. A flat substrate with coplanar dice is formed, which is the base of the following planar processing.

Step 3 The coating of the dielectric material. The screen printing technique is used to selectively coat a dielectric interlayer on the surface of the substrate, which defines the via holes on the pads of the dice. The screened dielectric paste also needs a curing to form a flat and solid adhesive layer.

Step 4 The metallization on the surface. Multiple metal layers are deposited on the whole surface. Electric contacts are formed with the Al pads through the via holes in the dielectric interlayer. RF sputtering is used to deposit thin-film Ti and Cu layers. Then electroplating is used to form thicker Cu deposition.

Step 5 The metal layer is patterned to form both the power and the control circuits as well as their I/O terminals.

Fabrication Process for LVEP Package

Fig. 8-4 Process steps of the low voltage embedded power technology

III.2. High Voltage Embedded Power Module

Fig. 8-5 illustrates the embedded power processing flow at the chip stage. These are described in detail in what follows.

1) Laser cutting

The process starts from patterning the ceramic carrier for the device. The carrier for the power semiconductor device die is a piece of alumina ceramic. The opening slots formed in the ceramic carrier by the laser can be divided into two groups. One group is the slots for embedding semiconductor devices, and the other group of slots are the vias, through which the conducting layers on both sides of the ceramic carrier can be connected. Some of the parameters of the laser process are dependent from each other. Their relationships are:

Pulse number: This is the number of pulses used for piercing and for drilling at one position.

Pulse width: The pulse width is the time the pulse remains ON during a pulse cycle.

Pulse spacing: $\text{Pulse Period } [\mu\text{s}] = \text{Pulse Spacing } [\text{in}] / \text{Stage Velocity } [\text{in/s}] * 10^6$

Duty cycle: $\text{Duty Cycle } [\%] = \text{Pulse Width } [\mu\text{s}] / \text{Pulse Period } [\mu\text{s}] * 100\%$

Laser power: $\text{Laser Average Power } [W] = (150 W/60\%) * \text{Duty Cycle } [\%]$

Pulse repetition rate: $\text{Rep. Rate } [\text{kHz}] = 1000 / (\text{Pulse Period } [\mu\text{s}])$

Dwell time: $\text{Dwell Time } [\mu\text{s}] = 1000 * \text{Pulse Number} / \text{Rep. Rate } [\text{kHz}]$

Table 8-2 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-2 Operations of laser cutting

Laser Cutting	
Equipement	Resonetics CO ₂ laser router system
Substrate to be cut	2 in x 2 in x 20 mil 96% alumina ceramic
Stage lasing velocity	0.1 in / s
Stage slewing velocity	1 in / s
Pulse spacing	0.0006 in
Laser power	50 W
Pulse number	270

2) Chip embedding

After using the laser machine to define a certain pattern on the ceramic carrier, a piece of Kapton sticky tape is pasted on the top of the ceramic carrier, then the ceramic carrier is flipped, and the sticky side of the Kapton tape acts as the bottom for the slot in the ceramic. The SiC power diode is put into the slots in the ceramic carrier. The top of the diode is stuck to the sticky side of the Kapton tape. Pressure is applied to the die and tape to make sure a close contact. The purpose of keeping close contact is to avoid the leakage of fluids in the later steps. Then epoxy EP3HT is dispensed into the gap between the device and the ceramic. The dispensing process should be slow in order to avoid forming bubbles inside the epoxy ring. The epoxy has

a high dielectric strength than air. Therefore, if there are bubbles in the epoxy and a high voltage is applied on it, the air bubbles will possibly be broken down.

Curing after dispensing is necessary to solidify the epoxy EP3HT which acts as a frame holding the semiconductor device. The curing profile consists of three temperature stages: 1 min at 50 °C, 1 min at 100 °C, and 10 min at 160 °C. The temperature increasing rate is 1 °C/min between two temperature stages. After curing, the module is left inside the oven for natural cooling. When the temperature inside the oven returns to room temperature, the package could be taken out for the next step.

The Kapton tape has to be peeled off from the cured epoxy and semiconductor devices. Table 8-3 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-3 Operations of chip embedding

Chip embedding	
Substrate	2 in x 2 in x 20 mil 96% alumina ceramic
Gap between die and substrate	0.5 mm
Embedding material	Epoxy (Masterbond EP3HT)
Curing profile	160 °C / 10 min
Duration of process	2.5 hr
Cooling method after curing	Natural cooling down

Fig. 8-5 Process steps of the high voltage embedded power technology

3) Metal shim soldering

A thin (5 μm) copper shim is directly soldered onto the pads of the semiconductor device using 210 °C solder paste. The copper shim has the advantages of shaping the subsequent printed polyimide insulating layer and increasing the bonding strength between pads and the subsequent sputtered copper interconnections. Before the subsequent sputtering, a Kapton tape ring has to be covered on the exposed surface around the copper shim of the semiconductor device. The reason of covering the Kapton tape ring is that the pad of the diode must be separated from the sputtered conducting interlayer to avoid short-circuiting the cathode and anode. In the same time, the epoxy ring has to be exposed in order for that the conducting interlayer can embrace the epoxy from both top and back sides to eliminate the electric field in the epoxy. Table 8-4 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-4 Operations of metal shim soldering

Shim soldering	
Equipment	Hot plate
Material	PbSn solder paste
Soldering temperature	210 °C

Table 8-5 Operations of RF sputtering

RF sputtering	
Equipment	RF sputtering machine
Temperature	Room temperature
Sputtered metal	Ti / Cu
Initial vacuum pressure	2×10^{-6} pa
Duration of Ar purge	30 min
Vacuum pressure after Ar purge	2×10^{-6} pa
Duration of Ti sputtering	15 min
Duration of 1 st Cu sputtering	15 min
Duration of 2 nd Cu sputtering	15 min

4) Top and bottom sputtering

The conducting interlayer is deposited by sputtering technology. A radio-frequency sputtering machine is used to deposit thin copper film on both surfaces of the substrate. The sputtering targets for this process are two kinds of metal. Copper is used as the major conducting material and Titanium is used as buffer layer to increase the bonding strength between copper film and ceramic substrate. Since only one side of the substrate can be sputtered at one time, the module needs to be flipped to complete the double-sided deposition and the duration is doubled. Once the sputtering finishes, the ceramic carrier and epoxy ring should be covered with copper film completely. The top and bottom copper layer are connected

by the conducting film deposited on the wall of via. Table 8-5 summarizes the operations of this step.

5) Insulating interlayer deposition

Interconnections are formed by depositing conducting layer too. Between the interconnecting and conducting interlayer, there must be a layer of insulating material. Polyimide Epo-Tek 600 is used for the insulation. The polyimide is deposited by screen printing. A mesh is used as the mask screen in this technology. The pads of semiconductor devices are covered by the masks on the mesh and other parts of the module are exposed to the permeable mesh. When the polyimide is printed on the mesh, the module will be deposited with insulating material on top surface of the module except the pads of the semiconductor devices. In the screen printing, the via must be filled intentionally to form a good insulation, otherwise in the subsequent sputtering step, the top and the bottom of the semiconductor device might be connected by the conductor inside the via. Because of the existence of the copper shim on the pad of device, the polyimide layer has an orthogonal corner at the copper-polyimide interface; otherwise the electric field in the polyimide could be increased by an acute corner, which possibly results in breakdown. As shown in Fig. 8-6, the curing profile for polyimide Epo-Tek 600 is 1min at 100 °C, 60 min at 150 °C, 30 min at 200 °C, and the temperature increasing rate is 1 °C/min. After 4.5 h curing, the module is naturally cooled down inside the heating oven.

Table 8-6 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-6 Operations of insulating interlayer deposition

Insulating interlayer deposition	
Equipment	Screen printing machine
Temperature	Room temperature
Module back side protection	Kapton tape
Deposited material	Polyimide (Epo-Tek 600)
Curing profile	150 °C / 60 min, 200 °C / 30 min
Temperature increasing rate	1 °C / min
Duration of curing	4.5 hr
Cooling method after curing	Natural cooling down

Fig. 8-6 Curing profile of the polyimide

6) Solder mask coating

The interconnections can be fabricated by the sputtering after the curing of polyimide. A smooth surface of the module is required to increase the bonding strength of the sputtered conducting thin film. Because the screen printing technology is used to deposit thick polyimide layer, the surface of the module could not be as smooth as alumina ceramic. Therefore a solder mask layer is used for smoothing the surface of the polyimide layer.

The solder mask is the mixture of DSR-3241BQ and DSR-3241A-GQ from Enthone. The mass ratio of the two composites is 1:4. Before coating the mixture, the back side of the module is covered by Kapton tape to protect the contamination of solder mask. After coating the solder mask on the surface of the module, a spin coating machine is used to spread the solder mask uniformly on the module. The spin profile includes both 750 rpm low speed and 2800 rpm high speed stages. The low speed stage lasts 15 sec and the high speed stage lasts 40 sec. The spin coated module needs 25 min soft baking at 80 °C.

A transparency is covered on the solder mask to pattern it. The package is exposed in ultraviolet light for 10 min. Then the package is developed using D4000 solution. In this step, only the solder masks on the pads of devices are washed away. The exposed pads are ready for the later sputtering to form interconnections.

Table 8-7 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-7 Operations of solder mask coating

Solder Mask Coating	
Equipment	Spin coating machine / oven
Solder mask materials	DSR-3241BQ / DSR-3241A-GQ (ENTHONE)
Module back side protection	Kapton tape
Spin profile	750 rpm / 15 s + 2800 rpm / 40 s
Soft bake profile	80 °C / 25 min
Duration of photolithography	8 min
Developing solution	D4000:DI water = 1 ml:20 ml
Cleaning method	Deionized water

Drying method	Nitrogen air flow
Curing profile	160 °C / 30 min
Duration of curing	2.5 hr
Cooling method after curing	Natural cooling down

7) Cleaning for thin film deposition

Contamination on the pads of dice greatly decreases the bonding strength of sputtering. Therefore, before the second sputtering, the surface of the solder mask must be cleaned. Besides conventional ultrasonic cleaning, plasma cleaning is used to remove the polymer on the pads of the dice. Table 8-8 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-8 Operations of cleaning

Ultrasonic cleaning		Plasma cleaning	
Equipment	Ultrasonic machine	Equipment	Plasma cleaner
Cleaning Materials	Acetone / Propocal / DI water	Cleaning Materials	Oxygen / Argon
Temperature	Room temperature	Temperature	Room temperature
Duration of cleaning	10 min for each solution	Duration of cleaning	3 min Oxygen plasma + cooling (twice) /
Drying method	Nitrogen air flow		3 min Argon plasma + cooling

8) Interconnecting metallization deposition

This step involves RF sputtering of Ti and Cu. It is nearly the same as step 4) except that step 8) needs only sputtering on the top surface of the package. Thus the duration is short.

9) Masking and Photolithography

The metallization on the surface of the package has to be patterned to form gate drive and power stage circuitry. The photoresist is first coated on the whole surface and then taped to a transparency mask. The back side of the package is protected by Kapton tape. The spin profile includes both 750 rpm low speed and 2800 rpm high speed stages. The low speed stage lasts 15 sec and the high speed stage lasts 40 sec. The spin coated module needs 45 min soft baking at 85 °C. Then the photoresist is exposed to the ultraviolet ray for 20 min and then developed using D4000 solution. The masked parts on the photoresist are washed away so that the metallization appears. Table 8-9 summarizes the operations of this step.

10) Electroplating

After step 9), the circuitry layout is patterned on the surface of the package, but the bonding strength of the sputtered metal is not big enough. To conduct high current performance, electroplating is carried out. The electroplating solution is copper sulfate. Small plating current is

selected so that the surface of plated copper is smooth and compact. The duration of electroplating is relatively so the current has to be monitored during the process.

Table 8-10 summarizes the operations of this step.

11) Wet Etching

After electroplating the package is cleaned with Aceton, Propocal and DI water as step 7). The remainder of photoresist can be removed in this cleaning step and the copper unplated is exposed. Microetching is needed to remove the sputtered thin metal layer to eventually form the desirable circuitry layout. The package is immersed in the Cu and Ti micro-etchant one after another until a good circuitry layout could be seen on the surface.

Table 8-11 summarizes the operations of this step.

Table 8-9 Operations of photolithography

Photoresist coating	
Equipment	Spin coating machine
Photoresist material	
Module back side protection	Kapton tape
Spin profile	750 rpm / 15 s + 2800 rpm / 40 s
Soft bake profile	85 °C / 45 min
Photolithography	
Equipment	Ultraviolet exposure machine
Temperature	Room temperature
Mask	Patterned transparency
Duration of photolithography	20 min
Developing	
Developing solution	D4000:DI water = 1 ml:20 ml
Cleaning method	Deionized water
Drying method	Nitrogen air flow

Table 8-10 Operations of electroplating

Cu electroplating	
Equipment	Electroplating machine
Temperature	Room temperature
Electroplating solution	CuSO ₄
Electroplating current	0.15 A
Duration of process	3 hr

Cleaning	Deionized water
Drying method	Nitrogen air flow

Table 8-11 Operations of wet etching

Cu microetching		Ti microetching	
Cu micro-etchant	6 g:100 ml	Ti micro-etchant	5% HF
Duration of process	30 min	Duration of process	30 min
Cleaning	Deionized water	Cleaning	Deionized water
Drying method	Nitrogen air flow	Drying method	Nitrogen air flow

III.3. Experiment for HVEP

In the prototype module, a Cree 2 kV SiC diode with gold solderable anode is packaged using the embedded power technology. Fig. 8-7 shows the result of each step in the fabrication process. The breakdown voltage of the package is tested by Tektronix 371 high power curve tracer. The reverse voltage is about 2 kV when the reverse current is 5 μ A.

Fig. 8-7 Fabrication results of a 2 kV SiC diode module

III.4. Comparison

The differences between low and high voltage embedded power fabrication process are the following.

1) Back side metallization. The high voltage package has back side metallization which surrounds the epoxy bulk to eliminate the high electric field at the lower corner of the diode.

2) Interlayer metallization. The interlayer metallization not only surrounds the epoxy bulk, but also forms a pair of paralleled plates with the top interconnections. The paralleled conductor structure changes the distribution of equipotential lines and greatly alleviates the electric stress at the upper corner of the diode, which is the major hotspot in this package structure.

3) Pad bonding enhancement. Because of the existence of the metal shim soldered to the pad, the bonding strength of the sputtering is larger than the bonding of Al pad and sputtered copper. This process can increase the reliability of the package at high power. On the other hand, the edges of the shim help to form orthogonal corners of the polyimide layer, which avoids the crowd of electric field.

All the steps for LVEP technology are included in the fabrication process for HVEP module. The low voltage embedded power process can be regarded as a subset of the high voltage embedded power technology.

IV. Broadband Planar Packaging

As the converter design advances, the power module is required to be operated at high frequency without degeneration. Thus the package design must consider the frequency issues and parasitic elements not only in the DC case but also in a broad range. Both PEEC method and circuit equivalent circuit could be used for the optimization of broadband module layout. This section describes the research methodology for studying the broadband planar packaging technology.

IV.1. Skin Effect at 500 kHz

At high frequency, the skin effect influences the dynamic characteristics of the power module. Different conductors have different skin depths due to different materials and dimensions. Because of the skin depth, the actual conducting area of the conductor is reduced, hence the resistance increases and the inductance decreases.

Generally, the parasitic impedances of the conductors can be extracted by Maxwell Q3D using the PEEC approach. In Maxwell Q3D, the parasitic elements are modeled only at high frequency and low frequency. In the transition region, there are no valid models to calculate parasitic inductance or resistance. In this case the model for the transition region is necessary for the power module working in this frequency range.

Each conductor has its low frequency and high frequency threshold. For a conductor of thickness d , permeability μ and conductivity σ , the skin depth used by Maxwell Q3D is

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi f \mu \sigma}} \quad (7-1)$$

If the skin depth is equal or greater than the cross section of the conductor, the current is distributed throughout the cross section of the conductor, and the resistance and inductance are almost constant with frequency. The upper frequency bound for DC region can be obtained

$$f_{DC} \leq \frac{1}{\pi d^2 \sigma \mu} \quad (7-2)$$

When the switching frequency is less than f_{DC} , the conductor is operated in low frequency range, and the impedance is calculated using DC model in Maxwell Q3D.

On the other hand, if the skin depth is less than one third of the conductor thickness ($\delta \leq d/3$), the current concentrates on the surface of the conductor, which increases the resistance and decreases the inductance. So the lower frequency bound for AC region is

$$f_{AC} \leq \frac{9}{\pi d^2 \sigma \mu} \quad (7-3)$$

When the switching frequency is higher than f_{AC} , the conductor is considered to be operated in high frequency range, and the impedance is calculated using AC model in Maxwell Q3D.

For the Direct Bond Copper (DBC) substrate used in CPES, the thickness of the copper layer on the DBC is 8 mil (about 200 μm). The permeability is 1.256629 N/A², and the conductivity is 59.6 MS/m. Therefore the high frequency threshold f_{AC} for this copper layer is 956.3 kHz, and the low frequency threshold f_{DC} for this copper layer is 106.3 kHz. If the converter is operated at 500 kHz, which is located in the transition region of the impedance-frequency graph shown in Fig. 8-8, the resistance and inductance models for the DBC interconnections are not valid in Maxwell Q3D.

Fig. 8-8 Impedance models in Q3D for different frequency

IV.2. Decomposed DC Parasitic Circuit for the Power Module

The broadband parasitic circuit model is developed from its DC circuit. The layout of a multi-chip power module is constructed in Maxwell Q3D and the parasitic elements of each branch of the conductors can be extracted by the software. The equivalent circuit should be valid for a certain frequency range which the converter is designed for. By utilizing the frequency dependent equivalent circuit, the current sharing between paralleled devices could be simulated accurately. According to the dynamic characteristic simulation, layout design of high current and high frequency module could be optimized. In Maxwell Q3D, the voltage of a piece of conductor is

$$V_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(L_{ij} \frac{dI_j}{dt} + R_{ij} I_j \right) = L_{ii} \frac{d}{dt} \left[\sum_{j=1}^n I_j \frac{L_{ij}}{L_{ii}} \right] + R_{ii} \sum_{j=1}^n I_j \frac{R_{ij}}{R_{ii}} \quad (7-4)$$

where L_{ii} is the self inductance and L_{ij} is the mutual inductance. For a well designed module, these parasitic elements are one or two orders of magnitude of self inductance so that they can be neglected. R_{ii} is the self resistance and R_{ij} is the mutual resistance. In DC analysis, the mutual resistance is zero.

A generic parasitic circuit schematic is shown in Fig. 8-9. Based on the materials, dimensions, and positions, the conductors inside the power module usually have different skin depth. Therefore different conductors have different equivalent parasitic elements and whole parasitic circuit have to be decomposed to include the detailed information of each section of the interconnections. A decomposed equivalent circuit is shown in Fig. 8-10. Two MOSFETs and two diodes are connected in parallel. One R-L branch represents a section of conductor. The net to ground capacitors in Fig. 8-10 represent the capacitance between conductors and the ground. For the thin conducting layers, the net-to-net capacitances coupling between conductors are negligible compared with the capacitance to ground.

Fig. 8-9 Simplified equivalent circuit for a power module

Fig. 8-10 Decomposed DC parasitic circuit for two paralleled MOSFETs and two paralleled diodes

IV.3. R-L Ladder Equivalent Circuit

The methodology is shown in Fig. 8-11. Considering the skin effect, the cross section of the interconnections can be divided into M concentric rectangular shells. The overall conductor can be thought of as the paralleling of all the conducting shells. At low frequency, the shells occupy the entire cross-section of the conductor. At high frequency, only a few outer shells can conduct current. The resistance increases and the inductance decreases because of the smaller cross section of the interconnections. Therefore the skin effect impedance depends on the frequency. To mimic the skin effect in a lumped circuit simulator like Saber, each shell is modeled as a resistor and an inductor in series. Thus the conductor can be represented by an M branch R-L ladder. The DC impedance of the R-L ladder must be equal to the DC impedance of the conductor under investigation [9][10][10]. The DC impedance of the conductor is extracted from Maxwell Q3D. Each branch of the series R-L representing the conductors should be replaced with the R-L ladder broadband model. Using this approach the interconnect impedances in the transition region can be modeled effectively.

Conductor is made of concentric shells:

R-L ladder for circuit simulation:

Elements in ladder:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} R_2 = R_1 x \\ R_3 = R_1 x^2 \\ \vdots \\ R_n = R_1 x^n \end{array} \right\}, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} L_2 = L_1 / x \\ L_3 = L_1 / x^2 \\ \vdots \\ L_n = L_1 / x^n \end{array} \right.$$

Constraint conditions:

$$R_{DC} = R_1 // R_2 // \dots // R_n$$

$$L_{DC} = L_1 // L_2 // \dots // L_n$$

Parameters: R_1, L_1, x

Fig. 8-11 Methodology for developing equivalent circuit of planar interconnections

The equivalent circuit developed for the skin effect is actually not a full bandwidth model. However, if the operation frequency of the converter is known in a certain range, the order of the R-L ladder can be calculated to fulfill the accuracy requirement for the model.

V. Conclusion

In this chapter, the package for a 10 kV SiC diode is discussed. The major features of the embedded power technology are its high power density, the mask-based process and the film deposition technology. The insulating dielectric is deposited using patterned screen-printing, the conducting layer is deposited using RF sputtering, the base substrate and interconnections are patterned by photolithography, and the chip-carrier ceramic frame is fabricated by computer-controlled laser cutting. Planar package structure is used to increase the power density and reduce the parasitic effects.

The issues in the original structure of the Embedded Power technology are addressed. Two metal layers are sputtered on the substrate. From simulation results using MEDICI, the electric stress in the package is greatly reduced due to the novel structure. Finally the fabrication process for the high voltage embedded power technology is described.

The methodology for studying broadband power module in a circuit simulator is also explored. Using the R-L ladder equivalent circuit, the interconnections of the package can be modeled from DC to high frequency. This methodology would be used to design and optimize the layout of the power module used in the 500 kHz converter.

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Chapter 9 PLANAR PACKAGING PROCESS FOR HIGH-VOLTAGE MULTI-CHIP POWER MODULE

I. Introduction

Power electronics are now driven by challenging requirements as volume, power density, costs, reliability, and operation temperatures [1]. The packaging of power electronics is critical factor to performance and reliability of power electronics systems. For traditional power multi-chip module, the devices are the mounted on the substrates via large solder area. The wire bonds are used to connect the upper device contacts because of the maturity of the process. However, the wire bond is known to be the main cause of failure of discrete devices under high voltage, high current applications due to the parasitic stray inductances. Wire bonded module also sets space limits to the integration depth of power electronic systems. The 2 dimension packaging structure also has limits on heat dissipation capability. The standard chip and wire module is shown in Fig. 9-1.

Fig. 9-1 Power chip and wire module [1]

For better thermal management and system performances, three dimension (3D) packaging aims at integration of entire modules and driver circuits in a compact stacked layer structure. The 3D modules include the metal post-interconnected parallel-plate structure (MPIPPS), flip-chip-on-flex (FCOF), stacked solder bumping (SSB), dimple-array interconnect (DAI) and double-side cooled direct solder interconnect developed at CPES [2]. The module is fabricated based on the soldering process. The devices are sandwiched between two circuit substrates such as direct bond copper (DBC) substrates. The devices are attached to the bottom substrate with solder by conventional solder die-attach processes. 3D modules are built as stacked assemblies with a second interconnection layer on top of the devices. A flexible substrate or a second DCB can be soldered on the dice leading to a multilayer assembly. A half-bridge flip chip on flex integrated power module is shown in Fig. 9-2.

Fig. 9-2 A half-bridge flip chip on flex integrated power module [2]

The 3D packaging approach has several advantages compared to the 2D packaging: (1) higher power density due to the compact layout; (2) less parasitic stray inductance proving improved switching behavior and reduced overvoltage; (3) compact integration of control electronic components on the power assembly; (4) improving heat paths and thermal resistance is reduced greatly [3].

I.1. Technical Objectives

In power electronic converter system, higher power density and higher efficiency is desired for cost reduction and space requirement. For reducing the volume of the converter, the high operating frequency can decrease the volume of the passive components. The high operating frequency leads to high switching losses, especially at the higher power levels. In order to avoid the degrading of the switching frequency at the higher power levels, device combining high blocking voltage and fast switching operation are required [4]. For sharing the voltages, the SiC JFETs are connected in series are discussed in [5]. A compact high voltage converter based on SiC JFETs is design in [4]. The increasing power rating of converters also needs higher current. The current sharing in paralleled IGBT is discussed in [6]. The parasitic parameters impact greatly on the power systems performances. Modeling and measurements of parasitic parameters for integrated power electronics modules is studied in [7]. Packaging parasitic inductance modeling in flip chip flex circuit packaging is studied in [8]. Double-Sided packaged IGBTs to improved thermal and switching characteristics is studied in [9]. The current sharing is compared between wire bonded module and planar power module in [10]. Switching characteristics on the power packaging module using solder bump technology is investigated in [11]. There are lots of works in this field besides mentioned.

Based on the above, the power module design is needed for the high system performance and reliability especially in high power density. Our study will explore voltage sharing power MOSFET module. This work is to series connect three low breakdown voltage rating MOSFET together instead of using one MOSFET in switched-mode power supply. The motivation of series connected MOSFET switch is to reduce the voltage stress of the MOSFET and thus improve the breakdown voltage. The series connected MOSFET will have lower energy loss than one single MOSFET due to the lower turn on and turn off voltage. Hence module thermal management and system performance will be improved.

I.2. Technical Approach

DulalCool™ N-channel NexFET power MOSFET from Texas Instruments was chosen to be the devices and direct bond copper (DBC) as the substrate. The patterns of top and bottom DBC substrates were designed with AutoCAD software. The patterns on the substrates were

fabricated with the laser-cutting machine (Resonetics Micromaching Technology, Nahsua, NH, USA) and the BTD-201B wet etcher (Kepro Circuit Systems Inc, Fenton, MO, USA). The reflow process was used to solder the devices to the substrates. Three modules are assembled. Finally, breakdown voltage test was performed to proved the improvement of voltage rating.

II. Selection of Materials

II.1. MOSFET

We choose DulalCool™ N-channel NexFET power MOSFET from Texas Instruments. The main features are DualCool™ pacage SON 5X6mm, optimized for 2-sided cooling, optimized for 5v gate drive, ultralow Qg and Qgd, and low thermal resistance. The diagram of top view and bottom view is shown in Fig. 9-3.

The product summary of CSD16325Q5C is shown in Table 9-1.

Fig. 9-3 DulalCool™ N-channel NexFET power MOSFET diagram

Table 9-1 The product summary of CSD16325Q5C [12]

V_{DS}	Drain to Source voltage	25	V
Q_g	Gate Charge total (4.5V)	18	nC
Q_{gd}	Gate Charge Gate to Drain	3.5	nC
$R_{DS(on)}$	Drain to Source On Resistance	$V_{GS}=3V$	2.1 mΩ
		$V_{GS}=4.5V$	1.7 mΩ
		$V_{GS}=8V$	1.5 mΩ
$V_{GS(th)}$	Threshold Voltage	1.1	V

II.2. The Substrate

The directed bonded copper (DBC) is used as the substrate for the interconnection for the devices. DBC has three layers with two copper layers as the outside layers and one layer of electrically insulated sandwich-bonded ceramic as the middle layer. The DBC structure is shown in Fig. 9-4.

Fig. 9-4 Top view and side view of the DBC substrate

DBC is manufactured as high temperature at about 1070°C in an inert atmosphere. The copper oxides forms a eutectic melt that wets and cools to form a strong bond between copper and ceramic. There are no solder or any other bonding materials between copper and ceramic surface. The ceramic used as the insulating materials include Al_2O_3 , AlN , Si_3N_4 and BeO [13]. Aluminum oxide is used here because it is easily available in the market and lab.

DBC offer many advantages for the power electronics packaging: The copper and ceramic are bonded together has a lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), which is much lower than the copper and closed to the ceramic. So the large area chip can be solder on the copper layer without risking stress damage. The copper is the high-purity, oxygen-free-high-conductivity (OFHC) type. The copper traces can be very low resistance that handles large current with more than 100A. The thick layer of the copper pad is effective for heat spreading for power device.

II.3. Solder Material

The top and bottom layers DBC are made with the interconnection patterns to connect the devices. The layers also work as heat spreaders and electrical shields. The external, buck and expensive heat sink can be eliminated.

We use a precision reflow machine to solder the device on the substrate. The low temperature solder is used because it is easy to reflow and eliminated the risk of overheating the devices during the soldering. SnPb eutectic solder paste is used here. The specification is as follows [14]:

Table 9-2 Specification of the SnPb eutectic solder paste

Alloy	SN63/PB37
Melting point	183oC
Particle size	Type 3 per J-STD-006
Power shape	Sphere
Halide content	9.5±0.5wt%
Viscosity	200-500ppm
Flux type	Resin flux ROLO J-STD-004

For handling and storage, solder paste should be stored at 0-10°C. The shelf life is 6 months from the production date and kept out of directed sunlight.

III. Design, Fabrication of Substrate, and Assembly

We use AutoCAD for the layout of the substrate. The substrate for connecting Source of Q1 and drain of the Q2 is shown in Fig. 9-5. The substrate for connecting Source of Q2 and drain of the Q3 is shown in Fig. 9-6. The opposite side of connecting substrate is a plane copper without pattern shown in Fig. 9-7. The brown color means copper and white color means ceramic.

Fig. 9-5 The substrate for connecting Source of Q1 and drain of the Q2

Fig. 9-6 The substrate for connecting Source of Q2 and drain of the Q3

Fig. 9-7 The opposite side of connecting substrate

We use Kapton® tape to transfer AutoCAD layout to the DBC substrate. The Kapton tape is used as 2.5mil-thick polyimide Kapton®. Kapton® has high temperature processing properties. A soft rubber roller is used to apply Kapton® tape on the DBC panel to press and push the tape evenly and avoid the air bubbles between the tape and the DBC.

Then we use laser cutting machine to cut the pattern on the Kapton® tape. The laser cutting machine is a made by Resonetics Micromaching Technology, Nahsua, NH, USA shown in Fig. 9-8.

Fig. 9-8 Laser cutting machine

For the cutting tape, the process parameters, pulse spacing, laser power and pulse number are set as 0.002 inch, 5 W and 10, respectively to ensure high dimension resolution. The DBC panel is attached on the work station by double stick tape to prevent the panel moving. The DBC substrates after laser cutting on Kapton® tape are shown in Fig. 9-9. After cutting the tape, the unnecessary parts are removed. The substrates after striped of tape are shown in Fig. 9-10.

Then the exposed copper is etched away. The etching machine is a BTD-201B. Bench-top developed (Kepro Circuit Systems Inc, Fenton, MO, USA). The etching solution is ferric chloride (FeCl_3). The BTD-201B is shown in Fig. 9-11.

Fig. 9-9 DBC substrate after laser cutting on tape

Fig. 9-10 Substrate after striped of tape

Fig. 9-11 The etching machine

Put the DBC panel in the machine and solution is pressure-sprayed on the DBC panel. The unmasked copper is etched away by chemical reaction. It takes about 1 hour for etching. When finish the etching, the DBC panel is rinsed in the water to remove the etching solution residue. Then a laser cutting process is used to cut the DBC panel as the substrate. The laser pulse spacing is 0.0006 inch. The laser power is 38 W and a power number is 300. The DBC panel is attached on the work station by double stick tape to prevent the panel moving. After etching and cutting DBC panels are shown in Fig. 9-12.

The Kapton® tapes on the DBC panel are cut for the solder paste area. Otherwise, the solder may overflow around the substrate. The DBC substrates after cutting solder paste areas are shown in Fig. 9-13.

Fig. 9-12 DBC substrate after etching and laser cutting

Fig. 9-13 DBC substrates after cutting solder paste areas

A ceramic mask helps to fix devices on the substrate. Or the devices may move on the substrate during the reflow process. The solder paste is printed on the exposed copper area. For easy soldering of two substrates together, we separately solder the devices on the panels. For the testing, the copper foil needs to be soldered on the edge of the DBC panel. The reflow

process is used for the soldering. The goal of reflow process is to heat the panel, melt the solder without overheating and damaging the devices. The reflow process consists of four zones: pre-heat zone, pre-reflow zone, reflow zone and cool-down zone. The reflow profile is shown in Fig. 9-14. A SIKAMA conduction belt oven is used in this process shown in Fig. 9-15. The belt speed is set as 6 inch/min.

Fig. 9-14 Reflow profile

Fig. 9-15 SIKAMA conduction belt oven

After reflow the devices and testing foil are soldered on the DBC panel shown in Fig. 9-16.

Fig. 9-16 Devices with the copper foils soldered on the DBC panels

Last, the two DBC panels with devices are soldered together by the second reflow. In order to keep the devices fixed on the substrate. The Kapton tape is used to hold these two substrates together shown in Fig. 9-17. Otherwise, the devices will move around during reflow. Three samples are assembled and shown in Fig. 9-18.

Fig. 9-17 Devices sandwiched between two substrates

Fig. 9-18 Three samples

IV. Electrical Characterization and Results

For the testing of the breakdown voltage of the power modules, we use a Tektronic 371 high power curve-tracer shown in Fig. 9-19.

For testing the modules breakdown voltage, the gate and source are shorted together. The testing setup is shown in Fig. 9-20.

Fig. 9-19 Tektronix 371B high power curve-tracer

Fig. 9-20 Testing setup of breakdown voltage

We test the one MOSFET, two series connected MOSFET and three series connected MOSFET breakdown voltages. The results are shown in Fig. 9-21, Fig. 9-22, and Fig. 9-23.

Fig. 9-21 One MOSFET 21.4V breakdown voltage

Fig. 9-22 Two series connected MOSFET 46.6V breakdown voltage

Fig. 9-23 Three series of MOSFET 70.8V breakdown voltage of sample 1

The breakdown voltages of three samples are summarized in the Table 9-3.

Table 9-3 Breakdown voltage of three samples

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Breakdown voltage (V)	67.5	70.8	75

V. Conclusions

This research is to study series connected power devices modules in order to improve breakdown voltage. The three series connected MOSFET power module is assembled. By using double side flip chip direct bond soldering, three series connected TI DualCool™ Power MOSFET devices are sandwiched in the double DBC substrates. The series connected packaging module shows good breakdown voltage.

The switch topology shows good results in switching behaviors and voltage sharing in simulations. For the future work, the drive circuit need be built in the power module and tested. The performances of the power module in voltage sharing and switching behavior and energy loss need to be studied. The voltage sharing multiple devices switch characteristics can be compared with one device switch. Series connected high voltage MOSFET and IGBT can be studied. The applications of voltage sharing switch need to be specified and tested.

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Chapter 10 IMPACT OF MOISTURE ON RELIABILITY OF DIRECT-BOND-COPPER (DBC) SUBSTRATES

I. Introduction

Power electronics has a long and glory history, and is supposed to have an even brighter future. The integration and packaging of power electronic modules has already been successfully developed and gradually industrialized [1]. Then the current challenge in this field becomes the development of power modules with high-frequency, high-voltage, and high-temperature.

Direct-bond-copper (DBC) substrates are widely used as the interconnect and support board for packaging power semiconductor chips in power devices and modules [2], [3], as shown in Fig. 10-1. DBC substrates provide excellent electrical isolation and thermal management, but their reliability is being questioned for high temperature applications in which they are subjected to large temperature swings of over 300°C. It has been reported that DBC substrates can survive thousands of cycles if subjected to moderate temperature cycling (-55°C ~150°C) [2]. Yet previous work indicated that DBC would fail in only a few tens of cycles if subjected to -55°C ~250°C temperature cycles. Meanwhile, it's also reported that the DBC lifetime under same condition could still exceed one thousand cycles if the DBC edges were sealed with certain encapsulation materials. Obviously, in this case, the encapsulant is playing a role in the lifetime enhancement. This enhancement is achieved may due to any mechanical support provided by the polymer, or may due to that the chemical resistance of polymer helps to prevent stress-corrosion cracking at high temperature. Since there have been very few works addressing on the chemical effects during DBC failure process, in this work, the hypothetical chemical effect in DBC failure will be studied.

Fig. 10-1 A power module with its top open to show the DBC substrates on which power chips were attached

I.1. Technical Objectives

Recently, an experiment was carried out to compare the lifetimes of DBC substrates with and without encapsulation of the copper-ceramic edges under temperature-cycling between -55°C and 250°C. It was found that all the non-encapsulated DBC samples delaminated in 20 to 30 cycles, while the encapsulated substrates lasted several hundred to one thousand cycles, as shown in Table 10-1. To explain this significant difference in lifetime between the two types of substrates, it was suggested that the polymer encapsulant might have prevented the chemical species in the atmosphere of the cycling chamber, such as moisture or oxygen, from reaching to

the copper-ceramic interface to initiate stress-corrosion cracking. Since most of the studies [4], [5], [6] thus far on DBC reliability have not addressed the role of chemical species on the failure, we believed that it deserved an investigation to help explain the observed improvement of reliability.

Table 10-1 Lifetimes of DBC substrates with and without encapsulation

	Non-encapsulated	Duralco 132 encapsulated	Epo-Tek 600 encapsulated
Lifetime (cycles)	20 - 30	300 - 600	600 - 1000

I.2. Technical Approach

To examine the suggested chemical effect in DBC failure, it's very important to investigate any chemical trace left on the delaminating surfaces. In this work, both optical microscopy and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) are used to observe and analyze the chemicals left on the delaminating surfaces. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is then used to observe the microstructure of the DBC substrate, which may reveal micro defects assisting crack extension. Finally, controlled atmosphere (Dry N₂) thermal cycling test is conducted to examine the DBC failure behavior in an environment lacking both oxygen and moisture.

II. Materials

Failed samples, which were encapsulated with Duralco 132 (Cotronics Co.), Epo-Tek 600 (Epoxy Technology Inc.), and non-encapsulated, were obtained after the former mentioned thermal cycling test. These samples were analyzed by optical microscopy and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

Large DBC substrates were etched and cut into small pieces (30 mm × 20 mm). During etching, 4 pieces were etched with step-edges while the other pieces were etched with sharp edges, as shown in Fig. 10-2 a) and b). These samples were to be used in scanning electron microscopy and the controlled atmosphere thermal cycling test.

Fig. 10-2 The as-prepared DBC samples a) with sharp edges (non-step-edged), b) with step-edges

III. Experiments and Results

III.1. Optical Microscopy

1. Experiments

Optical microscope (LEICA G27, LEICA Microsystems) is used to characterize the fracture surfaces of non-encapsulated DBC samples and encapsulated samples with Duralco 132 and Epo-Tek 600, respectively. The copper layers were peeled off from each as-failed DBC structures and then placed under the microscope. The edges from where the samples started to fail were of main interest. The microscopic images would show signs of chemical corrosion at the sample edges, if any.

2. Results and discussions

Optical microscope images show the general features of the fracture surfaces.

Fig. 10-3 shows the edge areas of the fracture interfaces of the peeled-off copper layers. a), b), and c) are from the sample encapsulated with Duralco 132, the sample encapsulated with Epo-Tek 600, and the non-encapsulated sample, respectively.

All images show that failed ceramic covers all over the copper layer and the failed ceramic layers become thicker as getting further away from the edges. Fig. 10-3 a) and c) show that the sample encapsulated with Duralco 132 and non-encapsulated sample would peel off right from the edge of the copper layer, while b) shows that the sample encapsulated with Epo-Tek 600 would peel off from the ceramic surface close to the edge. These signs indicate that cracks resulting in the final failure initiate at the ceramic surfaces or at the edge of the copper-ceramic interfaces, and then grow gradually into the ceramic matrix.

Also, all images show a dark line along the edge of the copper, which is supposed to be one type or a mixture of several types of copper oxides. These copper oxides were possibly created due to certain corrosion effects either during the thermal cycling process or during the DBC manufacture process.

Fig. 10-3 Fracture interfaces of Cu, a) Encapsulated with Duralco 132, b) Encapsulated with Epo-Tek 600, c) Non-encapsulated

III.2. X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

1. Experiments

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy was then used to investigate on the chemicals deposited at fracture surfaces of the above-mentioned 3 types of DBC samples. The samples were cut into small pieces ($\sim 5 \text{ mm} \times 5 \text{ mm}$) to fit the sample holders of the XPS instrument. At each time, the sample holders were carefully adjusted, so that the edge area of each sample would be exposed to X-ray. A resolution of $200 \mu\text{m} \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ was used to scan each sample's edge area. Several points were studied on each sample to compare if great difference would occur.

2. Results and discussions

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy results give the composition of chemicals deposited at the fracture surface.

Fig. 10-4 gives the XPS results for the dark edge of the copper layers from the failed samples. a), b), and c) are from the encapsulated sample with Duralco 132, encapsulated sample with Epo-Tek 600, and the non-encapsulated sample, respectively.

XPS results for all samples show obvious O1s, C1s, and Al2p peaks. The location of these peaks correspond to the binding energies of electrons in the 1s orbits in oxygen atoms, electrons in the 1s orbits in carbon atoms, and electrons in the 2p orbits in aluminum atoms, respectively. Therefore, the presence of these peaks proves the presence of the corresponding materials at the surface area under inspection. The aluminum and some oxygen are supposed to be from the ceramic in the DBC structure, while the carbon is supposed to be from the environment or any other types of pollution. For all samples, there's almost no peak at around 955 eV and 933 eV, which represent the binding energy of Cu2p 1/2 and Cu2p 3/2 electrons (electrons in the degenerated 2p orbits in copper atoms).

These results indicate that the peeled-off surfaces are mostly covered by ceramic and almost no copper is present even at the edge area of the peeled-off surfaces. This means that cracks would immediately go into the ceramic matrix and propagate inside it until the whole sample fails. Such result is contradictory to Yoshino's [6] research, which states that crack would first propagate along the interface and then deflect into the ceramic matrix. However, the reason why the samples studied in this work would fail in another way is beyond the scope of this chapter.

III.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

1. Experiments

Scanning electron microscopy was used to characterize the microstructure of non-cycled DBC samples. One piece of non-cycled DBC sample (non-step-edged) was cut and then mounted in epoxy resin (Buehler Ltd.). The as-mounted sample was then polished with a series of silicon sand paper, with grit of 200, 320, 400, and 600. The sample was then polished by silica dispensers, with grit of 5 m, 1 m, 0.5 m, and 0.3 m. Gold was deposited on the sample surface through sputtering to provide the electrical pathway. The sample was then loaded in the SEM chamber; the backscatter detector was used to obtain the surface information. Surface microstructures of the ceramic matrix and the copper-ceramic interfaces were studied.

2. Results and discussions

Scanning electron microscopy images give microstructure information of a cross-section of the alumina matrix and that of the copper-alumina interface.

Fig. 10-5 gives the SEM images of the alumina. a) and b) have a magnification of $1200\times$ and $5200\times$, respectively. Fig. 10-5 a) shows the general feature of the alumina matrix. The whole surface appears to be rough with large volume defects (pores) occasionally located on it. The rough surface and the occasionally existed volume defects reflect a relatively low density of the alumina ceramic. Fig. 10-5 b) gives a close look at the pore area. The pore appears to be long and wide, and also pretty deep in the direction perpendicular to the image.

Fig. 10-4 XPS result of fracture surfaces (Cu side) of a) Duralco 132 encapsulated sample; b) Epo-Tek 600 Encapsulated sample; c) Non-encapsulated sample

Fig. 10-5 SEM images of Alumina surface a) 1120x; b) 5200x

Such huge pores, as well as the loose matrix, would result in relatively quick crack propagations inside the ceramic matrix. Furthermore, if large volume defects as shown in Fig. 10-5 b) happen to locate at the substrate surface, they may also help with the initiation of cracks.

Fig. 10-6 gives the SEM images of the alumina-copper interface. a) and b) have a magnification of 2300× and 1120×, respectively. Fig. 10-6 a) gives a rough interface at the alumina-copper joint. The particles used to form the ceramic bulk can be easily distinguished, and small pores exist at the interface due to the low density of the ceramic. Fig. 10-6 b) shows a defect at the copper side of the interface. Such defect is most likely resulted during the manufacture process from the vaporization of water in the ambient air.

The existence of such interfacial defects, as the above-mentioned pores and volume defects would also help with the crack initiation at the interface and its propagation.

Fig. 10-6 SEM images of DBC interface a) 2300x; b) 1120x

III.4. Controlled Atmosphere Thermal Cycling Test

1. Experiments

To investigate the impact of chemicals existing in the ambient air on the DBC lifetime, controlled atmosphere thermal cycling test was carried out. The environmental thermal chamber (Tenney TU-JR, LR Environmental Equipment Co. Inc.) was programmed to go repeatedly from -55°C to 250°C, with each cycle lasting about 45 minutes. 4 step-edged samples and another 4 non-step-edged samples are placed inside the environmental thermal chamber. Dry nitrogen tank was connected to the chamber and nitrogen was flown into it before the thermal cycling test began. The test was started when the air in the chamber was almost all replaced by the nitrogen. The pressure was carefully adjusted and nitrogen was kept flowing in and out of the chamber to keep the pressure constant. The chamber was opened every day at the same time to check whether the samples inside had failed.

2. Results and discussions

The environmental thermal chamber was opened after one day (32 cycles). All the non-step-edged substrates are found to be failed, while the step-edged ones still hold. This result is very much similar to the results of experiments conducted in ambient air (without the controlled atmosphere), which reported that non-step-edged samples would fail in 20~30 cycles.

The result of this controlled atmosphere thermal cycling test indicate that the chemicals existed in the ambient air, that is, oxygen and water vapor, are actually of little effect on the failure of DBCs.

Therefore, the mechanics is still the main reason for failure in this case. The reason why great lifetime difference would occur between encapsulated and non-encapsulated samples is still unclear at this stage, yet it is supported by now that chemical effects during the thermal cycling test have only little impact on DBCs' lifetime.

IV. Conclusions

Optical microscopy and x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy were used to characterize the failed DBC substrates with encapsulation by Duralco 132 and Epo-Tek 600, and those without encapsulation at all. The results show that the samples start to fail either from the copper edge at the interface or from the ceramic surface close to the edge of copper. Instead of growing along the interface and then deflecting into the ceramic matrix, the cracks would grow directly into the ceramic.

Scanning electron microscopy images reveal weak points existed in the substrates, which would possibly result in the mechanical failure of DBCs in the thermal cycling tests.

Results from the controlled atmosphere thermal cycling test failed to support any suggested chemical effects on the lifetime of DBC samples. This finding points to a careful examination of the mechanical stress state along the edge of the copper-ceramic interface as a possible reason for the observed reliability improvement in encapsulated DBC.

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Chapter 11 ENCAPSULATION MATERIALS FOR HIGH-VOLTAGE, HIGH-TEMPERATURE POWER ELECTRONIC PACKAGING

I. Introduction

Power semiconductor devices like BJT, MOSFET, Schottky diode, and JFET are available on the market today, which can operate up to a temperature range of 175°C. Recently developed SiC devices, however, can have an operating temperature that exceeds 600°C, and currently the operating temperature of SiC power devices has already reached 200°C [1], [2], [3]. Compared to conventional Si devices, the development of SiC devices would broaden the range of temperature requirements of the semiconductor packages.

However, when assembling a high-voltage and high-temperature power electronic package, as shown in Fig. 11-1, the capabilities of conventional materials are greatly limited. Encapsulants, for example, could be one of the limitations. Polymeric encapsulants are widely used in electronic packaging industries to protect chips and interconnections from external environmental damages, such as moisture, solvents, gases, and radiation [4]. For power electronic packaging, encapsulants are also expected to be able to improve the voltage ratings of the packages [5].

The wider application temperature range also challenges the conventional encapsulants, which are designed mainly for applications below 175°C. Therefore, identifying new encapsulants for higher temperature application is necessary. The purpose of this work is to compare several available encapsulants for their high-temperature (250°C) dielectric performances, and to find ways to incorporate the encapsulants into a planar package.

Fig. 11-1. Cross-sectional view of a plane-bonded power module

I.1. Technical Objectives

Currently, very few works have been done to address the encapsulation issues for high temperature application up to 250°C. Hence, in this work, potential encapsulation materials from a variety of vendors will be surveyed, and encapsulants suitable for high-voltage, high-temperature power electronic packaging will be selected from several existing candidates.

This chapter aims at selecting one of more encapsulants for high-voltage, high-temperature power electronic packaging, and hopefully figuring out a selecting procedure for encapsulants of specific application requirements.

The first property studied in this study is the processability of the material. The processability is listed first because any potential material must be processable. The processability test

constitutes materials flow, materials curing, and test vehicle breakdown tests. Materials flow and curing are designed to test whether the material will leave voids or cracks before and after curing, if flown beneath the chip. The test vehicle breakdown is designed to check whether or not the high dielectric strength of the material could be sustained when flown under the chip.

On all the materials proved to be processable, dielectric characterization was performed to test the dielectric strength and permittivity of the materials. It'll be desirable if the material has high dielectric strength (>10 kV/mm [6]), and that high dielectric strength can be sustained at higher temperature (up to 250°C).

Afterwards, the degradation of dielectric strength and permittivity with respect to thermal aging time is investigated. Usually, when subjected to prolonged heating, polymeric materials will degrade either by hydrolysis process or by bond-breaking in the main chains [7]. In that case, it's expected that dielectric strength of the material to be impacted by thermal aging. Meanwhile, the permittivity may also be impacted. The extent of property degradation will reflect the reliability of a material as encapsulant for high-voltage and high-temperature application, and is therefore worthwhile to study.

I.2. Technical Approach

Most encapsulation materials are thermosetting, which allowed easy printing and potting. These thermosetting polymers are usually cured at certain temperature below their glass transition temperature (T_g) and form cross-linked non-flowing materials.

Glass transition temperature (T_g) is a very important parameter for polymeric materials. Theoretically, at T_g , material properties are subjected to dramatic changes. For example, when temperature is increased from below T_g to above it, the modulus would drop and the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) would increase at T_g . Considering that CTE mismatch would arise whenever two materials in contact are subjected to temperature change, and that stresses would be generated accordingly, when selecting encapsulation materials, it's much better to make sure that T_g is beyond the temperature swing range of the electronic package, so as to avoid even large internal stresses. Based on their glass transition temperatures, several materials are selected for further investigation.

To investigate the dielectric performances of each material, a planar capacitor with the material under test as the dielectric is built. The capacitance of the capacitor is measured, from which the permittivity of the material is calculated. Electrical breakdown test is also conducted to the planar capacitor. The dielectric strength of the material is then calculated from the breakdown voltage.

Two types of power modules are also built to prove the potentials of the selected encapsulants. The first type is a wire-bonded module with three diodes in series, whereas the second type is a planar-bonded module with a dummy device. Electrical breakdown tests are performed on these modules before and after encapsulation.

I.3. Theoretical Information

i) Thermosetting polymers

Thermosetting polymer may be defined as polymer networks formed by the chemical reaction of monomers [8]. This type of material is generally flowable before curing, and the monomers would cross-link and form giant macromolecules consisting of covalently bonded repeating units during the polymerization process. Once cured, this material will not turn into the

original small monomers or flow again, unless the action of temperature or a reactive solvent destroys the covalent bonds presented.

ii) Viscous flow

The flow of encapsulation materials under the chips is similar to the flow of underfill, especially when the effects of solder pumps are ignored. After the chip was assembled to the substrate, the dispensed underfill will be dragged into the small gap between the chip and the substrate by capillary force, and this type of flowing is called viscous flow [9], [10]. The viscous flow between chip and substrate has been nicely modeled by M. K. Schwiebert et al. [9], and the flow time is given by (11-1).

$$t = \frac{3\eta L^2}{h\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (11-1)$$

Where, t – the viscous flow time;

μ – the absolute viscosity of the fluid;

L – the length of the chip;

h – the gap distance;

γ – the surface tension of the liquid-vapor interface;

θ – the wetting angle that the encapsulant makes with the planes.

This conclusion is indicating that the flow time would be prolonged for larger size chip. Yet fortunately, in this paper, it's also mentioned that vacuum would shorten the flow time. And it's suggested that vacuum enhancements can generate driving pressures of up to one atmosphere (105 Pa).

iii) Breakdown voltage and dielectric strength

Dielectric breakdown voltage is defined by the ASTM standards [11] as the potential difference at which dielectric failure, which is an event that is evidenced by an increase in conductance in the dielectric under test limiting the electric field that can be sustained, occurs under prescribed conditions in an electrical insulating material located between two electrodes.

The dielectric strength is defined as the voltage gradient at which dielectric failure of the insulating material occurs under specific conditions of test. Considering a planar capacitor as shown in Fig. 11-2, when voltage is applied between the two electrodes separated by the dielectric material of a thickness h , the highest voltage that can ever be sustained is recorded as the breakdown voltage, V_B . And in this case of a paralleled capacitor, if the voltage gradient is considered uniform, then the dielectric strength is calculated as (11-2).

$$E_B = \frac{V_B}{h} \quad (11-2)$$

Where, E_B – dielectric strength of dielectric material;

V_B – breakdown voltage of the paralleled capacitor;

h – the thickness of dielectric materials.

Fig. 11-2 Schematic of breakdown voltage and dielectric strength in a paralleled capacitor

II. Survey of Encapsulants for High-Temperature

As mentioned previously, two categories of materials may be suitable for high-voltage, high-temperature power electronic packaging. In this section, materials existing in the market are reviewed, and five candidates are presented.

a. Epo-Tek 600 (Polyimide) is developed by Epoxy Technology [12]. This material is a single component, high temperature, low CTE screen printable polyimide composition designed for alpha particle protection, power chips protection, and general purpose environmental / mechanical protective coating for chips. The Tg of this material is higher than 260°C, the CTE below Tg is 10 ppm, and the dielectric strength is approximately 16.9 kV/mm. The properties of this material provided by the data sheet fitted the requirements for conventional encapsulants, so it could be a potential candidate for high-voltage, high-temperature application. Yet unfortunately, the mechanical data is incomplete based on the data sheet, and properties at elevated temperature are lacking.

b. Epo-Tek 390 (Polyimide) is also developed by Epoxy Technology. This is a single component, solvent containing, low viscosity polyimide designed for high temperature applications found in semiconductor, hybrid, optical and medical devices. It is used mostly as a coating and dielectric layer. A 280°C Tg is provided by the data sheet, however, other mechanical data and dielectric strength are not available.

c. Cyclotene 3022 (Benzocyclobutene, i.e. BCB) is developed by the Dow Chemical Company [13]. This is a dielectric resin derived from B-staged bisbenzocyclobutene monomers. This material has a Tg higher than 350 °C, which is around 100°C higher than the highest application temperature interested in this work. At room temperature, the modulus of this material is 2.9 GPa, and the CTE is 42 ppm. The dielectric strength of this material is also high: the provided data by the manufacture is 530 kV/mm. Although data under high temperature are lacking, based on its room temperature property, this material seems to be good for encapsulation purpose.

d. Nusil CF-4721 (Silicone resin) is developed by Nusil Silicone Technology [14]. This is a high-temperature solvent-free thermosetting resin for encapsulating electrical and electronic units. This material could work over a broad temperature range (up to 300°C). Also, it has good dielectric properties at high temperatures and humidity. The durometer of this material was 75 in Shore D scale. Such hardness indicates a high modulus and low CTE, because theoretically, Hardness or modulus and CTE are inversely proportional, the higher the hardness and modulus, the lower the CTE. The Tg and dielectric strength are not provided by the data sheet. Considering that this material could sustain its cured property up to 300°C, it's highly possible that it has a Tg higher than 250°C. Also, based on data provided by the technician, this material's dielectric strength should fall in the range of 19 kV/mm - 30 kV/mm. This information provides a material with high Tg and low CTE, and therefore may be suitable for high-voltage, high-temperature power electronic packaging.

e. Nusil R-2188 (Silicone elastomer) is developed by Nusil Silicone Technology. This is a solvent-free, two-part, translucent silicone system. It's designed for potting, encapsulating, and

coating of modules, relays, power supplies, delay lines, or complete electronic units to provide excellent shock and vibration dampening. As the data sheet provided, this material has a durometer of 20 in Shore A scale, and elongation of 674%, which means that this material is soft and elastic. The dielectric strength provided is 17.7 kV/mm. If such value could be sustained in the package, the dielectric property would also fulfill the requirement. The glass transition temperature is not provided in the data sheet, but such type of silicone material generally has a T_g as low as -100°C. Although these properties at elevated temperature are not provided, this material still seems to be suitable for an encapsulant for high-voltage and high-temperature packaging.

f. Nusil EPM 2422 (Silicone) is developed by Nusil Silicone Technology. This is a high-temperature, low-viscosity thermosetting silicone material for protection of electric components and assemblies against shock, vibration, moisture, dust, chemicals and other environmental hazards. As the data sheet provided, the glass transition temperature of this material is around -100°C. The CTE below T_g is 10 ppm/°C, whereas that above T_g is 490 ppm/°C. The durometer and the elongation of this material are 40 in Shore A scale and 125%, respectively, which mean this is a soft elastic material. It's also provided by the data sheet that this material has a dielectric strength of 21.7 kV/mm.

g. Nusil EPM 2482 (Silicone gel) is developed by Nusil Silicone Technology. This is a high-temperature, low-viscosity thermosetting silicone gel material designed for potting and encapsulating electronic components and assemblies. As a typical silicone gel material, cured Nusil EPM 2482 is soft and tacky. The dielectric strength is not provided in the data sheet. But based on data provided by the technician, this material's dielectric strength should fall in the range of 19 kV/mm - 30 kV/mm.

h. MasterSil 800 (Silicone elastomer) is developed by Master Bond [15]. This material is a self leveling, free flowing, low viscosity material that allows filling minute crevices and voids in sealing and potting applications. Claimed by technical data sheet, this material has a maximum application temperature up to 300°C. This elastomer has a durometer of 26 in Shore A scale and an elongation of 260%. The dielectric strength is around 20 kV/mm.

The properties of these eight materials are given in Table 11-1.

Table 11-1 Properties of the seven selected potential encapsulants

Material	Durometer	T _g (°C)	CTE (ppm/°C)	Dielectric strength(kV/mm)	Composition
Epo-Tek 600	73 (Shore D)	260	10	16.9	Polyimide
Epo-Tek 390	N/A	275	28	N/A	Polyimide
Cyclobutene 3022	N/A	>350	42	530	Benzocyclobutene
Nusil CF-4721	75 (Shore D)	300	N/A	19~30	Silicone resin
Nusil R-2188	20 (Shore A)	<-55	N/A	17.7	Silicone elastomer
Nusil EPM 2422	40 (Shore A)	<-95	490	21.7	Silicone
Nusil EPM 2482	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	260
MasterSil 800	26 (Shore A)	<-55	N/A	19.7	Silicone elastomer

III. Experiments and Results

III.1. Processability

This section presents materials processability testing. The flow test, the curing test, and the encapsulated test vehicle breakdown test were conducted to all of the eight selected potential materials. By analyzing the results of these tests, one can easily determine whether or not one material is applicable for encapsulation. Meanwhile, the same testing methodology would also be suitable for selecting other thermosetting encapsulation material.

1. Methodology

The methodology of processability testing includes materials flow test, materials curing test, and the encapsulated test vehicle breakdown test. To test the materials' flowability, each material should be dropped on one side of the die and let flow automatically to the other side based on capillary effect. The die filling time, the flow front shape, and the as-flown texture constitute the material's flowability. In the curability test, each material should be carefully cured as flown into the testing structure. The texture formed after curing is considered as the material's curability, which is a significant parameter when selecting an appropriate encapsulant. In the encapsulated test vehicle breakdown test, the dielectric strength of material between the silicon chip and the DBC substrate was measured. The dielectric strength measured via this method is the dielectric behavior of the test vehicle encapsulated with certain type of material, rather than that of that material itself. Therefore, by comparing the dielectric strength of the test vehicle and that of the material encapsulating the test vehicle, one can easily recognize the relationship between processability of a material and the overall dielectric strength of the package encapsulated with that material.

2. Flowability

The materials flow test includes, the materials' flow front shape, the die filling time and the resulted materials overall flowing features. Materials curing test is designed to evaluate if a material would end up with a void-less and crack-less texture after curing. Encapsulated test vehicle breakdown test aims at testing the dielectric strength of the material encapsulating the test vehicle. The result of this test would somehow reflect the overall processability of that material.

i) Experiments

In the flowability test, a 6 mm × 6 mm glass piece was used as a dummy die. The glass piece was chosen for dummy die was because of the transparency of glass and the similarity of materials wetting behavior on glass and metal surfaces. The transparency of glass dummy die allowed direct observation on the material's flowing behavior over the whole flowing process.

The substrate used in this test was silver-coated DBC substrate. The bare DBC substrate (approximately 20 mm × 20 mm) was immersed into nitric acid for around 10 minutes. This process allowed all the copper oxides on the DBC surface to be cleared away. The substrate was taken out when oxides residue was all cleaned away and metallic shine and copper grain structure was observed on the DBC surface. Immediately after taken out, the substrate was thoroughly rinsed with de-ionized (DI) water. After cleaning, the substrate was placed into the nickel plating solution, with the cathode and anode carefully connected to the power supply. The current was quickly adjusted to around 160 mA, that is, 20 mA/cm². Area of both sides of the DBC substrate was considered because electro-plating on the front and back sides were conducted simultaneously. After 15 minutes of nickel plating, the power supply was shut down and the sample was taken out and rinsed with DI water. Immediately after rinsing, the sample was immersed into Cyanide bath solution for about 15 seconds, which would clean away any possible nickel residue on the DBC surface. The substrate was rinsed again with DI water and then placed into the silver strike solution. The silver strike current was close to 160 mA (20 mA/

cm²), and the strike process should last for 10~15 seconds. The substrate, together with the plating electrodes, was then quickly transferred into the silver electro-plating solution. The silver electro-plating current is approximately 80 mA, corresponding to a 10 mA/cm² current density. The silver electro-plating process should last for 20 minutes. After the 20-minute silver electro-plating, the power supply was shut down and the sample was removed from the electro-plating equipment. Upon removal, the sample was rinsed thoroughly with DI water and then immediately dried with KimWipes (Fisher Scientific).

The glass dummy die was then glued onto the silver plated substrate using double-sided Kapton® tape (Du Pont), as shown in Fig. 11-3. The Kapton® tape was chosen because it has relatively uniform thickness and it could endure temperature as high as 400°C [16].

Upon the construction of the above test structure, materials' flowability could be studied simply by dropping 1 - 2 drops of material on one side of the glass dummy die and observing the corresponding flowing behavior.

First of all, the shape of the flow front of a material determined whether or not this material would lead to voiding, as the material was applied into the planar gap between the chip and the substrate. According to the argument of J. P. Goodelle, et al, two shapes of flow front, flat and wedge, as shown in Fig. 11-4, will not lead to voiding [17].

Fig. 11-3 Materials flow tester. 6 mm × 6 mm glass dummy die glued on silver-plated DBC substrate with 2 layers of double-sided Kapton® tape

Fig. 11-4 Schematic examples of desirable front shapes, a) flat and b) wedge shape

The die filling time indicated the filling rate of a material. High filling rate is obviously more desirable, but this is not suggesting that a material with low filling rate would never fit for being an encapsulant. The die filling time is counted in seconds as the material is flowing from one side to the other of the 6 mm × 6 mm glass dummy die. After enough time for flowing, the material texture under the glass dummy die would reflect that materials overall flowing property. A desirable encapsulant would thoroughly fill up any small gap in the test structure and result in void-free texture.

Considering that Epo-Tek 600 has high viscosity, the flowability test of it was conducted in vacuum condition. And for Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer, which had second highest viscosity among the five materials, the flow test was conducted both in air and in vacuum. After enough time for flowing, the material texture under the glass dummy die would reflect that materials overall flowing property. A desirable encapsulant would thoroughly fill up any small gap in the test structure and result in void-free texture. And on the contrary, if a material would not fill the gaps between the substrate and the die, or would lead to voiding after filling, that material would not be suitable for encapsulating purpose.

MasterSil 800 automatically cured in air at room temperature within a short time, so instead of letting it free-flow into any gap, injection molding might be a more suitable way to process it. To simulate the condition of injection molding, another test structure was designed, as shown in Fig. 11-5. This tester was built by attaching a silicon chip on top of a glass substrate with double-sided tape, as shown in Fig. 11-5 (a). The tape simulated the solder joint in a real module, and the glass substrate was used again due to its transparency and similarity of material wetting behavior to that on metal surfaces. Between the edges of the chip and the substrate, a thin gap was created (around 0.1 mm thick and 0.5 mm wide), which was supposed to be filled by encapsulant, as shown in Fig. 11-5 (b). The injection molding process was simulated by pushing the material into the thin gap with a sharp-tip syringe. As the syringe went around the chip, the material was pushed into the thin gap at the edges. The flowability and the curability could then be examined.

Fig. 11-5 Processability tester for MasterSil 800. (a) Top view; (b) bottom view

ii) Results and discussions

The first property evaluated in the materials flow test was the materials' flow front shape, and the results were shown in Fig. 11-6.

Fig. 11-6 a) showed the flow front of Epo-Tek 600 (Epoxy Tech.) under the glass dummy die. Obviously there was no sign of flowing of this material. The most possible reason for this is the high viscosity of it. From this it's known that high viscosity was unfavorable for an encapsulant that was required to be filled in small gaps. In this way, high viscosity had rendered Epo-Tek 600 not applicable for an encapsulant.

Fig. 11-6 b), c), d), e), f), and g) revealed the flow front shapes of Epo-Tek 390 (Epoxy Tech.), Cyclotene 3022 (Dow Chemical), Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin (Nusil Silicone Tech.), Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer (Nusil Silicone Tech.), Nusil EPM 2422 silicone material (Nusil Silicone Tech.), and Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel (Nusil Silicone Tech.), respectively. It's clear that all these four materials exhibit flow front shapes similar to the wedge shape cited above, which was claimed to be advantageous for a void-free encapsulant texture.

Fig. 11-6 Top view of flow fronts of, a) Epo-Tek 600; b) Epo-Tek 390; c) Cyclotene 3022; d) Nusil CF-4721; e) Nusil R-2188; f) Nusil EPM 2422; g) Nusil EPM 2482. Size of all glass dummy die: 6mm × 6mm

The property considered next was the materials filling time. The filling time of the selected five materials under a 6 mm × 6 mm glass dummy die was recorded in Table 11-2. Together with the die filling time, materials' as-filled texture was also captured, as shown in Fig. 11-7.

Based on these data, it's confirmed twice that Epo-Tek 600, the material that was too thick to flow, would not fill the gap underneath the glass dummy die. Yet surprisingly, the much more fluid material, Epo-Tek 390 would neither thoroughly fill the underneath gap. The problem with this material was the fast drying speed of it. This material dried in seconds when the total volume exposed to air was small. Therefore, it would get dried before it flowed from one side of the die to the other. This result indicated that materials dried too fast would not fit for encapsulant.

Table 11-2 Die (6 mm × 6 mm) filling time of Epo-Tek 600, Epo-Tek 390, Cyclotene 3022, Nusil CF-4721, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482

	Die (6 mm × 6 mm) filling time (sec)
Epo-Tek 600 (Polyimide)	Not filling
Epo-Tek 390 (Polyimide)	Not filling
Cyclotene 3022 (BCB)	10 - 20
Nusil CF-4721 (Silicone resin)	2 - 3
Nusil R-2188 (Silicone elastomer)	40 - 60 in air / 10 - 15 in vacuum
Nusil EPM 2422 (Silicone material)	20 - 30
Nusil EPM 2482 (Silicone gel)	20 - 30

The other five materials, Cyclotene 3022, Nusil CF-4721, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482, could all fill in the gaps between the glass dummy die and the DBC substrate, resulting in a void-free look. As a result, these five materials had passed the flowability test.

Fig. 11-7 Materials as-flown, a) Epo-Tek 600; b) Epo-Tek 390; c) Cyclotene 3022; d) Nusil CF-4721; e) Nusil R-2188 flown in air; f) Nusil R-2188 flown in vacuum, g) Nusil EPM 2422, h) Nusil EPM 2482. Size of glass dummy die: 6mm × 6 mm

For MasterSil 800 silicone elastomer, which required processing techniques other than potting and flowing, the processability test was conducted separately. The resulted material texture is shown in Fig. 11-8. It's shown in the figure that MasterSil 800 would fill the gap underneath the chip, and the later curing result indicated no noticeable change in the material texture. Thus, based on the previously drawn conclusion, it could be fair to consider this material processable, once the proper processing technique was adopted.

Fig. 11-8 Processability tester injected with MasterSil 800

3. Curability

Thermosetting materials needed to be cured at room temperature or elevated temperature. This process allowed the polymer chains to cross-link and thus form a non-flowing hardened material. The curing profiles used in this work were obtained from the vendors and may be slightly modified based on our experiences.

i) Experiments

Since two of the eight selected materials didn't pass the previously conducted materials flow test, so in this part of the experiment, only the left six materials were tested for their curing property. And the curing profiles these materials were shown in Fig. 11-9.

Cyclotene 3022 (Dow Chemical) was firstly subjected to a pre-treatment of a 12-hour room temperature overnight drying, which allowed most room temperature evaporating solvents to escape from the test structure. After this room temperature pre-treatment, the test structure with Cyclotene 3022 flown in was cured on a series of hot plates according to the curing profile. After cured, a slow cooling rate was favored because slowly cooling rate limited cracking within the material.

Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin (Nusil Silicone Tech.) had one or more components very sensitive to O₂, and therefore required a curing atmosphere in absence of O₂. Dry N₂, which was used in this work, was one recommended atmosphere by the vender. Beside N₂, vacuum was also tried, but as the material was cured in vacuum, the low pressure would result in the decrease of the material's boiling point, which rendered vacuum an unfavorable curing condition. Therefore, when curing the test structure with Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin flown in, the whole piece of sample was placed in the environmental chamber (LR Environmental Equipment Co. Ltd.), which could be sealed and thus able to keep the inside atmosphere unchanged as the curing process going on. The chamber was afterwards carefully sealed and pumped down with a mechanical vacuum pump. Meanwhile, the temperature control was turned on, so the chamber was heated and the temperature would be displayed on the control panel. As pumped down, the vacuum pump was shut down while the chamber was still sealed and being heated. Dry N₂ tank was then connected to the chamber and N₂ was slowly flown into it. N₂ tank was closed until the temperature reached 150°C and isothermally stayed for 15 minutes. For the cooling process after curing, the temperature control was shut down and the chamber was open, and the sample was taken out when the temperature reached room temperature.

Nusil R-2188 (Nusil Silicone Tech.) can be cured at 150°C for 30 minutes. The sample with NusilR-2188 silicone flown in was heated on a hot plate with a ramp rate of 10°C/min until 150°C was reached. The sample was soaked for 30 min before cooled down. The ramp rate of heating and cooling may not be important.

Nusil EPM 2422 (Nusil Silicone Tech.) can be cured at 60°C for 4 hours. The sample with Nusil EPM 2422 silicone flown in was heated on a hot plate with a ramp rate of 10°C/min until 60°C was reached. The sample was soaked for 4 hours before cooled down. The ramp rate of heating and cooling may not be important.

Nusil EPM 2482 (Nusil Silicone Tech.) can be cured at 150°C for 30 minutes. The sample with Nusil EPM 2482 silicone flown in was heated on a hot plate with a ramp rate of 10 °C/min until 150°C was reached. The sample was soaked for 30 min before cooled down. The ramp rate of heating and cooling may not be important.

MasterSil 800 (Master Bond) can be cured at room temperature for 24 hours. According to the technician from the manufacturer, increasing the curing temperature may not help the material to cure faster.

Since the result of the curability revealed that vacuuming helped further removing the air trapped in the polymers, all of the samples were subjected to vacuuming for at least 20 min.

ii) Results and discussions

The five materials passed the flow test were then cured according to their own curing profiles. Especially, the results of Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer flown in air and in vacuum were shown respectively. The resulting as-cured material features were shown in Fig. 11-10.

Fig. 11-9 Curing profiles of a) Cyclotene 3022, b) Nusil CF-4721, c) Nusil R-2188, d) NusilEPM 2422 silicone; e) NusilEPM 2482 silicone resin; f) MasterSil 800 silicone elastomer

Fig. 11-10 a) showed the as-cured Cyclotene 3022 under the glass dummy die. Huge bubbles and a few cracks were observed. Bubbles were most probably resulted from the material outgassing during the curing process. A lot of thermosetting material originally contained a variety of solvents, and as the material was being cured, the solvents would evaporate and thus escape from the material. This phenomenon was called outgassing, and consequently, outgassing would lead to shrinkage in the total volume of the material. Since the

material itself was uniform, outgassing would happen everywhere in that material. Therefore, when the material was flown into the thin, large-area gap between the die and the substrate, outgassing would also happen beneath the die. However, at the same time of outgassing, the material was being cured and thus getting more and more viscous, and therefore would not flow into the gap anymore to compensate the volume shrinkage beneath the die. As a result, bubbles generated would be trapped there and the as-cured testing structure would appear like what Cyclotene 3022 was showing.

Fig. 11-10 Materials under glass dummy die as-cured, a) Cyclotene 3022; b) Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin; c) Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer flown in air; d) Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer flown in vacuum; e) Nusil EPM 2422; f) Nusil EPM 2482

Fig. 11-10 b) showed the as-cured Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin under the glass dummy die. Although no bubble was observed in this material, it was obvious that cracks located almost everywhere. The absence of bubble indicated that this silicone material was intrinsically low outgassing, while the popularity of cracks indicated that the material was very brittle. As it was known, many thermosetting materials required to be cured at elevated temperature rather than room temperature. Therefore, as the temperature dropped down to room temperature, stresses between the material and the die and the substrate would be induced by the coefficients of thermal expansions (CTE) mismatch. For a brittle material, cracks would then easily develop because cracking was the most universal way for brittle material to release intrinsic stresses.

In contrast, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482 are a soft, elastic material, so they would not rely on cracking to compensate the stresses induced by CTE mismatch. However, when comparing Fig. 11-10 c) and d), it could be seen that small bubbles would be generated in the test structure that had Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer flown through in air but not in the one had it flown through in vacuum. Considering that Nusil R-2188 was a relatively viscous material (Viscosity 9000~12500 cPs), when it was dropped on one side of the glass dummy die and driven to the other side by capillary force, the material itself might trap or solve a little amount of air. And during the curing process, the air would be repelled from the material and thus gathered as small bubbles. Hence, the comparison of these results suggested that viscous materials like Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer preferred vacuum assisted capillary flow.

Similarly, cured MasterSil 800 is also a soft, elastic material, which exhibits low outgassing as well. Therefore, as stated above, MasterSil 800 formed neither crack nor void after being cured in the test structure. As a result, MasterSil 800 is also considered processable.

4. Test vehicle breakdown

i) Experiments

In this part of the work, test vehicles with more complicated structure were designed to imitate real electronic packages, so as to evaluate the processability of the selected materials. The test vehicle design and fabrication process were shown in Fig. 11-11.

Fig. 11-11 a) showed the schematic of a planar structure electronic package with encapsulant sealing the gap between the silicone chip and the DBC substrate. In this case, thin gaps only occupied a very limited space between the chip and the substrate and therefore won't severely challenge the encapsulation material.

Fig. 11-11 b) showed a modified structure, in which the soldering area is relatively small. Consequently, between the chip and the substrate, the small area-coverage of solder induced a gap that is thin in the vertical direction but long in the horizontal directions. In such a structure, it's required that all the gaps to be entirely and uniformly filled by encapsulant, and if not, early breakdown of the structure would occur once voltage was applied between the chip bottom and the substrate upper surface. Because of its great challenge to encapsulation material, the test vehicle for breakdown test used in this work was constructed based on this type of schematic.

Fig. 11-11 The processability test vehicle construction, a) Schematic of general electronic package; b) Schematic of test vehicle, most severe case for encapsulants; c) Patterned DBC substrate, coated with electroplated silver; d) Solder preform and spacer on substrate; e) Test vehicle as processed

The test vehicle was then constructed with a silicon chip, which was coated with silver on its bottom side, a patterned DBC substrate electro-plated with nickel and silver, and 95Pb5Sn solder preform. Bare DBC substrate was firstly etched into the desired pattern, as shown in Fig. 11-11 c), the as-etched DBC substrate showed dark red color and had copper oxide residues occasionally on the surface. Four islands were left over on the substrate for future dielectric breakdown testing. Wire bonds were then used to connect each isolated copper piece on the substrate, which would let current to flow through the whole substrate during the electro-plating process. After wire bonding, the whole substrate, together with the wire bonds, was cleaned in the nitride acid for around 10 minutes. When all the oxide residues on copper surface were cleaned away, the substrate was taken out and rinsed well with DI water. Then the substrate was subjected to electro-plating of nickel and silver, the plating procedures and parameters were the same with those used in the section of Flowability. The as-plated substrate was shown in Fig. 11-11 d). After electro-plating, all wire bonds were stripped off. Kapton tape (3.5 mil) was cut into small strips and applied on the substrate, as shown in Fig. 11-11 e). These Kapton tape stripes were used to control the distance between the chip and the substrate, and thus guarantee that the chip is parallel to the substrate. 95Pb5Sn solder preform (0.10 mm) was then cut into small squares (approximately 1.5 mm \times 1.5 mm) and applied under the four corners of the chip, as shown in Fig. 11-11 e). Finally, the chip was carefully placed on top, and the whole structure was subjected to vacuum solder reflow, with default reflow profile for 95Pb5Sn solder preform. Fig. 11-11 f) showed the as-fabricated test vehicle.

When encapsulating the test vehicle, each material was dropped on only one side of the chip and let freely flow to the other side. The flowing and the following curing processes were using the same parameters and equipments as those used in the section of Flowability. After encapsulating, wires were soldered to the substrate at points shown in Fig. 11-12. Since the back of silicon chip was coated with silver through E-beam, when the chip was soldered on the DBC substrate, the four corners of it would be electrically connected to the four blocks of copper that was in contact with solder preform, as shown in Fig. 11-11 e). Meanwhile, the four thin islands that were originally covered by Kapton tape spacers were insulated from the chip bottom by the encapsulant that was applied into the test vehicle. In this way, simply by attaching wires at each pair of the soldering points, the breakdown between the thin copper island and the chip could be achieved and the approximate dielectric strength of that test vehicle could be measured.

Fig. 11-12 Wires soldered to test vehicle. a) One pair of wires soldered to test vehicle; b) The solid dots, the stripe dots, and the blank dots represents the other three pairs of wires

ii) Results and discussions

To test the impact of voids and cracks lying in the encapsulation layer on the overall dielectric strength of the package, the test vehicle breakdown test was designed. Test vehicles encapsulated with Cyclotene 3022 (BCB), Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin, Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer, Nusil EPM 2422 silicone, and Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel were tested separately.

MasterSil 800 may require an injection molding system to fill a large-area gap (as shown above). Therefore, it's not included in this test due to the lack of processing facility.

It was very obvious that test vehicles encapsulated with Cyclotene 3022 and Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin had their dielectric strength relatively low, and the test results were also less consistent. In comparison with those two materials, Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer has much higher dielectric strength and the results were in good consistency. Table 11-3 compares the experimental dielectric strength of test vehicles with the dielectric strength of the corresponding material provided by the manufacturer. Clearly, the dielectric strengths of both Cyclotene 3022 and Nusil CF-4721 silicone resin were greatly reduced as they were applied as encapsulants, while the dielectric strength of Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer was retained.

These results suggested that curing-induced voids and cracks would not be favorable, because these processability problems would greatly impact on the overall dielectric behavior of the electronic package. As a result, soft, elastic materials that were low outgasing would be more suitable for encapsulation purpose.

Table 11-3 Dielectric strength of test vehicles encapsulated with Cyclotene 3022, Nusil CF-4721, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482

Material	Processability	Test Vehicle Dielectric Strength (kV/mm)	Theoretical Dielectric Strength (kV/mm)
Cyclotene 3022	Poor	6-8	530
Nusil CF-4721	Poor	8-10	19-30
Nusil R-2188	Good	~ 20.9	17.7
Nusil EPM 2422	Good	~20.0	21.7

Nusil EPM 2482	Good	~ 20.0	19-30
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5. Conclusions

Eight high-temperature encapsulants were surveyed for planar structure packages. In the processability test, Epo-Tek 600 and Epo-Tek 390 failed in the flowability test because Epo-Tek 600 had too high a viscosity (~160,000 cPs) and Epo-Tek 390 dried too fast (dried in five seconds), which prevented free flowing. Cyclotene 3022 and Nusil CF-4721 did not pass the curability test because Cyclotene 3022 induced voids under the die due to its approximately 40% outgassing, while Nusil CF-4721 cracked after curing due to its brittle nature. Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, Nusil EPM 2482, and MasterSil 800 exhibited low outgassing and formed soft, elastic matrices and thus passed the processability tests.

III.2. Dielectric Strength and Permittivity

Encapsulation materials generally assume the dielectric responsibility in the package, thus materials with high dielectric strength would be desired. This section presents the methodology for dielectric strength and dielectric constant test.

1. Methodology

The methodology involves constructing a planar capacitor with the material under test as the dielectrics with a known thickness. When voltage is applied to the capacitor, a voltage gradient that is almost distributed uniformly would be generated.

By measuring the capacitance of the planar capacitor, the permittivity of the dielectric material can be calculated:

$$C = \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 \frac{A}{d} \quad (11-3)$$

where, C – the capacitance;

A – the area of overlap of the two plates;

ϵ_r – the relative static permittivity of the dielectric material between the plates;

ϵ_0 – the electric constant ($\epsilon_0 \approx 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Fm}^{-1}$);

d – the separation between the plates.

With the same planar capacitor, when the voltage applied between the two plates is gradually increased, the dielectric material will finally breakdown. The voltage at which the dielectric breaks down is recorded as the breakdown voltage of the planar capacitor. Then the dielectric strength of the material can be calculated by dividing the breakdown voltage by the separation between the two plates.

$$E_{\text{max}} = \frac{V_B}{d} \quad (11-4)$$

where, E_{max} – the dielectric strength of the dielectric;

V_B – the breakdown voltage of the sample;

d – the thickness of the sample.

2. Permittivity and dielectric strength of Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800

i) Experiments

To build a planar capacitor, a 2' × 2' glass substrate (McMaster-Carr) was chosen to serve as the bottom plate. The Edwards 306 sputtering system was used to metalize the substrate with a Cr/Ni/Ag tri-layer. The materials were screen-printed onto Cr/Ni/Ag-metalized glass substrates and cured according to the curing profiles. The thickness of the screen-printed materials was controlled by Kapton® spacers to around 0.1 mm. Five silver electrodes were then sputtered onto the as-cured polymer, as shown in Fig. 11-13. In this way, the glass substrate metalized with Cr/Ni/Ag could serve as the bottom electrode, whereas the sputtered silver on the polymer film could serve as the top electrodes. Since one sample had five individual top electrodes and a shared bottom electrode, five tests could be performed on it. A Hipot mega-ohm meter 200B was used as the power supply, with its cathode and anode connected to one set of top and bottom electrodes at a time. The threshold current was set to around 1 mA. The permittivity test was conducted by measuring the capacitance of the sample between one set of top and bottom electrodes with an Agilent 4294A impedance analyzer. The oscillation level was set at 500 mV.

High-temperature dielectric performance was the part of most interest in this work. The encapsulants were brought to an elevated temperature for breakdown tests. It was expected that polymeric encapsulants would have worse performance at high temperature than at room temperature, although it was desired for the dielectric performance to be retained even at high temperatures. The sampling temperatures were 25°C, 100°C, 150°C, 200°C, and 250°C.

ii) Results and discussions

The dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil R-2188 are shown in Fig. 11-14, which clearly shows that both the dielectric strength and the permittivity decrease with increasing temperature. The dielectric strength drops from 34.5 kV/mm at 25°C to only 20.6 at 250°C, which represents a 40% degradation. Meanwhile, the permittivity decreases from 4.1 to 3.3 at 1 kHz and from 4.4 to 3.3 at 1 MHz.

The dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil 2422 are shown in Fig. 11-15. The dielectric strength and permittivity also decrease as the temperature increases. Throughout the temperature range of 25°C to 250°C, the dielectric strength decreased from 43.3 kV/mm at room temperature to 26.6 kV/mm at 250°C, indicating a 39% degradation. The permittivity of Nusil 2422 dropped from 4.3 to 3.3 at 1 kHz and 2.8 at 1 MHz.

Fig. 11-13 Top view of the sample for dielectric characterization

Fig. 11-14 Dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil R-2188

Fig. 11-15 Dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil 2422

The dielectric strength and permittivity of MasterSil 800 are shown in Fig. 11-16. The permittivity of MasterSil 800 is almost as twice as that of the other two silicone materials. (9 for MasterSil 800 at room temperature vs. approximately 4.5 for Nusil R-2188 and Nusil EPM 2422 at room temperature) The dielectric strength of MasterSil 800 at room temperature is lower than the other two silicone materials at least by a factor of two. Both permittivity and dielectric strength of MasterSil 800 silicone elastomer decrease with increasing temperature. Throughout the temperature range of 25°C to 250°C, the dielectric strength decreased from 16.9 kV/mm at room temperature to 7.9 kV/mm at 250°C, indicating a 53% degradation. The permittivity dropped from 9.5 to 7.0 at 1 kHz and 9.4 to 6.3 at 1 MHz.

Fig. 11-16 Dielectric strength and permittivity of MasterSil 800

3. Dielectric test of Nusil EPM 2482

i) Experiments

Nusil EPM 2482 is a silicone gel material, which is usually soft and tacky. A similar structure, which is shown in Fig. 11-17, was designed for Nusil EPM 2482, because the aforementioned testing structure may not be suitable for this material. Fig. 11-17 (a) shows the design of the upper electrode. Five electrodes with traces leading to the four corners were sputtered onto a clean glass substrate. The metallization was a tri-layer of Cr/Ni/Ag. The bottom electrode was fabricated with the same metallization on a glass substrate of the same size but with no pattern on it. The tester was assembled with the two electrodes facing each other, separated by four 150 μm glass spacers at each corner, as shown in Fig. 11-17 (b). The material was then flown from one of the four corners through the gap between the two substrates. After the gap was entirely filled, the structure with the material in it was cured according to the curing profile of Nusil EPM 2482.

After curing, the dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil EPM 2482 could be measured. Metal clamps were attached to the structure for electrical conduction, as shown in Fig. 11-17 (b). Between each top electrode and the shared bottom electrode, the dielectric strength and permittivity of Nusil EPM 2482 were planned to be measured with the Hipot mega-ohm meter 200B and Agilent impedance analyzer 4294A. An elevated temperature test, which is similar to that carried out for Nusil R-2188 and Nusil 2422, was also planned for this material.

However, it was observed that voids were formed between the two glass substrates one day after the material was cured, as shown in the following section. The test results would be inaccurate with the presence of voids, so this test method was not used for dielectric testing. Future research may involve modifying the current testing method for dielectric properties of Nusil EPM silicone gel.

Fig. 11-17 Tester for dielectric properties of Nusil EPM 2482: (a) design of the upper electrode; (b) assembled tester

To roughly check the dielectric strength of Nusil EPM 2482, a simple structure was designed, as shown in Fig. 11-18. A DBC substrate was etched into three independent islands. These islands served as electrodes in this structure. The first and the third electrodes were wire-bonded together, resulting in a small distance between the bonded wire and the central electrode. When voltage was applied between one of the side electrodes and the central one, the air between the bonded wire and the central electrode would finally break down as the voltage increased. The bonded wire was gently pushed toward the central electrode. For a gap of about 100 μm , the breakdown voltage was approximately 800 V.

Fig. 11-18 Design of the sample for dielectric strength measurement for Nusil EPM 2482

After the tester was encapsulated with Nusil EPM 2482, voltage was again applied between one of the side islands and the central island. A voltage of 1.2 kV was applied at 25°C, 100°C, 150°C, 200°C, and 250°C for approximately 1 minute. If no failure in the material was observed, the voltage applied was increased by 200 V. The same tests were repeated until the material was broken down or until 2 kV was reached (the dielectric strength of silicone material is generally 19 kV/mm -30 kV/mm at room temperature, and decreases at higher temperatures).

ii) Results and discussions

It was observed that voids were formed between the two glass substrates one day after the material was cured, as shown in Fig. 11-19. These voids were possibly caused by slow volume shrinkage after curing – silicone gels tend to gradually lose moisture and monomers after curing [18]. In this structure, a very thin layer of material (0.1 mm) was spread out over a large area (around 5 cm × 5 cm) between two parallel plates. Since the two surfaces of Nusil EPM 2482 were both constrained by the metalized glass substrate, the flexibility of this material was greatly limited by the low aspect ratio. As a result, the shrinkage at the central area would not be accommodated by deformations in the material matrix. Instead, as moisture and monomers diffused out, separation within material matrix was observed. Thus, the dielectric properties of Nusil EPM 2482 were not characterized in this way. Also, Nusil EPM 2482's capability of encapsulating large-area plane-bonded module would be questionable, which is planned to be further investigated in future research.

Fig. 11-19 Tester for dielectric properties of Nusil EPM 2482 – one day after curing

For Nusil 2482, the gap (shown in Fig. 11-18) that originally broke down at only around 800 V survived 2 kV throughout the temperature range of 25°C - 250°C once it was encapsulated. The test results are compared in Fig. 11-20.

Fig. 11-20 Comparison of the breakdown voltages of air and Nusil EPM 2482 over the same thin gap

4. Conclusions

In the dielectric property test, within the temperature range of 25°C - 250°C, both the dielectric strength and the permittivity of all three materials (Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800) decreased with increasing temperature. Nusil R-2188 had its dielectric strength dropped from around 34.5 kV/mm to 20.6 kV/mm, representing 40% degradation. Also, dielectric constant of Nusil R-2188 at 1 KHz and 1 MHz within the same temperature range exhibited roughly 30% degradation. Nusil EPM 2422 degraded 39% in dielectric strength from 43.4 kV/mm to 26.6 kV/mm and degraded roughly 42% in dielectric permittivity. MasterSil 800 degraded 53% in dielectric strength from 16.9 kV/mm to 7.9 kV/mm and degraded around 33% in dielectric permittivity.

Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel was also proven to have relatively high dielectric strength (more than twice of the dielectric strength of the air) throughout the temperature range of 25°C -250°C.

III.3. Dielectric Performance of Encapsulated Modules

1. Methodology

Encapsulants in a power module is expected to protect the module from early breakdown resulted from the low dielectric strength of air. To investigate the dielectric performance of encapsulated module, a high voltage is purposely applied across a thin gap of approximately 100 μm . The dielectric materials in the gap will be finally broke down as the voltage increases. In this test, the breakdown voltage of encapsulated and non-encapsulated module is compared to prove the dielectric performance of encapsulants.

As stated previously, MasterSil 800 may require an injection molding system to fill a large-area gap. Therefore, it's not included in this test due to the lack of processing facility.

2. Assembly and Encapsulation of Wire-Bonded Power Module

i) Experiments

To prove the dielectric capability of each encapsulant in a real package, a power module was fabricated with three Cree SiC diodes in series. A wire-bonded structure was chosen here because the top surfaces of the diodes were not solderable. The voltage rating of each diode was 600 V. With three of these diodes in series, the total voltage drop within the package would be 1800 V. A patterned direct-bonded copper (DBC) was used as the substrate. The DBC substrate was electro-less plated with silver before diodes were attached to it with sintered silver

joint. After the die-attaching process, the three diodes were connected in series, as shown in Fig. 11-21.

To better reveal the dielectric properties of the encapsulants, the negative electrode was intentionally designed to be under the wire bond connected to the positive electrode and the anode of the left diode. Reverse voltage was then applied between the two electrodes of the module via a Tektronix 371B curve tracer. The bonded wire that was connected to the positive electrode was pushed closer to the negative electrode until the air broke down at a voltage of around 900 V.

Fig. 11-21 Module with three diodes in series

After this, each module was encapsulated with one of the three materials. To encapsulate the module, two drops (around 0.05 ml per drop) of material were used (Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482 were used for each module) to encapsulate the wire bond at the location where air breakdown occurred, as shown in Fig. 11-22. Vacuum was employed to remove any air that was trapped in the un-cured encapsulant. Each encapsulant was then cured according to the curing profile recommended by the respective manufacturers. Reverse voltage was again applied between the positive and negative electrodes. The breakdown voltage of the encapsulated module was expected to be around 1800 V, which three times the breakdown voltage of each diode.

ii) Results and discussions

Fig. 11-22 Encapsulated module with three diodes in series

After the three wire-bonded power modules were encapsulated with Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482 (shown in Fig. 11-22), a reverse voltage was applied between the positive and negative electrodes of each module.

The module encapsulated with Nusil R-2188 survived its rated voltage, 1.8 kV, throughout the whole temperature range discussed in this paper: - 25°C to 250°C.

The same phenomenon was also observed for the power modules encapsulated with Nusil EPM 2422 and Nusil EPM 2482. These results indicate that all these three materials, Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer, Nusil EPM 2422 silicone, and Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel, could successfully protect a real wire-bonded power module from early breakdown caused by air.

3. Assembly and encapsulation of planar-bonded power module

i) Experiments

To investigate the dielectric capability of each encapsulant in a planar power package, a planar module was designed with a dummy device incorporated in the bottom substrate. A DBC substrate was etched into a pattern that was similar to a regular chip, as shown in Fig. 11-23. The pattern created an anode and an extended guard ring around it. On one side of the guard ring, there was an anode terminal, which was later connected to the anode with another un-patterned DBC substrate. Both DBC substrates were electro-less plated with silver.

Fig. 11-23 DBC substrate patterned into a dummy chip

The anode and the anode terminal were shorted together via the upper DBC substrate, as shown in Fig. 11-24 and Fig. 11-25. Sintered silver was used to form all joints so that the module could be tested at 250°C.

The desired breakdown voltage of the module was specified at 1200 V, which was the rated voltage of the IGBTs used in hybrid electric vehicles. To compare the breakdown voltages of the modules with and without encapsulation, the gap between the two DBC substrates was set at 0.1 mm, since at this thickness air was observed to breakdown at 800 V. The 0.1 mm gap was achieved by controlling the thickness of the bond line between the lower and upper DBC substrates. Two samples with each type of encapsulant were tested to prove the repeatability of the experiment results.

Fig. 11-24 Cross-section of the planar power module

Fig. 11-25 Assembled module with two DBC substrates

ii) Results and discussions

With a pre-set voltage rating of 1.2 kV, the planar-structure modules encapsulated with different materials were investigated to discover their behavior at high temperatures. Results indicate that Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and Nusil EPM 2482 could all support 1.2 kV within the temperature range of 25°C - 250°C. Therefore, in terms of dielectrics, all three of these materials (Nusil R-2188 silicone elastomer, Nusil EPM 2422 silicone, and Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel) are suitable for encapsulating planar-structure power modules.

The reverse voltage characteristics of the wire-bonded and the planar-bonded modules are summarized in Table 11-4.

Table 11-4 Reverse characteristics of wire-bonded and planar-bonded modules with and without encapsulation

Material	Voltage Supported (25°C - 250°C)			
	Wire-bonded Module		Planar-bonded Module	
	With encapsulant	Without encapsulant	With encapsulant	Without encapsulant
Nusil R-2188	> 1800 V	800 – 900V	>1200 V	~ 800 V
Nusil EPM 2422	> 1800 V	800 – 900V	>1200 V	~ 800 V
Nusil EPM 2482	> 1800 V	800 – 900V	>1200 V	~ 800 V

4. Conclusions

From the electrical point of view, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 were all proven to be suitable for high-temperature, high-power packaging. From 25°C - 250°C, the three materials all successfully protected the wire-bonded power module until the rated voltage (1.8 kV) was achieved. In the planar power module, it was proven that all these three materials could support a voltage drop of 1.2 kV across the thin gap that would otherwise break down at 800 V in air.

III.4. Impact of Thermal Aging on Encapsulants

1. Methodology

High-temperature encapsulants needed to be capable of working at a temperature of 250°C or higher. When polymeric encapsulants were subjected to prolonged heating, however, a certain amount of degradation usually occurred. Therefore, it's possible that dielectric properties varied with respect to thermal aging time.

In this section, materials that had passed the processability test were aged at 250°C for up to four weeks, with the sampling points as three days, one week, two weeks, and four weeks. Changes in permittivity and dielectric strength were monitored.

2. Impact of thermal aging of dielectric performances

i) Experiments

Samples structured as shown in Fig. 11-13 were also used for aging. After being assembled, the samples were placed in the Isotemp Programmable Muffle Furnace (Fisher Scientifics), the soaking temperature of which was set to 250°C. Two thermocouples hung inside the furnace to monitor the temperatures close to the ceiling and the floor indicated that the temperature variation was within $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

ii) Results and discussions

This section was interested in the thermal aging effect on encapsulants' dielectric properties because thermal aging was expected to weaken the material.

In the aging test, it was observed that the heating process hardened the materials, resulting in visible cracks in Nusil R-2188 and Nusil EPM 2422, as shown in Fig. 11-26.

Fig. 11-26 Cracks in aged samples, (a) Nusil R-2188 after 28-day aging; (b) Nusil EPM 2422 after 14-day aging

During thermal aging, the network structure of polymers might be weakened by decomposition and evaporation of the chemical. The decomposition and evaporation could result in a more densified matrix with less cohesion among the oligomers. The densification might explain the hardening effect, while the loss of cohesion might explain the cracking behavior.

The change in dielectric strength and permittivity with respect to thermal aging time is shown in Fig. 11-27 and Fig. 11-28. Nusil R-2188 had its dielectric strength stable within 14 days of aging at 250°C and then dropped from around 33 kV/mm to 13 kV/mm. Nusil EPM 2422 exhibited the most significant drop in its dielectric strength. Within three days of aging, the dielectric strength dropped from 43.4 kV/mm to roughly 11 kV/mm, and the value kept dropping slowly as the aging proceeded. MasterSil 800 also exhibited a significant drop from around 15 kV/mm to around 5 kV/mm in dielectric strength within three days of aging.

One reason for the sudden drop in dielectric strength was the cracking behavior observed in the aging process. As soon as the cracking occurred, the dielectric strength decreased significantly. This might explain the sudden drop in dielectric strength of Nusil R-2188 and Nusil EPM 2422. For MasterSil 800, although no cracking was observed, the dielectric strength was also reduced to only around 5 kV/mm. This was more likely due to compositional or structural

change in the material matrix during the aging process. Chemical and microstructural analysis on the aged samples will be conducted in the future, so as to better understand the impact of thermal aging.

Permittivity of Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 appeared slowly dropped with respect to thermal aging. Compared with dielectric strength, permittivities of Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 appeared much more stable. Nusil R-2188 had its permittivity dropped from 4.2 to 3.8 in 28 days, representing a 9% drop. Nusil EPM 2422 had its permittivity dropped from 4.2 to 3.0, representing a 29% drop. MasterSil 800 had a variation of 26% in permittivity, with the lowest value observed at 7 days.

Fig. 11-27 Dielectric strength of Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 with respect to aging time

Fig. 11-28 Dielectric strength of Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 with respect to aging time

3. Conclusions

In the thermal aging test, the Nusil R-2188 sample cracked after being aged at 250°C for four weeks, resulting in a dramatic drop in its dielectric strength. Nusil EPM 2422 cracked after just three days of aging at 250°C, which significantly decreased its dielectric strength from 43.3 kV/mm to only 9.7 kV/mm. MasterSil 800 exhibited no cracking within the four weeks of aging, yet its dielectric strength still dropped from 15 kV/mm to only 5 kV/mm. The dramatic drop in dielectric strength was possibly a result of matrix cracking or changes in material composition and microstructure. The permittivities of the three materials appeared to be more stable with respect to aging time. The permittivity of Nusil R-2188 dropped only 7% in permittivity from 4.3 to 3.8, that of Nusil EPM 2422 dropped 29%, and that of MasterSil 800 dropped 26%. In the

future, the degradation behavior will be more carefully investigated through chemical analysis and microstructural analysis. The results may help better understand the degradation process.

IV. Conclusions

Eight high-temperature encapsulants were surveyed for planar structure packages. In the processability test, Epo-Tek 600 and Epo-Tek 390 failed in the flowability test because Epo-Tek 600 had too high a viscosity (~160,000 cPs) and Epo-Tek 390 dried too fast (dried in five seconds), which prevented free flowing. Cyclotene 3022 and Nusil CF-4721 did not pass the curability test because Cyclotene 3022 induced voids under the die due to its approximately 40% outgassing, while Nusil CF-4721 cracked after curing due to its brittle nature. Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, Nusil EPM 2482, and MasterSil 800 exhibited low outgassing and formed soft, elastic matrices and thus passed the processability tests.

In the dielectric property test, within the temperature range of 25°C - 250°C, both the dielectric strength and the permittivity of all three materials (Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800) decreased with increasing temperature. Nusil R-2188 had its dielectric strength dropped from around 34.5 kV/mm to 20.6 kV/mm, representing 40% degradation. Also, dielectric constant of Nusil R-2188 at 1 KHz and 1 MHz within the same temperature range exhibited roughly 30% degradation. Nusil EPM 2422 degraded 39% in dielectric strength from 43.4 kV/mm to 26.6 kV/mm and degraded roughly 42% in dielectric permittivity. MasterSil 800 degraded 53% in dielectric strength from 16.9 kV/mm to 7.9 kV/mm and degraded around 33% in dielectric permittivity. Nusil EPM 2482 silicone gel was also proven to have relatively high dielectric strength (more than twice of the dielectric strength of the air) throughout the temperature range of 25°C -250°C.

In the electrical breakdown test, Nusil R-2188, Nusil EPM 2422, and MasterSil 800 were all proven to be suitable for high-temperature, high-power packaging. From 25°C - 250°C, the three materials all successfully protected the wire-bonded power module until the rated voltage (1.8 kV) was achieved. In the planar power module, it was proven that all these three materials could support a voltage drop of 1.2 kV across the thin gap that would otherwise break down at 800 V in air.

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Part IV

Analysis and Design of a Dual-Active-Bridge DC/DC Converter

Chapter 12 TOPOLOGY STUDY AND DAB ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

I. Introduction

I.1. Technical Objectives

The objective of this chapter is to design a methodology for the final SiC-based converter design. The key to optimization is to establish the relationships of the cost functions with design conditions, constraints, and parameters. For a certain application, many different topologies can be used. The tradeoff between various topologies should consider their impact on device rating requirement, need for passive energy storage elements, control feasibility. The relationships required for conducting such trade off and comparison needs to be developed, including ripples, losses, and even control strategies. This chapter is trying to start the study on the systematic way of study a topology for comparison and optimized design. But the SiC-based devices have the potential to work at high power simultaneously at high switching frequency. At this operating condition, the non-ideal effects of the components and the control effect should be taken into the consideration. The design procedure in this chapter combining with the previous modeling works shown in previous chapters should provide enough confidence to design the final converter without design, construction, debug, redesign iteration.

I.2. Technical Approach

For further optimization between different topologies. A certain topology – Dual Active Bridge (DAB) – is analyzed and a prototype converter is designed to study the optimization process of a certain kind of converter. The modulation scheme and soft switching criteria are studied to look into the influence on the power stage design. During design, each part is firstly selected by calculation utilizing general used models. Then detailed device models are involved in the simulation to verify the calculation. The comparison of the two results of calculation and simulations shows that high switching frequency caused non-ideality makes the general used model not accurate enough for the design. Models including device detail must be used for the correct design. Especially for the high power density designs where only small margin is left.

II. Literature Survey

Full-bridge circuits usually have lower current stress and are suitable for high power application. This survey explores three topologies with full bridges on both side of the isolation transformer.

II.1. Isolated Buck-Boost Converters

Fig. 12-1 shows the topology of an isolated buck-boost converter that connects a voltage-fed full bridge to one side of the transformer, and a current-fed full bridge on the other side. When operating in buck mode, energy flows from the voltage-fed side to the current-fed side. The current-fed side bridge works as a synchronous rectifier. The switches in the phase leg have opposite gate signals, and both work at a 50% duty cycle. By phase shifting the gate signals of the two phase legs on the voltage-fed side, the leading phase leg switches operate under zero voltage switching (ZVS) conditions and the lagging phase leg switches operate

under zero current switching (ZCS) conditions. The amount of energy that flows to the output side is controlled by the phase shift angle of the two phase leg gate signals.

Fig. 12-1 Isolated buck-boost converter

When operating in boost mode, energy flows from the current-fed side to the voltage-fed side. The bridge's switch pairs that are in diagonal positions operate at a duty cycle larger than 0.5. The dc inductor L is charged during the overlapping period when four bridge switches are on, and discharged when one diagonal switch pair is turned off. In boost mode, if the output capacitor voltage is not high enough, the circuit lacks soft-switching capability and cannot start by itself. In addition, transient voltage occurs on the switches on the current fed side because of the leakage inductance of the transformer. There are some possible solutions for these problems, but all the solutions require additional components and control, which add to the complexity and lower the power density of the converter.

II.2. Series Resonant Converters (SRC)

The series resonant converter has two voltage-fed full bridges connected to a resonant tank with a transformer serially connected to the resonant loop for isolation. The topology of the SRC is shown in Fig. 12-2. The operation of the converter is symmetric when energy flows bi-directionally.

Fig. 12-2 Series resonant converter

Usually, the load-side bridge operates as a synchronous rectifier. The source-side bridge generates a square wave, which will excite a sinusoidal current in the resonant tank. The amount of energy that flows to the load side is controlled by the frequency of the square wave or the duty cycle of the square wave [1].

The SRC can also be operated as two full bridges generating a 50% duty cycle square wave on each side of the resonant tank. The power flow is controlled by the phase shift of the two square waves [2]. More power is circulating between the source and the load when operating in this mode.

For all the operating modes, the SRC topology can achieve ZVS when operating above the resonant frequency, but the ZVS condition is limited by the load. At light load, the resonant current is not enough to complete the ZVS procedure.

The disadvantage of this topology is that it has a high-current and high-voltage resonant capacitor that is bulky. It usually also requires a large resonant inductor, but when operating at a high frequency, the transformer leakage inductance can be utilized as the resonant inductor.

II.3. Dual Active Bridges (DAB)

The DAB topology shown in Fig. 12-3 was first introduced in the 1980's [4]. It has two full bridges on the two sides of the transformer. The leakage inductance of the transformer is used as an energy storage and transfer component. It operates at a fixed frequency. Each full bridge generates a 50% duty cycle square wave with a certain phase shift. The energy flows from the leading side to the lagging side. The amount of energy is controlled by the phase shift angle. With this modulation scheme, the topology naturally has ZVS capability for both bridges. Similar to the series resonant topology, it suffers hard switching while operating at very light load condition.

Fig. 12-3 Dual active bridge converter

Because the DAB topology fully utilizes the parasitic, it usually has the smallest magnetic components weight [3],[5] and is widely used as an isolation stage [6],[7]. For these reasons, it is selected as the baseline design for further study and comparison.

III. Dual Active Bridge Converter Topology Study

III.1. Modulation Scheme

To balance the stress on the switching device, the converter is usually controlled following these guidelines:

- The two switches in one phase leg are driven by complementary 50% duty cycle gate signals.
- The two phase legs in one bridge are controlled with a certain phase shift to control the duty cycle of the quasi-square wave.
- The two bridges are controlled so that the quasi-square wave on the terminals of the transformer has a phase shift that can control the energy flow.

The original modulation scheme proposed in [4] is a 50% duty cycle phase shifted square wave as shown in Fig. 12-4:

Fig. 12-4 Waveform of original modulation for DAB converter

The operation can be analyzed in the time domain. The switches that are on in each time slot are listed in Table 12-1:

Table 12-1 On-state switches in different time slots

t_0-t_1	t_1-t_2	t_2-t_3	t_3-t_4
s1, s4, s6, s7	s1, s4, s5, s8	s2, s3, s5, s8	s2, s3, s6, s7

The leakage inductor current i_p as a function of time is:

During time $[t_0-t_1]$:

$$i_p(t) = \frac{v_i + v_o'}{L} (t - t_0) + i(t_0) \quad (12-1)$$

where $i_p(t_0)$ is the initial current at time t_0 , and v_o' is the output side voltage that is reflected on the input side of the transformer.

During time $[t_1-t_2]$:

$$i_p(t) = \frac{v_i + v_o'}{L} (t - t_1) + i(t_1) \quad (12-2)$$

Since the current wave form is symmetric, $i(t_2) = -i(t_0)$

Then $i(t_0)$ can be solved to be:

$$i(t_0) = \frac{\pi(v_i - v_o') + 2\theta v_o'}{2\omega L} \quad (12-3)$$

where $\theta = 2\pi t_1/T_s$ is the phase shift angle, and $\omega = 2\pi/T_s$, T_s is switching period.

The output current is the average value of the inductor current during t_1 and t_3 :

$$i_o = \frac{v_i \theta (\pi - \theta)}{\pi \omega L} \quad (12-4)$$

The input current is the average value of the inductor current during t_0 and t_2 :

$$i_i = \frac{v_o' \theta (\pi - \theta)}{\pi \omega L} \quad (12-5)$$

The average power flowing from input to output is

$$P = \frac{v_i v_o' \theta (\pi - \theta)}{\pi \omega L} \quad (12-6)$$

The output voltage is controlled by controlling the power flow to the output side.

The original scheme has a lot of reactive power, especially during a heavy load. A method to improve the efficiency is proposed in [8]. The main idea is to short the transformer by controlling the output bridge when the secondary current starts to draw power from the output. The waveform of its operation is shown in Fig. 12-5.

When the inductor current reaches zero, the transformer's secondary winding is shorted until the controlled phase shift angle is θ .

With steps similar to those used in the analyses of the original scheme, from the constraint $i(\beta) = 0$, the value of β can be solved:

$$\beta = \frac{(1-d)\pi + d\theta}{2+d} \quad (12-7)$$

where $d = \frac{nv_o}{v_i}$ is defined as voltage gain of the converter.

The output power of the controlled circuit is:

$$P = \frac{dv_i^2}{2(2+d)^2 \omega L} \left((1+d-2d^2)\pi + 4(1+d+d^2)\pi\theta - 2(2+2d+d^2)\theta^2 \right) \quad (12-8)$$

Fig. 12-5 Waveform of modulation scheme in [7]

The output power vs. phase shift angle of the two control methods when $d = 1$ are shown in Fig. 12-6.

Fig. 12-6 Output power vs. phase shift angle for two modulation schemes

It can be seen that the maximum power delivered is decreased by this method.

Because the original modulation scheme can only achieve ZVS in a limited range, several methods [9]-[11] are proposed to extend the soft switching region. Their main idea is to decrease the duty cycle of the square wave with phase shift angle control to manipulate the inductor current to be a form that is good for ZVS. When $d > 1$, the secondary side duty cycle is decreased. When $d < 1$, the primary side duty cycle is decreased. Fig. 12-7 shows the operating waveform of this kind of method:

(a) $d > 1$, external mode, (b) $d > 1$, internal mode, (c) $d < 1$, external mode, (d) $d < 1$, internal mode

Fig. 12-7 Modulation scheme to extend ZVS region

For a certain operating point, a pre-calculated γ is usually used, and the power flow is controlled by the phase shift angle θ . For example, in [11], γ is set to be $d\pi$ when $d < 1$, or π/d when $d > 1$; in [9] and [10] look-up tables are used for γ .

In some specific applications, the switching current is so large that the turn-off loss is more significant than the turn-on loss. A modulation scheme to reduce the turn-off current is proposed in [12] and [13]. Its working waveforms in accordance with the output power are shown in Fig. 12-8.

Fig. 12-8 Modulation scheme to achieve ZCS

For a heavier load, the trapezoidal current mode is used. The currents at t_0 , t_3 , t_4 , t_7 and t_8 are controlled to be zero, and so at these time points the switches act under ZCS. The switches act at other time points are under ZVS. For lighter loads, the triangular current mode is used. The currents at t_0 , t_2 , t_3 , t_5 and t_6 are controlled to be zero, so the switches act at these time points are under ZCS. The switches act at other time points are under ZVS. Although the turn-on procedure on t_4 and t_6 of the trapezoidal current mode t_3 and t_6 for the triangular current mode is completed with zero current flow into the switches, the energy stored in the junction capacitors is lost during the procedure.

III.2. Soft Switching Region Analysis

The DAB converters are usually controlled to let all the switches be under ZVS except the modulation scheme in [12] and [13]. The control method lets several switches act under ZCS and the other switches under ZVS. For this scheme, the ZCS requirement is satisfied by the control. The ZVS requirement is easy to meet due to its high current application. The soft switching region of that scheme is not discussed in this section. For other modulations, the

voltage on the primary and secondary winding of the transformer can be drawn as a unified waveform, as illustrated in Fig. 12-9. It is required that $0 \leq \alpha, \gamma \leq \pi/2$, and $0 \leq \tau \leq \pi$. For the range $0 \leq \alpha, \gamma \leq \pi/2$, $\pi/2 < \tau \leq \pi$, there is always a combination in $0 \leq \alpha, \gamma \leq \pi/2$ and $0 \leq \tau \leq \pi/2$ that outputs the same average current but with less circulating power. So the range $0 \leq \alpha, \gamma \leq \pi/2$ and $\pi/2 < \tau \leq \pi$ is not used. Different modulation schemes correspond to different additional constraints on α , τ and γ .

Fig. 12-9 Unified modulation waveform

A. Ideal Case Analysis

In an ideal case, the energy stored in the junction capacitors and snubber capacitors is ignored, and the magnetizing inductance of the transformer is considered to be infinite. In this case, only the direction of a phase leg's output current is required for the phase leg to switch under ZVS. Fig. 12-10 shows the circuit of a phase leg. The capacitor shown in the figure is the sum of the junction capacitors and the snubber capacitor if there is one in the design. The switch symbol is only the resistive part of a device.

Fig. 12-10 Circuit of a phase leg

It is easy to see that when current commutates from the bottom switch to the top switch, the output current I should be less than zero to charge the bottom capacitor and to discharge the top capacitor and finally let the top diode conduct before the top switch is turned on to reach ZVS. Similarly, the output current should be greater than zero when the current commutates from the top switch to the bottom one.

With this requirement, the value of the transformer's primary-side current as defined in Fig. 12-3 at the different times shown in Fig. 12-4 should be:

$$i_p(t_0) < 0, i_p(t_1) > 0, i_p(t_2) > 0, i_p(t_3) < 0 \quad (12-9)$$

For the conventional modulation scheme, the relationship among α , τ and γ are: $\alpha = \pi/2$, $\gamma = \pi/2$ and $0 \leq \tau \leq \pi/2$. The ZVS boundary is solved to be:

$$\tau > \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right) \quad \text{for the input bridge, and} \quad (12-10)$$

$$\tau > \frac{\pi}{2} (1-d) \quad \text{for the output bridge} \quad (12-11)$$

The ZVS operating region drawn on the output current vs. voltage gain plane is shown in Fig. 12-11.

Fig. 12-11 Soft-switching region of conventional modulation scheme in ideal case

For the modulation scheme shown in Fig. 12-5, the relations among α , τ and γ are: $\tau = \pi - (1+d)\gamma$, $\alpha = \pi/2$. The ZVS boundary is solved to be:

$$\tau > \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right) \quad \text{for the input bridge, and} \quad (12-12)$$

$$\tau > \frac{\pi}{2}(1-d) \text{ for the output bridge} \tag{12-13}$$

Although the phase shift angle limit is the same here as in the conventional modulation, the output current range is changed. The ZVS operating region drawn on the output current vs. voltage gain plane is shown in Fig. 12-12.

Fig. 12-12 Soft-switching region of modulation scheme in Fig. 5 in ideal case

Table 12-2 lists the ZVS boundaries for all possible combinations of α , τ and γ that will control power to flow from primary to secondary.

Table 12-2 ZVS boundaries of different α , τ and γ combinations

α , τ and γ relation	ZVS boundary
$\tau - \gamma < -\alpha$, $\alpha < \tau + \gamma < \pi - \alpha$	$\alpha \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right) < \tau < \alpha \left(\frac{1}{d} - 1\right), \alpha < d\gamma$
$-\alpha < \tau - \gamma < \alpha$, $\tau + \gamma < \alpha$	$\gamma(1-d) < \tau < \gamma(d-1), \alpha > d\gamma$
$-\alpha < \tau - \gamma < \alpha$, $\alpha < \tau + \gamma < \pi - \alpha$	always hard switched
$-\alpha < \tau - \gamma < \alpha$, $\pi - \alpha < \tau + \gamma < \pi + \alpha$	$\tau > (1-d)\gamma, \tau > \alpha \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right), \tau > \pi - (1+d)\gamma, \tau > \pi - \alpha \left(1 + \frac{1}{d}\right)$
$\alpha < \tau - \gamma < \pi - \alpha$	always hard switched

$\alpha < \tau + \gamma < \pi - \alpha$	
---	--

From Table 12-2 only three mode can achieve ZVS. This three mode are summarized in Fig. 12-13 and Table 12-3.

Fig. 12-13 Waveforms of different operational modes

Table 12-3 Basic equations of DAB converter

	Waveform mode		
	a	b	c
$i_{lp}(t_0)$	$-\alpha + (\tau + \alpha)d$	$-\alpha + d\gamma$	$-\alpha + d(\pi - \alpha - \tau)$
$i_{lp}(t_1)$	$-\alpha + \gamma d$	$\tau - \gamma + d\gamma$	$\tau - \gamma + d\gamma$
$i_{lp}(t_2)$	$\alpha + (\tau - \alpha)d$	$\alpha - d\gamma$	$\alpha + d(\tau - \alpha)$
$i_{lp}(t_3)$	$\alpha - \gamma d$	$\tau + \gamma - d\gamma$	$\pi - \tau - \gamma - d\gamma$
Output current	$2d\alpha\tau / \pi$	$2d\gamma\tau / \pi$	$\frac{d(2\pi(\alpha + \gamma + \tau) - 2(\alpha^2 + \gamma^2 + \tau^2) - \pi^2)}{2\pi}$
Primary device rms current	$\sqrt{\frac{3\alpha^2\pi + 2\alpha^3(d-2) + 6d\alpha(-\pi\gamma + \gamma^2 + \tau^2) + 3d^2\gamma^2(3\pi - 4\gamma)}{6\pi}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{-4\alpha^3 - 6\alpha d\pi\gamma + 3\alpha^2(\pi + 2d\gamma) + d\gamma(6\tau^2 + 3d\pi\gamma + 2\gamma^2(1-2d))}{6\pi}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{-4\alpha^3 - 3\alpha d\pi(\pi - 2\tau) + 3\alpha^2(\pi + d\pi - 2d\tau) + d(\pi^3 - 3\pi^2(\gamma + \tau) + 3\pi((1+d)\gamma^2 + 2\gamma\tau + \tau^2) - 2(2d\gamma^3 + 3\gamma^2\tau + \tau^3))}{6\pi}}$

$d = nV_o/V_i$ is voltage gain. Currents are normalized to: $V_i/\omega L$. Powers are normalized to: $V_i^2/\omega L$

By appropriately selecting α , τ and γ for a certain output current at a certain voltage gain, the ZVS region can be theoretically extended to the first quadrant of the voltage gain vs. output current plane.

For example, when $d > 1$, at full load, let $\alpha = \gamma = \pi/2$ and control τ for output current until $\tau = \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right)$. Then keep $\alpha = \pi/2$ and $\tau = \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d}\right)$ and decrease γ to further decrease the current. When γ is decreased to $\frac{\pi}{2d}$, keep $\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2d}$ and $\alpha = \pi/2$ then continue to decrease τ to decrease the output current to zero. When $d < 1$, at full load, let $\alpha = \gamma = \pi/2$ and control τ for the output current until $\tau = \frac{\pi}{2} (1 - d)$. Then keep $\gamma = \pi/2$ and $\tau = \frac{\pi}{2} (1 - d)$ and decrease α to further decrease the current. When α is decreased to $\frac{d\pi}{2}$, keep $\alpha = \frac{d\pi}{2}$ and $\gamma = \pi/2$ then continue to decrease τ to decrease the output current to zero. When $d = 1$, just keep $\alpha = \gamma = \pi/2$ and ZVS occur on the whole output current range.

B. Influence of Junction Capacitor

If the energy stored in the junction capacitors cannot be ignored, a minimal current in the leakage inductance is required to complete the ZVS commutation procedure. To study the influence of the junction capacitors, some assumptions are made:

- No new commutation starts before the previous commutation is finished.
- Primary side switches do not commute at the same time as the secondary switches, so the bridge that is not commutating and the transformer can be modeled as a voltage source. In the analyses, v_1 is the commutating-side voltage source, and v_2 is the equivalent voltage source of the non-commutating side voltage source and the transformer.

The commutation can be divided into three cases.

Case 1 is when four switches of a bridge act together, as shown in Fig. 12-14.

Fig. 12-14 Equivalent circuit for four switches of a bridge commutate together

Taking the left phase leg commutating from the top switch to the bottom switch and the right phase leg commutating from the bottom switch to the top switch as an example, equations can be written from the circuit:

$$i_L = 2C \frac{dv}{dt} \quad (12-14)$$

$$i_1 = 0 \quad (12-15)$$

During the commutation, the energy delivered from the passives to the voltage sources are:

$$E_{deliver} = \int v_2 i_L dt - \int v_1 i_1 dt = \int 2Cv_2 \frac{dv}{dt} dt = 2Cv_2 \int dv \quad (12-16)$$

The voltage v change is v_1 during the whole commutation, so:

$$E_{deliver} = 2Cv_2 v_1 \quad (12-17)$$

The sum of the energy stored in the capacitors does not change in the process. All the energy is provided by the inductor. If the commutation starts with the minimal amount of current in the inductor, the current reaches zero at the end of the procedure. Then:

$$E_{deliver} = \frac{1}{2} Li_{L_min}^2 \quad \text{and} \quad (12-18)$$

$$i_{L_min}^2 = 4v_1 v_2 C / L \quad (12-19)$$

For the commutation in the reverse direction, the same result can be obtained by the same process.

Case 2 is when one phase leg commutates to short transformer winding. The equivalent circuit for this case is shown in Fig. 12-15. The commutation is from the top switch to the bottom switch.

Fig. 12-15 Equivalent circuit when switches in only one phase leg of a bridge commutate

Equations can be written from the circuit:

$$i_L = 2C \frac{dv}{dt}, \text{ and} \quad (12-20)$$

$$i_1 = C \frac{dv}{dt} \quad (12-21)$$

During the commutation, the energy delivered from the passives to the voltage sources are:

$$E_{deliver} = \int v_2 i_L dt - \int v_1 i_1 dt = \int 2Cv_2 \frac{dv}{dt} dt - \int Cv_1 \frac{dv}{dt} dt = 2Cv_2 \int dv - Cv_1 \int dv \quad (12-22)$$

The voltage v change is v_1 during the whole commutation, so:

$$E_{deliver} = 2Cv_2v_1 - Cv_1^2 \quad (12-23)$$

As in Case 1, the sum of the energy stored in the capacitors does not change in the process. All the energy is provided by the inductor. If the commutation starts with the minimal amount of current in the inductor, at the end of the procedure, the current reaches zero. Then:

$$E_{deliver} = \frac{1}{2} Li_{L_min}^2 \quad (12-24)$$

$$i_{L_min}^2 = (4Cv_2v_1 - 2Cv_1^2) / L \quad (12-25)$$

Case 3 is when one phase leg commutates to apply the bus voltage to the transformer winding. The equivalent circuit is the same as that shown in Fig. 12-15 except that the commutation is from the bottom switch to the top switch.

Equations can be written for this circuit:

$$i_L = 2C \frac{dv}{dt}, \text{ and} \quad (12-26)$$

$$i_1 = C \frac{dv}{dt} \quad (12-27)$$

During the commutation, the energy delivered from the passives to the voltage sources are:

$$E_{deliver} = \int v_2 i_L dt - \int v_1 i_1 dt = \int 2Cv_2 \frac{dv}{dt} dt - \int Cv_1 \frac{dv}{dt} dt = 2Cv_2 \int dv - Cv_1 \int dv \quad (12-28)$$

The voltage v change is $-v_1$ during the whole commutation, so:

$$E_{deliver} = -2Cv_2v_1 + Cv_1^2 \quad (12-29)$$

As with the earlier cases, the amount of energy stored in the capacitors does not change in the process, and all the energy is provided by the inductor. The current reaches zero at the end of the procedure if the commutation starts with the minimal amount current in the inductor. Then:

$$E_{deliver} = \frac{1}{2} Li_{L_min}^2, \text{ and} \quad (12-30)$$

$$i_{L_min}^2 = (-4Cv_2v_1 + 2Cv_1^2) / L \quad (12-31)$$

From the analyses, we see that a minimal amount of current is usually required to complete the commutation. If the energy requirement as determined from the previous calculation is, there is no energy limit for the commutation, but the current direction criteria in (9) is still a must.

To illustrate this point, we take the conventional modulation as an example. All the commutations are from Case 1. For the input bridge, the voltage source v_1 and v_2 are of the same sign. A minimal amount of current that is greater than zero is required for commutation. The soft switching region is reduced by this requirement. For the output bridge the voltage source v_1 and v_2 are different signs. Only current direction is required. Taking $i_{L_min}^2 = |4v_1v_2LC| = 0.1\pi v_o / 4\omega L$ for example, the soft switching region with and without the consideration of the influence of capacitors is shown in Fig. 12-16. The soft switching region will be reduced from the area encompassed by solid line, which is the same as that shown in Figure 11 to the area to the right of the dashed line. The solid line and dashed line determined by the output bridge overlap.

Fig. 12-16 Soft switching region of conventional modulation with and without consideration of influence of junction capacitors

For the unified modulation waveform, for case 2, the minimal energy required can be theoretically reduced to zero by set $v_1 = 2v_2$. However, the energy requirement in Case 3 will be doubled when v_1 and v_2 are of different signs and this condition is unavoidable.

C. Magnetizing Inductor Influence

When considering the magnetizing inductance, the transformer is usually modeled as its T-Shaped equivalent circuit, as shown in Fig. 12-17.

Fig. 12-17 T-shaped equivalent circuit of a transformer

Replacing the inductor in Fig. 12-14 and Fig. 12-15 with the equivalent circuit causes the inductor and voltage source v_2 to become a circuit as shown in Fig. 12-18.

Fig. 12-18 Equivalent circuit for transformer and non-commutating bridge

Due to the existence of L_m , when $i_2 > 0$, $|i_L| > |i_2|$, and when $i_2 < 0$, $|i_L| < |i_2|$. This shows that the existence of L_m decreases the energy flowing into and out of voltage source v_2 . This means a coefficient $k < 1$ should be added to the part of the energy related to v_2 . The energy requirement becomes:

Case 1:

$$i_{L_min}^2 = 4k v_1 v_2 C / L \quad (12-32)$$

Case 2:

$$i_{L_min}^2 = (4k C v_2 v_1 - 2C v_1^2) / L \quad (12-33)$$

Case 3:

$$i_{L_min}^2 = (-4k C v_2 v_1 + 2C v_1^2) / L \quad (12-34)$$

From (12-32)-(12-34), we see that, in Case 1, the magnetizing inductance always helps to reduce the minimal energy required for commutation. In Case 2 and Case 3, the magnetizing inductance helps to reduce the maximum energy requirement. However, for certain commutation, magnetizing inductance may either increase or decrease the necessary energy.

IV. Si MOSFET based DAB Converter Design

Before building the final SiC-based converter, a Si-based converter is designed and constructed to verify the design methodology.

IV.1. Design Specification

To verify the design methodology, the design specification tries to approach a similar working condition as the SiC MOSFET. The bus voltage is selected as half of the device rated voltage. The switching frequency is kept the same as the final converter. The rated power is reduced to half of the final converter because of the decrease of the bus voltage. The ripple specification is kept the same. The specification is summarized in Table 12-4.

Table 12-4 Prototype DAB converter specification

Input voltage	270V-330V	Output voltage	300V
Switching frequency	500kHz	Rated power	5kW
Input voltage ripple*	2% max input voltage	Output voltage ripple*	2% max output voltage
Output voltage accuracy	1% output voltage		

* Calculated with assumption that all ripple current flows into the filter capacitor.

IV.2. Operating Point Selection

A. Theoretical Calculation

As shown in last year's report, at this high frequency, the heatsink contribute most of the volume of the converter. So the operation point should be selected to minimize the worst case device loss, which should occur at full load point if the converter is soft switched. For the converter to design, the output voltage and full load current is fixed. At this point, the converter should work under ZVS condition, the conduction loss dominants the device loss and is chosen to be minimized. In our design, primary side and secondary will use the same power stage. So the on resistance is the same. Thus, the ratio of root mean square of the primary side device rms current $I_{s_rms_p}$ and secondary side device rms current $I_{s_rms_s}$ to converter output current is selected to be the criteria for operating point selection.

Since operational modes (a) and (b) in Fig. 12-13 introduce more reactive power flowing between source and load to maintain soft switching. At full load, only mode (c) is used to keep device utilization ratio high.

From Table 12-3, we can get the ratio we used for the design calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\sqrt{I_{s_rms_p}^2 + I_{s_rms_s}^2}}{I_o} &= \frac{I_{s_rms_p} \sqrt{1+d^2}}{I_o} \\
 &= \frac{\sqrt{-4\alpha^3 - 3\alpha d\pi(\pi - 2\tau) + 3\alpha^2(\pi + d\pi - 2d\tau)} \cdot \sqrt{1+d^2}}{2\pi(\alpha + \gamma + \tau) - 2(\alpha^2 + \gamma^2 + \tau^2) - \pi^2} \quad (12-35) \\
 &= \frac{\sqrt{6\pi}}{2\pi}
 \end{aligned}$$

To maximize the current output capability. The angles α and γ are set to $\pi/2$. Then (12-35) can be simplified to:

$$\frac{\sqrt{I_{s_rms_p}^2 + I_{s_rms_s}^2}}{I_o} = \frac{\sqrt{(d-1)^2 \pi^3 + 12d\pi\tau^2 - 8d\tau^3} \cdot \sqrt{(1+d^2)\pi}}{2\sqrt{6}\tau(\pi-\tau)} \quad (12-36)$$

Calculate this ratio for each combination of voltage gain $d = nV_o/V_i$ and phase shift angle τ . A surface can be plot from the calculation result. Fig. 12-19 shows the contour graph of the surface.

Fig. 12-19 Contour graph of device utilization ratio at different operating point

From Fig. 12-19 we can easily see that the minimal ratio value at certain phase shift angle is at the point where voltage gain equals to one. And the smaller phase shift angle leads to smaller rms current. But ZVS requirement limit the feasible region. Also, to simplify the design, the voltage gain should be set to larger than one or less than one in the whole voltage range which can keep one full bridge work under ZVS on the full load range.

Thus, the nominal operating point is selected to be $d = 1.1$, and the voltage gain for the specified input voltage range is $1 \leq d \leq 1.22$, which keeps the secondary side bridge always soft switched. Since $V_i = V_o = 300V$, the transformer turns ration should be set to 11:10 to obtain the designed voltage gain.

To determine the minimal phase shift angle required by soft switching, switch junction capacitors should be taken into the consideration. Since the capacitance varies with devices, iteration is required. Considering possible devices that could be used, $C = 200pF$ is selected to be the initial value.

The commutation of selected full load modulation waveform is shown in Fig. 12-14. The minimal current requirement is (12-32). So the commutating current should be at least:

$$I_{cp} = 2\omega\sqrt{dLC} \quad (12-37)$$

From equations in Table 12-3, the commutating current should also be:

$$I_{cp} = \alpha + d(\tau - \alpha) = \pi/2 + d(\tau - \pi/2) \quad (12-38)$$

Solve τ from (12-37) and (12-38):

$$\tau = 2\omega\sqrt{LC/d} - \frac{\pi}{2d} + \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (12-39)$$

The converter is designed to be soft-switched above half load. So at this boundary point:

$$I_o = \frac{d\tau(\pi - \tau)}{\pi} \frac{V_i}{\omega L} = \frac{5000\text{W}/2}{300\text{V}} \quad (12-40)$$

Solve L from (12-39) and (12-40):

$$L \approx 4.32 \times 10^{-6} \text{H} \quad (12-41)$$

The phase angle at full load can be obtained from:

$$I_o = \frac{\tau(\pi - \tau)}{\pi} \frac{V_i}{\omega L} = \frac{5000\text{W}}{300\text{V}} \quad (12-42)$$

Thus

$$\tau = 58^\circ \quad (12-43)$$

To summarize, the operating point is $\tau = 58^\circ$, $d = 1.1$ for the normal condition at full load. The transformer should be designed with 4.32×10^{-6} H and turns ratio of 11:10 to get to that point.

B. Simulation Results

The converter is simulated in Saber to verify the design. The simulation schematic is shown in Fig. 12-20. This schematic is used through the whole design procedure.

Fig. 12-20 DAB converter simulation schematic

Two operating point output full power and half power are simulated. Instead of calculated 58° and 23° phase shift angles. The simulated phase shift angles are 68° and 29° accordingly. This is because the simulation includes device loss and need more power at input. Another reason is that the existence of dead time reduces the duty cycle then decreases the transferred power.

(a) $P_o = 5 \text{ kW}$

(b) $P_o = 2.5 \text{ kW}$ **Fig. 12-21 Simulated device gate signal and voltage**

The simulated device gate signals and voltages are shown in Fig. 12-21. The top four signals are gate signals of the four bottom switches in the phase legs. The bottom four signals are the voltage on the four bottom switches in the phase legs in the same sequence as the gate signals.

From the waveform we can see at full load 5 kW, all voltage transition are during the dead time. All the switches are soft switched. At half load 2.5 kW, voltage jump can be seen in the red circled part at which one switch is turning on. The device is not fully soft switched. The simulation verified the previous calculation on soft switching limit and operating point selection.

IV.3. Active Components Selection

Since the conduction loss is expected to be the dominant limit of the design. CoolMOS with fast recovery body diode embedded is selected to be the switching device. The calculation here is to determine the device rating and estimate the device loss.

A. Theoretical Calculation

The active devices are usually selected by adding certain margin to ideal condition device stress. The stress should be considered includes peak voltage and rms current. Peak voltage is 330V from specification. Using device rms equation in Table 12-3, the primary and secondary device rms currents at full load are:

$$I_{p_rms} = 14.77\text{A} \quad (12-44)$$

$$I_{s_rms} = dI_{p_rms} = 16.25\text{A} \quad (12-45)$$

Base on these, 600V MOSFET should be used. MOSFET current rating is more related to the thermal limit. Since at high frequency, switching loss is a large part of the total loss, a MOSFET rated 47A is selected. The model is APT47N60 which is from MicroSemi. For the device loss estimation, it is hard to be done by only calculation because the converter operates at different modes includes soft switching, hard switching and the status between them. Only simulation is used to obtain the loss.

B. Simulation Result

To capture the device loss, the device voltage and current as shown in Fig. 12-22 are sampled for the calculation. This figure shows examples of one phase leg. But loss of all four phase leg is all captured.

Fig. 12-22 Device voltage and current sampling points

From the simulation, we can capture the voltage and current waveform as shown in Fig. 12-23. The loss is of the whole phase leg and calculated as $P_{LOSS} = V_B I_B + V_T I_T$. By doing this, the energy stored in the junction capacitors which is released lossless during ZVS procedure are not considered into the loss.

Fig. 12-23 Simulated voltage, current and loss waveform of one phase leg

To reduce switching loss, SiC Schottky diodes CSD60020 from Cree are used as anti-parallel diodes. The bode diodes are blocked using low voltage Si Schottky diodes. The total loss can be obtained by just average the loss power. The switching loss should be got from integrating the loss at the switching transient. This procedure is repeated at different output power to search the worst case. The simulated data are shown in Table 12-5. We can identify the worst point is at full load, when power flows in the reverse direction. At this point, a heatsink with 0.08 °C/W thermal resistance can keep all the device work under allowed temperature rise.

Table 12-5 Simulated device loss with separate freewheeling diodes

	Primary side device loss	Secondary side device loss
$P_o \approx 5kW$	56W	47W
$P_i \approx -5kW$	24W	63W
$P_o \approx 0kW$	49W	12W
$P_i \approx 0kW$	50W	10W

From the simulated data we also verified our operating point selection which keeps the secondary switch under ZVS. The primary side switches are hard switched at light load so when the output power is near zero, their loss reaches a local peak value. The secondary side switches loss is mainly related to the output power. The switching loss only contributes a small portion of it.

IV.4. Passive Components Selection

The passive components in the DAB converter include the transformer and the buses capacitors. The transformer design procedure is described in Chapter 15. Only the selection of the bus capacitors is discussed here.

A. Theoretical Calculation

For the passive component including bus capacitors and the transformer, the commutation transient is too short to affect the selection of these components. So the model without junction capacitor is used to describe the converter.

The key parameters for the capacitor selection are capacitance, voltage and rms current. The capacitor voltage is the bus voltage which is 330V. The capacitance and rms current can be calculated from the detailed current waveform shown in Fig. 12-24. i_{sb} is secondary side bus current. i_o is output current. The difference of them is the current flowing into the secondary bus capacitor.

Fig. 12-24 Secondary bus current and output current

To calculate the capacitance, just let the shaded part of the current to charge the capacitor and the voltage ripple should be less than the specification. The shaded area equals to:

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_2} |i_{sb} - i_o| dt \leq \Delta V \cdot C_s \quad (12-46)$$

The voltage ripple ΔV should be limited to less than 1% max output voltage which is 3V

Use equation from Table 12-3 to get the key point current and the capacitance can be solved:

$$C_s = 4.5 \mu\text{F} \quad (12-47)$$

Similarly, the primary bus capacitance can be obtained:

$$C_p = 3.5 \mu\text{F} \quad (12-48)$$

Since the primary and secondary power stages are the same, $C = 8.9\mu\text{F}$ is the minimal required value.

The secondary bus capacitor rms current is

$$I_{s_C_rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{t_2 - t_0} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} (i_{sb} - i_o)^2 dt} = \frac{\sqrt{(d-1)^2 \pi^4 + 12(d-1)\pi^2 \tau^2 - 8(d-3)\pi \tau^3 - 12\tau^4}}{2\sqrt{3}\pi} \quad (12-49)$$

It reaches maximal value when $\tau = 58^\circ$

$$I_{s_C_rms_max} = 22.95\text{A} \quad (12-50)$$

The primary bus capacitor rms current also reaches its maximal value at this point:

$$I_{p_C_rms_max} = 20.85\text{A} \quad (12-51)$$

So the requirement of the bus capacitor is:

Voltage rating: 330 V

Rms current: 22.95 A

Capacitance: 4.5 μF

B. Simulation Result

Real capacitor has ESR and ESL which will make the ripple larger than expected. Since there is always margin in the real design, detailed analytical model which can push the design to the limit is not necessary. Simulation is used to help decide the value of the capacitance. The simulation circuit is shown in Fig. 12-25.

Fig. 12-25 Simulation circuit for output voltage ripple

The capacitor that will be used is ceramic capacitor which has very low ESL and ESR. Thus 2nH ESL and 2m Ω ESR is assumed for the simulation. The peaks in the output voltage are caused by the switching transient current and could be reduced by adding decoupling capacitors near the switches. From the simulation result shown in Fig. 12-26, 20 μF capacitance with 0.1 μF decoupling capacitor added can meet the output ripple requirement and is used in the design.

(a) Bus capacitance 8.9 uF only

(b) Bus capacitance 20 uF with decoupling capacitor

Fig. 12-26 Simulation results for output voltage ripple

IV.5. Controller Selection

To control the real hardware, a digital controller will be used. For this kind of high frequency application, two aspect of the controller should be checked: PWM resolution and calculation speed.

If no dithering is used, voltage change caused by one bit change in the PWM signal should be no more than the voltage accuracy requirement. In DAB converter, instead on duty cycle, phase shift angle is controlled. The minimal angle change that can be obtained is:

$$\Delta\theta_{\min} = \frac{t_{1bit}}{T_s} 2\pi \tag{12-52}$$

t_{1bit} is the time change of one bit PWM reference change. T_s is the switching period. The DAB converter's output voltage is indirectly controlled by output current. So at light load, where the load impedance is large, it is hard to control output voltage precisely. Here only down to 10% of full load is considered. At lighter load, only the current change is limited to the same amount as which at 10% of full load.

At 10% of full load, the normalized output current is:

$$I_{o10\%} = 0.1d \frac{\frac{58\pi}{180} \left(\pi - \frac{58\pi}{180} \right)}{\pi} \approx 0.0755 \quad (12-53)$$

To assure less than 1% voltage difference, the current error should be less than 7.55×10^{-4} .

For operational mode (c) in Fig. 12-13

$$\frac{dI_o}{d\tau} = \frac{d(\pi - \tau)}{\pi} \quad (12-54)$$

The maxim current change caused by certain phase angle change is

$$\Delta \tau \left. \frac{dI_o}{d\tau} \right|_{\tau=0} = 1.1 \Delta \tau \leq 7.55 \times 10^{-4} \quad (12-55)$$

$$\Delta \tau \leq 6.86 \times 10^{-4} \quad (12-56)$$

Thus

$$\Delta \theta_{\min} = \frac{t_{1bit}}{T_s} 2\pi \leq 6.86 \times 10^{-4} \quad (12-57)$$

$$t_{1bit} < 0.219\text{ns}$$

If counter based PWM generator, a clock frequency of 4.6 GHz should be used and is impossible. Controller with very high resolution PWM generator should be used for the control. TMS320F28335 from Texas Instruments is used. It has a High resolution PWM Generator implemented by delay-line and provides a PWM resolution of 150 ps [2] which is equivalent to 6.67 GHz counter based PWM generator. It has a floating point unit work at 150 MHz and is the fastest single chip solution found at the design time. According to [3], the DAB converter can be controlled by a single voltage loop using PI regulator. It is considered to be fast enough to implement the regulator. To test the calculation speed requirement, a PI controller is implemented in a real controller and it takes about 50 clock cycle to finish the calculation while one switching period contains 150 clock cycles. There is still enough time for the auxiliary work.

V. Conclusion

A Si MOSFET based converter is designed before the final SiC converter is built. Intensive simulation is involved to verify the calculation result obtained from the simplified models. The averaged signals such as output current, rms currents, etc. matched calculation results pretty well as expected. All signals related to circuitry and components parasitic such as voltage ripple and switching loss need to be simulated to get useful result. Or the model will become too complicated to be analytically calculated.

The designed converter is constructed and being tested. It will be used to verify the simulation result. Simulation models will be improved if significant difference is found. After correct the simulation model, the methodology in this chapter along with the model developed in previous chapters will be used for the final SiC converter design.

VI. References

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Chapter 13 MODULARIZED DESIGN, TESTING AND MODELING OF A GENERAL-PURPOSE PHASE-LEG PEBB

I. Introduction

The concept of the Power Electronics Building Block (PEBB) is aimed at achieving better performance, higher reliability and even lower cost for power electronics systems, where a converter can be built quickly and reliably by just connecting several PEBB modules together, allowing for faster design and construction of a power conversion system for even non-power-electronics engineers [1]. For practical applications, a basic building block is usually defined at a sub-converter level, and mostly as a phase-leg (i.e. a half-bridge structure). Modularization and integration of PEBB at this level provide many advantages towards converter construction. Not only can the design complexity be maintained at an appropriate level, but also the application flexibility can be maximized, as many commonly used topologies utilize phase-legs as the basic sub-circuits, such as the voltage-source inverter (VSI) for three-phase applications, and phase-shifted full-bridge converter for DC-DC applications, as seen in Fig. 13-1. The dual-active-bridge converter (DAB) presented in the last chapter is just another example using this basic component.

Fig. 13-1 Voltage-source inverter (left) and phase-shifted full-bridge converter (right) with phase-legs highlighted as the basic sub-circuit

Considering the medium power level (~ 5 kW) of the DAB topology adopted in this project, this chapter is therefore focused on the modularized design of a general-purpose MOSFET phase-leg PEBB, optimized for high-frequency operation up to 500 kHz. The design first starts with hybrid Si CoolMOS and SiC Schottky diode combination (called Si-version phase-leg hereafter) to optimize the performance of the phase-leg aimed at 300 to 400 V DC bus voltage and 10 to 20 A RMS current operation range. This version of phase-leg is built and fully tested to reveal and verify the considerations during the design process. Based on that, a complete SiC-version phase-leg using SiC MOSFETs and SiC diodes is then designed for the operations at 600 to 800 V and 5 to 10 A RMS current ranges. The performance of the SiC phase-leg is predicted using the modeling methodology presented in the previous chapters of this report. Comparisons are also made between phase-legs using Si and SiC technologies.

I.1. Technical Objectives

There are three basic requirements and hence objectives for the targeted general-purpose phase-leg PEBB.

(1) Gate drive scheme

The switching duty cycle range determines what technology should be adopted for the gate driver. For PWM type converters, the duty cycle can vary from 0% to 100%, while for phase-shifted converters the duty cycle is usually fixed at about 50%. In order for the phase-leg to be “general-purpose” and not constrained by topologies, the gate drive scheme should be carefully compared and selected, as some commonly used technologies such as transformer and bootstrap gate drivers may not work for this target.

(2) Power stage layout

As it has been pointed out previously, the demand for higher switching frequency requires faster switching speed of the power devices. As the impact of the circuit parasitic impedances becomes more and more serious under higher dv/dt and di/dt , the circuit layout and the corresponding parasitics, especially of the power stage, need to be more carefully designed and controlled, so that the power devices can be switched as fast as possible while still maintaining minimal voltage and current stresses under the circuit parasitics.

(3) Necessary protection functions

As a modularized design, the phase-leg PEBB should also be self-protective against the misuse of the users. In this design, the dead-time preserving function, over-current protection and over-temperature protection will all be considered to ensure that the phase-leg is working in its safe operation range.

As a preliminary study for the packaging-level PEBB module design, this work will first start with PCB-based phase-leg with all discrete components. Considering the above requirements, the modularized design process presented in this chapter will involve the proper selection of power switches, driving scheme, control and protection strategies, and finally systematic testing sequence of the phase-leg module. On the other hand, the module terminal behaviors, from both the control side and the power side, will be fully characterized and tabulated so that the up-level designers can utilize just the module datasheet for the converter design without worrying about the physics inside the module. All these related issues will be addressed and discussed in this chapter.

I.2. Technical Approach

The design process takes into account many guidelines about the device selection, gate driving scheme, and power stage layout design. The Si-version phase-leg is designed according to these guidelines, and is then tested and characterized in a systematic procedure. Based on that, a phase-leg datasheet is tabulated for the future converter design. Meanwhile, hierarchical phase-leg modeling and simulation are also carried out to verify the Si phase-leg design, and to predict the performance of the SiC phase-leg.

II. Device Selections

II.1. Selection of Si MOSFET

Considering the voltage level (300 V) and current range (~15 A RMS and ~20 A peak) of the proposed DAB converter in full load (5 kW), the selection of Si MOSFET is narrowed down to Si CoolMOS rated at 600 V and around 45 A, with enough voltage and current margins left. The CoolMOS technology basically combines the benefits of the fast switching speed (i.e. low switching loss) of a MOSFET and the low on-state resistance (i.e. low conduction loss) of an IGBT [2], and thus is ideal in this work for the 600 V level phase-leg PEBB aimed at high-frequency operation. Major CoolMOS manufacturers are surveyed, such as Microsemi, IXYS, and Infineon, etc., and the devices with desired ratings and package (TO-247) are tabulated and compared in Table 13-1 and Table 13-2.

Table 13-1 summarizes the important parameters about the MOSFET static performances. Among these the most critical one is the on-state resistance $R_{DS(on)}$, which directly reflects the conduction loss of the device. The average $R_{DS(on)}$ for CoolMOS of this current rating is about 60 m Ω , while the minimum can be as low as 40 m Ω and maximum as high as 150 m Ω . Since $R_{DS(on)}$ is a function of both gate-source voltage V_{GS} and drain current I_D , the comparison between devices based on this number is not completely fair as different test conditions are used by different manufacturers. Therefore in the table the loss ranking is performed within each manufacturer where test conditions are similar.

On the other hand, the junction-to-case thermal resistances of regular TO-247 packages are quite similar between different devices (about 0.3 K/W). The ISOPLUS-247 package of IXYS IXKR47N60C5, however, has 50% higher R_{thJC} because double-bonded-copper (DBC) is used as the substrate which makes the back copper plane of the package isolated from the device terminals. Unlike regular TO-247 package where the MOSFET drain is directly attached to the back plane, this design eliminates the need of the insulation layer between the device and the heatsink. However, this also makes it hard to be mounted onto the heatsink because there's no mounting hole on ISOPLUS-247 package [3].

Table 13-1 Survey of CoolMOS I – static performances

Manufacturer	Part No.	BV_{DSS} (V)	I_D (A)	$R_{DS(on)}$ (Ω)	$V_{GS(th)}$ (V)	R_{thJC} (K/W)	Remarks	Loss Rank*
Microsemi	APT47N60BC3	600	47	0.06	3	0.3	FREDFET	1
Microsemi	APT47N60BCF	600	46	0.083	4	0.3	FREDFET	2
Microsemi	APT43F60L	600	45	0.15	4	0.16	MOS8 FREDFET	3
IXYS	IXKR47N60C5	600	47	0.04	3	0.45	ISOPLUS-247	1
IXYS	IXKH47N60C	600	47	0.06	3	0.3	-	2
Infineon	SPW47N60CFD	600	46	0.07	4	0.3	-	3
Infineon	SPW47N60C3	600	47	0.06	3	0.3	-	1
Infineon	SPW47N65C3	650	47	0.06	3	0.3	-	1

* Loss is ranked based on $R_{DS(on)}$ values and ranking is performed within each manufacturer.

Table 13-2 tabulates the dynamic parameters of the MOSFETs. For junction capacitances, most manufacturers adopt the same test condition where capacitances are measured at 25 V drain-source bias and 1 MHz small-signal frequency. However, these numbers are insufficient to represent the dynamic performance of a device since the junction capacitances are strongly nonlinear functions of V_{DS} and their values change drastically during the device switching transients. Comparatively, Q_{GS} and Q_{GD} from the gate charge diagram are better

representatives of the switching performance, with Q_{GS} mainly indicating the turn-on / turn-off delays and current rise / fall speed, and Q_{GD} mainly affecting the voltage rise / fall speed [4]-[5].

Table 13-2 Survey of CoolMOS II – dynamic performances

Manu.	Part No.	C_{ISS} (pF)*	C_{OSS} (pF)*	C_{RSS} (pF)*	Q_{GS} (nC) **	Q_{GD} (nC) **	Test Cond.	t_r (ns) ***	t_f (ns) ***	dv/dt (V/ns) ♦	Speed Rank ♦♦	Ringing Rank ♦♦♦
Microsemi	APT47N60BC3	7015	2565 800 @ 50 V	210 40 @ 50 V	29	110	300 V, 47 A, 10 V	27	8	50	~1	~3
Microsemi	APT47N60BCF	7290	1735 200 @ 400 V	41 21 @ 400 V	43	135	300 V, 46 A, 10 V	30	15	80	~2	~2
Microsemi	APT43F60L	8590	800 170 @ 400 V	90 25 @ 400 V	45	90	300 V, 21 A, 10 V	55	44	-	~3	1
IXYS	IXKR 47N60C5	7000	9000 250 @ 200 V	270 4.5 @ 200 V	35	50	400 V, 44 A, 10 V	20	10	50	1	~1
IXYS	IXKH 47N60C	7000	2000 280 @ 100 V	120 42 @ 100 V	30	110	350 V, 40 A, 10 V	27	10	-	2	~1
Infineon	SPW47N60CFD	7700	2200 200 @ 400 V	77 20 @ 400 V	54	130	480 V, 46 A, 10 V	30	15	80	3	2
Infineon	SPW47N60C3	6800	5000 110 @ 400 V	145 55 @ 100 V	24	121	350 V, 47 A, 10 V	27	8	50	~1	1
Infineon	SPW47N65C3	7000	2300 220 @ 400 V	100 30 @ 400 V	35	120	480 V, 47 A, 10 V	27	14	50	~1	3

* If not specified, junction capacitances are measured at $V_{GS} = 0$ V, $V_{DS} = 25$ V and $f = 1$ MHz.

** See column on the right for the test conditions.

*** Rise time t_r and fall time t_f are obtained under resistive load. V_{GS} , V_{DS} , I_D and R_G vary for each MOSFET.

♦ dv/dt is the maximum permissible rate of rise of off-state voltage across the MOSFET.

♦♦ Speed is ranked based on Q_{GS} and Q_{GD} values. Ranking is performed within each manufacturer.

♦♦♦ Ringing is ranked based on C_{OSS} values at high V_{DS} bias. Ranking is performed within each manufacturer.

Fig. 13-2 gives a more detailed illustration of a typical gate charge diagram. Basically there are three segments in a gate charge curve. Take MOSFET turn-on process for instance: The first slope stands for the turn-on delay charge (before V_{GS} reaches $V_{GS(th)}$) and current rise charge (after V_{GS} reaches $V_{GS(th)}$), during which most of the gate current is used to charge the C_{GS} of the MOSFET (i.e. Q_{GS}). The plateau region after that represents the V_{DS} fall period, when V_{GS} keeps constant and almost all the gate current goes to charge the Miller capacitance C_{GD} (i.e. Q_{GD}). At the end of this segment the MOSFET is fully turned-on. The third segment of the curve is then representing the gate overcharge which simply brings the gate-source bias to the full turn-on voltage and reduces the channel resistance. The shape of the gate charge curve is therefore influenced by V_{DS} , I_D and turn-on gate voltage V_{DRIVE} , although it is not sensitive to the driving speed, or R_G . Generally speaking, the smaller the gate charges are, the faster the device can be switched [6]-[7].

Fig. 13-2 Typical gate charge diagram

The fact that the gate charge is strongly related to the test condition (i.e. V_{DS} , I_D and V_{DRIVE}) makes the comparison of switching speed more difficult among different MOSFETs, as Table 13-2 clearly shows that different test conditions are used to obtain the gate charge values. From this angle, the comparison by datasheet values here is just a quick but very rough way to determine the switching speed of a MOSFET. Also note that the turn-on and turn-off times (t_r and t_f) are not used for speed comparison as they are obtained under resistive load with various switching speed. They are listed here only as a reference but not decisive parameters.

On the other hand, the potential ringing caused by fast switching speed is also considered by examining the C_{OSS} value at high V_{DS} bias, as suggested by the parametric study presented in Chapter 4. Still, in different datasheets the junction capacitance curves are given up to different V_{DS} bias (ranging from 50 V to 400 V), which makes the comparison not fair enough. The ringing ranks, likewise, only give a rough idea about the potential device stresses under high switching speed.

The dv/dt value in Table 13-2 provides a measure of the maximum permissible dv/dt on an off-state MOSFET without false triggering the device. This will be further discussed in the gate drive design section of this chapter.

Considering the potential high-frequency application of the phase-leg PEBB, the selection of Si CoolMOS is based on the criteria of switching speed (gate charge), conduction loss ($R_{DS(on)}$), and device stress due to ringing (C_{OSS} at high V_{DS}), with speed being the most significant and ringing being the least. Based on the data in Table 13-1 and Table 13-2, the following candidates are selected:

IXYS IXKR47N60C5,

IXYS IXKH47N60C,

Microsemi APT47N60BC3,

Microsemi APT47N60BCF, and

Infineon SPW47N60C3.

At the time of this work, only IXKR47N60C5 and APT47N60BCF are available without lead time. To facilitate future cooling system installation, APT47N60BCF with regular TO-247 package is finally selected for the Si-version phase-leg PEBB.

II.2. Selection of SiC Schottky Diode

The SiC Schottky diode is chosen as the freewheeling diode of the phase-leg PEBB due to its superior reverse recovery characteristics compared to the conventional high-voltage PiN diodes, which can significantly reduce the switching loss of the phase-leg if running at high frequency. Table 13-3 is a survey of SiC diodes from two major manufacturers – Cree and Infineon. Due to the power level of the DAB converter, only devices with average forward current I_F greater than 10 A are summarized.

Table 13-3 Survey of SiC Schottky diodes

Manufacturer	Part No.	V_{RRM} (V)	I_F (A)	V_F (V)	Q_C (nC)	R_{thJC} (K/W)	Remarks
Cree	C3D10060A	600	10	1.5	25	1.1	TO-220
Cree	C3D20060A	600	20	1.5	50	0.55	TO-247, 2 x 10 A
Infineon	IDT16S60C	600	16	1.5	38	1.1	TO-220 decapped
Infineon	SDT12S60	600	12	1.5	30	1.7	TO-220 decapped
Infineon	IDT12S60C	600	12	1.5	30	1.3	TO-220 decapped
Infineon	IDH12SG60C	600	12	1.8	19	1.2	TO-220, thinQ 3G
Infineon	IDT10S60C	600	10	1.5	24	1.5	TO-220 decapped
Infineon	IDH10SG60C	600	10	1.8	16	1.25	TO-220, thinQ 3G
Infineon	IDH10S60C	600	10	1.5	24	1.5	TO-220

Similarly, these SiC diodes are also evaluated and compared based on loss (by V_F), speed (by Q_C) and ringing (by C_J). Finally, Cree C3D20060A (600 V, 20 A) is selected mainly considering the current rating required for DAB operation. Note that the maximum junction temperature for Cree diodes is 175 °C, and their current rating is evaluated at 150 °C case temperature. This equivalently indicates that I_F is much greater than 20 A at 25 °C case temperature – the test condition used for Si CoolMOS, which means enough margin has been left in the current rating for the freewheeling diodes.

II.3. Selection of Si Blocking Diode

The body diode of the Si CoolMOS APT47N60BCF has a forward voltage of 1.2 V, while the SiC diode has 1.5 V from Table 13-3. A blocking diode thus should be added in series with the MOSFET to prevent the body diode from conducting, as shown in Fig. 13-3. In this work, Si Schottky diode 62CTQ030PbF from Vishay is selected as the blocking diode, whose main parameters are listed in Table 13-4. The selection of the blocking diode considers the low voltage drop of Schottky diodes which minimizes the conduction loss, the current conduction capability which is compatible with the Si MOSFET, as well as the low blocking voltage which will impact the zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) operation of the MOSFET.

Fig. 13-3 Phase-leg PEBB structure

Table 13-4 62CTQ030PbF main parameters

Manufacturer	Part No.	V_{RRM} (V)	I_F (A)	V_F (A)	R_{thJC} (K/W)	Package
Vishay	62CTQ030PbF	30	60	0.44	1.2	TO-220AB

For high-switching-frequency operation, it is a common practice that the MOSFETs are working in ZVS mode to eliminate the turn-on loss, so as to minimize the total switching loss. This is usually realized by conducting the anti-parallel freewheeling diode first before turning-on the MOSFET, thus creating a zero-voltage environment for the main switch. However, with the existence of the blocking diode, the MOSFET drain-source voltage won't be totally zero when the freewheeling diode is conducting. This phenomenon is explained through Fig. 13-4 (a) to (d).

In the figure, the capacitors paralleled to the MOSFETs and diodes are the MOSFET output capacitance C_{OSS} and the diode junction capacitances C_J respectively, with C_{JB} representing that of the blocking diode and C_{JF} the freewheeling diode. Assuming the original load current is flowing out of the middle point, as shown in Fig. 13-4 (a), and the top MOSFET is on while the bottom is off. At the moment of the top MOSFET turning-off, the load inductor starts to draw currents from both top and bottom devices' junction capacitors. During this interval, the bottom MOSFET's C_{OSS} starts to discharge through the C_J of its blocking diode, as illustrated in Fig. 13-4 (a). V_{DS} and the overall V_{BOT} start to decrease while V_{BD} starts to build up. When V_{BD} reaches the breakdown voltage of the diode, the discharge current is diverted to flow through the diode reversely, and V_{BD} stays at the breakdown voltage, as Fig. 13-4 (b) suggests. Meanwhile, V_{BOT} keeps decreasing until the low-side freewheeling diode starts conducting, the moment when ZVS can happen. However, due to the existence of the blocking diode, there will be some residual voltage on V_{DS} which is less than or equal to V_{BD} (seen in Fig. 13-4 (c)), and when the bottom MOSFET is turned-on, the remaining charge on C_{OSS} will be dissipated

through the MOSFET channel, causing some extra amount of turn-on loss, as shown in Fig. 13-4 (d).

Fig. 13-4 Impact of the blocking diode on the MOSFET ZVS operation

Note that there doesn't have to be such an interval as Fig. 13-4 (b), which means the blocking diode does not necessarily go through a reverse conducting period. The final remaining voltage on V_{DS} (or equivalently V_{BD}) is determined by the ratio of C_{JB} and C_{OSS} , or the charges stored in these two capacitors. If the freewheeling diode starts conducting before the blocking diode breaks-down, then V_{DS} will be smaller than the breakdown voltage.

The above analysis has been verified by a low-side double-pulse test of the phase-leg (The phase-leg tests will be further discussed in later sections). The experimental waveforms in Fig. 13-5 clearly shows the remaining voltage on the MOSFET when the freewheeling diode is conducting. For the MOSFET-blocking diode combination in this design (i.e. APT47N60BCF and 62CTQ030PbF), this residual voltage is around 25 V, less than the V_{RRM} of the diode.

Fig. 13-5 Experimental waveforms showing the impact of the blocking diode

The possibility of reversely conducting the blocking diode poses another requirement for the selection of this diode, namely the junction capacitance of the diode should not be too small to incur any destructive reverse current through the diode. If necessary, additional capacitance can be paralleled to the blocking diode to reduce the residual voltage. Fig. 13-6 shows the test waveforms where an additional 20 nF is paralleled to the blocking diode. As seen, the residual voltage is reduced to around 10 V.

Fig. 13-6 Experimental waveforms showing the impact of the blocking diode with additional 20 nF capacitance

On the other hand, Fig. 13-7 shows the simulation waveforms of the same low-side double-pulse test. The only difference is that the top MOSFET is turned-on after the freewheeling diode conducts, in order to achieve ZVS. As seen from the left figure, the residual V_{DS} of the top MOSFET reduces from around 25 V to around 10 V, consistent with the experimental results. The turn-on energy thus slightly reduces from 647 nJ to 405 nJ, while the turn-off energy also sees a slight reduction from 34.7 μ J to 33.8 μ J.

Fig. 13-7 Simulation waveforms showing the impact of the blocking diode with and without 20 nF external capacitance. (Left) Switching transient waveforms, (right) Turn-on and turn-off energies

It also needs to be noted that adding an external capacitance to the blocking diode won't greatly change the switching speed of the phase-leg, as suggested by Fig. 13-7. The equivalent capacitance of the MOSFET and the blocking diode is given by

$$C_{eq} = \frac{C_{JB} C_{OSS}}{C_{JB} + C_{OSS}} \quad (13-1)$$

During the interval represented by Fig. 13-4 (a), the MOSFET has high bias voltage while the blocking diode voltage is low, so generally one has $C_{JB} \gg C_{OSS}$, which leads to $C_{eq} \approx C_{OSS}$. Therefore, increasing C_{JB} does not change C_{eq} too much.

However, it will be a different story if one adds extra capacitance to C_{OSS} . This is because, once the blocking diode breaks-down, it behaves like a voltage source with a parallel capacitance of C_{OSS} (see Fig. 13-4 (b)). Increasing C_{OSS} thus will definitely slow the switching speed of the phase-leg. This can also be verified through simulation.

Based on the above analyses, it can be concluded that the selection of the blocking diode should also consider its C_J , especially the ratio of C_J and the C_{OSS} of the MOSFET. The main consideration is to avoid breakdown and the destructive reverse current of the blocking diode. If necessary, external capacitance can be paralleled to the diode. This will help lower the residual voltage and slightly reduce the turn-on energy.

III. Gate Drive Circuit Design

III.1. Comparison of Different Gate Drive Techniques

The major concern about the gate driver design in a phase-leg is how to drive the high-side MOSFET. Table 13-5 gives a summary of the most popular high-side gate driver techniques [8].

Table 13-5 Summary of high-side floating driver techniques

Method	Basic Circuit	Key Features
Floating Gate Drive Supply		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full gate control for indefinite periods of time • Cost impact of isolated supply is significant (one required for each high side MOSFET) • Level shifting a ground referenced signal can be tricky. Level shifter must sustain full voltage, switch first with minimal propagation delays and lower power consumption • Opto isolators tend to be relatively expensive, limited in bandwidth and noise sensitive
Pulse Transformer		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple and cost effective but limited in many respects • Operation over wide duty cycles requires complex techniques • Transformer size increases significantly as frequency decreases • Significant parasitics create less than ideal operation with fast switching waveforms
Charge Pump		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be used to generate an "over-rail" voltage controlled by a level shifter or to "pump" the gate when MOSFET is turned on • In the first case the problems of a level shifter have to be tackled • In the second case turn on times tend to be too long for switching applications • In either case, gate can be kept on for an indefinite period of time • In efficiencies in the voltage multiplication circuit may require more than two stages of pumping
Bootstrap		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple and inexpensive with some of the limitations of the pulse transformer: duty cycle and on-time are both constrained by the need to refresh the bootstrap capacitor • If the capacitor is charged from a high voltage rail, power dissipation can be significant • Requires level shifter with its associated difficulties
Carrier Drive		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives full gate control for an indefinite period of time but is somewhat limited in switching performance. This can be improved with added complexity

In order for the phase-leg PEBB to be “general-purpose” and not constrained by converter topologies, the gate driver should be able to work in a wide duty cycle range and provide certain protection functions (e.g. DESAT). As seen from the table, the inexpensive and commonly-used techniques such as pulse-transformer and bootstrap are all constrained in duty cycle range and protection implementation. Based on these considerations, in this design the floating gate drive supply with an optocoupler is adopted for the high-side gate driving. However, this technique also has the disadvantages of longer propagation delay, less dv/dt immunity, and higher cost compared to the transformer gate driver [9]-[12].

III.2. dv/dt Induced Turn-On and dv/dt Limit of MOSFET

The dv/dt induced turn-on is a common problem for IGBTs and MOSFETs. As seen in Fig. 13-8, when turning-on the top switch S1 in a phase-leg, a positive dv/dt will occur on the bottom switch S2, which generates a current I_{Miller} into the gate loop through the Miller capacitor of S2. I_{Miller} produces a voltage drop on the gate resistor and the driver output resistor. If this voltage exceeds the turn-on threshold, the MOSFET will be falsely triggered and a shoot will happen, causing catastrophic failure of the phase-leg. This issue will become even worse when the converter is operating, because the MOSFET gate threshold voltage will generally reduce with the increasing junction temperature [13].

Fig. 13-8 dv/dt induced turn-on due to Miller capacitance

Two necessary conditions can be extracted from the above statement: (1) The MOSFET should be in the static off-state, and (2) there is a positive dv/dt on the MOSFET drain-source terminals.

These are commonly satisfied conditions in the hard switching mode. As seen in Fig. 13-9 (a), assuming that the load current is flowing into the phase-leg, the current will first flow through the top freewheeling diode when the top MOSFET is off. When the bottom MOSFET turns-on, the current will be commutated from the diode to the MOSFET. Meanwhile, the bottom V_{DS}

starts to drop and a positive dv/dt appears on the top MOSFET, causing spikes and ringing on the gate voltage. If the spike is higher than the gate threshold, a false turn-on will happen.

In contrast, if the load current flows in the opposite direction, it will first go through the top MOSFET when it is on. While this MOSFET turns-off, the load inductor charges the top MOSFET C_{OSS} and discharges the bottom MOSFET C_{OSS} , producing a positive dv/dt on the top MOSFET. The turn-on of the bottom MOSFET, however, will happen only after the bottom freewheeling diode starts conducting to achieve ZVS. At this moment there is no dv/dt on either MOSFET, thus no Miller induced turn-on will happen under ZVS operation.

Fig. 13-9 Commutation processes for (a) hard switching and (b) ZVS

Considering the above two conditions, the following model can be used to qualitatively study the dv/dt limit of a MOSFET. As illustrated in Fig. 13-10, C_{GS} and C_{GD} represent the gate-source capacitance and Miller capacitance of the MOSFET, while R_G is a lumped resistance of MOSFET internal gate resistance R_{GI} , external gate resistance R_G , as well as the gate driver output resistance R_{DRIVE} .

Fig. 13-10 MOSFET dv/dt limit model

To simplify the model, it is assumed that both capacitances are linear, and a voltage source with a constant ramp rate (dv_{DS}/dt) is applied to the drain-source terminals. Therefore, one has

$$C_{GD} \frac{d(v_{DS} - v_{GS})}{dt} = \frac{v_{GS}}{R_G} + C_{GS} \frac{dv_{GS}}{dt} \quad (13-2)$$

Rearrange (13-2) and one can get

$$v_{GS} = R_G C_{GD} \frac{dv_{DS}}{dt} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \right) \quad (13-3)$$

where the time constant $\tau = R_G(C_{GS} + C_{GD}) = R_G C_{ISS}$, and dv_{DS}/dt is a constant number.

The time-domain waveform for (13-3) is displayed in Fig. 13-11. As seen, the gate voltage v_{GS} is approaching its steady state value in an exponential way. The final asymptotical level is proportional to R_G , C_{GD} and V_{DS} ramp rate, while the approaching speed is determined by R_G and C_{ISS} .

Fig. 13-11 Time-domain waveform for (13-3)

Let $R_G = R_{GI}$, meaning that the MOSFET gate is directly shorted to its source, and assume

$$R_{GI} C_{GD} \frac{dv_{DS}}{dt} > V_{GS(th)} \quad (13-4)$$

then

$$\frac{dv_{DS}}{dt} > \frac{V_{GS(th)}}{R_{GI} C_{GD}} \quad (13-5)$$

which means that under this dv_{DS}/dt , the induced turn-on must happen as long as the voltage ramp is applied for enough long time and no extra measures are taken. For this reason, the term $V_{GS(th)}/(R_{GI} C_{GD})$ is usually defined as the MOSFET natural dv/dt limit [9].

However, if

$$R_G C_{GD} \frac{dv_{DS}}{dt} < V_{GS(th)} \quad (13-6)$$

then the false trigger will not happen anyway under this voltage ramp.

A more commonly seen condition is

$$R_G C_{GD} \frac{dv_{DS}}{dt} > V_{GS(th)} \quad (13-7)$$

Under this condition, the false trigger may or may not happen, depending on the exponential term, or the time constant, $R_G C_{ISS}$. If dv_{DS}/dt ends (i.e. switching transient finishes) before v_{GS} hits the gate threshold, there won't be induced turn-on. Otherwise false trigger will happen.

Equations (13-3) through (13-7) qualitatively explain the influence of the circuit parameters on the MOSFET dv/dt induced turn-on, from which the following methods can be concluded to mitigate the false trigger [13]:

(1) Reducing the gate loop total resistance R_G . This method mainly decreases the V_{GS} steady state level to be lower than $V_{GS(th)}$ under dv_{DS}/dt , as suggested by Fig. 13-11.

(2) Paralleling external capacitance to C_{GS} . This method mainly postpones the moment when v_{GS} hits the threshold, so that the false trigger won't happen during the switching transients. However the disadvantages are longer delay time, lower switching speed, and more gate drive power loss.

(3) Providing a negative turn-off bias ($-V_{OFF}$). This method mainly increases the gate threshold margin from $V_{GS(th)}$ to $(V_{GS(th)} + V_{OFF})$. However, in order to achieve this, a negative power supply is usually needed for each MOSFET, which will increase the total cost of the phase-leg.

III.3. Gate Drive Circuit Design

The gate drive circuit for the phase-leg should have the following functions:

- (1) Providing electrical isolation between the power stage and the control stage;
- (2) Possessing large enough output current capability;
- (3) Possessing protection functions such as under-voltage lock-out (UVLO) and DESAT, etc;
- (4) Being able to suppress the dv/dt induced turn-on.

Based on these considerations, the gate driver chip selection is narrowed down to the optocoupler gate drivers with the active Miller clamp function. The active Miller clamp is a technology where an additional transistor is connected between gate and source of the MOSFET to produce a low impedance path and prevent the Miller current from flowing through the gate driver [13]. Two manufacturers are providing chips with this technology, Avago and ST. Table 13-6 summarizes these devices.

Table 13-6 Optocoupler gate drivers with active Miller clamp function

Manufacturer	Part No.	I_{OUT} (A)	DESAT	UVLO	Fault Feedback	Others
Avago	ACPL-330	1.5	y	y	y	
Avago	ACPL-331	1.5	y	y	y	
Avago	ACPL-332	2.5	y	y	y	
Avago	ACPL-333	2.5	y	y	y	Auto fault reset

ST	TD350	0.75 / 1.2	y	y	y	Non-isolated, two-step turn-off, separate source/sink outputs
ST	TD351	0.75 / 1.0		y		Non-isolated, two-step turn-off
ST	IDT10S60C	0.75 / 1.0	y	y		Non-isolated

From the above table, ST gate drivers are non-isolated and are thus ruled out. Avago ACPL-331J is finally selected in this design. This chip has 890 V maximum working insulation voltage, 1.5 A maximum peak output current, 180 ns typical propagation delay, 1.7 A Miller current shunt capability, and UVLO / DESAT protection functions [14]. The final gate drive circuit design is shown in Fig. 13-12.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-12 Gate drive circuit schematics. (a) Gate driver, (b) Gate driver power supply

A. Output Current Enhancement

Instead of driving MOSFETs directly by ACPL-331J, a totem-pole gate driver IXYS IXDN414 is added in-between to enhance the driving current capability. The IXDN414 is a high-speed, high-current, non-isolated gate driver designed to drive the MOSFET to their minimum switching time and maximum practical frequency limits [15]. The peak source / sink current is 14 A for this chip thanks to its very small output resistance, and the rise / fall time is around 10 ns when driving 5 nF capacitive load – similar load as the input capacitance of the selected CoolMOS. IXDN414 uses MOSFET totem-pole and thus the required input current is very small (at μA level). Considering this, ACPL-331J is chosen over the other optocouplers of the same series with higher output current.

B. Active Miller Clamping Transistor

An additional PNP transistor DIODES DPLS325E is added to boost the Miller clamping capability of ACPL-331J. This design is based on the following considerations. (1) The peak Miller clamping current of ACPL-331 is 1.7 A, while this current can be pushed to 6 A with the use of DPLS325E. (2) Because of IXDN414, the optocoupler cannot be placed close enough to the MOSFET it's driving and therefore the loop between the MOSFET gate and the optocoupler's internal Miller clamping switch is not optimized, which may still cause gate voltage oscillations during the shunting process and then lead to false trigger [13]-[14]. The additional PNP transistor, however, can be placed as close to the MOSFET as possible to minimize the gate-to-source loop, creating a very small shunting impedance. In this case, the transistor's base terminal will be controlled by ACPL-331J's internal clamping switch with bigger loop impedance. Nevertheless, this loop is less important as the transistor has high gain and the base current is small.

Note that the selection of the base-emitter bias resistor (R16 in Fig. 13-12 (a)) is also important for the Miller clamping effect of the transistor. ACPL-331J uses the V_{CLAMP} pin to measure the gate voltage and control the internal switch accordingly, and in this design V_{CLAMP} is connected to the base of the transistor, while the emitter and MOSFET gate has the same voltage. Therefore, putting too big resistance between base and emitter will delay the sensing of the gate voltage by V_{CLAMP} pin and delay the turn-on moment of the transistor to shunt the Miller current in time. Contrarily, using too small resistance will cause too much Miller current to flow through the base instead of the collector. Based on both the experiment and the simulation, 100 Ω is chosen to achieve the optimal performance.

C. Input Resistors

A total of 320 Ω input resistance is needed to provide enough input current to turn-on the optocoupler. This resistance is split into two 160 Ω resistances (R5 and R9 in Fig. 13-12 (a)) to enhance the common-mode transient immunity (CMTI) of the chip [16].

D. Bypass Capacitors

The selection and the layout of the bypass capacitors in Fig. 13-12 (a) also play an important role in the performance of the gate driver circuit, as the high transient gate currents are actually drawn from these capacitors to turn-on and turn-off the MOSFET. Generally speaking, the bypass capacitors should be placed directly across the bias and the ground pins of the driver chip, and the total value should be no less than 50 times the load capacitance. SMT ceramic and tantalum capacitors are usually better choices as they have the lowest ESRs and ESLs [9][10][17].

In this design, a 0.1 μF ceramic cap and a 10 μF tantalum cap (C1 / C2 and C7 / C8 in Fig. 13-12 (a)) are used for each bias (VCC and VEE), which is more than 100 times the input capacitance of the selected MOSFET (~ 7 nF), to provide stable bias voltages for high-frequency operation.

E. Gate Drive Power Supplies and Gate Resistors

A negative turn-off bias is desired in this work to push the MOSFET switching speed without suffering from the dv/dt induced turn-on. For this design, a 15 V turn-on bias and a -2.5 V turn-off bias are proposed for the gate driver. Generally for CoolMOS, the $R_{DS(on)}$ won't change too much when the gate voltage increases from 10 V to 20 V. However, 15 V is still chosen in this case simply because ACPL-331J has an UVLO protection of 12 V. On the other hand, -2.5 V is chosen for the turn-off bias in order to reduce the total required gate charge and the output power from the power supplies. As these power supplies are supposed to provide bias voltages for the floated side of the gate driver, isolated DC-DC converters are selected in this design.

The following equation can be used to determine the maximum output power of the power supply [9][10][17]:

$$P_{GATE} = V_{DRIVE} \cdot Q_G \cdot f_{sw} \quad (13-8)$$

where V_{DRIVE} is the total driving voltage, Q_G is the total gate charge, and f_{sw} is the switching frequency. Note that charging and discharging the MOSFET gate require the same amount of energy, regardless of how fast or slow it occurs [18].

Considering that V_{DRIVE} is constant, the average output current of the gate drive power supply can be derived from (13-8) as

$$I_{GATE(av)} = Q_G \cdot f_{sw} \quad (13-9)$$

Fig. 13-13 shows the gate charge curve of the selected MOSFET APT47N60BCF. As seen, the total gate charge is $(390 + 15) = 405$ nC for -2.5 V to 15 V driving voltage and 480 V V_{DS} bias.

Fig. 13-13 Gate charge curve of APT47N60BCF

Substituting these numbers into (13-8) and (13-9), and assuming 500 kHz switching frequency which is the target of this work, one can get the required power of

$$P_{GATE(on)} = 15 \times 405 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 3.04 \text{ W}$$

$$P_{GATE(off)} = 2.5 \times 405 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 0.51 \text{ W}$$

and the average gate current of

$$I_{GATE(av)} = 405 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 0.2 \text{ A}$$

Therefore, for the 15 V power supply, the maximum output capability should be greater than 3 W and 200 mA in order to support the high frequency operation up to 500 kHz. Besides power, another critical parameter in the power supply selection is the isolation capacitance between the input and the output. Generally, this capacitance should be as small as possible to reduce the coupling between input and output due to the common mode dv/dt.

Several DC-DC converter manufacturers have been surveyed to find the proper power supply, including Traco, XP Power, V-Infinity, and Murata PS, etc. XP JHM0624S15 is finally chosen to provide VCC for the floated side of the gate driver, which accepts 24 V input voltage, generates 6 W, 15 V and 400 mA output, and has an I/O isolation capacitance of 20 pF.

For VEE, because 2.5 V is not a standard output voltage for most isolated DC-DC converters, a 5 V power supply XP IL2405S is chosen to work with a linear regulator National LM1117 to step down the voltage. Considering that half of the output power will be dissipated by the linear regulator, IL2405S is capable of 5 V, 2 W, and 400 mA output, with enough margins left. A typical I/O capacitance of 60 pF can be found for this device.

To further improve the common-mode noise immunity, a common-mode choke is connected in series with each power supply on the floated side, as shown in Fig. 13-12 (b).

It is also important to note that $P_{GATE(on)} \approx 3 \text{ W}$ is the total power required for the gate drive power supply to charge the input capacitance C_{ISS} of the MOSFET. If linear capacitance is assumed for C_{ISS} , approximately half of $P_{GATE(on)}$ will be finally stored in C_{ISS} and the rest of the power will be dissipated through the resistors along the gate loop, including the driver output resistor R_{DRIVE} , gate resistor $R_{G(on)}$, and MOSFET gate internal resistor R_{GI} . For the current design, $R_{DRIVE} \approx 0.6 \Omega$, $R_{GI} \approx 0.6 \Omega$, and $R_{G(on)}$ is generally several Ohms, depending on the required switching speed. With this said, most of the power will be dissipated through $R_{G(on)}$ by heat. If $R_{G(on)} = 5 \Omega$, then

$$P_{RG(on)} \approx \frac{1}{2} \frac{R_{G(on)}}{R_{DRIVE} + R_{G(on)} + R_{GI}} P_{GATE(on)} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{5}{0.6 + 5 + 0.6} \times 3.04 \approx 1.23 \text{ W} \quad (13-10)$$

For the turn-off gate resistance, the result is similar. Enough margins should thus be set to avoid over-heating of these resistors under high frequency operations. As illustrated in Fig. 13-12 (a), three 1 W SMD 2512 resistors are paralleled to act as the turn-on and turn-off gate resistors respectively in this design. As the experiments will show later, however, the temperatures of these resistors will still be over 100 °C when the MOSFETs are driven at 500 kHz.

IV. Control Circuit Design

IV.1. Control Scheme and CPLD Selection

The control scheme diagram of the phase-leg is illustrated in Fig. 13-14, with (a) being the block diagram and (b) being the logic gate diagram.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-14 Control scheme of the phase-leg

There are four major parts in the control circuits. The input PWM signals (PWM1 and PWM2) are pre-conditioned through a dead-time generation block before reaching the gate driver. The over-current protection is implemented using the DESAT and fault feedback functions of ACPL-331J. The over-temperature protection, on the other hand, is realized by comparing the sensed heatsink temperatures with preset references. Both protections, when triggered, will send fault signals (OTP and OCP) to the up-level controller and light on the respective LED indicators on the phase-leg board. Besides these, there is one additional over-current protection reset signal (OC_RST) to reset the fault state, and one shutdown signal (SHTDN) to turn-off both the top and bottom switches if necessary by blocking the PWM signals.

To simplify the digital part of the control circuits, a CPLD XC9536-15VQ44I from Xilinx is chosen to coordinate the dead-time generation and the protection functions. This CPLD has 36 macrocells and supports both 3.3 V and 5 V operations.

IV.2. Dead-Time Generation

In order for the phase-leg to be “general-purpose”, the dead-time generation block should have the following functions:

(1) Independent top and bottom input signals are required to provide the maximum driving flexibility for the phase-leg.

(2) Based on the switching speed, the gate signals of the phase-leg should keep an intrinsic minimum dead time when the input signals from the controller have a dead time less than that. This is to prevent the phase-leg from possible shoot-through failure.

(3) If it is necessary for the phase-leg to have longer dead time, such as in some ZVS operating conditions, the gate signals should be able to follow the dead time of the input signals, as long as this time is greater than the intrinsic minimum value.

These functions are important for the phase-leg to keep its generality in different topologies and operating conditions. In hard-switching situations, the input signals usually have fixed dead time and the proposed dead-time generation block can prevent the possible overlapping of the turn-on signals. On the other hand, in soft-switching conditions, longer dead time of the gate signals may be required for the commutation to finish, and this time can be actively controlled by the input signals.

Fig. 13-15 (a) shows the digital logic circuit to realize the above functions. Fig. 13-15 (b) shows an example of the timing diagram.

As seen, whether one input signal can pass through the AND gate depends on the other ENABLE input, which is further dependent on the state of the other output signal. The key to realizing the above mentioned functions is to have different propagation delays of the inverter for low-to-high and high-to-low transients. More specifically, t_{PLH} ($= t_{EN}$) should be greater than t_{PHL} ($= t_{DIS}$) for the inverter.

Take Fig. 13-15 (b) for example. Assume that the initial conditions for TOP_IN and BOT_IN are H and L respectively. It is easy to derive that TOP_EN = H, BOT_EN = L, and TOP_OUT = H, BOT_OUT = L. When TOP_IN changes to L, TOP_OUT becomes L after the AND gate delay time of t_{PHL} . Because BOT_IN becomes H after $t_{controller}$, which is less than the low-to-high delay time t_{EN} of the inverter, BOT_OUT needs to wait for BOT_EN to swap its state. Therefore, although the dead time of the input signal is $t_{controller}$, the real dead time seen by the gate driver is actually $t_{EN} + t_{PLH} \approx t_{EN}$.

Fig. 13-15 Dead-time generation function. (a) Digital logic, (b) timing diagram

On the other hand, if assuming that the initial conditions for TOP_IN and BOT_IN are L and H respectively, it is easy to derive that $TOP_EN = L$, $BOT_EN = H$, and $TOP_OUT = L$,

BOT_OUT = H. BOT_IN swaps to L and after $t_{\text{controller}}$, TOP_IN swaps to H. Because $t_{\text{controller}}$ is longer than t_{EN} this time, TOP_EN has already become H before TOP_IN changes to H state. Therefore, the output signals will have the same dead time of $t_{\text{controller}}$ as the input signals.

In summary, the real dead time of the gate drive signals will be determined by the following equation:

$$t_{\text{DeadTime}} = \begin{cases} t_{\text{Intrinsic}} & \text{if } t_{\text{Controller}} \leq t_{\text{Intrinsic}} \\ t_{\text{Controller}} & \text{if } t_{\text{Controller}} > t_{\text{Intrinsic}} \end{cases} \quad (13-11)$$

A realization of Fig. 13-15 (a) using analog circuit is shown in Fig. 13-16. For high-to-low transient of the inverter, the diode will be conducting and the inverter toggles its state at once. For low-to-high transient, however, the charge stored in the capacitor slowly discharges through the resistor, resulting in a longer delay time for the inverter to toggle. In this way different propagation delays can be achieved.

Fig. 13-16 Analog circuit for the dead time generation

For the CPLD implementation of this function, the pure digital circuit illustrated in Fig. 13-17 can be used to replace the inverter and the R-C-D network in Fig. 13-16, without additional analog circuit components. Basically in this circuit, an input signal is passed through two channels with different delays, and then recombined by the multiplexer to produce the different delay time for the rise edge and the fall edge.

Fig. 13-17 Digital circuit for the dead time generation. (a) Digital logic, (b) timing diagram

The proposed dead-time generation circuit is also verified through experiments. Fig. 13-18 (a) shows the conceptual circuit with color coded signals, while Fig. 13-18 (b) to (d) display the input signals with 50%, 60%, and 40% duty cycles respectively, and the corresponding output waveforms as well. As seen, a minimum of 80 ns dead time is preserved for the 50% and 60% duty cycle cases. However, when the input dead time is increased to 200 ns for the 40% duty cycle case, the output signals follow the same dead time as the inputs.

(c)

(d)

Fig. 13-18 Test waveforms of the dead-time generation circuit

IV.3. Over-Current Protection

Two options are recommended by the manufacturer to perform the DESAT over-current protection for ACPL-331J, which are shown in Fig. 13-19. Fig. 13-19 (a) uses the internal charging current from the DESAT pin to charge the blanking capacitor C_{BLANK} to produce the blanking time and the voltage bias on the DESAT pin. Fig. 13-19 (b), on the other hand, introduces another current to charge C_{BLANK} from the output of the optocoupler through R_B , in which way the blanking time and the over-current trigger level can be more flexibly controlled [19]. This option is finally adopted and is slightly modified in this design, as illustrated in Fig. 13-20.

Fig. 13-19 Two optional DESAT over-current protection circuits

Fig. 13-20 DESAT circuit used in the phase-leg

In Fig. 13-20, D4 is a 600 V diode with fast reverse recovery and low junction capacitance, whose cathode is connected to the drain of the MOSFET. When the MOSFET is turned-on, the anode voltage of D4 (V_{D4}) will be clamped at V_{DS} plus V_{FWD} of the diode. Since the MOSFET V_{DS} is approximately linearly proportional to its channel current, the MOSFET current can thus be detected by V_{D4} . This voltage is further divided by R1 and R6, and the divided voltage V_{DESAT} will be fed to the DESAT pin of ACPL-331J. Node V_{D4} is also connected to the output of ACPL-331J (V_{OUT}) through a current limiting resistor R15, in order to draw some amount of current to charge C_{BLANK} . In parallel with C_{BLANK} are one Schottky diode and one Zener diode which limit V_{DESAT} to be within the safe range of -0.2 V to 8.2 V.

The values of these resistances and capacitance in Fig. 13-20 are critical as they determine the overall performance of the over-current protection. The influence and selection of each of these components will be explained in the following paragraphs. To simplify the analysis, D1, D2 and D6, R17 are first neglected, and R6 are assumed to be zero so that there is no voltage dividing. This will bring us back to the original circuit shown in Fig. 13-19 (b).

Fig. 13-21 (a) shows the equivalent DESAT circuit, and Fig. 13-21 (b) illustrates the current directions during the turn-on process. When the gate drive voltage changes from low to high, V_{DRIVE} will charge the capacitor C_{BLANK} through R_1 , and the capacitor voltage V_{DESAT} will increase accordingly. Due to the turn-on delay of the MOSFET, V_{DS} won't drop to zero at once. During this delay interval, D_{DESAT} will keep blocking voltage and V_{DESAT} will keep rising. Therefore, C_{BLANK} needs to be carefully chosen such that it won't rise too fast to trigger the protection before the MOSFET turns-on normally. After the MOSFET is completely switched on, V_{DS} drops to less than V_{DESAT} which makes D_{DESAT} start to conduct and discharge C_{BLANK} . Finally V_{DESAT} will be clamped at $V_{DS} + V_{DDESAT}$.

During turn-off, after the gate drive voltage drops from high to low, C_{BLANK} starts discharging through both R_1 and R_2 , and V_{DESAT} starts decreasing. D_{DESAT} won't block voltage until after the MOSFET turn-off delay time. After that, however, there are also two currents that will charge C_{BLANK} . One is the reverse recovery current of D_{DESAT} , and the other is the charging current of the diode junction capacitor. These two pulse currents will produce a voltage spike on C_{BLANK} which may falsely trigger the protection. This is illustrated in Fig. 13-21 (b).

To solve this problem, an additional resistor-diode (R-D) branch has been proposed to shunt the pulse currents, as displayed in Fig. 13-22. This branch will not affect the turn-on process, but for turn-off it can provide an extra current shunting path to clamp V_{DESAT} . This R-D branch is composed by D6 and R17 in Fig. 13-20. It needs to be noted that, however, if a negative turn-off bias is used, such as -2.5 V in this design, a static current will flow through R1, R6, D6 and R17 when the MOSFET is not switching. This current can be controlled by carefully calculating the resistance values.

Fig. 13-21 The operation principle of the DESAT circuit. (a) Equivalent circuit, (b) turn-on process, (c) turn-off process

Fig. 13-22 DESAT circuit with the additional R-D branch

Simulations have also been performed to show the individual effect of these components. Fig. 13-23 shows the simulation circuit in Saber, which is basically a high-side double-pulse tester. The shaded part is the DESAT circuit. Fig. 13-24 through Fig. 13-27 exhibits the effects of C_{BLANK} , R_1 , D_{DESAT} junction cap, as well as the R-D branch. As suggested by Fig. 13-24 and Fig. 13-25, too small C_{BLANK} and R_1 will result in too fast charge / discharge speeds of the capacitor, and consequently cause voltage spikes during turn-on and turn-off transients, which may falsely trigger the protection. Fig. 13-26 suggests that a DESAT diode with smaller junction capacitance is better as it minimizes the pulse charging current during turn-off. With the R-D branch, however, V_{DESAT} can be quickly clamped to V_{DRIVE} during turn-off to avoid any false-triggering voltage spikes, as illustrated by Fig. 13-27.

Fig. 13-23 DESAT simulation circuit in Saber

Fig. 13-24 Effect of C_{BLANK}

Fig. 13-25 Effect of R_1

Fig. 13-26 Effect of C_J of D_{DESAT}

Fig. 13-27 Effect of R-D branch

The above analyses pose the following requirements for the selection of the DESAT circuit components.

(1) R_1

A too small R_1 will cause V_{DESAT} spike during turn-on due to the overly fast C_{BLANK} charging speed, which may falsely trigger the protection. Meanwhile, this will also increase the static current drawn from the gate driver, causing more burdens on the power supply.

Contrarily, a too big R_1 will slow down the slew rate of V_{DESAT} and lower the sensitivity of the protection.

(2) C_{BLANK}

A too small C_{BLANK} will cause V_{DESAT} spikes at both turn-on and turn-off moments, leading to potential false triggering. A too big C_{BLANK} will have the same effect as a too big R_1 .

(3) D_{DESAT}

Besides meeting the blocking voltage requirement, the DESAT diode should also have very fast reverse recovery characteristic and very small junction capacitance to reduce the pulse currents during turn-off.

IV.4. Over-Temperature Protection

The over-temperature protection of the phase-leg is simply achieved by a comparison circuit, with a comparator (Analog ADCMP601) with hysteresis and a thermistor (Ametherm PANR103395-408) with negative temperature coefficient (NTC). The circuit is shown in Fig. 13-28. On each phase-leg board, there are two sets of such circuit to sense the temperatures of both MOSFETs. The thermistors can be mounted very close to the MOSFETs on the heatsink to sense the case temperatures. A proper hysteresis is set for the comparator based on the voltage divider networks, such that the protection will be triggered at a higher temperature and automatically reset at a lower temperature. A potentiometer (RP2 in Fig. 13-28) is also utilized to adjust the trigger level, which is dependent on the power dissipation of the devices under worst case operation and the thermal resistances of the cooling system.

Fig. 13-28 Over-temperature protection circuit

IV.5. Schematics of the Si-Version Phase-Leg

Fig. 13-29 through Fig. 13-32 shows the schematics of the phase-leg.

Fig. 13-29 Schematic of the power stage

Fig. 13-30 Schematic of the gate drivers

Fig. 13-32 Schematic of the control circuit

V. PCB Design

V.1. Overall Board Layout

Fig. 13-33 shows the overall board layout of the phase-leg PEBB. Basically the PCB is divided into two sections: the power stage and the control stage, with each stage on one end of the board, as shown in Fig. 13-33 (a). This design clearly separates the high-power and the low-power parts of the circuit, and minimizes the interference between them. From the side view, one can see that the power devices are mounted under the phase-leg board and 90 degrees bent to be able to land on the heat spreader or heatsink. Bypass capacitors are provided between the DC rails to filter out the high-frequency ringing during the switching transients. The power terminals can be connected to the external circuitry by screwing an additional DC bus board on them.

Fig. 13-33 Overall phase-leg board layout. (a) Top view, (b) side view

V.2. Power Stage Layout

One may already notice the non-conventional layout of the power stage from Fig. 13-33 (a), where the top switch is put together with the bottom freewheeling diode and vice versa. This consideration is based on the parametric study results presented in Chapter 4, which have concluded that the main switching loop inductance is the most critical parasitic impedance that needs to be minimized to reduce the high-frequency oscillation during the switching transients. In that study, the conclusion is obtained from a double-pulse tester which contains a switch pair of a top diode and a bottom MOSFET. This conclusion is intuitively reasonable because the commutation only occurs between these two devices in a switch pair. As illustrated in Fig. 13-34 (a), during switch turn-off, a positive di/dt appears in the freewheeling diode and the same di/dt with a negative sign appears in the switch, because these two currents add up to an almost constant load current during the switching process. Equivalently, there is a current with negative di/dt flowing from +VDC to -VDC, i.e. the main switching loop. This di/dt produces voltage drop on the loop inductance which will add to the DC bus voltage, and also resonates with the junction capacitances of the devices, causing both overshoot and ringing on the MOSFET's V_{DS} and I_D . The same analysis also applies to the switch pair with top switch and bottom diode, which is displayed in Fig. 13-34 (b).

From this stand point of view, a phase-leg should be treated as two switch pairs rather than top and bottom MOSFET/diode pairs. Therefore, it is more reasonable to put the devices in a

switch pair close enough to each other to reduce the main switching loop, as suggested by Fig. 13-35.

Fig. 13-34 Switch pairs

Fig. 13-35 Conventional phase-leg vs. improved phase-leg

This conclusion directly leads to the power stage layout design in this work. As seen from Fig. 13-36, the DC bus terminals are put close to each other on the centerline of the PCB board, and the two switch pairs are placed on each side of the centerline to minimize the main switching loops. Big copper planes are used in the middle layers for the DC bus to provide better impedance characteristics. Eleven ceramic bypass capacitors (totally $1.1 \mu\text{F}$) are paralleled between the bus rails to shunt the high-frequency ringing current. The position of the middle point, however, is less important as it is connected to the load usually with large impedance.

Fig. 13-36 Power stage layout of the phase-leg PCB.
 (a) Top layer, (b) mid layer 1, (c) mid layer 2, (d) bottom layer

V.3. Gate Drive Circuit Layout

According to Chapter 4, the gate drive loop should also be minimized in the phase-leg. In this work, the design rule is to minimize the Miller clamping transistor loop first, and then the gate drive loop. The corresponding PCB layout is shown below.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-37 Gate drive circuit layout. (a) Top side, (b) bottom side

V.4. Evaluations of PCB Parasitics

The parasitic impedances of the PCB have been evaluated by means of both measurement and simulation. The measurements are performed on the real PCB with an Agilent 4294 impedance analyzer, while the simulations are performed on the PCB model created with Ansoft Q3D. The related issues regarding the measurement and simulation of package parasitics can be found in Chapter 3 and Chapter 5 respectively, and won't be discussed in detail here. The inductances of the major loops, namely the main switching loops and the top gate driver loops (the bottom gate driver layout is symmetrical), have been evaluated, whose results are shown in Fig. 13-38.

Fig. 13-38 Simulation and measurement of the PCB loop inductances

As seen from the figure, the measured main switching loop inductances are only around 17 nH for the two switch pairs, thanks to the improved layout design. The gate driver loops have about twice the inductance of the main loops. These loops cannot be made smaller due to several factors: (1) the Miller clamping transistor is placed closest to the MOSFET, pushing the gate driver away; (2) the package of the gate resistors is big (2512) and six of such resistors are paralleled for each MOSFET in order to take more dissipation under high frequency operation; and (3) there is also a MOSFET mounting hole on the PCB board which can be found from Fig. 13-37.

The simulated inductances are a little bigger than the measurements, but still correctly reflect the relationship between the loop area and the loop inductance, which indicates that the simulation results are trustworthy. These results will be used later in the phase-leg simulations.

A comparison has also been made between the conventional phase-leg layout and the improved layout. To make the comparison, another PCB is designed with the regular layout, as shown in Fig. 13-39. Fig. 13-40 shows the comparison of simulated switching loop inductances between the two layouts. As seen, for both switch pairs the conventional layout will have bigger loop inductances. Moreover, the loops are less symmetrical in inductance for the regular layout.

Fig. 13-39 Conventional power stage layout for comparison. (a) Top layer, (b) mid layer 1, (c) mid layer 2, (d) bottom layer

Fig. 13-40 A comparison of main switching loop inductances between conventional and improved layouts

V.5. PCBs of the Si-Version Phase-Leg

Fig. 13-41 through Fig. 13-44 shows the four layers of the phase-leg PCB. The final board is $142 \times 85 \text{ mm}^2$ in size.

Fig. 13-43 Middle layer 2 of Si-version phase-leg

VI. Testing and Characterization of Phase-Leg PEBB

This section presents the testing and characterization processes of the Si-version phase-leg. Pictures of the phase-leg PCB board are displayed in Fig. 13-45.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-45 Si-version phase-leg. (a) Front side, (b) back side

VI.1. Control Propagation Delay

The control propagation delay is defined as the delay time from the input of the CPLD to the output of the gate driver. This time is basically the same for both the rising edge and the falling edge. As Fig. 13-46 shows, the delay time is around 200 ns, most of which is contributed by the optocoupler (around 180 ns).

Fig. 13-46 Control delay time. Yellow & cyan – inputs; magenta & green – outputs

VI.2. Power Dissipation of Gate Resistors

This test is to verify the selection of the gate resistors. As previously said, the gate resistors will dissipate around 1.25 W under 500 kHz operation. Therefore, six 1 W, SMD 2512 resistors are used for $R_{G(on)}$ and $R_{G(off)}$ respectively to withstand such high dissipation. Fig. 13-47 displays an infrared image of the PCB board when only the top side gate resistors are driven at 500 kHz. As seen, these resistors are the hottest area on the board which reaches over 100 °C. Although this is still safely under the maximum working temperature of the resistors, which is 150 °C, it is still desirable to have some forced air blowing the surface of the board to cool down the temperature.

Fig. 13-47 Infrared image of the gate resistors when driven at 500 kHz

VI.3. Double-Pulse Switching Tests

Fig. 13-48 shows the double-pulse test setup of the phase-leg. A capacitor bank with IGBT over-current protection is connected between the DC voltage source and the phase-leg to provide the large transient current, and to prevent potential shoot-through failure during the test.

The phase-leg is also mounted on an aluminum heat spreader and placed on the hotplate in order to characterize the switching performances under different junction temperatures. As part of the hardware debugging process, the phase-leg has gone through a systematic testing process as illustrated in Fig. 13-49 (a) through (f). The test first starts with a standard double-pulse test circuit, with only the bottom MOSFET and the top freewheeling diode, in step (a). In step (b) and (c), the bottom freewheeling diode and the top MOSFET are added to the phase-leg. Note that in (c) the MOSFET gate is shorted to source (or negative bias) to avoid dv/dt induced turn-on. Step (d) is similar to (c) except that the MOSFET is turned-off through normal gate resistor. In step (e), the high-side Miller clamping transistor is finally added to the phase-leg. Step (f) is also testing the complete phase-leg but in a high-side double-pulse configuration.

Fig. 13-48 Phase-leg test setup

Fig. 13-49 Phase-leg test sequence

Main concerns in the phase-leg testing process include the switching speed (delay times and slew rates), the device stresses (voltage and current overshoots and ringing), and the cross-talking between top and bottom devices, all of which can be adjusted through different turn-on and turn-off gate resistances. By hardware test iterations and simulation verifications, the gate resistances have finally been reduced to 5 Ω for turn-on and 2 Ω for turn-off. Typical switching waveforms of the phase-leg under 300 V, 12.6 A load conditions are displayed in Fig. 13-50.

The double-pulse tests have been repeated at 300 V, under varying load currents from 5 A to 20 A, and under both 25 °C and 125 °C junction temperatures. Switching waveforms, times and energies have all been recorded for these tests and will form part of the phase-leg “datasheet” in the later section.

(b)

Fig. 13-50 Typical switching waveforms under 300 V, 12.6 A.
(a) Low-side DPT, (b) high-side DPT

VI.4. Cross-Talking Test

Cross-talking of the top and bottom switches is measured in the high-side double-pulse test, where the waveforms (V_{GS} , V_{DS} and I_D) of the bottom MOSFET are measured with single-ended passive probes. The main concern of testing cross-talking in the high-side DPT instead of the low-side one is to avoid the use of the differential probes which are sensitive to the common mode noises. Fig. 13-51 shows the waveforms of the low-side double-pulse test, where a differential probe connected to CH4 (green) clamps both of its clips to the source of the top MOSFET. Theoretically this voltage should be constantly zero as the probe is actually “shorted”. However, great ringing can be observed in the differential probe measurement due to the common-mode dv/dt during switching process, which would make the cross-talking measurement inaccurate.

Fig. 13-51 Common-mode noise of the differential probe

Measuring the low-side waveforms while switching the high-side MOSFET will solve the above problem, considering that the circuit structure and the PCB layout are basically symmetrical. Fig. 13-52 shows the test waveforms of the bottom MOSFET in a high-side DPT under 300 V, 12.6 A switching condition. The dv/dt induced turn-on is supposed to happen during the turn-on process of the top MOSFET. As seen from the figure, the dv/dt applied on the bottom MOSFET is 12 V/ns, while the measured peak V_{GS_BOT} is about 3.4 V, less than the gate threshold voltage of the MOSFET – thanks to the Miller clamping circuit in the gate driver. Note that the measurement loop also contributes to the spikes in V_{GS_BOT} . In this sense the actual clamping effect is better than what is observed.

Fig. 13-52 Cross-talking waveforms in a high-side DPT under 300 V, 12.6 A switching condition

VI.5. Si-Version Phase-Leg Datasheet

As a modularized design, the datasheet of the phase-leg PEBB should provide the users with enough information on the terminal behaviors of the phase-leg in order for them to perform the converter design. Based on this consideration, the following data can be summarized and organized in a “datasheet” form.

A. Absolute Maximum Ratings

($T_C = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ unless otherwise specified.)

Power stage:

Symbol	Characteristic (Test Conditions)	Value	Unit
V_{DC}	DC bus voltage	400	V
BV_{DSS}	Drain-source voltage	600	V
I_D	Continuous drain current Continuous drain current @ $T_C = 100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	46 29	A
I_{DM}	Pulsed drain current (Repetitive, pulse width limited by T_{JMAX})	115	A
I_S	Continuous freewheeling diode current Continuous freewheeling diode current @ $T_C = 150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	30 20	A

I_{SM}	Pulsed freewheeling diode current (Repetitive, 10 ms half sine wave)	134	A
T_{JMAX}	Maximum junction temperature	150	°C

Control stage:

Symbol	Characteristic (Test Conditions)	Value	Unit
V_{IN}	Control supply voltage	24 ± 10 %	V

B. Static Electrical Characteristics

($T_C = 25\text{ °C}$ unless otherwise specified.)

Power stage:

Symbol	Characteristic (Test Conditions)	Value	Unit
I_{DSS}	Drain-source leakage current ($V_{DS} = 600\text{ V}$, off-state)	20	μA
	Drain-source leakage current ($V_{DS} = 600\text{ V}$, off-state) @ $T_C = 150\text{ °C}$	5000	
$R_{DS(on)}$	Drain-source on-state resistance ($I_D = 29\text{ A}$)	0.083	Ω
	Drain-source on-state resistance ($I_D = 29\text{ A}$) @ $T_C = 150\text{ °C}$	0.208	
V_F	Reverse conduction voltage ($I_S = 10\text{ A}$)	1.5	V
	Reverse conduction voltage ($I_S = 10\text{ A}$) @ $T_C = 175\text{ °C}$	2.0	

Control stage:

Symbol	Characteristic (Test Conditions)	Value	Unit
V_{IL}	Low-level input voltage	< 0.8	V
V_{IH}	High-level input voltage	> 2.0	V
V_{OL}	Output low voltage ($I_{OL} = 24\text{ mA}$)	< 0.5	V
V_{OH}	Output high voltage ($I_{OH} = -4.0\text{ mA}$)	> 2.4	V

C. Dynamic Electrical Characteristics

($T_C = 25\text{ °C}$ unless otherwise specified.)

Power stage:

Symbol	Characteristic (Test Conditions)	Value	Unit
t_{d_on}	Turn-on delay time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	37	ns
t_{on_s}	Turn-on transient time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	56	ns
t_{on_c}	Total turn-on time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	93	ns
t_{d_off}	Turn-off delay time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	120	ns
t_{off_s}	Turn-off transient time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	6	ns
t_{off_c}	Total turn-on time (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)	125	ns
t_{dt_min}	Minimum dead time to avoid shoot-through (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 5\text{ A}$) @ $T_C = 125\text{ °C}$	190	ns
E_{on}	Turn-on switching energy	251	μJ

	(Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 20\text{ A}$)		
E_{off}	Turn-off switching energy (Diode clamped inductive load, $V_{DS} = 300\text{ V}$, $I_D = 5\text{ A}$)	20	μJ

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-53 Switching times. (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off

Fig. 13-54 Switching energies

Fig. 13-55 Switching waveforms and definitions. (Left) turn-on, (right) turn-off

VII. Phase-Leg Modeling

Two models have been built for the phase-leg for different study purposes. One model is built with detailed PCB parasitics model to predict the switching transients before testing, and to help verify the hardware design. For the other model, the PCB model is replaced by lumped loop inductances to achieve less accurate but faster simulation speed, which is mainly for the purposes of converter design and verification. The former model will be further used to predict the switching performance of the SiC-version phase-leg, while the latter one will be used for the DAB design and simulation in the final chapter.

VII.1. Phase-Leg Model with Detailed PCB Parasitics Model

Similarly as what is presented in Chapter 3 and Chapter 5, the PCB parasitics of the phase-leg is extracted by Ansoft Q3D and then converted to Saber template. The device models, including those of the MOSFET, the blocking diode, the freewheeling diode, and the Miller clamping PNP transistor, etc., can all be obtained from the manufacturers. The gate driver totem-pole is modeled by ideal switches with the same rise / fall times as what is measured, and

the Miller clamping function of the optocoupler is simplified by ideal comparators and switches, as illustrated in Fig. 13-56 (a) and (b). Fig. 13-56 (c) shows the complete phase-leg model in a high-side DPT configuration.

Fig. 13-56 Phase-leg model with detailed PCB parasitics model. (a) Gate drive totem-pole model, (b) simplified model for Miller clamping function of ACPL-331J, (c) complete model simulating a high-side double-pulse test

Several things can be studied with the detailed phase-leg model. First of all, the different phase-leg layouts can be respectively modeled and their impacts on the switching performance can be predicted before hardware testing. For example, Fig. 13-57 compares the phase-leg switching waveforms in the conventional layout (Fig. 13-39) and the improved layout (Fig. 13-36), where 12 V higher spike voltage and heavier ringing can be observed during turn-off for the MOSFET in the conventional layout. Based on this simulation, the improved layout would be chosen by the designer over the conventional one.

(a) (b)
**Fig. 13-57 Switching waveform comparison for different PCB layouts (300 V, 23 A).
 (a) Turn-on, (b) turn-off**

Another purpose of this model is to verify the circuit design. An example of this is to verify by simulation the effectiveness of the Miller clamping transistor. As the simulation waveforms in Fig. 13-58 (a) suggest, without the transistor the MOSFET V_{GS} would peak up to over 5 V, and the drain current would reach about 12 A, indicating partially turn-on of the device. With the transistor, however, the gate voltage spike is suppressed below the MOSFET threshold voltage, and the drain current reduces to only 7 A. The same phenomena can be observed in the experimental waveforms, validating the Miller clamping circuit design.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 13-58 Simulation and experimental waveforms on the effect of the Miller clamping transistor. High-side DPT, 300 V, 12.6 A. (a) Without transistor, (b) with transistor

VII.2. Phase-Leg Model with Lumped PCB Parasitic Inductances

Another phase-leg model is built with PCB parasitics network simplified by lumped loop inductances, based on the measurement results. This is to speed up the simulation and serves the purposes of the future converter simulation and analysis. Fig. 13-59 shows the model structure. Note that for ease of usage for the up-level designers, the model has been built hierarchically, where the model users only need to concern about the external connections (two gate inputs and three power terminals) without worrying about the detailed structures inside the phase-leg, even though the internal waveforms are still accessible to the users. The last chapter will demonstrate the converter simulation results with the use of this model.

Fig. 13-59 Hierarchical phase-leg model without detailed PCB model

VIII. Design, Analysis and Simulation of SiC-Version Phase-Leg PEBB

The same design process is repeated to build a SiC-version phase-leg PEBB which utilizes the 1200 V, 20 A SiC MOSFET introduced in Chapter 2. The design will be performed based on both theoretical calculations and simulations with detailed device models.

VIII.1. Selections of Power Devices

The main switch of the SiC phase-leg is Cree's 1200 V, 20 A SiC MOSFET, characterized previously in Chapter 2, as this is the target device at the time of this work. The selection of the freewheeling diode is based on the same criteria presented in Section II of this chapter. To match the voltage and current ratings of the main switch, finally a 1200 V, 10 A SiC Schottky diode from Cree (C2D10120) is chosen. This device has around 30 A DC current conduction capability at room temperature, and the forward voltage drop is typically 1.6 V.

Because the body diode of the SiC MOSFET has a forward voltage less than 1.5 V, and the conduction of the body diode is not recommended by the manufacturer due to the potential device degradation issue (see Chapter 2), a low-voltage Si Schottky diode is therefore added in series with the MOSFET to block the body diode. The selected blocking diode is MBR2535CT from DIODES, which is rated at 35 V and 30 A.

VIII.2. Gate Driver Design and Calculations

The gate drive circuit structure is the same as that of the Si-version phase-leg, and the turn-on and -off bias are still 15 V / -2.5 V. Only the gate driver power supply needs to be reselected since the SiC MOSFET has a completely different gate charge characteristics. From the characterization results in Chapter 2, it has already been noticed that the SiC MOSFET has a much smaller input capacitance compared to typical Si CoolMOS. The measured gate charge from the switching waveforms indicates around 90 nC gate charge for the SiC MOSFET, which is four times smaller than APT47N60BCF used for the Si phase-leg. Considering that, the power needed for the floated gate driver supply for 500 kHz operation can be recalculated as

$$P_{GATE(on)} = 15 \times 90 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 0.675W$$

$$P_{GATE(off)} = 2.5 \times 90 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 0.113W$$

And the average output current is only

$$I_{GATE(av)} = 90 \times 10^{-9} \times 500 \times 10^3 \approx 45mA$$

This result greatly relieves the burden on the gate driver power supply and opens more options for the design. The final choice of the isolated power supply is a single device THB6-2423 from Traco Power, which generates 6 W total output power and ± 15 V dual outputs. The +15 V will feed to the MOSFET gate directly, and the -15 V will be linear-regulated to -2.5 V to serve the negative bias.

Since the gate drive power is smaller, the number of gate resistors can also be reduced. For SiC phase-leg, one 1 W, SMD 2512 chip resistor will be sufficient to serve as either on or off gate resistor, instead of three for the Si phase-leg. This can greatly reduce the space on the PCB board for these resistors and accordingly reduce the gate loops.

VIII.3. Simulations of SiC Phase-Leg

Simulations of the double-pulse test have been used to predict the switching performance of the SiC phase-leg. The SiC MOSFET model is developed in Chapter 2, and the models of the freewheeling diode and the blocking diode are obtained from the manufacturers. The same PCB model is used assuming that the PCB layout stays unchanged. The simulation circuit is similar to Fig. 13-56 (c).

The typical switching waveforms of the SiC phase-leg are displayed in Fig. 13-60. Fig. 13-61 (a) through (c) exhibit the switching times and energies versus different drain current under 600 V bus voltage.

Directly comparing the switching performance between Si and SiC phase-legs are not fair enough as they are obtained from different methods and the switching conditions vary a lot. Furthermore, considering the model accuracy, the real switching losses of SiC phase-leg can be slightly higher than what is shown here (see Chapter 2). Nevertheless, the great improvement in the switching times, especially the turn-off times, is evident. As seen from Fig. 13-61 (b), the main contributor to the complete switching time is no longer the turn-off delay - which in Si case is more than 100 ns, but the transient time. The turn-off delay has been reduced to only 20 ns, thanks to the small input capacitance of the SiC MOSFET. This is desired feature especially for high-frequency operation where the delay time is critical for the control bandwidth.

Fig. 13-60 Simulated switching waveforms (600 V, 10 A, $R_G = 5 \Omega / 2 \Omega$) of SiC phase-leg

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 13-61 Predicted switching times and energies.
(a) Turn-on times, (b) turn-off times, (c) switching energies

IX. Conclusions

This chapter has presented the design and analysis of Si and SiC phase-leg power modules based on the PEBB concept. The design has been focused on pushing the device switching speed while still constraining the phase-leg in its safe operation area, namely controlling the device stresses and providing proper protections. Detailed technical issues such as the dead-time generation, Miller clamping gate driver, power stage layout, etc, have been discussed. Systematic testing and characterization processes have also been reported. A datasheet describing the terminal behaviors of the Si phase-leg has been summarized consequently for the ease of the designers in building converters with these phase-legs - the core concept of PEBB.

One of the drawbacks of the design is the use of the optocoupler which generates about 180 ns delay time. This is not very ideal for the control bandwidth once the converter is running in closed-loop operation. Another issue with the phase-leg is the delay time of the over-current protection - the intrinsic delay time for ACPL-331J's sensor pin to respond to the increasing current when the MOSFET is turned-on, which is almost 900 ns [19]. In fast switching speed and high switching frequency operations, this may result in too slow response to a over-current, especially a shoot-through failure. Possible solution to these issues is to use digital isolators with totem-pole gate drivers to provide isolation, and to build discrete comparators for over-current detection. Digital isolators have much smaller delay time (usually around 20 ns) and provide bi-directional data transfer, which is good for both gate input signals and fault feedback signals. This can be the extension of this work in the future.

X. References

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Chapter 14 REDUCED ORDER TERMINAL BEHAVIORAL MODELING OF A PEBB

I. Introduction

In Chapter 3, a detailed physics based model of the SiC based PEBB was developed. This detailed model helps in understanding the characteristics and performance of the SiC MOSFET operation under the influence of circuit parasitics. Such a model is immensely useful in presenting the designer with all the pertinent technical data that aids in the design of the PEBB, and furthermore to validate its performance under various operating conditions. However, in a typical hierarchical approach to design, the waveforms of the terminal quantities are of particular interest, rather than a detailed model that captures every single detail in the operation of the PEBB.

A 'black box' circuit model that captures only the terminal waveforms shall aid in rapid simulations and performing design iterations while designing a converter system. Furthermore, since only terminal waveforms are to be captured, and that too based on the behavioral description of the PEBB, it indicates the possibility of reduction in order of the model. This implies that such a model would simulate a lot quicker, and would be free from the numerical convergence issues that have traditionally plagued the detailed physics based models.

In this chapter, an attempt to develop such a terminal behavioral model is presented. The detailed waveforms from the physics based model of Chapter 3 serve as the starting point of the modeling effort presented here. It is intended to reproduce the waveforms at the terminals with a minimal order model. A dual switching function based approach concept that is derived from the concept of the ideal SPDT switch is the cornerstone of this modeling approach. The procedure of generating this time domain signal from available measured data is a salient feature of the research presented here. Furthermore, the phase leg of the PEBB is split into two semi-legs, and is analyzed in detail. The dual switching functions drive linear circuit elements, viz. dependent voltage and current sources and produce the desired terminal waveforms.

The model presented here is validated for operation under various switching conditions of DC link voltage and output current. The results obtained are then compared with those obtained from the detailed switching model. It is proposed that this model could be further refined and improved upon to include the effect of parasitic ringing. Furthermore, the effect of temperature on the switching waveforms could be studied in detail and an augmented thermal model could be developed to completely validate the concepts presented in this novel modeling approach.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The following are the major technical objectives of this chapter:

- a) To develop a reduced order terminal behavioral model of the SiC MOSFET based PEBB.
- b) The model shall be a circuit based model, rather than a block diagram model. This means that the terminals of the proposed model can be connected to other electrical systems/converter buses, and can be simulated using a common circuit simulator.
- c) It is intended to reproduce only the terminal waveforms that shall aid in the rapid design iterations and prototyping of the converter topology and expedite system level simulations.

- d) The model developed shall be a reduced order one, implying very fast simulation times (at a maximum simulation time step of 1ns) and relatively free from numerical convergence errors.
- e) A major objective is to encapsulate all the intricacies of the physics based PEBB (including gate drivers, parasitics, switching logic, power devices etc.), while retaining simplicity and achieving model reduction. In short, such a terminal model is intended to be positioned in between the overly simplified switching model built using ideal switches, and the immensely complicated and intricate physics based model.
- f) The following parameters of both the terminal voltages and current waveforms are intended to be captured:
 1. Rise and Fall Times
 2. Delay Times
 3. Overshoots and Undershoots
 4. Ringing Frequency
 5. Settling Time
- g) The steady state (full conduction/blocking) waveforms of the terminal voltages and currents need to be captured.
- h) The proposed model shall provide the designer with good estimation of conduction and switching losses.
- i) The model shall capture the above mentioned parameters, under various operating conditions of DC link voltage and output current.
- j) The developed model shall also be amenable for use under various temperatures of the PEBB operation, i.e. an integrated thermal model is envisaged.
- k) The above mentioned parameters are targeted to be captured such that the relative error in each of them would be expected to be the order of around 10%.
- l) The proposed model is intended to work satisfying all the above specifications and tolerance limits, as long as all components within the PEBB (drive logic, power stage, gate resistance etc.) remain unchanged.

I.2. Technical Approach

Fig. 14-1 Proposed architecture of the 4 terminal behavioral circuit model

As shown in Fig. 14-1, the proposed model is envisaged to be a four terminal circuit model. The top terminal is intended to be connected to the Positive bus of the DC link, while the bottom terminal is intended to be connected to the negative bus of the DC link. The driving logic is basically the logic signal that drives one of the active devices of the PEBB. The driving of the other switch is decided by the dead-time which is input separately to the simulation model.

To build up this model, the PEBB power stage (also referred to as a phase leg) is split into two separate so-called semi-legs, each comprising a MOSFET and a diode. The switching behavior of a semi-leg can be modeled using a dependent voltage source and a dependent current source. The control input for each of these sources is obtained from two suitably shaped switching functions. In order to obtain these control signals, double pulse tester experiments are conducted using the PEBB and the terminal voltage and current waveforms are recorded. These waveforms are suitably shaped as described in the forthcoming section, to obtain the respective control signals.

After capturing the salient features of the semi-leg, viz. all the rise times, fall times, delay times etc., the behavior of parasitic ringing due to the influence of circuit and device parasitics is modeled. This parasitic ringing behavior is reproduced with the help of a small number of passive components. Finally, the model of the complete phase leg is completed by combining the two semi-leg models and including additional considerations like the dead-time etc. A detailed explanation of each of the stages in the modeling process is explained below.

II. Modeling the ‘Semi-Leg’

Neglecting the influence of all device/circuit parasitics, as well as the driving logics, the main power stage component of the PEBB can be considered to be a phase leg as shown in Fig. 14-2.

Fig. 14-2 The phase-leg (switching power stage portion within a PEBB module)

For a phase leg under operation of a clamped inductive load, as in Chapter 3, the current always commutes from one set of MOSFET to the opposite diode and vice-versa. For example, for a positive output current (as indicated by the sign convention shown in Fig. 14-2), when the

Bottom MOSFET turns off, the top diode continues to carry the inductor (common) current. This well-known concept is exploited to formulate, what is referred to here as a “Semi-Leg”. The complete phase leg is split into two MOSFET-diode pairs, each semi-leg consisting of only the switch pair that are involved in a particular commutation process. The terminal waveforms of this semi-leg are now captured by constructing a semi-leg model.

II.1. Obtaining Terminal Waveforms from Experimental Model

The detailed procedure for obtaining the waveform data from the PEBB has been elucidated in Chapter 3. The waveform data of the semi-leg comprised of the Low-side MOSFET and Top Diode pair (as shown in Fig. 14-3), is imported from the oscilloscope into the MATLAB, through the GPIB cable and Instrument Control toolbox.

Fig. 14-3 Semi-Leg under investigation (shown in black)

The model developed shall now onwards, use the Semi Leg Configuration formed by the low side MOSFET and top diode pair, and shall make use of the DP Tester configuration described in Chapter 3 for the modeling procedure.

II.2. Reduction of Waveform Data

The waveforms thus obtained, may contain a large number of samples (depending on the sample rate of the digital oscilloscope). The simulation model is desired to be run at a time step not less than 1ns. So, all details of the waveforms within that time frame that was captured by the oscilloscope can now be discarded. Moreover, if successive measurements of either the voltage or the current waveforms differ each other by less than 100 micro units (A or V), such data points can also be discarded. Thus we get a significant reduction in the size of data that has to be handled, and analyzed in the future.

Fig. 14-4 MOSFET turn-off voltage & current waveforms at 600V DC link voltage, at 8A drain current and 5 Ohms gate resistance

Fig. 14-4 illustrates the waveforms before and after reduction of data points. The reduced data point waveform matches almost completely with the original data point waveform obtained from simulations. Thus, it evidently points out that this reduced data set shall be sufficient to reproduce back these waveforms from the model.

The waveforms captured using the experimental model captures the operation of the phase leg under various device/circuit parasitics. Thus we need to calculate the effect of the parasitics in the above waveforms and back-calculate their effects and separate them out from the model, for obtaining an accurate model. However, as a first order approximation and concept verification, the reduced data waveforms can be directly used to construct our proposed

terminal model. Later, the effect of PEBB parasitics, as well as parasitics of the converter and the bus, external to the PEBB can be analyzed and a more accurate model can be developed.

II.3. Three Terminal Switch and Dual Switching Functions

The switch-diode pair in Fig. 14-3 can be replaced with an ideal SPDT switch, and furthermore, by the well-known three-terminal switch model. The three-terminal switch consists of a dependent voltage source and a dependent current source, driven by the same switching function. Fig. 14-5 illustrates the concept of this well-known three terminal switch.

Fig. 14-5 The three terminal switch formed by the switch-diode pair

However, in a physical MOSFET-diode pair, the turn-on & turn-off transitions do not happen instantaneously. The typical turn-on & turn-off waveforms of an ideal MOSFET are shown in Fig. 14-6.

Fig. 14-6 Typical MOSFET turn-on and turn-off (conceptual) waveforms of a MOSFET-diode pair

The waveforms shown in Fig. 14-6 are only a conceptual set of waveforms for a typical MOSFET switching behavior. For the SiC MOSFET based PEBB, the actual waveforms shall not be smooth as shown here. Also, due to reverse recovery process of the diode, there will be overshoots in the MOSFET waveforms. Moreover, due to device package and circuit parasitics there will be ringing during the turn-on and turn-off processes. In addition, many other second order effects will determine the actual shape of the switching waveforms.

However, it is evident that it is impossible to capture even the basic non-idealities of Fig. 14-6 using the ideal three terminal switching model of Fig. 14-5. However, the simplicity of the network (only one voltage and current source) encourages retaining the basic framework of the model, while just modifying the switching function suitably.

The switching function (which is the same as the gating logic signal) of Fig. 14-5 is split into two switching functions. The control signal driving the dependant voltage source is referred to as the ‘Voltage Switching Function’, while the one driving the current source is referred to as the ‘Current Switching Function’. According to the basic laws of circuit theory, viz. the KVL and KCL, the each switching function can be made completely independent of each other. Thus, it is possible to achieve any desired waveform shape for both the MOSFET voltage and current.

Fig. 14-7 The splitting of gating signal into the dual switching functions

Fig. 14-7 shows the splitting of the Gating signal into the dual switching functions described above. A sample simulation waveform result shown in Fig. 14-8 illustrates that it is indeed possible to achieve any desired wave shape by suitably adjusting the two switching functions.

Fig. 14-8 Saber simulation showing the verification of the dual switching function concept

Thus any desired waveform can be obtained simply by using two suitably shaped switching functions. Since, only terminal waveforms need to be captured, the research problem has been narrowed down to a problem of determining the appropriate time-domain switching functions. The next few sections deal with precisely this topic, of determining the switching functions.

II.4. Obtaining the Normalized Switching Functions

Since, the modeling task has modeled down to obtaining the switching functions as accurately, the reference waveform for the modeling exercise must also be an equivalent switching function. From the DP tester results of Chapter 3, terminal waveforms of the voltage and current were obtained. The next task is to obtain the dual switching functions, s_v and s_i .

It has been experimentally found that Double Pulse Tester switching waveforms are quite different for different operating conditions. The measured waveforms and their characteristics (like delay time, rise time, peak overshoot, settling time, ringing frequency etc.) vary significantly and is dependent on the DC link voltage and the drain current at the time of turn-off and turn-on. Therefore, the experimental switching waveforms are normalized with respect to the turn-on and turn-off output current (current through the common terminal), in order to obtain the normalized current switching function, s_i . Similarly, the measured drain-source voltage is normalized with respect to the DC link voltage to get the desired voltage switching function, s_v . In the power stage of the three terminal switch, these functions multiply with the common current, and the DC-link voltage to obtain the desired terminal voltage and current waveforms.

A MATLAB script was developed in order to normalize the values of switching function for various terminal waveforms obtained under different operating conditions. All the waveforms were obtained at a constant operating temperature. Therefore the thermal behavior of the switching waveforms has not been studied in this modeling effort.

Fig. 14-9 through Fig. 14-12 illustrate the concept of the normalization of the waveforms. They show turn-on and turn-off voltage and current waveforms and their corresponding switching functions.

Fig. 14-9 Turn-off drain current & its corresponding current switching function S_i (600V, 8A)

Fig. 14-10 Turn-off drain current & its corresponding current switching function S_i (600 V, 8A)

Fig. 14-11 Turn-on drain current & its corresponding current switching function S_i (600V, 8A)

Fig. 14-12 Turn-on drain-source voltage & corresponding current switching function s_v (600V, 8A)

It should be noted that the shape of the voltage switching function, s_v , seems inverted, when compared to the original drain-source waveform. This is because this switching function drives the dependent voltage source, which is equivalently represents the voltage across the top diode. Hence, by Kirchhoff's voltage law, this voltage must be difference of the DC-link voltage and the Drain-Source voltage of the MOSFET. Hence, the switching function is inverted. On the other hand, the current switching function retains the same wave shape as the actual drain current. This is because the current switching function drives the dependent current source and is intended to represent the MOSFET current in the switch-diode pair equivalent of the three terminal switch.

II.5. Parametric Study and Characterization of Switching Waveforms

The switching function that completely describes the switching waveforms, including all the intricacies of the turn-on and turn-off process cannot be generated with a single describing function. The salient parameters of all the waveforms are dependent on the current operating point (turn-on/off current and DC link voltage). A comparative plot of the turn-off switching functions for various cases, shown in Fig. 14-13 summarizes the challenges just described.

Fig. 14-13 Turn-off drain current waveforms at various DC link voltages and turn-off currents

Similarly, the remaining three other switching functions can also be plotted. The problem at hand, therefore necessitates a detailed parametric study to identify the salient parameters of the switching functions, and to understand their dynamics as a function of DC link voltage and turn-on/turn-off current.

For all the four switching functions, delay time is considered, and analyzed. For the current rise switching function, the current rise wave shape is treated as linear, and characterized. For the voltage fall waveform, it is modeled by using an exponential function. Similarly, suitable algebraic describing functions are determined and each of the salient characteristics is constructed piece-by-piece in the time-domain to obtain the complete switching function during the entire turn-on and turn-off transition process. Therefore the major slopes and salient characteristics are thus identified, and modeled. On top of this model, high frequency ringing effects are added by introduction of reactive components and modeled.

II.6. Delay Time of Voltage Switching Function

A statistical study was done to understand the trend of the delay time of the voltage switching function as a function of the operating conditions.

Table 14-1 On-delay time of voltage switching function as function of common current

Sl. No.	DC Link Voltage (V)	Common Current (A)	$S_{v_{on}}$ delay time (ns)
1	600	6.134	16.90
2	600	8.180	17.30
3	600	10.220	17.65

4	200	8.04	19.80
5	400	8.06	18.87

Fig. 14-14 Variation of delay time of turn-on voltage switching function with DC-link voltage and common current

A linear (first order) polynomial is used to generate the delay time. Such a generated time delay is implemented in Saber using a custom developed on-delay block. The on-delay function thus generated is simulated. Fig. 14-15 through Fig. 14-17 show the typical simulation results achieved by using only the on-delay functionality explained above.

Fig. 14-15 Simulation results (600V, 8A) turn-on waveforms

Fig. 14-16 Simulation results (600V, 10.22A) turn-on waveforms

Fig. 14-17 Simulation results (400V, 8A) turn-on waveforms

Table 14-2 Comparison of simulation and experimental results

Sl. No.	DC Link Voltage (V)	Inductor Current (A)	Sv_on delay time (ns)		% Deviation	Mean % deviation
			Simulation using 3D look-up table (fitted) model	Experimental Results		
1	200	8	19.939	19.8	0.702	-0.101
2	400	8	18.619	18.87	- 1.33	
3	600	8	17.298	17.3	-0.011	
4	600	6.134	16.964	16.9	0.379	
5	600	10.22	17.678	17.65	0.159	

A similar analysis of statistical surface fitting, trend analysis, and simulation is performed for the on-delay of the current switching function, as well as the off-delay times of the voltage and current switching functions. The off-delay concept is implemented in Saber using a custom off-delay block developed for the purpose.

At the end of this section, all the delay times have been successfully modeled using the approach of surface fitting. Simulation results indicate close matching with the experimental results.

II.7. Modeling the Current Rise

During turn-on transition, at the end of the delay time, current begins to rise. The typical turn-on current switching function is shown in Fig. 14-18.

Fig. 14-18 A typical MOSFET turn-on drain current waveform

As highlighted in Fig. 14-18, during the rise-duration, the current switching function varies almost linearly with time. The slopes of the current rise waveform change as a function of the operating conditions. Thus, a study can be made, to understand the variation of rise-slope as a function of the operating conditions, as shown in Table 14-3.

Table 14-3 Rise slope of current switching function as a function of DC link voltage & common current

Sl. No.	DC Link Voltage (V)	Drain Current (A)	Rise slope ($\times 10^8$)
1	200	8.040	2.5233
2	400	8.060	3.1500
3	600	8.180	3.9318
4	600	6.134	5.2938
5	600	10.220	3.3325

The above table was incorporated as a look-up table in Saber. The output of this look-up table is the desired slope. This is fed in as input to a Linear Rise Time block, as shown in Fig. 14-19.

Fig. 14-19 Saber schematic showing implementation of Linear Current Rise

The current falling waveforms during turn-off transition are also similarly modeled.

II.8. Modeling the Drain-Source Voltage Fall during Turn-on

A typical switching function for describing the voltage fall during turn-on transient is shown in Fig. 14-20.

Fig. 14-20 A typical voltage turn-on switching function

As explained earlier, during voltage turn-on transient, when the drain-source voltage falls, the voltage switching function, v_v increases from zero to one. Now, the highlighted portion in Fig. 14-20 represents the transition region during the voltage turn-off. The minor glitch before this transition region is ignored, and treated as part of the voltage on-delay time.

Now, the highlighted portion is fitted as an exponential polynomial of the following form

$$y = a e^{bt} + c e^{dt}$$

The results of a typical curve-fitting exercise are shown in Fig. 14-21.

Fig. 14-21 Curve fitted results of voltage turn-on switching function

Table 14-4 Trend of the coefficients as a function of the DC link voltage & common current

Sl. No.	DC Link Voltage (V)	Drain Current (A)	Polynomial Coefficients			
			a	b (x 10 ⁵)	c	d (x 10 ⁷)
1	200	8.040	0.9849	1.0220	-5.957	-9.091
2	400	8.060	0.9890	0.2678	-5.280	-8.875
3	600	8.180	1.0050	-0.6834	-3.563	-7.327
4	600	6.134	0.9990	-0.2688	-4.254	-8.575
5	600	10.220	1.0130	-1.3450	-3.125	-6.401

Note that for all the curve/surface fits, goodness of fit statistics are analyzed, and ensured that the fitted curve/surface has the minimum possible error with respect to the measured data.

Similarly, the voltage turn-off transients are captured by a similar method of data analysis and curve fitting. An algebraic equation to obtain these coefficients is developed in Saber, and simulated to obtain the desired wave shapes.

III. Simulation of Behavioral Model and Sample Results

III.1. Simulation Setup and Hierarchical Schematics

The DP tester circuit was used as the simulation vehicle to determine the validity of the model developed thus far. The simulation was performed in Saber. The simulation schematic to obtain each of the salient features is shown from Fig. 14-22 through Fig. 14-27.

Fig. 14-22 DP tester used for the validation of the Semi-Leg terminal behavioral model

Fig. 14-23 Three terminal switch controlled by the dual switching functions

Fig. 14-24 Generation of the switching functions

Fig. 14-25 Schematic to model the current switching functions during turn-on transitions

Fig. 14-26 Implementing the current-rise logic through look-up table for the slopes

Fig. 14-27 Detailed model showing the exponential rise logic for voltage

Fig. 14-28 Comparison of developed simulation model vs. original experimental data (600V, 8A) for turn-on voltage switching function

Fig. 14-29 Comparison of developed simulation model vs. original experimental data (600V, 8A) for turn-on current switching function

Fig. 14-30 Comparison of developed simulation model vs. original experimental data (600V, 6.14A) for turn-on current switching function

Fig. 14-31 Comparison of developed simulation model vs. original experimental data (600V, 6.14 A) for turn-on voltage switching function

IV. Future Development of Model

A. Peak Overshoot

The model developed thus far has captured only the major slopes, rise times, fall times etc. Among the objectives of the model development, other parameters like peak overshoot, addition of high-frequency ringing etc. are yet to be achieved. The next step in the development of the model is to reproduce the peak overshoot of the current and voltage waveforms as a function of the operating conditions. The peak overshoot in the MOSFET drain current waveforms is due to the reverse recovery phenomenon in the top diode.

Table 14-5 Peak overshoot characteristics of current switching function

Sl. No.	DC Link Voltage (V)	Inductor Current (A)	Peak Time (ns)	% Overshoot
1	200	8	22.5	61.8
2	400	8	20.4	79.5
3	600	8	19.1	86.7
4	600	6.134	18.4	123.2
5	600	10.22	19.6	65

Efforts to this end have already been started. Based on the study of the peak overshoot of the MOSFET drain current waveform, Table 14-5 illustrates the trend of the peak-overshoot parameter to be modeled. This shall be incorporated into the model in the future.

B. Modeling High Frequency Ringing

Parasitic ringing can be seen in both the voltage and current waveforms. Typical waveforms illustrating the parasitic ringing can be seen in both the voltage and current waveforms, as illustrated in Fig. 14-32.

Fig. 14-32 Simulation waveforms illustrating parasitic high frequency ringing in MOSFET current and voltage waveforms

It is proposed that the parasitic ringing be modeled with the help of a single inductor and capacitor. The inductor being connected in series with the dependent voltage source of the three terminal switch, and the capacitor being connected in parallel with the dependent current source. Although the reactive components are non-linear in practice, it is thought that an equivalent linear/constant reactive component values may be determined. This is encouraged by the presence of a seemingly-dominant pole in the system, as can be inferred from the time-domain simulations.

C. Combining into a Single Phase Leg

The modeling process presented here, is for a semi-leg, a concept that was discussed in detail in the beginning of the chapter. However, a PEBB consists of all two semi-legs. Hence, the results obtained using this model has to be extrapolated, and suitably modified to obtain the complete model of the entire phase leg. Therefore, additional considerations like inclusion of dead-time between triggering the switches etc. need to be factored in. Also, the effect of circuit layout parasitics has to be factored in to obtain the complete equivalent model of the PEBB.

All the above mentioned modeling steps are to be done, and form the future aspects of the research on the reduced order terminal modeling of the PEBB.

V. Conclusions and Discussions

This chapter presents a novel approach of modeling only the terminal waveforms of a PEBB, which are the quantities of interest to a converter system developer. Such a reduced order terminal behavior model is intended to capture all the essential details from a terminal point of view, while encapsulating the intricate component level details of the PEBB. The complete PEBB is split into two halves, each half being referred to as a semi-leg. Also, a novel concept of using the three-terminal switch driven by double switching functions has been presented.

Waveforms obtained from the Double Pulse Tester experiment of the SiC MOSFET were used to start the modeling process. The waveforms were reverse-engineered and normalized to obtain the two suitable double switching functions. The research problem was therefore simplified into generating the two switching functions in the time-domain. Rigorous data analysis, curve/surface fitting and statistical interpretation of results were performed on the salient features (delay time, rise time, fall time etc) of the waveforms. Based on this, a terminal behavioral model was developed to capture the salient parameters of the switching waveforms. Simulation results suggest the validity of the model under various operating conditions.

The model has to be further improved to incorporate additional switching phenomenon. Firstly, the model does not capture all the parasitic ringing caused due to the interaction of the switching phenomenon of the PEBB with parasitic elements on the layout board. Secondly, the model does not account for the significant peak overshoot in the voltage and current waveforms. Thirdly, all the modeling process presented in the chapter was developed only for the semi-leg of a Switch-Diode pair. The modeling process has to account for the other set of switch-diode pair and combine the two-phase legs. Complications arising out of this combined Phase Leg, viz. dead-time and other non-idealities have to be taken care of.

VI. References

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Chapter 15 SINGLE AND THREE-PHASE TRANSFORMER COMPARISON AND DESIGN

I. Introduction

The idea of “solid-state transformer” has been introduced by Navy researchers in 1980 [1], and later developed with isolation transformer included [2, 3]. As an alternative to the bulky distribution transformer, it greatly improved the power density of the power distribution system. In a typical solid-state transformer system, rather than connecting the transformer to line frequency buses directly, semiconductor devices are used to increase the operating frequency of the transformer, as shown in Fig. 15-1, which largely reduces the volume of the transformer [4].

Fig. 15-1 Typical isolated solid-state transformer configuration

As experimental data shows, in solid-state transformer, cores and windings still dominates the weight and volume [3, 5]. Thus for further power density improvement of the solid-state transformer system, in addition to the analysis of new topologies [6, 7, 8] and control schemes [9, 10, 11, 12], a lot of efforts have been spent on the improvement of passive design of the transformer. In traditional power transformer design methods, the design variables are usually the core (shape, material), wire (gauge, winding structure) and the way to combine the both (core type or shell type transformer). And the design constraints often fall into maximum acceptable temperature rise of the application and maximum flux density in the core that will not cause saturation. Hence in previous literature for power transformer design and optimization, one focus is mainly on the improvement of constraints, as in [13], where core materials have been studied for good performance at higher temperature with lower loss. And the other focus is on better selection of the design variables, including developing more accurate loss and thermal models of the transformer [13, 14, 15], as well as the implication of different optimization algorithms into the solution of the numerical models [16, 17, 18]. The former one indicates a better guidance in selecting design variables according to constraints, and the latter one makes the process of finding the best solutions of the variables faster, and more robust.

In the report, we focus on adding one more design variable, the phase number, into the design and optimization of the power transformer. In previous publications, the structure of three-phase transformer has been shown to be material-saving versus three single-phase transformers [19]. But research work on one single-phase and one three-phase transformer comparison is limited and not comprehensive. One case study in Section III shows that, comparing with single-phase transformer, when assuming same apparent power, flux and current density, three-phase transformer has 12.5% benefit in area product A_p , which is one key factor that predicting the core size of the transformer in traditional design method [20]. Though only an estimation, it shows the potential of density improvement when using three or even

multi-phase transformers in solid-state transformer system. In several cases of previous works, the implementation of multi-phase transformers has already been realized in different solid-state transformer topologies [21, 22, 23]. However, focusing on system level design and analysis, these papers discussed not much about the influence of adding phases on physical design of the power transformer. [23] has tried to compare the single and three-phase transformer design in the DAB systems and developed one set of comparison criteria for the design of DAB1 and DAB3. With assumptions in [23], $V_{core} / V_{winding}$ is represented by $P_{core} / P_{winding}$ for both single and three-phase transformers in DAB1 and DAB3. However, $P_{core} / P_{winding}$ is found to vary by different turn number ratio.

From literature survey mentioned above, we found that the comparison between single and three-phase transformer power density is needed in solid-state transformer design but no clarified conclusion has been reached yet.

I.1. Technical Objectives

This report will try to analyze and find a result for the power density comparison of single and three-phase transformer in solid-state transformer systems, and determine the effect of phase number on transformer power density.

I.2. Technical Approach

DAB1 and DAB3 systems are selected as one typical example of the solid-state transformer topology as discussed in [24]. Two optimization design methods for the transformer in DAB systems have been developed. And based on the criteria developed in [23] and some more assumptions, the design results of single and three-phase transformers are compared and analyzed in different operation conditions. Comparison results show that the structure of the three-phase transformer leads to bigger volume when temperature rise is the design limitation and smaller one when flux and current densities are constrained. And when all the three specifications hit the limit, the difference of volumes of single and three-phase transformer is within 5%. One 20 kHz, 300V, 1 kW prototype system has been built and verifies the analysis.

II. Introduction to DAB Circuits and Comparison Criteria

II.1. Single and Three-phase DAB Analysis

The DAB1 topology shown in Fig. 15-2 is first introduced in the 1980s. It has two full bridges on the two sides of a transformer. Each full bridge generates a 50% duty cycle square wave with certain phase shift at a fixed frequency. The leakage inductance of the transformer is used as energy storage and transfer component. The energy flows from the leading side to the lagging side. And the amount of energy is controlled by the phase-shift-angle. The topology has a natural zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) capability for both bridges. But it relegates to hard switching when operating at very light load condition [24].

Fig. 15-2 DAB1 Topology

Firstly introduced in [24], DAB3 topology (Fig. 15-3) has one more phase-leg added in both primary and secondary bridge, and one three-phase transformer is connected for isolation and voltage regulation instead of the single-phase one in DAB1. Similar control scheme can be applied to DAB3, with fixed frequency and complementary 50% duty cycle for upper and bottom switches, but the phase angle between phase legs on one side is 120° , instead of 180° in DAB1. DAB3 is also a bidirectional converter. The energy flows through the leakage inductance of the transformer, and the direction and amount are determined by the phase-shift-angle between the two switch bridges. And there is a natural ZVS capability for both bridges of DAB3 too, except at very light load condition.

Fig. 15-3 DAB3 Topology

As a summary, the output power of DAB1 and DAB3 is shown in Table 15-1. V_i is the input DC bus voltage and V_o is the output voltage. I_L is the current going into transformer, and P_o is the power transferred through the leakage inductance L of the transformer. Φ is the phase-shift-angle between the two bridges, d is the voltage regulation parameter when output voltage is referred to the primary side as (15-1)

$$d = \frac{N_1 V_o}{N_2 V_i} \quad (15-1)$$

Table 15-1 DAB1 and DAB3 output power comparison

	DAB1	DAB3 ($0^\circ < \Phi < 60^\circ$)	DAB3 ($60^\circ < \Phi < 90^\circ$)
P_o	$\frac{V_i^2}{\omega L} d \phi \left[1 - \frac{\phi}{\pi} \right]$	$\frac{V_i^2}{\omega L} d \phi \left[\frac{2}{3} - \frac{\phi}{2\pi} \right]$	$\frac{V_i^2}{\omega L} d \left[\phi - \frac{\pi}{18} - \frac{\phi^2}{\pi} \right]$

As can be seen from Table 15-1, for either DAB1 or DAB3, same transferring power P_o can be realized by different combinations of (d , L , Φ), which defines the operating point of the system. Different operating points result in different optimized designs of transformers. Hence, to compare the design of single and three-phase transformer, corresponding operating points of DAB1 and DAB3 are found first. Assumptions are made, with reference to [23], indicating DAB1 and DAB3 to:

- 1) Have identical transferred power, and operating frequency, input and load voltage and same voltage regulation d ;
- 2) Both work in soft-switching area;
- 3) Have the same working efficiency when transformer loss is not considered;
- 4) Have the same total die area of the switches.

Based on the loss analysis in [23], the RMS value of the current going through single-phase (I_{L1}) and three-phase (I_{L3}) transformers should have a ratio of 3:2.

Thus to find comparable design of DAB1 and DAB3, the operating point of DAB1 can be first determined, with a selection of L , d and Φ that makes the whole DAB1 system of relatively high efficiency. Transformer current I_{L1} can be determined from calculation or simulation, and the corresponding DAB3 will 2/3 of the DAB1 current. With $d_3=d_1$, the other two variables of L_3 and Φ_3 can be determined by I_{L3} and P_o .

One example of 20 kHz, 5 kV and 250 kW case is shown in Table 15-2.

Table 15-2 Case study for DAB1 and DAB3 operating point selection

	DAB1	DAB3
P_o	250kW	250kW
f	20kHz	20kHz
V_i	5000V	5000V
V_o	5000V	5000V
I_{Lrms}	56.72A	37.81A
$N_1:N_2$	1	1
L_{jk}	352.75 μ H	255.43 μ H
Φ	30.6°	31.8°

III. Transformer Design Optimization

The basic idea of transformer optimization design can be summarized as five parts: design variables, conditions, constraints, the physical model, and the optimization objectives [13, 25]. When the model is set up, a selected optimization algorithm can be used to find a combination of as the optimized design of the transformer, achieving the highest power density.

For this work, design conditions have already been determined in the discussion of criteria of DAB1 and DAB3 in *Section II*. And the optimization objective is power density. Dimensions of

the core and turn number are defined as design variables. Two different approaches to consider design constraints have been used in analysis. Since this work does not focus on the algorithm, MATHWORKS™ MATLAB Optimization Toolbox is utilized [26]. The detailed models are explained below.

III.1. Design Objectives and Variables

For case study in this report, core type transformers are selected as an example for both single and three-phase transformers. For single-phase one, two U cores are combined and half of the primary and secondary windings are wound coaxially on either leg of the core. Correspondingly, two E cores are utilized for the three-phase transformer, with the center posts processed so that all three legs have the same width. The primary and secondary windings of each phase are wound on each leg, also coaxially. The structures of single and three-phase transformer are shown in Fig. 15-4 and Fig. 15-5.

As the optimization objective, the volume of the transformer is defined as the cubical space occupied by the transformer [20]. The design variables include the winding turn number N and the four key dimensional parameters of the core, as a , b , d and h , which respectively stand for the width of the main flux path, the width of the window, the thickness of the core and half the height of the window of the transformer.

Fig. 15-4 Single-phase core type transformer structure

Fig. 15-5 Three-phase core type transformer structure

As a result, the volume of the transformer, together with other geometrical parameters of the core and windings of both single and three-phase transformers can all be expressed with the design variables in Table 15-3.

Table 15-3 Single and three-phase transformer geometrical configuration

Core Type Transformer	Single-phase	Three-phase
Cross Sectional Area A_c	$A_c = ad$	$A_c = ad$
Window area A_w	$A_w = 2bh$	$A_w = 2bh$
Mean Length per Turn l_0	$l_0 = 2(a+b+d)$	$l_0 = 2(a+b+d)$
Transformer width l_1	$l_1 = 2a+2b$	$l_1 = 3a+3b$
Transformer thickness l_2	$l_2 = d+b$	$l_2 = d+b$
Transformer height l_3	$l_3 = 2a+2h$	$l_3 = 2a+2h$
Transformer volume V	$V = l_1 \times l_2 \times l_3$	$V = l_1 \times l_2 \times l_3$
Core volume V_c	$V_c = (2a+b)(2a+2h)d - 2hbd$	$V_c = (3a+2b)(2a+2h)d - 4hbd$
Transformer thermal area A_t	$A_t = 2(l_1l_2 + l_1l_3 + l_2l_3)$	$A_t = 2(l_1l_2 + l_1l_3 + l_2l_3)$

III.2. J-B Methods for Transformer Design Optimization

According to traditional transformer design method in [20], the area product A_p is one key factor for core selection. For single-phase transformer, it is defined in (15-2):

$$A_{p1} = A_{c1} \times W_{A1} \quad (15-2)$$

Since there are two window areas and three legs, the area product of three-phase core type transformer is defined in (15-3):

$$A_{p3} = \frac{3}{2} \times A_{c3} \times W_{A3} \quad (15-3)$$

Thus the comparison of single and three-phase transformer size can be referred to the ratio of area product as (15-4):

$$\frac{A_{p1}}{A_{p3}} = \frac{A_{c1} \times W_{A1}}{\frac{3}{2} \times A_{c3} \times W_{A3}} \quad (15-4)$$

Considering the relationship between flux density and cross-sectional area, cross-sectional area of single and three-phase transformer cores can be replaced by flux density in (15-5).

$$A_c = \frac{\Sigma V \times t}{N \times B} \quad (15-5)$$

In (15-5), A_c is the cross-sectional area of the core. B is the flux density going through the core. V is piece-wise voltage applied on the transformer and t is the corresponding time duration for each V . According to the voltage and flux density waveforms of DAB1 and DAB3 shown in Fig. 15-6 and Fig. 15-7, single and three-phase transformer cross-sectional areas can be calculated and summarized as in (15-6).

$$A_c = \frac{V_{in}}{k_c f N B} \quad (15-6)$$

For single-phase transformer, $k_c = 4$, and for three-phase transformer, $k_c = 9$.

Meanwhile, window area W_A can be written in (15-7):

$$W_A = \frac{k_s NI}{k_u J} \quad (15-7)$$

In (15-7), k_u stands for the fill factor of the window. W_A is the window area and I is the current going through each turn of windings. k_s is one coefficient which is determined by the portion of the area occupied by each side of windings. According to Fig. 15-4 and Fig. 15-5, for single-phase transformer, $k_s = 2$ and for three-phase one, $k_s = 4$.

Fig. 15-6 DAB1 transformer terminal voltage and flux density waveform

Fig. 15-7 DAB3 transformer terminal voltage and flux density waveform

As a result, the area product comparison for single and three-phase transformer can be changed into density product comparison in (15-8):

$$\frac{A_{p1}}{A_{p3}} = \frac{A_{c1} \times W_{A1}}{\frac{3}{2} \times A_{c3} \times W_{A3}} = \frac{\frac{V_{in}}{4fN_1 B_1} \times \frac{2N_1 I_1}{k_u J_1}}{\frac{3}{2} \times \frac{V_{in}}{9fN_3 B_3} \times \frac{4N_3 I_3}{k_u J_3}} = \frac{9}{8} \frac{B_3 J_3}{B_1 J_1} \quad (15-8)$$

Meanwhile, flux and current density can be expressed as (15-9) to (15-12) for single and three-phase transformers:

$$B_1 = \frac{V_{in}}{4fN_1 A_{c1}} \quad (15-9)$$

$$B_3 = \frac{V_{in}}{9fN_3 A_{c3}} \quad (15-10)$$

$$J_1 = \frac{2N_1 I_1}{k_u W_{A1}} \quad (15-11)$$

$$J_3 = \frac{4N_3 I_3}{k_u W_{A3}} \quad (15-12)$$

Hence, if setting flux and current density limits of single-phase transformer equals to three-phase one as the design constraints, the area product ratio, which stands for the volume ratio, will be around 9/8 for single and three-phase transformer, which shows a benefit in volume for three-phase transformer.

According to (15-9) to (15-12), both B and J are functions of the five design variables defined in Fig. 15-4 and Fig. 15-5. Thus one optimization model can be summarized

as in Table 15-4. And considering the constraints, it is named as *J – B Method* for Transformer Design Optimization.

Table 15-4 J – B model for transformer design optimization

Optimization variables: $a, b, d, h,$ and N
Optimization (Minimization) Object: $V_{1\phi} = (2a + 2b) \times (d + b) \times (2a + 2h)$ $V_{3\phi} = (3a + 3b) \times (d + b) \times (2a + 2h)$
Design Constraints: $\begin{cases} B_{1\phi} = B_{\max 1} \\ B_{3\phi} = B_{\max 3} \end{cases}, \begin{cases} J_{1\phi} = J_{\max 1} \\ J_{3\phi} = J_{\max 3} \end{cases}$

Considering the real design, additional constraints should include the positive requirement of $a, b, d,$ and $h,$ and the positive integer requirement of turn number $N.$ Also to avoid strange shape of the core, some constraints have been set for the relationships between the four dimensional variables according to commercial core dimension lists from MAGNETICS® [27]. With the use of the MATHWORKS™ MATLAB® Optimization Toolbox, the design solution can be found numerically.

III.3. T-B Methods for Transformer Design Optimization

In practical design, the constraints limiting the power density of the transformer are often the saturation flux density B_{sat} and the maximum allowed temperature rise $T_{rise}.$ Thus one more design optimization method is developed in this report based on the inequality constraints of flux density and temperature rise, named as *T-B Method* in short.

According to (15-9) and (15-10) and Table 15-3, the flux density can be summarized as (15-13) for both single and three-phase transformers.

$$B = B(a, b, d, h, N) < B_{\max} \quad (15-13)$$

Here, as an example design, one simplified thermal model of the transformer is used from [20], as (15-14) shows:

$$T_{rise} = 450 \times \left(\frac{P_{core} + P_{winding}}{A_t} \right)^{0.826} \quad (15-14)$$

In (15-14), the core loss P_{core} has the expression of (15-15), considering different core materials:

$$P_{core} = V_{core} \times k_{wave} \times K \times f^\alpha \times B^\beta \quad (15-15)$$

In the equation, flux density B and V_{core} can be expressed by the four dimensional variables a, b, d and h as well as turn number N in (15-9) and (15-10) and Table 15-3. And K, α, β are core loss parameters from Steimetz Equation which can be found in core material datasheet. Constant k_{wave} here stands for the waveform coefficient of the core loss according to

[14, 15]. In sum, the expression of core loss has only variables of a , b , d , h and N , which can also be simplified as:

$$P_{core} = P_{core}(a, b, d, h, N) \quad (15-16)$$

The winding loss of the transformer can be modeled with (15-17):

$$P_{winding} = k_{AC} k_m k_u \rho N^2 \frac{l_0}{W_A} \quad (15-17)$$

In (15-17), k_{AC} is the AC resistance coefficient according to [27], which is a constant when switching frequency is set. k_m stands for the coil numbers in the transformer, for single-phase transformer, the value is 2 and for three-phase, it is 6. According to Table 15-3, the mean length per turn of the winding l_0 and the window area W_A can both be expressed by the dimensional variables a , b , d and h . As a result, the whole winding loss can be simplified as below:

$$P_{winding} = P_{winding}(a, b, d, h, N) \quad (15-18)$$

Since the surface area A_t in (15-14) is also one function of the dimensional variables a , b , d and h shown in Table 15-3, the temperature rise can be summarized as (15-19):

$$T_{rise} = T(a, b, d, h, N) < T_{max} \quad (15-19)$$

As a result, according to (15-13) and (15-19), the two constraints of the design, flux density and temperature rise can both be written as functions of the five common variables a , b , d , h and N .

Thus the optimization function can be summarized as Table 15-5. Similar with the J-B Method, more constraints about a , b , d , h , and N are added in the calculation.

Table 15-5 J – B model for transformer design optimization

Optimization variables: $a, b, d, h, \text{ and } N$
Optimization (Minimization) Object: $V_{1\phi} = (2a + 2b) \times (d + b) \times (2a + 2h)$ $V_{3\phi} = (3a + 3b) \times (d + b) \times (2a + 2h)$
Design Constraints: $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} B_{1\phi} < B_{max} \\ B_{3\phi} < B_{max} \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_{1\phi} < T_{max} \\ T_{3\phi} < T_{max} \end{array} \right.$

IV. Single and Three-phase Transformer Comparison

One case study has been carried out at 20 kHz, 250 kW, 5000 V as an example. The operating points of DAB1 and DAB3 are as shown in Table 15-2.

By using J-B Method, the maximum current density is selected from 100 A/cm² to 500 A/cm², and maximum flux density from 0.3 T to 0.7 T. Optimization calculations have been carried out

at each point of (B_{max}, J_{max}) and the volume comparison results of single and three-phase transformers are shown in Fig. 15-8. And for further analysis, the temperature rise of each design has been calculated and compared in Fig. 15-9, based on the thermal model discussed in Section III. 3. From Fig. 15-8, it is apparent that at that range of B_{max} and J_{max} , three-phase transformer has a smaller volume than single-phase one.

Fig. 15-8. J-B method: volume

Fig. 15-9. J-B method: Trise

One detailed chart is drawn in Fig. 15-10, which shows the comparison of single and three-phase transformer volumes at 0.3 T and 300 to 500 A/cm². The average difference between the volumes of the two transformers is 12%, which is close to the estimation from the area product analysis before. However, when looking at the thermal condition of the design, three-phase transformer has a higher temperature rise at every point of Fig. 15-9. And by detailed analysis in Fig. 15-11, at 0.3 T, and 300 to 500 A/cm², the average temperature rise of three-phase transformer is 20% higher.

Fig. 15-10 Detailed volume comparison at 0.3 T, 300 to 500 A/cm²

Fig. 15-11 Detailed Trise comparison at 0.3 T, 300 to 500 A/cm²

Table 15-6 shows the design of transformers by using *T-B Method*. When setting $T_{max} = 100$ °C and $B_{max} = 0.4$ T, the temperature rise has reached the limit but the flux density has not, and single-phase transformer is more bulky than three-phase one, about 11.8% larger.

Table 15-6 T-B design results: temp. rise reaches constraints

	1Φ	3Φ
Volume (inch ³)	720.2	634.3
B_{max} (T)	0.2773	0.3234
J_{max} (A/cm ²)	427.1	425.5
Temp. Rise (°C)	100	100
Core Loss (W)	284.8	251.3
Winding Loss (W)	282.2	249
Total Loss (W)	567	500.3
Turn number	33	53
a (mm)	52.8	57.1
b (mm)	58.6	64.7
d (mm)	58.6	64.7
h (mm)	97.7	107.8

And when setting $B_{max} = 0.2$ T, and T_{max} as 100 °C, both constraints are met in the optimization, as shown in Table 15-7. In this case, the volume of single and three-phase transformer has little difference. The three-phase is no more than 4% larger.

Table 15-7 T-B design results: both T & B reach constraints

	1Φ	3Φ
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<i>Volume (inch³)</i>	782.9	810.2
<i>B_{max} (T)</i>	0.2	0.2
<i>J_{max} (A/cm²)</i>	520.6	506.0
<i>Temp. Rise (°C)</i>	100	100
<i>Core Loss (W)</i>	120.7	167.7
<i>Winding Loss (W)</i>	455.8	445.6
<i>Total Loss (W)</i>	576.5	613.3
<i>Turn number</i>	73	42
<i>a (mm)</i>	62.1	54.9
<i>b (mm)</i>	69	61
<i>d (mm)</i>	69	61
<i>h (mm)</i>	115	101.7

By setting $T_{max} = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $B_{max} = 0.2\text{ T}$, as shown in Table 15-8. The volume of three-phase transformer is larger. But the temperature rise has not reached the limit for either transformer.

Table 15-8 T-B design results: B reaches constraints

	1 Φ	3 Φ
<i>Volume (inch³)</i>	1270.6	1146.5
<i>B_{max} (T)</i>	0.2	0.2
<i>J_{max} (A/cm²)</i>	301.9	359.0
<i>Temp. Rise (°C)</i>	59.37	72.31
<i>Core Loss (W)</i>	206.4	255.6
<i>Winding Loss (W)</i>	204.6	253.3
<i>Total Loss (W)</i>	411	508.9
<i>Turn number</i>	44	27
<i>a (mm)</i>	80.3	68.5
<i>b (mm)</i>	89.2	76.1
<i>d (mm)</i>	89.2	76.1
<i>h (mm)</i>	92.0	73.7

From the *J-B Method* and *T-B Method* design results, a conclusion can be got that: when same boundary of temperature rise has been reached for both single and three-phase transformer, three-phase transformer is larger than single-phase one. And when same flux and current density limits have been reached, three-phase transformer is smaller.

V. Experimental Verification

Considering the available experiment conditions, one scaled down prototype DAB1 and DAB3 system (300 V, 20 kHz, 1 kW) is built for preliminary verification of the *T – B Method*. According to the operating points selection criteria described before, DAB1 and DAB3 are designed as in Table 15-9:

Table 15-9 DAB1 and DAB3 operating points for experiments

	DAB1	DAB3
P_o	1 kW	1 kW
f	20 kHz	20 kHz
V_i	300 V	300 V
V_o	180 V	180 V
I_{Lrms}	2.26 A	1.50 A
$N_1:N_2$	1	1
L_{lk}	580 μ H	580 μ H
Φ	42°	60°

DAB1 and DAB3 power stages are built based on two IGBT Modules 6MBP20RH060 by Fuji Electric®. The optimized design is carried out firstly for both single and three-phase transformers. And the available commercial cores which are close to these two optimized design results are selected as the sample transformers for comparison, as shown in Fig. 15-12 and Fig. 15-13 and. And Fig. 15-14 and Fig. 15-15 shows the operating waveforms of DAB1 and DAB3 when single and three-phase transformers are connected.

Fig. 15-12 Thermocouple locations in single-phase transformer

Fig. 15-13 Thermocouple locations in three-phase transformer

Fig. 15-14 DAB1 experimental and simulation results comparison

Fig. 15-15 DAB1 experimental and simulation results comparison

Thermocouple from OMEGA[®] has been placed on the yoke (A) and winding (B) of both single and three-phase transformer as shown in Fig. 15-12 and Fig. 15-13.

And the temperature tests results for single and three-phase transformer DAB1 and DAB3 operation is shown in Table 15-10 and Table 15-11:

Table 15-10 Single-phase transformer

Volume	6.42 inch ³	
°C	A	B
T_{amb}	26	28.8
T_{steady}	68	63
T_{rise}	40.4	34.2
T_{calc}	28.6	

Table 15-11 Three-phase transformer

Volume	5.26 inch ³	
°C	A	B
T_{amb}	29	28.6
T_{steady}	78.4	72
T_{rise}	49.4	43.4
T_{calc}	31.5	

From Table 15-10 and Table 15-11, it is found that the test temperature rises of both single and three-phase transformers are higher than the calculated value. And the temperature rise on the yoke is higher than the temperature rise on the winding for both two transformers. The temperature rise of the three-phase transformer is higher than the single-phase transformer for both yoke temperature and wire temperature.

VI. Conclusions

A comparison of single and three-phase transformer optimized design in DAB solid-state transformers has been carried out. Case study results show that three-phase transformer has the benefit of higher power density when flux and current density is the design constraints. When temperature rise reaches the limit for the design optimization, three-phase transformer has no apparent advantages in power density, comparing with single-phase transformer.

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Chapter 16 NANO CONTROLLER

I. Introduction

A digital controller is now a mandatory part in many medium to large power converters. Previously sponsored by ONR, a Universal Controller shown in Fig. 16-1 for PnP PEBB-based power electronics systems is designed in CPES. The main goals for developing have been firstly to reduce their design cycle time and cost, secondly to increase their flexibility, modularity, and re-configurability, thirdly to increase their reliability, supportability, and maintainability; and fourthly to increase their overall capacities and capabilities.

(a) Top side

(b) Bottom Side

Fig. 16-1 Pictures of universal controller

As shown in our previous work on PnP PEBB-based power electronics systems, this controller was designed to offer enhanced and powerful computational resources as well as a variety of communication interfaces, and was built over a DSP/FPGA digital system architecture.

As time flies, this ten-year-old controller is still working in many applications, but some applications, such as high switching frequency converters, interleaved converters, start to require more computation force or higher system density, which is beyond the Universal Controller's capability. Thus, a new controller – Nano Controller – is proposed and being designed in CPES. It provides faster calculation speed in a smaller volume. And the peripherals such as AD converter and PWM generator are also improved to meet the requirement of the new applications.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The objective of this chapter is to design a controller for use with PEBB based applications. The controller should small which is important for high density converter design. It also needs to

be fast to work with the new semiconductor devices which could switch at several times higher frequency than the traditional Si devices. A more important thing is that the controller architectures should make the systems open, flexible, and simple to use. It should have flexible interface to work in different conditions to be universal.

I.2. Technical Approach

To design a controller to meet all the need, first, the necessary functions are listed and divided into several groups to be implemented. The specification of these function blocks are defined. Then the detail interconnections between the groups are designed. A unified communication protocol between the function groups is defined. Finally, a first module – CPU and PWM generator is implemented.

II. System Architecture

The requirement of the new controller is to be smaller, faster. To accommodate the fast development of the digital processors, the functions of the new controller should be expandable. New function module or better module of current existing function could be added to meet the possible more strict requirements of more complex system in the future.

Considering these requirements, a modular stackable structure is used for the new digital controller. Because the size for each board is small and the distance between the boards is also very limited, this new digital controller is named as Nano Controller.

Fig. 16-2 Nano Controller architecture

The architecture of Nano Controller is shown in Fig. 16-2. The functions of Nano Controller are divided into several modules, such as CPU module, AD module and other auxiliary module.

These boards can communicate with other boards by a internal high speed system bus marked in Fig. 16-2.

II.1. Hardware Architecture

A. Function Block Partition

A common power converter controller usually requires the following functions: calculation unit, PWM generator, AD converter and necessary signal conditioning circuit, digital IO, communication and debug interface. In this controller, a main module is designed having all the functions except the debug interface to work as a single board solution for the application that requires very high power density that even this small controller matters. But this kind of application usually requires limited resources which make this design possible. Then each of the functions except the PWM generator is implemented in a separate module to provide flexible and powerful resource.

To summary, a complete system provides the following modules.

- CPU / PWM generator:

The module's main function is to provide the calculation force and PWM generator which is suitable for high switching frequency applications, multi-level converters, or interleaved converters. Thus, it needs a fast calculation unit, a multi-channel high resolution PWM generator. To simplify the development work, the calculation unit is selected to be a fast floating DSP which could be programmed using C language. For low switching frequency applications, the PWM generator could be implemented using FPGA. But FPGA implementation does not have high enough resolution for high switching frequency up to a few mega Hz. So a dedicate PWM generator using delay line with self-calibration capability to deal with the voltage and temperature shift is preferred.

Besides these main functions, this is the module is selected to be the all-function module since its main function is the core ones. A few AD channels and basis communication function is provided also on this module.

- Debug interface

This module is not a mandatory part of the controller in an application. But it helps to indicate the system state and identify the problem. All the functions on the module are selected based on this criterion.

- AD

The AD module provides multi-channel powerful AD with basic signal conditioning circuit. Based on current design of the CPU / PWM generator module, 16 channel, 16 bits, AD sampling at 10 Mbps is proposed. If more channels are need, only an additional module need to be installed due to its modular structure.

- Communication

The communication is to provide data exchange capability with the host computers or other Nano controller. The bandwidth requirement depends on the applications. To work with all applications, it should provide as much as bandwidth as possible, but still less than the internal bus. Another important thing is synchronization. Ethernet is proposed for this purpose. It provides 100Mbps/s or 1000Mbps/s

according to implementation. With IEEE – 1588 standard, time could be synchronized to sub-micro second scale.

From the above list, only the main CPU/PWM generator module, the debug interface module and a demo power supply module are built. The architecture will be tested using multiple the same modules to test the internal communication and coordination. Besides these core modules, other modules are proposed and will be added when the application requires.

B. Signal Distribution

To make the controller system modular, a high speed internal communication bus is proposed. Only with such a bus, the functions of the system could be put into different modular without the limitation of bandwidth.

As the bus speed increases, it is harder to use parallel bus because the delay introduced by the length difference of the traces will cause synchronization problem. Serial connection is used in such condition. For high speed communication, synchronized connection is usually used, which require a clock signal to synchronize with the data. When the speed goes even higher, even just making the trace length of clock signal and data signal the same is a burden. So the clock signal is embedded into the data by using certain encoding method. Also, for high speed application, differential signal is preferred than the single end ones. In our design, a serial LVDS channel using 8b/10b encode is selected because its wide acceptance, such as PCI expresses and Gigabits Ethernet, which make it easier to find off-shell implementation.

Another change from low speed to high speed communication is that point-to-point private connection is used rather than shared bus. In our design, shared bus is abandoned due to this reason. But to send data to arbitrary destination board a multi-drop connection method is used. In one channel, there is only one sender. All the other boards on the same channel only listen and the data they need to send are delivered on their own private channel.

In the design, limited by the system cost and complexity, only 8 independent communication channels are provided in the communication bus. In other words, up to 8 boards in the Nano Controller system can talk to each other. However, for a real complex system, if 8 boards cannot meet the requirement, one or more of the boards can work as communication boards to link two or more Nano Controller systems together, so the function of Nano Controller can be further expanded.

C. Power Distribution

In current digital and analog mixed signal system, there exist lots of voltage levels. A distributed dc bus is used widely in such design: a DC bus provides single voltage to all the load modules, then the point of load (POL) power supplies converter the voltage to the required ones. This architecture is proved to be robust and efficient in many applications, thus it is selected in the design. But instead of a single voltage DC bus, a bus providing ± 15 V is used. This is because for better analog circuit performance, a negative supply is necessary.

To suppress the noise, linear regulators are used to provide power for the analog part of the circuit. For most of the digital part, outputs of switching mode power supplies are directly used after filtering for high efficiency. But second stages of linear regulator is added to provide cleaner supplies for the high speed and sensitive part of the digital circuit such as clock circuit,

and high speed communication part of the FPGA. Fig. 16-3 shows the diagram of power distribution.

Fig. 16-3 Power distribution architecture

III. Module Implementation

III.1. CPU and PWM Generator

On all of the boards which need to receive or send data by high speed communication bus, one FPGA is used to take charge of the communication function. After considering the function requirement, chip footprint size and cost, the FPGA ECP2M50E-5F672C from Lattice Company is selected. Each FPGA features 8 channels of embedded SERDES which can transfer data between parallel format and series format and can support LVDS up to 3.125GHz. These 8 channels of embedded SERDES can meet the requirement of high speed communication between boards in Nano Controller. Other than that, each FPGA has 48k 4-input lookup table (LUT), 4Mbits embedded memory, 88 multipliers and 339 IOs, which is enough to meet the system requirement. Each FPGA has a 672 BGA footprint (2.7 cm by 2.7 cm), which is small enough.

For calculation, the TMS320C28346 high-performance floating-point DSP from TI Company is selected. The C28346 delivers 300 MHz of floating-point performance, 516KB of single-access RAM, and PWM modules with 65 picoseconds of resolution.

The embedded high resolution PWM generator is the main reason to select this DPS for Nano Controller system. Each DSP can output 18 channels of 12bit resolution PWM waveform at 70 kHz. For the paralleled structure, only 12 channels PWM are needed and for the high power density rectifier 12 bit resolution PWM is good enough. If really high resolution PWM signals are needed, the DSP can alternately generate 9 channels PWM signals with 60ps which means 12 bit resolution at 4MHz or 14 bits resolution at 1MHz. Even though for future project, the calculation speed is not fast enough, this DSP can at least be used a PWM generator in the Nano Controller system. The DSP also provide communication controller for general serial

communication and CAN protocol, which could be used when work as single board solution. The footprint of each DSP chip is 256 BGA, which is only 1.7 cm by 1.7 cm.

To make the CPU board a single board solution for some projects with simple topology such as DC-DC converter, other than the DSP and FPGA, 4 channels ADs are included on each DSP board. High speed high resolution AD chips are also desirable to increase the system control accuracy. LTC1407 AD chip from LINEAR Technology company is selected. Each chip has 3Msps sampling ADC with two simultaneous differential inputs. In other words, for each chip, one system analog signal can be sampled and converted into digital signal at the speed of up to 3Msps. Or two system analog signals can be sampled and converted into digital signal at the speed of up to 1.5Msps. The resolution is 14bits, which is high enough for most of the power electronics projects. In addition, this AD chip has 80dB common mode rejection at 100 kHz and 14 mw low power dissipation, with the footprint size only 3.2mm by 5 mm. All of these outstanding features make this AD the choice in Nano Controller.

The size of CPU board is 9.5cm by 6.5cm which is a little larger than a credit card size. The other boards in Nano Controller will be designed to be the same size.

Fig. 16-4 Top and bottom pictures of the CPU board

For some application requires a little bit more resource, some CPU board are used together. One is acting as a real CPU board, and the other ones only works as peripherals such as AD or PWM generator. Actually, this is also an advantage of the architecture, since the resource on each board can be shared by the other boards in this system.

III.2. Debug Interface

Debug interface is an important module used in the development stage. The module provides a human interface to interact with other modules. It does not need high speed communication with other part of the controller. Thus it is designed to connect to a module using general IO connector which is routed to the FPGA IO pins on the function modules for flexibility. To be safe, all the components on the debug interface are designed to be isolated from the Nano Controller. Optocouplers are used for this purpose.

The module designed include one LCD, 8 LED, 8 bits DIP switch, 4 button, 2 channels of DA, two potentiometer whose positions are converter into frequency and a USB interface to talk to a host computer. These peripherals provide both digital and analog inputs and outputs plus an interface to host computer which could be used for data logging, remote control and other high level tasks.

Fig. 16-5 Picture of the debug interface

III.3. Mother Board / Power Supply Module

To be used in any real application, a power supply or a mother board is required for the Nano Controller. For a simply single board application, the power supply to the CPU/PWM generator module and all other functions except the ones provided by the module should be built on the mother board. For applications that will involve several modules, the main functions of the mother board are to supply the power and to provide necessary buffering to the signals.

The power supply board show in Fig. 16-6 is designed as a demo for the applications. It can also be used to start the design and debug work without doing any specific PCB. The board supports up to four boards in the system. A PFX40-48WD15 DC-DC converter from TDK-

Lambda is used, which can output +/- 15V voltage with 40W. Since the pin density is too high to use the PWM signals from CPU/PWM generator board directly and buffer is desired to increase the signal drive capability, the PWM signals are connected to the power supply board first and then sent to power stage through buffer chips. Since its one serve demonstration and debug purpose, only these two simple functions are implemented here.

Fig. 16-6 Top and bottom pictures of Power supply board.

A system with two CPU boards and one power supply board is shown in Fig. 16-7 to show its profile. Each board takes less than 0.6 inch height.

Fig. 16-7 Picture of a Nano Controller system

Chapter 17 DAB SYSTEM DESIGN AND TEST

I. Introduction

In the area of power electronics energy conversion systems, there is a general trend to higher power density and higher efficiency. For example, in distributed energy system, many efforts are made to replace the bulky line transformer with solid-state high switching transformer which employs power electronics converter. The Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter is a competitive topology as a solid-state transformer solution due to its advantages of soft-switching behavior, simple structure and ease to scale to high voltage and high power. Recently a lot of attention was drawn on the DAB converter, and it is reported that DAB converter can be widely used in many application where galvanic isolation and bi-directional power flow are required, such as automobile, renewable energy utilization, energy storage system [1-4].

As shown in Figure 17-1, in common DAB converter design using Si devices, the switching frequency is usually below one hundred kHz [5]. A lot of research are focused on how to push the DAB converter to high power and high switching frequency application, recently some results reveals that SiC devices shows the potential to greatly increase the system efficiency and power density [5, 3, 6].

Figure 17-1 Common converter switching frequency vs. output power

In the previous chapters, the operation principle of the DAB DC-DC converter is fully analyzed, the transformer design procedure is established, what is more a Si-MOSFET-based phase leg is well designed, modeled and fabricated. The combination of these works makes the design and fabrication of a high switching frequency high power density DAB system become feasible.

I.1. Technical Objectives

The goal of this chapter is to design a Si-MOSFET-based DAB converter system as a demonstration of high power, high frequency static-state-transformer. As a generally knowledge,

high switching frequency can make the system beneficial, such as smaller passive component and higher bandwidth. As shown in Table 17-1, for the first prototype the targeted power rating is 5 kW, and we try to push the switching frequency to its limit, and explore the possible bottlenecks and issues and corresponding solutions at such a high switching frequency. Those endeavors are expected to accumulate enough knowledge and experience for the future SiC version converter with even higher switching frequency and higher power density.

Table 17-1 Prototype Si DAB converter specifications

Input Voltage	270V-330V	Output Voltage	300V
Switching Frequency	500 kHz	Rated Power	5kW
Input voltage ripple*	2% max input voltage	Output voltage ripple*	2% max output voltage
Output voltage accuracy	1% output voltage		

I.2. Technical Approach

Although we have well designed phase legs, there are still many system level challenges to design a real converter system of high power density and high switching frequency. Specifically how to achieve a compact system structure with low parasitic inductance while maintain good thermal management is very critical.

To achieve a compact system structure, a cable free structure is proposed for our application. Due to the symmetry of the primary side circuit and secondary side circuit, a symmetrical system structure is straightforward; additionally to fulfill the functions of converter, feedback and conditioning circuit, protection circuit, DC bus, heatsink as well as controller unit are also needed consideration in the symmetrical structure design.

For the thermal management issue, the dominant part of losses in DAB converter is the switching losses due to the high switching frequency. As a result good prediction of switching losses at different operating point is important and necessary in the design of a suitable heatsink. Double pulse test on our phase legs is carried out to measure the switching energy of switches at different current level under temperature of 25°C and 125°C. We also can find the switching current and RMS current of switch at different operation points through simulation. Combined these knowledge the worst thermal dissipation operating point can be found and the heatsink design becomes straightforward.

Parasitic parameters on phase leg and DC bus have a great impact on the switching behavior of devices especially in high switching frequency application. Inductance in the commutation loop causes high voltage spike on device and increases the switching energy; Inductance in the gate charging or discharging loop can slow down the switching speed and increase the switching energy. To minimize those parasitic inductances involves minimization the inductance on the phase leg as well as inductance on the DC bus. The design of phase leg is already presented in the previous chapter. In this chapter, how to minimize the parasitic inductance on DC bus are studied for different bus structure.

II. System Design

The DAB system consists of primary side and secondary side, each side includes two phase leg boards and one bus board as shown in Figure 17-2. Each phase leg board has three terminals, the DC+ terminal, DC- terminal and AC terminal. The DC+ and DC- terminals are connected with the bus board; the AC terminal is connected to the transformer. The primary side two phase legs share one bus; the secondary side two phase legs share another bus. In both bus boards the DC voltage and DC current information are sensed and fed back to an interface board. The interface board collects and conditions the feedback analog signals then feeds the conditioned signals into controller unit. From the other side interface board also receives PWM signals and other control signals from controller unit and sends them into phase legs. As for the controller unit, it includes a digital controller board and an A/D converter board.

Figure 17-2 System configuration

II.1. Structure Design

Considering the symmetry of DAB converter, the symmetrical system structure is straightforward and easy to implement. To make the system compact and reduce the parasitic inductance, the connections between different boards are realized by direct board-to-board connectors instead of cables.

Figure 17-3 System structure

As shown in the Figure 17-3, for each side the two phase legs sit on the heatsink, the bus board is placed closely to main circuit of phase leg boards, the DC+ and DC- terminals are connected with bus board through screws; such a structure and connection makes the loop between the DC bus and switching device small, as a result parasitic inductance in the commutation is low. The interface board sits above the auxiliary circuit parts of phase leg board and covers all four phase leg. The controller will sit in the middle of the interface board. Such an arrangement separates the main circuit part and control or auxiliary circuit part, and can reduce the electromagnetic interference.

II.2. Bus Board Design

To minimize the parasitic inductance in the DC bus, the laminated bus board is a preferred option and chosen in our application. In the bus board design we expect the bus board not only can be used for the present 600V Si-MOSFET version DAB converter but also can adapt to the future 1200V SiC-MOSFET version one. So the voltage insulation design is for the 600V DC bus. Another consideration is how many layers should the bus board be designed to achieve low inductance. We consider and compare two-layer and four-layer bus board.

Shown in Figure 17-4, the left side is the four-layer board design and the right side is the two-layer board design, both board designs have the same length and width and same connectors' position. The pads on the board mark the connector's position. For example the pads named DC+ are the position of connector corresponding to phase leg's DC+ terminal. In the four-layer board first and third layer are the positive DC bus and the second and fourth layer are the negative DC bus, while in the two-layer board, the top layer is the positive DC bus and the bottom one is the negative DC bus. The thickness of each layer is set to 1mm.

Simulation based on the Q3D is carried out to evaluate the parasitic parameters between the input DC terminals and terminals connecting phase legs. The simulation results are shown in Table 17-2. From the results, it is found that the two-layer bus and four-layer bus have the equivalent inductance while the capacitance on four-layer bus is three times large as that of

two-layer bus due to the larger equivalent area between DC+ bus and DC- bus. From the inductance point of view, the two-layer bus is competitive with the four-layer bus because of equivalent inductance and lower cost; on the other hand, the larger parasitic capacitance can reduce the required DC-link capacitors. In the end, we choose the four-layer bus board considering the fabrication availability.

Figure 17-4 Bus board comparison on four-layers (left) and two-layers (right) board

Table 17-2 Parasitic parameters comparison on the four-layers and two-layers boards

Structure	Inductance on DC+ bus	Inductance on DC- bus	Mutual Inductance between DC+ bus and DC- bus	Capacitance between DC+ bus and DC- bus
2 Layers bus	19.8nH	19.0nH	6.6nH	130.8pF
4 Layers bus	19.5nH	18.6nH	6.6nH	375pF

According to the design results in chapter 12, the minimum DC bus capacitance meeting the voltage ripple is 4.5 μ F. Ceramic capacitors have low profile and low ESR, in our application sixty 400V, 0.22 μ F ceramic capacitors are used in each bus board considering the capacitance reduction at rising temperature.

The DC current and DC voltage on both primary and secondary side are needed to sense and fed back to the controller. Thus a current transducer of LAH 25-NP is placed on the board, a voltage divider is used here to transfer the 300V high DC voltage to 5V low DC voltage.

The PBC layout and the picture of the bus board in shown in Figure 17-5 and Figure 17-6. The measured inductances on the bus board using impedance analyzer are shown in Table 17-3. We can find the measured values are close to the designed values.

Figure 17-5 Layout of bus board

Figure 17-6 Picture of bus board

Table 17-3 Measured parasitic inductance on bus board

Terminal 2 Terminal	DC + input	DC- input
DC +	22.8 nH	
DC -		21.3nH

II.3. Interface Board Design

The interface board includes the feedback voltage and current signal conditioning circuits, protection logic circuits, auxiliary power and connectors with phase legs and controller. The layout and picture of interface board is shown in Figure 17-7 and Figure 17-8, symmetrical structure and cable free connection make the interface board long enough to cover all the four phase legs; the connector with controller unit is placed in the middle of the board while the primary and secondary side circuits are placed on the left and right part of the board. This board is a four-layers design, the top layer is for the digital and analog signal; the first mid layer is for

+3.3V and +15V power; the second mid layer is for the ground; the bottom layer is for -15V power and the rest of signals.

Figure 17-7 Layout of interface board

Figure 17-8 Picture of interface board

A. Connectors

In Interface board different connectors are used to exchange information and power with other boards. As shown in Figure 17-9 (a), a 2x40 connector is used to connect with controller; through this connector PWM signals and other controller signals are received from the controller and trip signals are sent to controller. Figure 17-9 (b) shows the connector with bus board, -15V and +15V power is provided to the current transducer on the bus board, while sensed DC current signal and sensed DC voltage signal from a voltage divider are received from the bus board. Figure 17-9 (c) shows the connector with one phase leg, two channel PWMs, trip signal and reset signal are sent to the phase legs, from the other side the over temperature protection signal and over current protection signal from phase legs are sent to interface board.

B. Feedback current and voltage conditioning circuits

The sensed DC current and DC voltage signals from the bus board are conditioned then sent to A/D converter through coaxial cables.

The DC voltage conditioning circuit is shown in Figure 17-10, the sensed DC voltage signal got from 1:60 voltage divider is sent into instrumental amplifier LT1167 to filter the common mode; after that a linear optical-coupler HCNR201 is used to isolate the main circuit side and the control or auxiliary circuit side; then another operational amplifier AD826 provides a low pass filter and proper gain to finish the conditioning on the voltage signal.

Figure 17-9 Connectors in interface board

The DC current conditioning circuit is shown in Figure 17-11 the sensed DC current signal from hall current transducer is transferred into a voltage signal via a resistor of 200Ω. The transfer ratio is 25A/5V. As the A/D converter can accept the input voltage range from -10V to +10V, the signal is fed into a two-order low-pass filter with gain of two.

Figure 17-10 DC voltage conditioning circuit

Figure 17-11 DC current conditioning circuit

C. Protection logic circuit

The main function of protection logic circuits is to generate the fault signal for over-current and over-voltage happens in DC bus or over-current and over-temperature happens in phase legs. As shown in Figure 17-12, the sensed and conditioned DC voltage and current signals from primary and secondary side are compared with threshold voltages, once the feedback signals exceed the threshold voltage, a fault signal of low logic will be generated. The latch chip 74F74 will latch the low logic, after a series logic combination a trip signal will be generated and sent to each phase leg to disable the PWM signals. A denotation LED diode will flash and show what kind of fault happened. After the fault is cleared, a reset signal from controller or triggered by pushing a button can reset the protection circuit.

Figure 17-12 Protection circuits on interface board

II.4. Heatsink Design

Before the heatsink design, the losses evaluation for the DAB converter is done to find the worst thermal case over the operation range. Considering the primary side switches suffer higher conduction losses and higher switching losses compared with secondary ones, we focus on the primary side switches losses. The switching current and RMS current are derived by simulation. The switching losses can be evaluated based on the switching energy data got from double-pulse test at 125°C; besides the switching losses the conduction losses can be evaluated with the R_{dson} at 125°C got from datasheet.

Two typical cases are studied and compared, the first case is that converter works at the full load under ZVS condition; the other case is that the converter outputs partial power and is under hard-switching condition. The losses calculation results for the two cases are shown in Table 17-4. From Table 17-4, we can find the case 1 with full output power has higher losses on primary switches due to the much higher conduction losses compared with case 2 of hard-switching at partial load. So the worst thermal case is found that at full output power the maximum primary switches losses P_{mos_loss} is 107.4W.

Table 17-4 Losses evaluation for ZVS and hard-switching cases

Case #	Output power(W)	Turning-on losses(W)	Turning-off losses(W)	Conduction losses(W)	Total losses(W)
1	4600	0(ZVS)	60.7	46.7	107.4
2	1040	32.1	25.3	2.3	59.7

The static thermal impedance model for the primary side switch is established and shown Figure 17-13. The losses of switch are modeled as a current source; the resistors R_{jc} , R_{pad} , $R_{heatsink}$ represent the thermal resistance of junction to case, thermal pad, and heatsink respectively. The design criterion of heatsink is to make sure the junction temperature of switch is below the limit temperature at worst thermal case. For the Si MOSFET in our application, the maximum junction temperature T_{jmax} is 125°C, the junction to case thermal resistance of this MOSFET is 0.3 C/W.

Figure 17-13 Thermal model

The thermal pad is to provide thermal conductive interface as well as electrical insulation between Si devices and heatsink. A thermal insulator pad CHO-THERM T500 from CHOMERICS is chosen in our application. The thermal impedance of this pad is 0.19 W-in²/W, and its breakdown voltage is 5000V.

Assume the ambient temperature $T_{ambient}$ is 25° C, the maximum thermal resistance of the heatsink $R_{heatsink_max}$ can be found to be 0.135 C/W according to equation (16-1)

$$T_{heatsink_max} = \frac{(T_{jmax} - T_{ambient})}{P_{Mos_loss}} - R_{jc} - R_{pad} \quad (16-1)$$

For a heatsink with this thermal resistance, an aluminum heatsink with air-cooling is chosen for our thermal solution. An online heatsink design tool named R-Tool is used to design the heatsink [7]. In our application all the primary side devices share one heatsink while the secondary side devices share another one. The dimension of the well designed heatsink are shown in Figure 17-14 and listed as follows: the width is 130mm, the Length is 170mm, the thickness is 12.5mm, and the height of the fins is 130mm.

The thermal simulation results with the air flow velocity of 4m/sec are shown in Figure 17-15 and Figure 17-16. The simulation results show the maximum case temperature of device is 73.7° C and the junction temperature of device can be derived as 106.8° C. So this heatsink can ensure the junction temperature of MOSFET is below 125° C with about 20° C margin at worst case.

Figure 17-14 Heatsink dimension

Figure 17-15 Simulation results (top view)

Figure 17-16 Simulation results (isometric view)

II.5. Controller Unit

A. Digital Controller Board

Digital controller board selected for the prototype is Universal Controller (UC) and it is introduced briefly in this section. UC is a topology free controller board which can implement high level control for a wide range of power electronic converters and systems both medium and high power. Figure 17-17 shows the UC board including its Xilinx FPGA, Sharc DSP and its communication ports such as I/O pins and fiber optic receiver/transmitters. The I/O pins are utilized to communicate with A/Ds on the signal conditioning and sensing board and receive the digital sampled signals. They are also used to configure the A/D's input pins for proper operation.

Figure 17-17 Universal controller board

The controller architecture consists of two main busses bridged by the FPGA. This approach allows for incremental debugging of the controller without having to worry about every block at once. This also allows for future architectures in which the FPGA could interact with the peripherals without having to know what the DSP is doing. An alternative would be to have a single bus with every peripheral connected to it. The controller architecture is shown in Figure 17-18.

Figure 17-18 Universal controller structure

The FPGA supports the DSP's access to other peripherals on the controller. The DSP interface has been designed according to the architecture described above. The DSP communicates with the FPGA using the data bus, the address bus, and some control signals as shown in Figure 17-19.

Figure 17-19 FPGA-DSP interface

B. A/D Conversion Board

This board includes the sensing circuit, signal conditioning circuit and AD conversion circuits as well as the over limit protection circuit. Figure 17-20 shows the board.

Figure 17-20 A/D board

On the board, there are two AD7864 AD converters. The AD7864 is a high speed, low power, 4-channel simultaneous sampling 12-bit A/D converter that operates from a single 5V

supply. The part contains a 1.65µs successive approximation ADC, four track/hold amplifiers, a 2.5V reference, an on-chip clock oscillator, signal conditioning circuitry, and a high speed parallel interface. The input signals on four channels are sampled simultaneously, thus preserving the relative phase information of the signals on the four analog inputs. The part accepts analog input ranges of +/- 10V.

The time sequence of signal conversion is shown in Figure 17-21.

Figure 17-21 Signal conversion time sequence between FPGA modulator, DSP and AD7864

Before going to AD7864, the input digital signal would first go through the low pass filter to attenuate the high frequency noise picked up by environment. The design of corner frequency of the low pass filter should consider the impact to the controller, since it would introduce phase lag into the data. Additionally, the corner frequency should be much higher than the control bandwidth as well as achieving good noise attenuation. The designed corner frequency is 7.3 kHz. The filter configuration is selected as Sallen-Key active low pass filter as shown in Figure 17-22.

Figure 17-22 Sallen-Key low pass filter configuration

The corner frequency of this type of filter is

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{R_1 R_2 C_1 C_2}} \quad (16-2)$$

The parameters value is listed below.

$$\begin{cases} R_1 = 48.7k\Omega \\ R_2 = 48.7k\Omega \\ C_1 = 560pF \\ C_2 = 1200pF \end{cases} \quad (16-3)$$

III. System Simulation

System level simulation can help us better understand the system operation and reduce the risk in the real test. Based the physical phase leg model developed in Chapter 13, actual converter level models can be established for in Saber environment.

A. Buck mode simulation

A buck converter model is firstly established, in which the top switch are driven by 50% duty cycle PWM signal and the bottom switch is kept off-state, as shown in Figure 17-23. This buck mode simulation is done to check the switch losses at hard switching operation according to the measured switching energy data from the double-pulses test at temperature of 25°C and 125°C.

Figure 17-23 Buck mode operation circuit

Table 17-5 shows the simulation results data are collected for different switching frequency of 20 kHz, 100 kHz, 400 kHz and 500 kHz at condition of 300V DC input voltage, 50μH load inductance and 16ohm load resistor.

Table 17-5 Simulation results of buck mode operation

Switching frequency(Hz)	Turn-on current(A)	Turn-off current(A)	MOSFET RMS current(A)
20k	0	24	14.9
100k	5.3	18.5	9.7

400k	5.9	9.4	5.3
500k	6.2	9.1	5.4

The losses on the top switch at the above operating points are evaluated at 25°C and 125°C respectively. The evaluation results are shown in Figure 17-24 and Figure 17-25. From the evaluation results one can find at switching frequency of 400 kHz and 500 kHz the switching losses are the dominant part of the total switch loss at these hard switching cases. Figure 17-26 shows that the turning-on losses contribute the majority of the total switching losses.

Figure 17-24 Losses evaluation at 25°C

Figure 17-25 Losses evaluation at 125°C

Figure 17-26 Switching losses breakdown at 25 °C and 125 °C

B. Diode rectifier mode simulation

Figure 17-27 shows the DAB converter level model in Saber. According to the design in chapter 12, the leakage inductance is 4.2µH. The parasitic parameters are taken into account so the total inductance on the primary side of transformer is set to 4.8µH. Another consideration is that an additional capacitor is connected in series with transformer to avoid transformer saturation and the capacitance is chosen to be 5µF. An 18ohm resistor is used as load. A series of open-loop control simulation are done and analyzed in the following.

Figure 17-27 DAB converter level simulation

Firstly the primary side switches is controlled with complimentary PWMs, and secondary side switches are kept turned-off and operate as a diode rectifier. Simulation results are shown in Figure 17-28, we can find the polarity of primary side voltage V_{pri} is determined by the PWM signals while the polarity of secondary side voltage V_{sec} is determined by the times when transformer current hits zero then changes direction and starts to conduct diodes. As shown, for the primary side switches the gate source driver voltage V_{gs_top} is applied after the drain source

voltage V_{ds_top} drops to zero, so the primary side switches achieve ZVS turning-on at this operating point.

Figure 17-28 Simulation results of diode rectifier mode

C. DAB mode simulation

Then simulation of DAB converter is done for two different loads, firstly the voltage source load is simulated then load of resistor is studied.

i) Voltage source load

The required phase shift angle θ can be calculated according to equation (16-4). Where P_{out} is the output power, f_s is switching frequency, L_r is leakage inductance, V_{in} is the input voltage, V_{out} is output voltage, n is the transformer ratio.

$$\theta = \frac{\pi - \sqrt{\pi^2 - 4 \cdot \frac{P_{out} \cdot \pi \cdot 2\pi \cdot f_s \cdot L_r}{V_{in} \cdot V_{out} \cdot n}}}{2} \tag{16-4}$$

Different phase shift angles are simulated and the results are shown in Figure 17-29, Figure 17-30 and Figure 17-31. As discussed in chapter 12 the secondary side switches are always in ZVS region, so we pay more attentions on if the primary side switches achieve ZVS or not. From the simulation results, in which I_{ds_top} , V_{ds_top} , I_{ds_bot} and V_{ds_bot} are the currents and voltages of primary side top and bottom switches, we can find at phase shift angle of 75 degree, the primary side switches achieve ZVS; however at phase shift angle of 45 and 15 degree, the ZVS is not achieved. According to the boundary calculation for ZVS in chapter 12, phase shift

angle of 45 degree should be within the ZVS region. So the simulation results seem conflict with the theoretical analysis, the reason for this conflict will be explained in the later analysis, it will be shown that the precondition for ZVS is not only the enough energy stored in the inductor but also the short enough dead time.

Figure 17-29 Simulation results for phase shift angle of 75 degrees

Figure 17-30 Simulation results for phase shift angle of 45 degrees

Figure 17-31 Simulation results for phase shift angle of 15 degrees

ii) DAB mode simulation with resistor load

Because the output characteristic of DAB converter is like a current source, different load resistors yield different output voltages under open-loop control. As a result the output power of the converter does not only depend on the phase shift angle but also the load resistance.

Figure 17-32 Simulation results of 85 degrees phase shift angle

Different cases with different phase shift angle θ of 85 degree, 30 degree and 10 degree are studied for a load resistor of 18ohm. The simulation results are shown in Figure 17-32, Figure 17-33 and Figure 17-34. From the simulation results, we can find the primary switches achieve ZVS at different phase shift angle of 85 degree, 30 degree and 10 degree. We also can observe that cases of phase shift angle 10 degree and 30 degree have the similar operating condition, and the phase shift angle can't control the output voltage and power. The later analysis will show the reason for that.

Figure 17-33 Simulation results of 30 degrees phase shift angle

Figure 17-34 Simulation results of 10 degrees phase shift angle

D. Simulation results analysis

i) Simulation results analysis for voltage source load

The simulation results for voltage source load of 300V are shown in Table 17-6. It is expected that ZVS can be achieved according to the analysis in chapter 12; however we can

find the ZVS condition show up for a short time then the voltage rise up before the turning-on instant. The following commutation process analysis can explain this situation.

Table 17-6 Simulation data of DAB with voltage source load

Phase shift angle	Output power(W)	ZVS or Not	Turnoff current(A)	MOSFET RMS current(A)
75	4570	ZVS	24.4	15.5
45	2840	NOT	9.8	8.3
15	1010	NOT	0	3.4

As shown in Figure 17-35, at t_0 instant, the primary side switches S2 and S3 turn off, and then primary side voltage V_p changes its polarity because the inductor energy charge/discharge capacitors and diodes D1 and D4 start to conduct; and inductor current i_{ip} begin to decrease. The time interval between t_0 and t_1 is the slot for the ZVS turning-on of S1 and S4. As we know there is a dead time T_{dead} to make no shoot-through over the full power range. T_{dead} has a great influence on the turning-on instant time of S1 and S4; if the turning-on time instant is beyond t_1 , the inductor current will change its direction and diodes D2 and D3 will conduct current; then the turning-on of S1 and S4 is hard-switching turning-on. Actually this is what we observed in the simulation.

Figure 17-35 Waveforms for the commutation process

The relationship of turning-on time instant and T_{dead} is shown in Figure 17-36, the time interval T_{delta} between the turning-off of T2&T3 and turning-on of T1&T4 can be derived by

$$T_{delta} = T_{dead} + T_{on_delay} - T_{off_delay} \quad (16-5)$$

where T_{on_delay} and T_{off_delay} are the turning-on delay time and turning-off delay time of switches. So one necessary condition of ZVS is T_{delta} is shorter than the time interval T_{t0t1} between t_0 and t_1 , as shown in equation (16-6).

$$T_{delta} < T_{t0t1} \quad (16-6)$$

According to the measure data in chapter 13, the turning-off delay time T_{off_delay} at low current is longer than that at high current, while the turning-on delay time is almost constant over the current range; and the dead time should be larger than the time difference between the turning-on delay time and turning-off delay time over the current range. As a result, T_{dead} is set to 225ns, and T_{delta} can be found to be 110ns according to device characterizes; while the T_{t0t1} depends on the phase shift angle can be expressed in equation (16-7). We can find the boundary of ZVS satisfying equation (16-6), as shown in Figure 17-37. So this limit on the ZVS range mainly because the device characteristics require relative long time dead time, the SiC device with higher switching speed may improve this situation.

$$T_{t0t1} = \frac{\pi \cdot (V_{in} - V_{out} \cdot n) + 2 \cdot V_{out} \cdot n \cdot \theta}{2 \cdot 2\pi \cdot f_s \cdot (V_{in} + V_{out} \cdot n)} \tag{16-7}$$

Figure 17-36 Relationship T_{delta} and T_{dead}

Figure 17-37 Relationship of T_{t0t1} and T_{delta}

ii) Simulation results analysis for resistor load

The simulation data for resistor load are collected and shown in Table 17-7. From the table we can see the ZVS turning-on are realized for all the three cases.

Table 17-7 Simulation data of DAB with resistor load

Phase shift angle	Output power(W)	ZVS or Not	Turnoff current(A)	MOSFET RMS current(A)
85	4325	ZVS	27.1	16.1
30	2196	ZVS	16.7	7.4
10	2160	ZVS	16.7	7.3

From the data collected we can find that cases of phase shift angle 10 degree and 30 degree have the similar operating condition. The following detailed analysis will reveal that the DAB operation of 10 and 30 degree phase shift angles actually is equivalent to the diode rectifier mode operation.

Figure 17-38 Simulation waveform for phase shift angle of 10 degrees

As shown in Figure 17-38, the phase shift angle between gate driver signals V_{gs_pri} and V_{gs_sec} is the time interval between t_1 and t_3 , and the actual phase shift angle between primary side and secondary side voltages V_{pri} and V_{sec} is the time interval between t_3 and t_5 ; obviously the interval between t_3 and t_5 is longer than the interval between t_1 and t_3 . As we know the actual output power and voltage is determined by the actual phase shift angle between V_{pri} and V_{sec} . that is why the shift angle of gate driver signals can't influence the output power at this operation range.

The process of commutations is illustrated in Figure 17-39. At beginning, primary side current flows through S1 and S4, and secondary side current flows through D5 and D8. At t_1 instant primary side gate source voltages become low voltage, after the turn-off delay time at t_3 instant the primary side voltage V_{pri} changes its polarity so after t_3 the primary current starts to

flow through D2 and D3. During t_3 and t_4 , S2 and S3 can be turned-on at ZVS condition, at the same time the secondary side current continuously flows through D5 and D8 even at t_4 the gate driver voltages of S4 and S8 are low, as a result the secondary side voltage polarity does not change during t_3 and t_4 . Until t_5 instant the secondary side current changes direction and make the diode D7 and D8 start conducting then the polarity of secondary side voltage changes. From the above analysis the secondary side voltage polarity change time is not determined by the gate source voltages but only depend when the diodes start to conducting. So the secondary side works as a diode rectifier.

Figure 17-39 Commutation process

It is worth to point out that when the time interval between gate driver signals is shorter than the time interval between t_3 and t_4 , the actual phase shift angle between the primary and secondary side voltages is constant and determined by the commutations between the diodes. This cause one issue for the DAB normal operation, the minimum output power is limited to the output power when the converter operates in diode rectifier mode. This issue becomes more serious when the switching frequency is high and relatively large leakage inductance.

The time interval between t_3 and t_4 is determined by the current at t_3 and voltage across the leakage inductor. The current at t_3 instant is given by

$$i_{t_3} = \frac{\pi(V_{in} - n \cdot V_{out}) + 2 \cdot \theta \cdot V_{out} \cdot n}{-2 \cdot 2\pi \cdot f_s \cdot L_r} \tag{16-8}$$

and the time interval between t_3 and t_4 is given

$$\Delta t_{3-4} = \frac{\pi(V_{in} - n \cdot V_{out}) + 2 \cdot \theta \cdot V_{out} \cdot n}{2 \cdot 2\pi \cdot f_s \cdot (V_{in} + n \cdot V_{out})} \tag{16-9}$$

The above equation is valid only at DAB mode operation, when enter the diode rectifier mode this equation is not valid anymore because in this mode the θ can't influence Δt_{3-4} anymore. So we need find the θ value at the boundary between DAB mode and diode rectifier mode; this θ decides the minimum output power. The boundary condition is defined by that the secondary side voltage changes polarity at the time the transformer current decreases to zero, this can be expressed by equation (16-10).

$$t_{delay_pri} + \Delta t_{3-4}(\theta) = t_{delay_sec} + \Delta t_{\theta}(\theta) \tag{16-10}$$

where t_{dealy_pri} and t_{dealy_sec} are turn-off delay times of primary side switch and secondary side switch. Δt_{θ} is the corresponding time interval for phase shift angel θ . Assume the turn-off delay time of primary and secondary side switches are the same. The relationship of Δt_{3-4} and Δt_{θ} for the output voltage of 300V and 200V cases is shown in Figure 17-40. One can notice that when the DAB converter works in buck mode with output voltage is 200V the boundary point is when output power is 1500 W; below that output power Δt_{3-4} is larger than Δt_{θ} , and θ can't control the power output. When DAB converter works in boost mode or the output voltage equal to input voltage, Δt_{3-4} is always smaller than Δt_{θ} over the entire power range, so the converter always stays in the DAB mode.

Figure 17-40 Relationship of Δt_{3-4} , Δt_{θ} and output power at 300V and 200V output voltage

IV. Test on DAB

The DAB test bench is set up and shown in Figure 17-41. In this test bench, a resistor bank of 18 ohm is used as load, the power rating for each resistor is 100 W. A DC power supply of HP 6483C rated at 440V and 25A is employed as the input DC source. Between the DC source and the bus board, a DC-link protection board based on IGBT de-sat protection function is used to provide additional protection.

In the test of DAB, we followed step-by-step test procedure, and started from one simple phase leg test then to complex system test.

Figure 17-41 Test bench for DAB converter

A. Half bridge mode test

Firstly a half bridge mode test was carried out to test the gate drive circuit and phase leg condition at ZVS operation point. The test circuit is shown in Figure 17-42. The two switches in one phase leg are driven by complimentary PWM signals. The test waveform at 300V input voltage and 500k Hz switching frequency is shown in Figure 17-43. In this half bridge mode, the switches achieve ZVS turning-on so we can check the status of phase leg at soft-switching condition. The commutation process in one switching cycle is illustrated in Figure 17-44. During t_0 and t_1 , the load current flows i_L out of bridge through D2; at t_1 instant, i_L decrease to zero then change its direction, so T2 starts to carry current; at t_2 instant T2 is turned off, during the dead time i_L starts to resonate with the parasitic capacitors C1 and C2; After t_3 the resonant process ends and top diode D1 starts to conduct and then top switch T1 is turned on at ZVS condition.

Figure 17-42 Half bridge test circuit

From the half bridge test results, we find the gate driver circuits work well at 500k Hz; and the turning-off voltage spike is small indicating the parasitic inductance in the commutation loop is small.

Figure 17-43 Test waveforms for half bridge test

Figure 17-44 Commutation process of the half bridge in one switching cycle

B. Buck mode test

The buck mode test can test the phase leg at hard switching condition. The test circuit is shown in Figure 17-45. In this test the top switch in the phase leg is driven by 50% duty cycle PWM signal while the bottom switch is kept off. A resistor of 16ohm and an inductor of 50μH are connected as a load. The tests are done at different switching frequency of 10 kHz, 100 kHz and 500 kHz. The test results match with the simulation results in the previous section.

Figure 17-45 Test circuit for buck mode

The test results indicate that the phase leg can work well at those hard-switching the operating points.

Figure 17-46 Test waveforms of buck mode at 20 kHz switching frequency

Figure 17-47 Test waveforms of buck mode at 100 kHz switching frequency

Figure 17-48 Test waveforms of buck mode at 500 kHz switching frequency

C. Rectifier mode test

The rectifier mode test results are shown in Figure 17-49 and Figure 17-50. The results show that the secondary side voltage polarity changes at the times that leakage inductor current changes its direction. The series connected capacitor is subject to a switching frequency ripple, and it can be seen that there is few volts DC voltage on the capacitor. Compared with the simulation waveforms shown in the previous section, the experiment results match the simulation results well.

Figure 17-49 Test waveform for diode rectifier mode

Figure 17-50 Test waveforms for diode rectifier mode (expanded)

D. DAB mode test

The DAB mode test is not finished yet, however we can make some comments based on the simulation results. The DAB converter design and control still needs further investigation, with focus on the non-ideal device characteristics related issue and low partial load related issue.

V. Conclusions

In this chapter, system design procedure for high switching frequency DAB converter is presented for the Si-MOSFET based version, the design results can be also applicable for

future SiC-MOSFET version converter. Extensive simulations based on actual Si device model are done to investigate the operation and behavior of DAB converter at different operating points. The test results match and verified the simulation results. The simulation results and test results validate the system design and show the feasibility to push the converter to such a high switching frequency. On the other side, from the results one can find the high switching frequency brings some penalties such as bulk heatsink and additional limit on ZVS range. Future research should focus on the design methodology for DAB converter and more advanced device like SiC switch.

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